

**Sport diplomacy as a soft power tool: A case study of the
Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games**

By

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Abstract

This research examines Japan's use of the Tokyo 2020 Olympics as an instrument to improve its foreign policy and international standing. By investigating the Tokyo 2020/21 Summer Olympic Games as a vehicle for soft power. This thesis has identified the gaps that need to be addressed by investigating sport diplomacy as a vehicle for soft power. The first is to identify what an ideal soft power strategy is, using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The second is to argue and discuss how soft power can be theorised as a concept in international politics using sport diplomacy as a soft power tool. This thesis reveals that Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy stems from an examination of Japan's government strategy in Prime Minister Abe's administration. This strategy entails the remilitarisation of Japan's military and Abe's role in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid.

The strategy under Abe's administration suggests that the re-interpretation of Japan's constitution and hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is a smart power strategy to make Japan's soft power and global visibility more effective in becoming a major international player. Thus, from the research findings and analysis, this research has developed a soft (smart) power framework that the strategy of Japan's government entails constitutional remilitarisation and the hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as an ideal soft (smart) power strategy for Japan.

Secondly, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, this research argued that the reason for the under-theorisation of soft power stems from the lack of engagement with the concept of key international relations theories that are vital in the field to create a clear foundation for the concept of soft power to be applied effectively. This research reveals that it is important to consider the three main international relations theories of realism,

liberalism and constructivism in any context where soft power is applied specifically in the context of sport diplomacy.

Finally, this thesis discusses Japan's sport diplomacy and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The discussion reveals that Japan's sport diplomacy has been successful but not so much for its soft power. However, the tourism boom from 2013 until 2018 may have indicated success in Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power by bidding and hosting international sports events such as the 2002 FIFA World Cup, the 2019 Rugby World Cup and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. However, this research shows that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games cannot be considered an effective soft power instrument due to the Covid-19 epidemic. This is because of the absence of sports fans, and sports tourists and because of the lockdown restrictions placed on the hosting of the Games. This narrative sits well with the low public support that indicates that there were echoes of soft disempowerment of soft power in the context of using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool.

Dedication

I would like to dedicate this thesis to my parents Dr U. Ilevbare and Sarah Ilevbare, they both worked together as a team and worked assiduously, making sure that I got to the utmost level of completing a PhD. Their life and determination even in the face of adversity, their encouragement and advice have been inspirational in arming me to pursue my dreams so far.

To Mum and Dad.

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THESIS STRUCTURE

Chapter 1

Chapter 2

Literature review

Concept

Chapter 4&5

Chapter 6

Thesis discussion

Chapter Summary

Chapter 2

This chapter will examine the concepts of diplomacy while discussing the definitions and types of diplomacy, namely, old or traditional diplomacy and new diplomacy. This chapter sets the foundation around the evolution and development of new diplomacy practices that involve the practice of sport diplomacy. This chapter discusses two types of diplomacy namely, cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy, significantly, the overlap of public diplomacy and nation branding, and the overlap between cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy. Conversely, the discussion of the types of diplomacy helps to introduce the relationship between sports and diplomacy in this chapter. Furthermore, this chapter delves into the discussion of sport diplomacy, highlighting the practices of sport diplomacy as a new form of diplomacy practice while discussing the critics and limitations of sport diplomacy. This is where the first meta-themes started to emerge and as I moved to the policy documents, this the meta-themes became more evident. See description of chapter 5 and 6 below

Chapter 3

This chapter lays out the methodological consideration to achieve the research aim of investigating Japan's soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a Vehicle for its soft power. This chapter points out the nature of the study by understanding its main features of classical realism and interpretivism research paradigms. This research does not only justify the research paradigm that leads to the methodological justification, but it also points out the ontological and epistemological positioning of the research aims and objectives. Secondly, this section discusses the different strategies used best to understand and obtain knowledge of how the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was used as a soft power strategy. This includes examining the rationale behind the utilisation of a case study approach and a qualitative approach and concentrating on the semi-structured interview, secondary data analysis and analysis of government documents. By taking the research paradigm, strategies and methods into consideration, they built together the purpose of collecting relevant data to answer the research aims and objectives.

Chapter 4

This chapter discusses the findings related to themes such as geopolitics in Asia, highlighting Japan's foreign policy and national strategy and unpacking the developments that indicate a shift in Japan's use of soft power resources, including the re-interpretation of Japan's constitution to accommodate the full exercise of its sovereign power as an independent country (Smart power). This chapter discusses the findings surrounding the Sport for Tomorrow programme as Japan's Olympic and sport diplomacy strategy or project as indicated in its diplomatic document, identifying, and discussing the various ways the Japanese government has been able to make use of this strategy to engage with the government of other countries.

Chapter 5

This chapter investigated the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power. The investigation process for this study includes the data collected and analyses through the lens of identifying Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power. The data collected for this study took into consideration several variables such as Japan's culture, political values and foreign policy, and national and international image. The open-ended and fairly broad interview questions were drawn together from themes that emerged from the literature review, interview discussions and from the analysis derived from the document data source of the study. These formed meta-themes and sub-themes for the analysis. The initial meta-themes emerged from the literature review but then other key meta-themes came from the document analysis. These formed the basis of the big picture areas for the interviews where further sub-themes emerged and further meta-themes.

Chapter 6

Having analysed the data and findings, this chapter will discuss extensively the key thematic areas revealed as recurring issues from the analysis to answer the aims, objectives and research gaps that were revealed. It is interesting to note the areas that kept being brought to the fore by interviewees and emphasised in policy documents. That said, as a researcher, I'm conscious that one always has to question why you are being told certain things and what is not being said is often important even if at first you can't see it. This is why it was important to triangulate between the range of interviewees, policy and political documents and the literature. What follows is a summation and discussion of those areas that were seen as the key thematic issues following that whole process of answering the research aim, objective and question.

Introduction

Chapter One

Background and Context of the Study

This thesis investigates Japan's soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for its soft power. This thesis draws on the connection between diplomacy and sport, sports serve or in some cases serve as a platform for diplomacy and its practices, and in turn, diplomacy impacts the sphere of sports. Therefore, this thesis investigates the interaction between sport and diplomacy, or diplomatic practices and sport; as the world becomes interconnected and globalised. New types of diplomacy are emerging, and sport diplomacy falls under these types of diplomacy. Examples of diplomacy practices are digital diplomacy, public diplomacy, sport diplomacy, and cultural diplomacy.

New diplomacy practices are closely related to old diplomacy practices, this is because they are concerned with achieving the foreign policy goal of a country (Melissen, 2006; Kelley, 2010; Beridge, 2015). Also, new diplomacy practice reflects the impact of globalisation challenges on the international system and old diplomacy reflects traditional security (Sending, et al., 2011; Ivanov, 2004). Considering this, the key difference between both diplomatic practices is the role of soft power, which is the ability to influence others through attraction and persuasion rather than coercion or force. Soft power is a valuable tool for diplomacy because it helps to build relationships and interests between countries without resulting in military or economic sanctions (Nye, 2008). However, there is great importance and emphasis on soft power, because it is important to build relationships and promote cultural exchange through, for example, digital diplomacy and public diplomacy, to promote a country's image abroad. In contrast, old diplomacy is focused on hard power resources such as military associations, economic sanctions, and the negotiation of arms control treaties (Barston, 2019,

Davenport, 2022). Therefore, it is clear to say that soft power could play an important role in building trust and cooperation between nations.

Furthermore, there are two phases of sport diplomacy, the first is hosting sports events and the second involves the interpretation and impact of that event (Postlethwaite & Grix, 2016; Rofe, 2018; Murray, 2017). In the first Phase, the hosting country could use sport as a diplomatic tool to achieve its national and foreign policy goals. This may include promoting national identity, showcasing achievements, and building relationships with other countries. In the second phase, the impact of the sporting event is evaluated and assessed. This includes the impact of the media coverage, assessing public opinion, and measuring the long-term diplomatic impact of the event. The success of sport diplomacy depends on both phases, and countries must be careful in hosting and interpreting sporting events if they want to achieve their diplomatic goals (Rofe, 2018). For example, the cases of Russia, Qatar and China as mega sport events hosts, depict the need why countries need to be careful, especially in cases where human rights groups have raised concerns about the labour conditions in the construction of stadiums in the case of the FIFA World Cup in Qatar, human right documented cases of mass surveillance, censorship, and repression of political dissent in the case of China and also the winter Olympics in Sochi marred by allegations of corruption and environmental damage in the case Russia.

Sport diplomacy is a powerful tool for building relationships and promoting mutual understanding between nations, but this is subject to political manipulation and propaganda in some cases (Rofe, 2018; Murray, 2017). Likewise, sport diplomacy is the use of sport as a tool to achieve foreign policy objectives by promoting cultural exchange, nation branding, and the building of relationships regionally and internationally (Rofe, 2018; Murray & Pigman, 2014).

It is important to note that sport diplomacy is not entirely new; therefore, the modern narrative of sport diplomacy has significant traction because of the growing recognition of the contribution of international sport to international relations. International sports events like the Olympic Games and FIFA World Cup provide platforms for countries to display their culture and national identity, and promote tourism, trade, and investment (Nauright, 2004; Knott, et al., 2010). These sports events are platforms to promote or facilitate political reconciliation, and to promote peace between conflicting nations. At the 2018 Winter Olympics in Pyeongchang, South Korea, President Moon Jae-in of South Korea and Leader Kim Jong-un of North Korea had a historic meeting that served as a major diplomatic breakthrough in their long-standing tension. This meeting is a recent example of reconciliation and the promotion of peace (Lee & Botto, 2018; Rowe, 2019). Sport diplomacy is used to address political and social issues, for example, racism, gender inequality and environmental sustainability. Programmes and initiatives such as Sport for Development and Peace allow sports organisations and governments to use sport to promote social inclusion, and well-being and to empower marginalised communities. In summary, sport diplomacy entails the recognition of sport as an influential tool for achieving foreign policy objectives, promotion of cultural exchange, building relationships and contributing to international relations.

Additionally, sport is also a powerful instrument for implementing soft power, which is the capacity of a nation to influence others via attraction and persuasion as opposed to coercion or force (Nye, 2017). Soft power is often compared with hard power, which refers to a country's military and economic strength (Kounalakis & Simonyi, 2011; Wagner, 2005). However, sports is a powerful source of soft power because it has a universal appeal that cuts across national borders and cultural differences, and this subtle narrative allows sports to serve as a universal language that can bring people together and foster multicultural understanding. Also, in terms of nationalism, sport possesses the ability to create emotional connections among

sports fans or athletes to develop loyalty and pride that extends beyond the sports arena (Allison, 2000). Emotional connections can translate into support for a country's broader values, culture, and governmental policies; and the international community recognise sports as a soft power tool and has invested in sport diplomacy or sports initiative programmes. This includes the hosting of international sports events such as the Olympic Games and the FIFA World Cup.

In Japan's case, Japan's government has promoted sports activity as a vehicle for diplomacy since the 1964 Tokyo Olympics, which was a turning point in Japan's post-war recovery (Yoshimi, 2019; Yuan, 2013). Japan has actively used sports to strengthen its diplomatic relations and soft power influence in recent years. For example, Japan has hosted some mega sporting events such as the FIFA 2020 World Cup, the 2019 Rugby World Cup, and recently the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games (Rookwood & Adeosun, 2023; Best, 2022). By hosting these events, Japan has created a platform to showcase its culture, values, and technological competence to the global audience (Kobayashi, et al., 2023). More importantly, Japan has engaged in an international sports development programme that provides support for countries to develop their sports infrastructure and talent (Yamamoto, 2012; Nam, et al., 2019). Japan's sport diplomacy is a key component of its foreign policy strategy, which aims to promote peace, stability, and prosperity in the Asia-Pacific region and beyond (Yamamoto, 2012). For example, the Sport for Tomorrow programme was launched in 2014 by the Japanese government to promote sports and physical education in developing countries where they have access to limited sports facilities and equipment (Okada, 2018; Okada, 2016). In addition, another aim of the programme is to promote the values of the Olympic Games through cultural exchanges. The key objective of the programme is to boost Japan's image globally, displaying Japan's commitment to sports and physical education. Japan's soft power entails the ability to attract and influence the foreign public through its culture, values, and ideas, rather than

through military or economic coercion and this explains Japan's constitutional pacifism found in Article 9 of its constitution (Panton, 2009). One of the main strategies of Japan's soft power is the Cool Japan initiative, to promote Japanese culture such as anime, manga, video games, and fashion that are perceived as cool and attractive to the foreign public (DaLIOT-BUL, 2009). The initiative was launched in 2002 by the Japanese government to increase the popularity of Japanese culture and this has since become a part of Japan's soft power strategy. The Cool Japan initiative has recorded some success, such as its economic benefits of exporting its cultures such as anime, manga, and video games with an estimated 17 billion worth (Holroyd, 2019; Otmazgin, 2014). The increase in Japan's global popularity in its pop culture, and the boosting of Japan's image abroad have helped Japan's tourism. Conversely, since the launch of the Cool Japan initiative by the Japanese government in the early 2000s, the initiative has received some backlash. The Cool Japan initiative has been criticised for its lack of cultural diversity and for focusing heavily on a myopic range of Japanese pop culture such as anime, manga, and J-pop, overlooking other important parts of the Japanese culture (Iwabuchi, 2015; Heng, 2014). This has led to debates that the Cool Japan initiative is shallow and excessively commercial.

Despite the significant investment from the Japanese government, the initiative has not been as successful in driving economic growth or the increase in Japan's soft power. Lack of sustainability or lack of long-term sustainability has been an issue for the Cool Japan initiative (Hong & Chen, 2017). This is because; many of the businesses under the initiative have struggled to sustain and maintain momentum once the initial funding from the government dried up. This, however, points out that there is a lack of investment in creating a sustainable business. Finally, the inability to connect with the local community is a failure or detractor surrounding the Cool Japan initiative. The initiative has been viewed as a form of cultural imperialism with critics pointing out that the promotion of the initiative does not consider local

cultural norms and preferences. This has led to a lot of criticism and pushback from some audiences (Heng, 2014).

Therefore, by investigating Japan's sport diplomacy as a vehicle for its soft power; using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a case study, it is important to highlight that the 1964 Olympic Games was a significant tool with a positive impact on Japan's soft power and global image post World War Two (Abel, 2012). However, Japan was eliminated from bidding between 2001 and 2009, and Tokyo ultimately won the bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games (Holthus, et al., 2020). Japan began utilising the Cool Japan project as a soft power tool and replacement before the Tokyo 2020 Summer Olympics. The Cool Japan campaign has not been as successful as during the Tokyo 1964 Olympics. The Cool Japan project has had sustainability issues, especially about long-term sustainability (Hong & Chen, 2017).

Statement of Research Problem

The literature review has explored diplomacy, the evolution of diplomacy, and other forms of diplomacy, including sport diplomacy as a new form of diplomacy used by the ministries of foreign affairs as a soft power tool, by looking into the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power. This study has embraced the concept of soft power, it has identified gaps in the literature about the usage and implementation of sport diplomacy as a soft power tool. The key arguments leading to the gap in the literature are Grix & Brannagan, (2016) argue Rather than offering a conceptual framework to comprehend a state's soft power strategy, Grix & Brannagan (2016) contend that discussions of soft power frequently centre on semantics or a failure to engage with the notion. Vuving, (2009) points out that one of the reasons for the widespread misunderstanding of soft power by scholars is the context that soft power is under-theorised and lacks academic refinement and analytical fuzziness. Similarly, and agreeing to (Mingjiang, 2009; Ichihara, 2006; Womack, 2009) respectively, argued that the equation of

power with power resources is another reason for the misunderstanding of soft power. Pointing out that, limited serious efforts have been made to theorise the causal mechanism between domestic politics and foreign policy, despite the need to bridge the gap between comparative politics and international relations. Nye noted that soft power was only one type of power and was rarely sufficient on its own in his study *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (Nye, 2004; Nye, 2017). He raised the following points: soft power is not a normative concept; "bad" people like Osama bin Laden can utilise it; and manipulating people's views is not always the best course of action (Nye, 2017, p. 2). Nye (2017) notes that while soft power is one facet of power, the capacity to integrate hard and soft power into mutually reinforcing strategies may be referred to as "smart power" (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State).

Thus, drawing on the discussions, this study examines the claim that, instead of offering a conceptual framework, discussions on soft power frequently concentrate on etymologies or instances of conceptual failure. Secondly, Soft power is under-theorised with limited resources and soft power is not a normative concept. Although, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) provided a framework for identifying an ideal soft power using the case of Germany's 2006 FIFA World Cup and Qatar's 2020 FIFA World Cup. This research argues that there is a need for further theorising of soft power. The research investigated the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power by answering the research aims, questions and objectives.

Research aim- To investigate Japan's soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for its soft power.

Objectives and research questions

Research objectives

- To identify an ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool.
- To critically evaluate Japan's sports diplomacy strategy as a positioning statement in global and regional affairs.
- To investigate the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool in Japan's sports diplomacy
- To investigate the use of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool in Japan's soft power strategy.

Question

- What is an Ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool?
- How do we theorise soft power as a concept in international politics using sport diplomacy as a vehicle?

Rationale and Significance

Sport diplomacy is not necessarily a new concept because the use of sport to promote relationships dates to ancient times when ancient Greeks used the Olympic Games to promote peace among cities. In modern times, however, sport diplomacy gained recognition in the mid-20th century. For example, the 1956 Melbourne Olympics saw an improved relationship between Hungary and the Soviet Union after a face-off in a water polo match (Daws, 2016). Another example is the 1971 Ping-Pong Diplomacy that transpired between the United States and China, facilitating a visit by U.S. President Richard Nixon to China (Kobierecki, 2016; Itoh, 2011). Recently, the Winter Olympics in Pyeongchang was an opportunity for North and

South Korea to engage in dialogue and improve relationships (Merkel & Kim, 2011). However, sport diplomacy is relatively new and can be traced back to the late 20th century. Scholars have always recognised the role of sport in promoting international relations and cultural exchanges. Nevertheless, sport diplomacy began to be used in academic literature in the late 1990s and early 2000s (Murray, 2018; Skey, 2022). With a significant increase in the number of academic publications, scholars from a range of disciplines like international relations, sociology, political science, and sports studies are now examining ways sports can be used as a tool for diplomacy (Murray, 2018). Furthermore, the term soft power was introduced by Joseph Nye an American political scientist in the late 1980s. While the concept has a root in the discussion of power in international relations, Nye's popularisation of the term developed the idea of soft power into a coherent conceptual framework. However, the combination of sport diplomacy as a soft power tool is relatively new and has gained prominence in the last decades (Grix & Houlihan, 2014).

As a result, the National Olympic Committee of Japan justified hosting the Olympic Games, stating that it would help Japan rebuild more quickly from the devastation caused by the earthquake and tsunami. Additionally, to boost Japan's economic growth, solutions to the country's growing demographic problems should be developed. Japan redefined its national identity after the Meiji Revolution and the Second World War (Nye 2004). Japan was able to rebrand and maintain its identity and culture through soft power means like its self-defence military and pacifism, the 1964 Olympic Games, and the Cool Japan initiative. However, Japan's image as an inward-looking society has not been adequately rebranded. On the other hand, Japanese nationals should be encouraged to think about participating worldwide because their country will host big athletic events like the FIFA World Cup in 2002 and the Rugby World Cup in 2019 in addition to the Olympic Games in Tokyo in 2020 (Jeong & Grix, 2023).

The goal of this endeavour is to unambiguously contribute to the redefinition of Japan's national identity.

Furthermore, the regional or geopolitical rivalry in Asia is an important rationale for this research. In a few years, many nations will find it difficult to host two major sporting events back-to-back like Japan: the 2020 Olympic Games and the 2019 Rugby World Cup. However, with the rise of countries like South Korea and China's economic superiority over Japan, this is an attempt by the Japanese government to overtake these countries, taking into consideration the political values of Japan and China, with the growing competition in soft power and hard power capabilities. Because of this, there is a clear trait from Japan's Prime Minister Abe and Suga to bring back the 1980s Japan by attempting to remilitarise Japan's constitution and back to when Japan was a top economic powerhouse in the world.

Therefore, the significance of this research is that it contributes to Knowledge by answering whether Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power are successful in rebranding its image. In doing so, this thesis provides an ideal soft power framework for sports diplomacy as a soft power tool in the context of Japan, which can be applied universally or considered for future case study research. More importantly, this research is significant because it provides a conceptual discussion and significance on how best to apply soft power in the context of sport diplomacy by considering the recognition of international relations theory in the discussion of sport diplomacy as a vehicle for soft power.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter Two

Part one of this chapter will discuss soft power as the conceptual framework for this research. This chapter will discuss soft power from the views of scholars who have engaged in the critics and debates around soft power. Enabling the researcher to develop the appropriate research questions aims and objectives includes helping to identify the gap in literature for contribution to the field of sport diplomacy. Equally, Part, one delves into the discussion of soft power from the views of Joseph Nye, the key author of the concept. It then moves on to discuss sport diplomacy and the historical overview of Japan's sport diplomacy, the limitations of Japan's sport diplomacy and the relationships between the Olympic Games, Japan's politics, diplomacy, and sports. This chapter is important because it provides a road map with an extensive literature review around the evolution of diplomacy, sport diplomacy as new diplomacy practice and the overview of Japan's diplomacy and sport diplomacy practices.

Secondly, this chapter will discuss the concepts of diplomacy, the definitions, and types of diplomacy, namely, old, or traditional diplomacy and new diplomacy. This chapter sets the foundation for the evolution and development of new diplomacy practices that involve the practice of sport diplomacy. This chapter discusses two types of diplomacy namely, cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy, significantly, the overlap of public diplomacy and nation branding, and the overlap between cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy. Conversely, the discussion of the types of diplomacy helps to introduce the relationship between sports and diplomacy in this chapter. Furthermore, this chapter explores the discussion of sport diplomacy, highlighting the practices of sport diplomacy as a new form of diplomacy practice while discussing the critics and limitations of sport diplomacy.

LITERATURE REVIEW PART ONE

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

CHAPTER TWO

2.1 What is soft power?

Discuss from Nye, (2017, p.3)

One of the most intriguing occasions was an invitation to address the School of Marxism at Peking University in Beijing. I was treated royally. When it came time for my lecture to some 1500 students, I was seated alone at a table on a podium covered with gorgeous flowers with a large screen on the wall behind me with an enlarged video of my performance. In the course of my speech, I addressed the question of how China could increase its soft power and I mentioned the harassment of the great Chinese artist Ai WeiWei as an example of too tight control over civil society. There was a slight titter in the crowd, but at the end of my lecture, the dean of the School of Marxism took the stage and gave a long flowery thanks that the author of the concept of soft power had come to address the school. As he went on, however, I noted that my translator was skipping much of what he said. I later asked a Mandarin-speaking Canadian friend who was present in the front row what the dean had said. In summary: “we are flattered to have Professor Nye here, but you students must realise that his use of the concept is overly political and we prefer to restrict it to cultural issues.” I have come to realise that concepts such as soft power are like children. As an academic or a public intellectual, you can love and discipline them when they are young, but as they grow, they wander off and make new company, both good and bad. There is not much you can do about it, even if you were present at the creation. As the Princeton political scientist, Baldwin (2016) has recently written, “Nye’s discussion of soft power stimulated and clarified the thoughts of policymakers and scholars alike—even those who misunderstood or disagree with his views”. Perhaps that is all one can hope for. (Nye, 2017, p. 3) ...

2.2 Understanding Soft Power from the Context of Joseph Nye; author of the concept

A conceptual framework reflects the thinking of the research process, it involves the concepts and factors adopted to systemise knowledge (Antwi & Hamza, 2015). A conceptual framework is a more specific and focused explanation of how a particular phenomenon works by identifying key concepts and variables involved and the relationships between them. The term power from the earliest study of political science until date has been a part of international relations and politics (Berridge, et al., 2001; Rothman, 2011; Baldwin, 2002). Power in international relations can be understood from two different schools of thought, which are the realist and liberal approaches. The realist approach is geared towards the utilisation of hard power by countries. Hard power comes across a wide range of coercive policies or diplomacy such as military actions, economic sanctions, and the cooperation of military alliances for mutual defence by states against one another. On the other hand, the liberalist approach is geared towards soft power. Soft power is the ability to co-opt instead of coercing, which contrasts with hard power.

Soft power is the ability to shape the influence or preference of other nations through attraction and appeal. By looking at the American military and economic power resources, Nye, (1990) coined the term soft power in his book *Bound to Lead* in 1990. He challenged the conventional views of the decline in American power, pointing out that power is the ability to affect others to get the outcomes one prefers, and power can be accomplished by coercion, payment, or attraction (Nye Jr, 1990). To Nye (1990), the idea that the United States was in decline had an impact on the concept of soft power. Paul Kennedy believed that America was suffering from an imperial overstretch and would soon follow in the footsteps of Edwardian Britain or 17th-century Spain, at the time his book *The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers* became a New York bestseller (Nye, 2017). Considering that Japan was surpassing America in terms of economic strength and the Soviet Union was surpassing the United States in terms of military force (Nye,

2017). From the above literature, power in the early 90s and from the traditional international relations or realist perspective is categorised into military and economic might, and these are key factors for a country to become active in global affairs. Scholars and professionals in the field of international relations, as noted by Nye (2017), frequently view power as material assets that may be placed on a person's foot or in a city. This is truer for neorealists like Kenneth Waltz than for traditional realists like Carr (1939), albeit not exclusively (1979). For example, realism is the assumption that states are the main actors in international relations, states act in their self-interest, and states want self-preservation and power. From this belief, classical realists emphasised domestic politics and human nature as the key factors in describing and characterising the state's behaviour and the causes of state conflicts. For classical realism, humans are not inherently generous, and they are self-absorbed and act out of aggression or fear (Kirshner, 2015). On the other hand, neo-realism emphasises the role of power in international relations. Neorealism views conflict and competition as enduring characteristics in international relations at the same, views international cooperation as limited potential. This means that, Because of the anarchy in the international system, states are unsure of the intentions and security of other states. However, this prompts them to engage in power politics (Jervis, 1999). Therefore, from the above discussions, coercion and payments are key factors in power play and the influence of others through ideas and attraction can set the agenda for others or get them to want what another wants (Nye, 2017).

From an analytical standpoint, to address a gap in the way analysts saw soft power, Nye (2017) talked about soft power. Although Nye talked about soft power in relation to American power, he believed that the idea of soft power is not limited to American or international behaviour (Nye, 2017). While soft power has taken a strong root in international relations, Nye (2017) applied the concept of soft power to organisations and individuals in his *book The Powers to Lead* (Nye, 2008). From a conceptual standpoint in the context of American politics from the

9/11 terror attack. Nye (2017) argued that though a congressional representative agreed privately about his views on soft power, it was impossible to use the term to address political audiences who wanted to hear the tough talk. In this context, he argued that there is a need to spell out the meaning of soft power. Pointing out that, practitioners incorrectly describe soft power as non-traditional forces such as culture and commercial goods and dismissing it on the ground of 'its, well, soft' (Nye, 2017, p. 2). In Nye's article, *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*, he pointed out that soft power was only one concept of power and rarely sufficient by itself (Nye, 2004) (Nye, 2017). He discussed that soft power is not a normative concept, meaning that soft power is a non-normative political concept in that it is used to describe the way the political system works, the behaviour of political actors and the outcomes of political processes. This contrasts with normative concepts that are used to evaluate how the political system should work or how political actors should behave. Therefore, it is not necessarily better to twist minds and that 'Bad' people like Osama bin Laden can exercise soft power (Nye, 2017, p. 2). However, in his definition of soft power, what remains constant over time is the ability to affect others and obtain preferred outcomes by attraction and persuasion instead of coercion or payment.

In the U.S. invasion of Iraq that proved disastrous, Nye saw the need to address and spell out the meaning of soft power. Amid the deteriorating situation in Iraq, Nye (2017) notes that soft power is merely one facet of power, and that "smart power" is the capacity to integrate hard and soft power into mutually reinforcing strategies (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State). as the co-chair of the Centre for Strategic and International Studies' "Smart Power Commission" in Washington, D.C., with John Hamre and Richard Armitage. Nye, (2017) depicted that the term smart power was clearly prescriptive rather than just analytical. However, moving away from the context of American foreign policy, China has managed to adopt the concept of smart power; while China has strategically developed its hard power

resources, its political leaders realise how acceptable it will be to apply soft power alongside its hard power (Akcadag Alagoz, 2019; Ivanov, 2020). This is where smart power comes into play. As China grows in its military and economic power, neighbours such as Japan, Korea and South Korea may be frightened into the balancing of the coalition.

However, by accompanying soft power to its intensification in hard power; China can weaken the incentives of the coalition from its neighbours. For example, in 2007, Chinese President Hu Jintao told the Chinese Congress of the communist party to invest more in their soft power, and President Xi Jinping continued this strategy (Nye, 2017). Since 2009, under Xi Jinping, China has invested approximately \$6.6bn, in building up its media presence to boost its international presence by trying to control the activities of foreign correspondents based in China (Blank & Kim, 2013). This media strategy is to tell China's story well and to boost its international influence (Wilson, 2022; Hunter, 2009). China's economic prosperity and the allure of its traditional cultures have contributed to its soft power, although with mixed results. According to Portland's research on global soft power, China is behind America in terms of all-around appeal across most of the world, including Asia. Portland is a consultancy in London that constructs an annual index of soft power of the top 30 countries. In the case of China, according to Nye (2017), China has to understand that civil society, not the government, possesses the majority of a nation's soft power. Second, propaganda doesn't appeal because it isn't credible. Thirdly, although it is hard to reconcile with strict party control, China needs to allow more latitude to the skills of its civil society. Lastly, China's territorial disputes with its neighbours also hinder its soft power. Therefore, it will not be desirable to construct Confucius institutes in Manila to teach Chinese culture if Chinese naval vessels are chasing Philippine fishing boats out of Scarborough (Nye, 2017). Thus, to put it simply, soft power is the capacity to achieve a desired result via seduction rather than by coercion or force. Nevertheless, the nation using soft power determines how well it may be applied. From the above definition,

democratic, liberal, undemocratic, or illiberal states may seek to wield soft power differently because of the way they might be seen by the foreign public. In this case, it is important to investigate how Japan has sought to wield its soft power and its available national and human resources as a tool for attraction.

2.3 Understanding the concept of power and soft power from academic scholars in the field

2.3.1 Traditional School of Thought on Power and the State

To address or critique the concept's shortcomings and to better connect soft power with their areas of interest or specialisation, scholars have attempted to adopt it. According to Gallarotti (2011), researchers of international politics have traditionally viewed power as a realist concept, which means they tend to support a rigid definition of power (Gallarotti, 2011). Power is defined by a prominent proponent of current realism Kenneth Waltz as a specific material capability that a state possesses; these material capabilities are referred to as "tangible assets" and are what gauge a country's military might (Waltz, 1979, p. 131). Furthermore, Gilpin (1981) defines power as "the military, economic, and technological capabilities of nations" and notes that "an industrial-military complex that can be utilised to threaten or mobilise troops is necessary for national influence in the final analysis." And the power of a nation is essentially determined by its "Muscle" (Gilpin, 1981, p. 13; Gallarotti, 2011).

The idea fits into the realist interpretation of the international relations system as being anarchic. International relations experts have examined a state's ability to exert worldwide influence using coercive power sources, such as force and threat. Nye suggested that having a positive reputation in international affairs is crucial. This reputation can come from a variety of sources, such as culture, which inspires respect and admiration and makes a country seem more appealing to other countries (soft power). This attractiveness can be so appealing that

other nations may be willing to attempt or emulate the policies and actions of the soft power nation's national or foreign policy. In contrast to hard power, the attractiveness of soft power will allow other nations to defer readily to their wishes on international issues by trying to avoid confrontations. Gallarotti, (2011) Argues that a country's attractiveness can be such that choices about matters impacting soft power countries will be limited to options that are advantageous to such countries. This implies that copying the behaviour of other countries results in a system of countries that behave consistently in their actions, policies, and objectives to uphold the interests of role-model countries (Gallarotti, 2011). Consequently, soft power modifies the environment in which other countries make decisions to advance the objectives of soft power countries.

2.3.2 Contemporary school of thought on power and the state

Moreover, soft power is deeply ingrained in both American foreign policy thought and practice, as noted by Kroenig et al. (2010). There is currently no established theory among academics that explains how a government can take advantage of soft power (Kroenig, et al., 2010). Nonetheless, a hypothesis regarding the circumstances in which a state's attempt to employ soft power is most likely to be successful was established by Kroenig et al. (2010). They contend that a state's attempts to use U.S. foreign policy to better its foreign policy environment and its attempts to employ soft power in the post-9/11 age are separated by several steps. The United States' inability to defeat the ideology of terrorism and win over Iraq's hearts and minds was partly due to the lack of the three prerequisites for soft power. The first theory, according to Kroenig et al. (2010), holds that states need to be able to communicate with the intended recipient in a way that roughly resembles a working marketplace of ideas. Second, it is necessary to try and modify the relevant target's mindset. Thirdly, for a state seeking to use soft power to succeed in international politics, the target's mindset needs to have a causal influence

on the result. While Kroenig, et al., (2010) point out the necessities for these conditions, they argue that when taken together, these conditions may or may not be sufficient for a state to effectively employ soft power.

In the case of the United States and Iraq, the application of soft power in Iraq was a fairly broad marketplace of ideas. However, the United States failed in its soft power because the conditions of soft power were never in place. The United States succeeded in communication but failed because the United States lacked credibility as a messenger and the U.S. occupation clashed with the core material interest of the Iraqi people (Kroenig, et al., 2010). Similarly, to Nye's address on the deficiency and misunderstanding of soft power, (Vuving, 2009) addressed the question of how soft power works by proposing two categories of how to understand soft power and what constitutes soft power. Soft power can be understood from a narrow and broader sense. Cultural influence is characterised by soft power in a limited sense. When used more broadly, soft power refers to non-military force that encompasses economic and cultural might (Vuving, 2009). Vuving, (2009) points out that one of the reasons for the widespread misunderstanding of soft power by scholars is the context that soft power is under-theorised and lacks academic refinement and analytical fuzziness, similarly and agreeing to (Mingjiang, 2009; Ichihara, 2006; Womack, 2009) respectively, they argued that the equation of power with power resources is another reason for the misunderstanding of soft power. Pointing out that, limited serious efforts have been made to theorise the causal mechanism between domestic politics and foreign policy, despite the need to bridge the gap between comparative politics and international relations. Especially when the dichotomy is also a reflection in the study of Chinese foreign policy. In addition, Vuving, (2009) points out that people tend to confuse resources with behaviour.

In other words, soft power is equated with some typical resources of soft power, called the vehicle fallacy. They are pointing out that this approach appears to make soft power concrete

and measurable (Vuving, 2009). In other words, power is mostly measured by how much power resources a state has, be it economic or cultural. On the other hand, Vuving, (2009) points out that power is not identical to its resources, depicting that the same resources can produce both hard and soft power, however, his point agrees with Nye's point where he points out that a bad person can also attract soft power. for example, the military as a typical hard power resource can coerce some people and attract some people when victory is achieved. On the other hand, soft power resources such as moral values can be used to persuade someone in a privately agreed meeting and force another when used to build social pressure (Vuving, 2009). By attempting to narrow the gap in the misunderstanding of soft power. Vuving, (2009) distinguishes between power resources and power currencies as two sources of power but two different kinds of sources from which power is derived. Power currencies is a property that causes power while power resources are usually properties of resources or activities.

Lukes (2005) characterises soft power as the ability to shape an actor's own interests, while hard power involves altering the incentive structures of others whose interests are assumed (Lukes, 2005, p. 95). Also, Mead, (2004) contends that Nye categorised military might and economic strength under the same heading of hard power. Military force is 'sharp' and economic strength is 'sticky' (Mead, 2004, pp. 46-50). He points out that the U.S. economic policies and institutions act as a 'sticky power' that attracts other countries to the U.S. system and then traps them in it. However, for Mead, (2004), economic or sticky power is different from hard or sharp power and soft power. Vuving, (2009) points out that Meads (2004) sticky power reveals that, economic power cannot stand alone and sticky power is no different than a form of smart power, the combination of both hard and soft power effectively. Also from a different dimension, Meads (2004) concept of sticky power agrees with Nye's (2017, p.2) explanation of soft power as a power that cannot stand alone, however, smart power through prescriptive appears to be an effective strategy.

Furthermore, by examining the British and American leadership, Meads (2004), depicts that, both systems allow for the freedom and functioning of the world economy that is propped up by a strong military and a web of liberal economic institutions, provided by hegemon whose behaviour was largely seen as acceptable (Vuving, 2009). For a better understanding of the notion of sharp and sticky power, Vuving (2009) provided several examples. The first is, why is military might important for sticky power? he explained that it was the British and then the U.S. navies that commanded the sea, therefore facilitating and guarding international trade. Secondly, why is soft power indispensable for sticky power? he used Nazi Germany as an example of having a formidable military and admirable economic power, however, its aggressive foreign policy turned its neighbours and the great powers into the enemy camp. Thirdly, why can economic strength alone not translate into sticky power? he gave an example of Japan after World War II, an economic superpower without military and international backup can attract others but ultimately cannot trap them. In summary, economic power straddles the areas of hard and soft power depending on the context of realisation, economic or cultural power can either be hard or soft power. However, stickiness is produced by smart power and not by soft power alone. However, according to Nye, (2004), three ways by which people can affect the behaviour of others to get what they want are coercion, payment and attraction which appears to be more accurate than Mead's distinction of Sharp, sticky and soft power according to Vuving (2009).

Finally to answer the question of what constitutes soft power as the power of attraction? Vuving (2009) proposed looking at the power currencies that cause attraction and these power currencies are Beauty, brilliance, and benignity (Vuving, 2009, p. 7). Benignity is an aspect of an agent's relations with others, especially with the client of soft power, for example, a positive attitude. Secondly, Brilliance refers to the high performance that one can accomplish when doing things and this relates to learning about the success of others, it generates soft power

through the production of admiration. In international relations, Brilliance includes a strong or awful military, a wealthy and vibrant economy, a rich and radiant culture, or a peaceful and well-run society. Thirdly, beauty relates to the actor's relationship with ideals, values, causes, or visions. Beauty in international relations includes resonance that draws actors closer to each other, and the creation of bilateral or multilateral relationships through shared ideals, values, causes or visions. And this brings a sense of security, identity and community. From the above discussion on the understanding of power and soft power, cultural events, exchange programs, broadcasting and teaching a country's language, and the promotion of the study of countries are tools of soft power. However, how these tools are employed could be perceived as hard or soft power depending on the context.

Furthermore, Rothman (2011) argues that soft power has not been fully utilised under specific tools and mechanisms by which soft power influences international actors by revising and creating a continuum of power that is based on the tools that are useful for understanding the different levels of soft power (Rothman, 2011). The distinctions between softer and tougher kinds of power are more subtle and less obvious than one may think, according to Rothman (2011), who uses only these two categories to create a typology of power. However, it is important to dissect the typology to generate a definition of power utilising both hard and soft power concepts and at the same time creating flexibility in the ways different resources can fit in the definition and relationship between softer and harder powers. By examining Nye's concept of soft power, Rothman, (2011) used (Goertz, 2008) concept of formation by examining the two poles or opposites of soft power.

The illustration below shows Rothman, (2011) Dichotomous and continuous power.

Source: Rothman, (2011) Fig 1

From the above diagram, Rothman, (2011) points out that different types of behaviours or actions are soft or harder depending on their location within the diagram. For example, from the diagram, the use of agenda-setting power fits somewhere in between coercion and attraction. Agenda setting does not fit well with the power of attraction but fits well with the non-military use of power in international relations. Rothman, (2011) depicts that in the context of reconceptualising the concept of power and developing a spectrum of power from the hardest to the softest forms. A small change such as clarifying the agenda-setting in the conceptualisation of soft power allows for a more dynamic concept in the comparison between different types of behaviours on a relative basis of softness and hardness. However, it allows for Nye's power of attractiveness to constitute one of the softest forms of power.

Furthermore, in the context of the diagram, the left pole of the diagram is one where the actor can take the life of another actor, Rothman, (2011) calls this the hardest form of soft power. This is because the actor wielding the power reduces the payoff of all but two of the targets to zero. This means that the basic attribute associated with hard power is physical coercion. The ability to physically manipulate another actor is the most effective and common way to use hard power to change the behaviour of another actor. In contrast to the right-hand pole, soft power reflects those powers that entail non-physical means to influence the actions of others. In this case, the most non-physical means involve the use of morals or ideals. These morals or norms could involve cultural practices which is an ideal type of non-physical power over the actions of others (Rothman, 2011). The above diagram from Rothman (2011) helps to

understand the different ways in which soft power and hard power vary. Also, the diagram can help identify behaviours and resources that are more likely to provide harder and softer influence over the outcome. To understand the behaviour and resources that are associated with hard power and soft power, Rothman (2011) proposed that command and military resources, economic forms of power, agenda-setting and institutional control which includes framing and rhetoric, normative framing and analytical framing should all be considered.

Military command and resources are self-explanatory forms of hard power resources as explained by previous scholars in this section. Economic forms of power which are just like the military forms of power can be used as both soft power resources and hard power resources. For example, International actors or states can withhold financial goods or aid or deliver economic sanctions or on the other hand of soft power, provide financial resources as an aid to help the target actor or state. The most revealing type of resources that need explanations that are different from what other scholars have said in terms of soft power, is Rothman's (2011) agenda-setting and institutional control. As noted by Rothman (2011), agenda formation receives little formal or systematic attention from many researchers of international affairs. Setting the agenda and exercising institutional control are typically seen as the second face of power, which demonstrates influence over other players and agenda manipulation (Bachrach & Baratz, 1971). Agenda framing is not a function of soft power, as noted by Rothman (2011) and Gallarotti (2010), as it creates winners and losers and conflicts of interest among actors rather than cooperation (Gallarotti, 2011).

2.4 Sports and the concept of soft power

Sport is an example of a cultural soft power instrument in the framework of soft power, where culture is a crucial component of global appeal. Sports are a cultural power and a component of a host country's soft power strategy, according to Bairner et al. (2017). (Bairner, et al., 2017). To accomplish social, political, and economic objectives, nations, towns, and communities have been using sports for public diplomacy and branding (Dubinsky, 2019). Dubinsky, (2019) depicts that the opening ceremony of the Olympic Games is a platform of soft power strategy in the context of the sports mega event and this is because of the huge preparation of international broadcasting and display of culture, technology, aerospace and military (Dubinsky, 2019 , p. 161). The benefits of gaining international exposure with a focus on culture and peace values, make sports a useful tool for countries to achieve international and public diplomacy goals.

Furthermore, Lee (2020) emphasised how international events promote political discourse when discussing soft power in politics and sports diplomacy. for instance, the PyeongChang Winter Olympics of 2018 were undoubtedly one of the most politicised major sporting events in history. This is because, following two years of rising political tensions, a real and observable improvement in relations between North and South Korea was observed (Lee, 2020). In this instance, the inter-Korean discourse was conducted diplomatically through the Winter Olympics. This is a perfect illustration of how international politics and major athletic events interact (Lee, 2020). Grix & Lee (2013) note that, despite hosting major sporting events, the expanding agency of big emerging nations has been disregarded in international affairs. They also talked about the importance of why big developing nations host major sporting events like the World Cup and Olympic Games in the framework of the politics of attraction. They point out that hosting mega sports events provides the opportunity for large developing countries like China, Brazil and South Africa should engage in public diplomacy to strengthen

and project their soft power inside the international system. Even while these nations have been successful in winning the right to bid on and host major sporting events, this helps to strengthen the influence of big developing nations in international politics. This entails establishing a new hierarchy within the international system as well as in international sports (Grix & Lee, 2013). There has been an increased political salience of sport among governments of different political kinds, who see mega sports events as a relatively cheap means of improving their nation's image, credibility, stature, and economic competitions and exercising dominance on the international stage (Grix & Lee, 2013).

Grix and Brannagan (2016) examined how Joseph Nye's theory of soft power has gained traction as a term for explaining why states—including developing states—are paying close attention to various forms of political and cultural appeal. They did this by analysing initiatives to address problems or providing an ideal model that outlines state soft power tactics. Grix & Brannagan (2016) note that political science and sports studies are used to define soft power and discuss how national leaders can obtain it in the context of mainstream international relations. This encompasses how attraction manifests itself in both short- and long-term power results. Grix & Brannagan (2016) expand on Joseph Nye's notion of soft power by focusing on sports and diplomacy, or sports diplomacy, which they refer to as the perfect kind of state soft power for use in upcoming empirical studies.

They argue that one of the problems with Nye's concept of soft power in academic discourse is that it has inspired debates that remain lofty with slippery concepts and opaque theories which make its use in research difficult (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). There has been a shift in the practice and attempt to manipulate soft power or the politics of attraction by liberal and illiberal states in international affairs. However, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) depict that the originality of this exegesis lies in the attempt to build out from an empirical study of sport diplomacy to construct a heuristic device that can be used in research to analyse further case

studies to understand the components of states soft power strategies. Most states see mega sports events as a wider diplomatic tool which cuts across all areas that can be considered as generating soft power. Grix & Brannagan, (2016) argues that the debates on soft power tend to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework with which to understand a state's soft power strategy.

However, to create a conceptual framework on how to understand a state's use of soft power, Grix & Brannagan (2016) investigated Qatar's sports diplomacy, which includes the country's claim to host the FIFA World Cup in 2022, and Germany's actual hosting of the 2006 FIFA World Cup. suggesting that a framework to comprehend states' soft power strategies by hosting major sporting events may be established by looking at similar situations. To Freeman, (2012), a nation's ability to organise events and the on-field success of its team in international athletic competitions both support nation-building and strengthen the country's reputation among global audiences and observers (Freeman, 2012). This can support national unity, foster nationalism, or increase the legitimacy of the state's administration both domestically and internationally (Freeman, 2012).

According to Mandell, institutionalised play and competition in sports and culture have become normal and profoundly ingrained in cultural life, as Freeman (2012) observed. People may know their favourite players or teams, but they may be unaware of how important sport is to the formation of their culture. On the other hand, it is not surprising that nationalism, politics, and sports are all closely related on a national and worldwide scale (Freeman, 2012; Mandell, 1999). Just like nationalism, sports create a mentality of us versus them and this can be unifying or dividing (Freeman, 2012). Brownell, (2008) discussed that the Olympics and FIFA World Cup are arguably the world's largest mega-sporting events that are filled with nationalistic rituals, from the singing of the national anthem, the raising of the national flag of the victorious athlete and the kissing of the nation's badge after or before a victory (Brownell, 2008). This

makes it ironic that while sports create a sense of global community with similar rules and practices, sports enhance a type of nationalism (Keys, 2013). Decision-makers are not immune to the sentiments and emotions sparked by sporting events, as Freeman (2012) notes. Politicians are engrossed in the thrill of winning and the sadness of losing. A government official aspires to be intimately linked to their nation's international sporting triumphs. For instance, national news media in America invites winning teams to the White House for photo ops and a chance to meet the president (Freeman, 2012). In the context of soft power, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) point out that there are four categories of the increasing influence of globalisation and the information revolution that have led to state's behaviour leading to an increase in the importance of soft forms of power. They propose that the first is on the increased use of soft power by academics, politicians and government authorities, private institutions and agencies, journalists and blog writers who have attempted to apply or adapt or measure soft power in their discussion of state-led policies. An example is the classification of the global obsession with K-pop music as a significant cog in South Korea's soft power offensive, one which has seen South Korea successfully overtake rivals like Japan as Asia's 'coolest child' (Measure, 2014; Grix & Brannagan, 2016). The second consists of politicians and government authorities who have referred to soft power in speeches and various state policies. An example is the former American Secretary of State, Hillary Clinton, referring to soft power and smart power at the 2013 Council for Foreign Relations in Washington (CBS, 2013; Grix & Brannagan, 2016). Similarly, In his speech on the importance of Scotland to Britain at the Olympic Park in East London in 2014, former British Prime Minister David Cameron described Britain's place in the world as a soft power superpower (Wintour, 2014). Another example is Chinese President Xi Jinping of the Chinese communist party who made a speech in Beijing in 2014 addressing the importance of raising China's soft power reach and the need to communicate China's message effectively to the world (Perlez, 2014).

Furthermore, countries like the United States have a workshop dedicated to the use of smart power at the United States Department of State's third annual conference on program evaluation in 2014. Similarly, the British Parliament 2013 established its committee on soft power and the UK's influence, which led to the publication of two volumes in March 2014. Finally, the centrality of soft power in the Australian government's public diplomacy strategy in 2014-16 lays out the state's plans to increase significant trade, investment and economic prosperity and promotion (Grix & Brannagan, 2016).

The third group includes the number of private institutions and agencies that are engaged in measuring the state's soft power. One example of such an organisation is the British Monocle Media Group, which together with the British Institute for Government publishes an annual soft power study that ranks the top thirty nations according to their government, diplomacy, food, culture, and sports (Monocle, 2022). Similarly, the Portland yearly Soft Power 30 tries to measure the soft power of countries via the public opinion of states and the top thirty countries based on diplomatic networks, cultural impact and government ideology (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). The fourth group consisted of academics who applied the concept of soft power in their attempt to theorise the states-led pursuit of soft power. for example, (Melissen, 2006) points out that it is cliché to state that soft power is more important in the global information age. This is because it validates the claims made by academics who contend that nations such as China are presently carrying out a soft power assault that involves UN peacekeeping missions and other humanitarian endeavours to promote its Confucius institutes overseas. It also covers China's ascent and the extent to which its media agencies, including Xinhua News Agency and Central China Television (CCTV), have gone global (Grix & Brannagan, 2016; Melissen, 2006).

Furthermore, In line with Melissen's (2006) point, other examples similar to China are India's international reputation for film excellence, business and technology which equates to soft

power (Blarel, 2012). Also, In the case of Russia, Nye, points out that Moscow failed to capitalise on the soft power opportunity and boost by hosting the 2014 Winter Olympic Games in Sochi which is an example of the use of Sport mega event as a signal of Russia's growing power (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). In sports studies, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) point out that soft power has taken longer around 20 years to gain traction within the sport study literature, longer than it took social capital. However, soft power as a growing concept in sports studies focuses on the identification of sport diplomacy or sport as a diplomatic or soft power tool for national political leaders and nations in general (Murray & Pigman, 2014).

2.5 International sports events as a soft power tool

It is important to clarify that the case study for this research is on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and Japan. However, it is important to clarify that it is appropriate and comparable to discuss different types of sport mega event. Especially in a case where countries like South Africa, Russia, Brazil, and Qatar have all hosted the FIFA World Cup which is perceived as a soft power or nation branding tool. Therefore, it is important to consider the FIFA World Cup as a mega and popular sports event in comparison to the Olympic Games as a soft power tool. Looking at how it has helped to build and improve the sport diplomacy of these countries. Grix & Brannagan, (2016) argues that the debates on soft power tend to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework to understand a state's soft power strategy. They point out that Nye failed to offer a solution about how states acquire soft power. However, by offering empirical examples of real-life cases to redress the lacuna of Nye's soft power. Grix & Brannagan, (2016) focused on an ideal type of scenario by drawing on empirical examples of Germany hosting the 2006 FIFA World Cup and Qatar's sport diplomacy to identify the universal application of soft power. Both case studies represent how a Western and non-Western state can apply soft power. Therefore, by adopting a four-year research strategy plan of data collection in conjunction with national

authorities in Europe, South America and the Middle East, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) generated a multi-state research project on leveraging strategies adopted by countries hosting mega-events.

In the case of Germany and Qatar, the data collection strategy was in two faces, the first is the collection of data analysis of documents between 2011 and 2015 in connection with foreign policy and soft power objectives of Germany and the Qatari authorities. The second stage included semi-structured interviews with key officials in Germany and Qatar between 2011 and 2015. Because sport is an under-researched but promising area for soft power and diplomacy, from their research Grix & Brannagan, (2016) decided to develop an ideal type of soft power to understand how states can use soft power. Secondly, Levermore & Budd (2004) points out that international relations and sport suffers from a case of continued neglect (Levermore & Budd, 2004) However, sports studies and literature have begun to engage with the political and diplomatic use of sport. Freeman, (2012) points out that mega sports events are significant soft power opportunities that act as major contributions to the improvement of a nation's image and the process, of profiling and highlighting themselves attractively and globally. Similarly, Lin, et al., (2008) point out that for international sporting success, athletic competition or staging of mega sports events provides an opportunity for states that seek to attract others with their values and culture and persuade them by projecting specific images, principles, achievements and visions to the foreign public (Lin, et al., 2008, pp. 23-32) Therefore, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) depicts that, another key reason to examine sport events cases as a soft power tool, is because sports events play a role in all five interlink states resources. These resources are important in a state's successful soft power strategy. Figure 1 below explains these five links;

(Grix & Brannagan, 2016). Fig.2

They point out that sport mega event includes culture and culture is central to making a state more attractive to others. This is one of the reasons Germany and China invest heavily in language institutes abroad; art, heritage, history and literature. Secondly, they depict that tourism has a close link with Branding and diplomacy and the fourth and fifth resources respectively are diplomacy and trade. They serve the purpose of attracting foreigners to the state, and they bring with them business for the tourist industry.

On the other hand, tourists can serve as multipliers passing on positive messages about the host country on their return home. Furthermore, Branding includes the aspects of tourism and culture and it helps to sell the country externally and this is an attempt to gain prestige on the world stage. Diplomacy is a broader aspect of the use of sports events as a soft power tool. Diplomacy entails the relationship between state-to-state relations, diplomacy includes the multiple actors who are involved in diplomatic relations. In this case, diplomacy includes state and non-state actors who undertake public diplomacy. In sport diplomacy, diplomacy includes the use of sports to achieve diplomatic purposes. For example, the role of the International Olympic Committee and other international non-governmental organisations is significantly increasing (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). Also in terms of trade resources, states use the above-

mentioned 5 resources for economic growth and increased global trade. Mega sports events are often used as a signal that a host nation has the required infrastructure and expertise to do business at the highest level (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). However, from the above-mentioned resources, art, language, national identity, morals and values are key characteristics of what an International sports event can offer.

In other words, mega sports events can positively impact, tourism growth, impact positively or negatively diplomatic relationships and affect trade. For example, a report from the Australian Tourist Commission suggested the accelerated development of Brand Australia by 10 years due to the Sydney Olympic Games in 2000. In the case of Germany, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) points out that hosting the 2006 FIFA World Cup offers an excellent example of how a state can actively seek to make itself more attractive and more influential on the world stage. In their interview with a desk officer at the German foreign office, the officer depicted that Germany spent almost a quarter of the whole foreign budget on culture and foreign policy which is almost 700 million Euro. Furthermore, the interview points out that, it is a long-term process of promotion of soft power, an attempt to bring people together and sport is a part of the promotion of Germany's culture (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). Germany believed that hosting the FIFA World Cup would help overcome its negative stereotype and help increase its tourism and position as an economic and scientific country. In an attempt to characterise an ideal type of soft power and to point out the possible ways that nations can gain soft power. Grix & Brannagan, (2016) developed a tabular strategy, Germany's soft power package of an ideal type of soft power through the hosting of mega sports events. As a long-term soft power strategy to use the FIFA World Cup as a tool to change its national image. The table below signifies the resources identified in the soft power ideal type, the cultural augmentation strategy that increased the international scope of Germany's World Cup in 40 different countries and 87 different international cities.

Germany's soft power Package (2006)

(Grix & Brannagan, 2016) Fig.3

From the aforementioned soft power package, the German Foreign Office implemented an overall cultural diplomacy strategy, with a focus on sport diplomacy (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). They arranged a whistle-stop welcome tour for each of the 31 qualifying nations, which had a significant positive impact on the event's media coverage. Additionally, in terms of trade, the 2006 FIFA World Cup was the most significant economic boost, according to a survey by the Association of German Chambers of Industry and Commerce. This was because German and international football fans were more eager to spend money. Almost 50% of all businesses reported a positive effect from the 2006 World Cup and increased sales in this context, and also, over two million tourists who attended the World Cup spent €600 million during the month of the tournament (Grix & Brannagan, 2016). However, the 2006 FIFA World Cup was identified as the underlying reason for the economic success of a positive business outcome. However, because reputational gain is hard to measure which is one of the dilemmas of soft

power. from Grix's research, the 2006 World Cup was a clear soft power strategy. Green (2007) points out that, such augmentation that includes putting on an activity, entertainment and services like mega sports events enhances and broadens the appeal of an event. However, in terms of explaining the soft power resources discussed by Grix, an augmentation of the World Cup as a soft power strategy identifies the overlap between soft power resources. For example, art, culture and heritage attract tourists and tourists attract trade if they stay long enough and spend money trade adds to the branding of Germany's image and all these help to make Germany a tourist destination.

Furthermore, in the case of Qatar, Qatar's growth in economics and wealth from the primary sale of crude oil and natural gas helps Qatar to invest heavily in its soft power through sport diplomacy. It is estimated that Qatar's nominal GDP per capita is almost double that of Germany's US\$93,965 compared to roughly US\$47, 589 and in the case of Qatar, a huge amount of its wealth has been invested in several sports events (IMF, 2022; Grix & Brannagan, 2016). Grix elaborates that most of Qatar's soft power objectives through sports rest upon the mechanisms of culture, tourism, branding, diplomacy and trade. But they argued that Qatar's engagement with international sports is recent and this means that the actual soft power outcomes have yet to materialise fully. However, they proposed an intended outcome that the Qatari government seeks to achieve. Below is Qatar's soft power package identified by Grix & Brannagan, (2016).

(Grix & Brannagan, 2016) Fig.4

Debunking negative perceptions and cultural stereotypes is one of Qatar's main objectives through sports. In this case, the Qatari authorities see the hosting of mega sports events as an ideal type of soft power to improve its standing on the international stage.

2.6 from soft power to soft disempowerment

This chapter has discussed soft power, defining it as a state's capacity to achieve its goals by attractiveness as opposed to force or bribery. Hard power, on the other hand, entails using force or financial inducements. When it comes to soft power, the host country can develop political agendas influenced by its desire to employ resources such as appealing cultures, progressive institutions, policies, and ideals (Nye, 2008). However, to project a favourable image and draw more tourists to their cultures, nations have started to employ soft power by holding massive sporting events. The hosting of sport mega events like the Olympic Games has seen illiberal nations or nations that are accused of human rights violations host these mega sports events.

For example, there have been critics and many articles discussions about host countries such as China, Russia and Qatar. These countries are accused of human rights violations and the opportunity to host mega sports events like the Olympics and FIFA World Cup.

However, scholars have discussed this as a soft power or smart power strategy, by addressing the case of Qatar as the host of the football World Cup Final in 2022, Brannagan & Giulianotti (2015) introduced the term soft disempowerment as a binary opposite term to soft power (Brannagan & Giulianotti, 2015). Because the hosting of mega sports events has become significant to the national government to increase its soft power through, cultural displays, the attraction of tourists and increased tourism, including the augmentation of national pride (Grix & Houlihan, 2014). But as Brannagan & Giulianotti (2015) point out, there's always a chance of soft disempowerment while trying to build powerful relationships. The term "soft disempowerment" describes situations in which a host nation may enrage, offend, or alienate people, which results in a decline in appeal or authority (Brannagan & Giulianotti, 2015). They make the point that the idea of "soft disempowerment" guarantees that academics and professionals think beyond the positive accumulation of soft power and instead consider how social acts can have both positive and bad effects that can either empower or disempower people.

Therefore, it is important to consider the term soft disempowerment because host nations are unprepared for the high level of global attention and scrutiny from the international media, human rights organisations, and the global public, (Chalip, 2006). For example, the 2008 Olympic Games were viewed as a soft power tool for China by advancing messages on ancient Chinese cultures and civilisation and gaining prestige from topping the medal table (Zhongying, 2008). The Beijing 2008 Olympic Games, in contrast, placed China in the critical position and spotlight in the context of its occupation of Tibet, the treatment of minorities such as the Uyghur people and high pollution levels, human rights and democracy (Brannagan &

Giulianotti, 2015; Nye, 2004). In this case, Brannagan & Giulianotti (2015), point out that the potential for negative publicity and loss of attraction can lead the host nations to lose more than they can gain in the context of destination image (Brannagan & Giulianotti, 2015; Higham, 1999).

LITERATURE REVIEW

PART TWO

2.2 What is Sport Diplomacy

According to Rofe (2016), a world-renowned expert on sports diplomacy with a broad research background, especially in the connections between the sporting world and diplomatic practice, there are many different actors and players involved in the diplomatic transactions brought about by sports. The interaction and comprehension between sport and diplomacy are furthered by these actors, which include individual athletes, national leagues and associations, and sports international governing structures, among others. According to Rofe (2016), there is a long-standing parallel between sport and diplomacy in international affairs, and both have been disregarded as ways to understand the relationships between various policies that are otherwise centred on nation-states (Rofe, 2016). According to Murray (2018), the word "sport diplomacy" is a recent addition that characterises a long-standing practice: the ability of sport to unite individuals, communities, and nations via a common passion for the game. In other words, Sport diplomacy, according to Murray (2018), is the deliberate, planned, and continuous use of sports, athletes, sporting events, and non-state actors to promote trade, development, education, policy, image, reputation, brand, and people-to-people relationships. Sport diplomacy can also be defined as a practice that helps the unique power of sport to bring people together, nations and communities. It is the use of sport to influence social, diplomatic, and political relationships (Stuart Murray, 2017; 2018). Explanatory, Sport diplomacy is the explanatory overplay to the network of evolving networks within the worlds of sport and diplomacy. Sport and diplomacy perform different functions but when examined closely, they serve the purpose of bringing different nations, cultures, and identities under one umbrella. Sport as a diplomatic tool is a soft power tool carried out by nations through international

sporting organisations, nation branding, technology, sports ambassadors and lobbying to show superiority and to share their cultures and ideas (Ari, et al., 2018).

Sports have transcended entertainment, though, and the political elite frequently takes advantage of them as they transition from conventional diplomacy to new diplomacy (Houlihan, 1997; Hill, 2003; Marvin, 1982; Howe, 2008). Sport diplomacy plays an interconnected public role in international governance, for example, the famous cricket diplomacy between Pakistan and Indian governors helped to reduce the tension over Kashmir (Showkat, 2013). Also, the introduction of 'Sport United' by the U.S. Department of State, sport diplomacy division aimed at bringing young Muslims in Africa, the Middle East, and South Asia together (sportanddev.org, 2015). By classifying sport diplomacy as a crucial idea of political, economic, social, and cultural exchanges, between nations, this strategy promotes international contact. Sports in many ways is a powerful tool for a lasting relationship between the government and the people because they attract people with differences in culture, identity, preference, and interest. According to Abdi et al. (2019), the main source of soft power as an interactive tool by the government is sport, and this is important to achieve the goals of public diplomacy. Sport provides an atmosphere and a condition for peace among nations and serves as an opportunity for diplomatic dialogue. Murray (2011) discussed that large sports events can bring people together and can lead to closer and more friendly relationships. However, the idea that mega sports events bring nations together may be seen as abstract if not explained clearly. This idea can be explained by the notion that mega sports events can create a positive relationship among nations, firstly, if there is a joint hosting between two nations, for example, the Korea-Japan 2002 FIFA World Cup. The second is in the context of public diplomacy and it involves the global interactions of sports fans and tourists from all over the world present in the host city. With this, it can then be argued that politics and culture can be recognised as an

important part of mega sports events or international sports events and therefore, categorised as sport diplomacy.

Historically, sports have been used as a powerful tool for both domestic and international peacebuilding and nation-building. Peacebuilding and nation-building have been achieved by hosting sports events via its image-building mechanisms, building a platform for dialogue, trust-building, reconciliation, integration, and anti-racism (Gates & Mogleiv, 2013). Gates (2013) points out that the mechanisms of sport diplomacy are not determined and controlled and can have unpremeditated consequences. South Africa is an example of how sport diplomacy plays a role in a domestic and international context. Before the end of apartheid and Mandela's rule, rugby in South Africa was a predominantly white sport (Bolsmann, 2014; Martin, 1984). The former president, Mandela used the rugby competition as an opportunity to create unity in South Africa. Rugby was moved from being a predominantly white sport to becoming a national sport played by all South Africans. This event was an opportunity through sport to create reconciliation and integration in a divided nation (Hoglund & Sunberg, 2008). A similar situation was in 1971 when the US table tennis team formally requested to be invited to China. The invitation, which resulted in friendly games between both teams, paved the way for the then US President Nixon to visit China, which as a result normalised the relationship between the USA and China (Murray, 2013). From these cases, sport diplomacy served as a peace-building mechanism between the two countries and in the case of South Africa, sport diplomacy served as a mechanism for peace, integration, and reconciliation. Furthermore, different countries have engaged in sport diplomacy in a variety of ways. In most cases, this comes in the form of hosting a mega sports event such as the Olympic Games and the FIFA World Cup. Other ways are through the sponsoring of sports exchange programs between countries or sports ministries.

Furthermore, diplomacy and international politics entail a culture of bargaining, which involves the process of give and take. This process is usually a strategic process expected to produce a result from the actions taken by the parties involved (Pouliot, 2016). However, In the process of sport diplomacy, there is a limitation to the process of give and take. This aspect of diplomacy and politics is driven by social norms and this social norm involves the mechanism of image building, building a platform for dialogue, trust building, reconciliation, and integration (Nygard & Gates, 2013). These mechanisms are not essentially attached to sport diplomacy or sport-related but can be applied in understanding sport diplomacy and its relationship to politics, diplomacy, and soft power.

In addition, sport as an institution and an instrument of soft power can be measured through four mechanisms. The first is image building, the second is sports events as a platform for dialogue, the third is sports as a tool for trust building between nations and lastly, sports as a catalyst for achieving reconciliation, integration, and promotion of anti-racism (Nygard & Gates, 2013). Firstly, hosting mega sports events puts the host nation at the centre of the world's attention for a period. Nations use this platform as an opportunity to utilise human capital and human resources that ordinarily would have been difficult to organise. Countries like China, South Africa and Brazil have been able to use mega sports events as a tool to announce their abilities as emerging world and economic powers (Cornelissen, 2010). For example, in the Sydney 2000 Olympic Games, North and South Korea decided to march under one flag during the Opening ceremony of the games (Lee, 2021). This highlights that image-building through sport can be used to achieve some form of political capital.

Image building through mega sports events on the other hand comes with its disadvantages. This means that in an attempt for the host nation to attract the world, part of the population is excluded or disadvantaged. For example, Mexico's policy was to relocate the poor out of the city during the 1968 Olympic Games. Another example is the protest from Brazilian citizens

against the methods used during the preparation of the 2014 FIFA World Cup and the 2016 Olympic Games are examples representing the disadvantage of Image-building efforts through sports mega-events (Gates & Mogleiv, 2013; Butler & Aicher, 2015). Mega sports events are also a platform for building the Image of not just the host nation but are utilised by other actors to gain recognition and awareness. The Black September attack on Israeli athletes in the 1972 Olympic Games is an example (Silke & Filippidou, 2020; Laor, 2022). In this case, the Olympic Games were used to capitalize on the symbolism of their cause. Furthermore, the 1980 Moscow Olympic Boycott by the USA protest of the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan, and the Soviet Union boycott of the Los Angeles 1984 Olympic Games in retaliation are examples of how other nations can counter the image-building effort of the hosting nation through the push of a certain political agenda (Dyreson, 2015; Eaton, 2016).

Furthermore, the Goodwill Games in Moscow was an opportunity for the USA and USSR to establish a channel for formal relations between both nations (Gates & Mogleiv, 2013). Likewise, Ping-pong diplomacy was an opportunity to open a peaceful dialogue between China and the USA (Hong & Sun, 2000). Historically, both South and North Korea have been in political and ideological conflicts since 1948. They attempted to reconcile in the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, where they discussed the opportunity for a united Korea, a second attempt was also made in the 1988 Seoul Olympics but was a failure. In the Sydney 2000, Olympic Games both countries decided to come under one flag (L.Churilov & Flitman, 2006).

In contrast, sports events can create an environment of displeasure on certain issues rather than dialogue. The case of Carlos and Smith raising their first black power salute during the US national anthem is an example. In this case, in contrast to dialogue, the IOC stripped them of their medals. In contrast to a similar situation, the IOC excused the continuous use of the Nazi salute by German athletes in the 1938 Berlin Olympic Games. Furthermore, sporting events may escalate more violence among nations with high tension and disagreement. The football

war in 1969 between Honduras and El Salvador is an example because the issues of land reforms and immigration created a huge tension between both nations. However, the 1970 FIFA World Cup Qualifying match and the riot during the game were a significant catalyst for the war (Gates & Mogleiv, 2013). In this case, sports were not a platform for dialogue but was a catalyst for war and provoking tension between the parties involved.

Since the resurrection of the Olympic Games, sports have been a regular feature of diplomatic relations but have been neglected in both theory and practice. Scholars focused more on the physical and domestic contribution of the games and sport was irrelevant to the *Haute politique* (Murray, 2017). Through the years of international politics, world war and the Cold War (international) sports have been present. However, sports were seen as less important during these times. The areas of theory and practice between (international) sport and (international) politics were a ‘backwater’, a ‘peripheral’ or ‘perfunctory aside’ (Murray, 2020). Chat (2016) in his work, *The Role of Sport in International Relations: National Rebirth and Renewal* discussed the importance of international sports (Olympic Games) specifically in Japan and cited examples of China and Russia. In the case of Japan, he based his argument on sport and national identity, that sport is a causal variable in determining national identity. This casual variable includes language, demography, history, strategic culture, religion, domestic politics, national leadership, and impact on national identity. Depicting that the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games was the renewal of the rebirth of post-war Japan. Explaining further, in the case of the 2014 Sochi Olympic Games, Vladimir Putin claimed that Russia is back and for the 2008 Beijing Olympic Games, they portrayed the games as marking three decades of Chinese modernization dating back to Deng Xiaoping (Chat, 2016). Therefore, these are all examples and narratives that suggest that sport diplomacy is the new form of diplomacy practice and how it is used is dependent on the country or the host country.

2.2.1 The theory and practice of sport diplomacy

Given a broadened understanding of sport and diplomacy, Rofe (2016) in the context of sport diplomacy, discussed and proposed a global diplomacy framework. His paper *Sport and Diplomacy: A Global Diplomacy Framework* challenged the narrow view of sport as simply a tool for traditional diplomacy. He argued for a more nuanced understanding of the complex relationship between the two phenomena by recognising the diverse actors involved and the multiple ways they interact. He emphasized the concept of global diplomacy which, transcends nation-states and involves a wider range of players like athletes, sports organisations, sponsors, and fans (Rofe, 2016). Furthermore, his framework is based on the three concepts of communication, representation, and negotiation. These concepts help us understand how different stakeholders use sports to communicate messages, represent identities and negotiate interests. Communication focuses on the exchange of information and the meaning of sport, for example, athletes carrying the national flag as a symbol of nationalism. Representation focuses on how sport is used to project national image and identities, both positive and negative and negotiations examine how actors use sport to achieve various goals, including political concessions, resolutions of conflicts and economic benefits (Rofe, 2016). However, it is important to acknowledge that it includes potential manipulation, politicisation and ethical concerns and examples of this are the exploitation of athletes, fuelling of nationalities tension, and human rights concerns. Therefore, there is a need for a deeper understanding of how sport and diplomacy intersect in a globalised world. This includes recognising the agency of various actors within sport diplomacy and moving away beyond a state-centric approach. Also, understanding the involving nature of sport and diplomacy, by acknowledging the increase in prominence of non-state actors and the impact of globalisation and digital technologies (Rofe, 2016).

Murray's (2018) book, *sport diplomacy origin, theory and Practice*, contextualised sport diplomacy and developed a theoretical framework for understanding sport diplomacy by distinguishing between four types of diplomacy: traditional, new, sport-as-diplomacy and sports anti-diplomacy. Similarly, Simon Rofe (2018) in his book *Sport and Diplomacy* explores the complex and multifaceted relationship between sport and diplomacy. He discussed in three parts, establishing the field of play by providing a conceptual overview of the field of sports diplomacy, types of sports diplomacy and the role of non-state actors in sports diplomacy the challenges and limitations (Rofe, 2018). Murray (2018) and Rofe (2018) discussed the role of non-state actors in sport diplomacy, arguing that they play an increasingly important role in sport diplomacy. However, they pointed out the challenges and limitations of using sport as a diplomatic tool, arguing that it is important to be realistic about the potential of sports diplomacy to achieve specific foreign policy objectives. Furthermore, Murray (2018) explained Traditional diplomacy as a characteristic of a realist state obsessed with survival, national interest and hard power and largely concerned with the traditional security agenda. Murray (2018) discussed traditional sport diplomacy as opportunistic use and strategic exploitation. In some cases, the abuse of elite sports, sports people, and sporting events to advance a state's foreign policy objective. However, while Murray called this form of sport diplomacy traditional, there is nothing new about this practice. Historical political events from the Olympic Games best describe Murray's traditional sport diplomacy. Putting into context, Hitler in the 1936 Olympic Games did not only use the Games to pass on the message Nazi propaganda but also that Germany was back, bigger, stronger, and better than everyone (Keys, 2013, pp. 134-135). More recently, in the case of China and the 2008 Olympic Games, the Games were used differently to send a narrative of strong nationalism via a good and positive performance from its opening ceremony. For the first time in the 2008 Olympic Games, China

topped the medal tally beating the USA and Russia. This sporting victory led to a growth in national pride and international confidence (Zhang, 2017).

However, in the history of the Olympic Games from 1896 till 2006, the USA has won the most medals with (2,520), Russia in second Place (1,865) and Germany (1681), these figures explain why Hilvoorde et al (2010, p.87) depicts that elite sport is the main vehicle for gaining national pride and inspiring national cohesion (Hilvoorde, et al., 2010). In the context of the 2008 Olympic Games and China's national pride, the hosting of the 2008 Olympic Games was an important platform for China's public diplomacy. Zhang (2016) depicts that before the Games, most of the world thought China was a nation of farmers standing in rice paddies wearing bamboo hats. However, during the opening ceremony of the Games, the image of China quickly changed. The 2008 Summer Olympic Games known as the most expensive aside from the Sochi Winter Olympics in 2014 was captivating and stunned a global television audience of about 1.1 billion people (Murray, 2017). The world witnessed a progressive, prosperous, civilized, urban, modern, and economic powerhouse, which was a pride of China.

Additionally, Murray (2018, p. 67) illustrates how traditional sport diplomacy appears to require the reinvention of a country's brand or image through major sporting events. Politically astute governments such as the United Kingdom (London 2012 Olympics), South Africa (2010 World Cup), and Brazil (2014 World Cup and 2016 Olympic Games) all sought after mega-events as an inexpensive way to boost their stature, image, economic competitiveness, and credibility, according to scholars like Grix and Lee (2013) and Acuto (2013). Murray and Pigman (2014, p.1102) acknowledged that the value of traditional sport diplomacy is that it amplifies a new message, promotes international understanding and friendship and dismisses stereotypes and biases. For example, the Germany 2006 World Cup was an example of and an opportunity for the introduction of 'destination Germany', which reemphasised a sense of national pride and improved the poor image, changing the already perceived stereotype of the

country (Grix, 2012). For example, The Japanese government and its Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA) have through football; deliberately tried to overcome stereotypes associated with the Second World War (Murray, 2018). This was done through the creation of the J-league in the 90s to improve the domestic and national Japanese football teams that will reflect the Japanese economic power and achievements after 40 years of post-war peace and prosperity (Mnazenreiter 2008). The Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs has also used football to maintain a peaceful environment for Japan's troops in Iraq and to bridge the divide between the Balkan states by inviting frequently Israeli and Palestinian youth players to participate in training camps in Japan (Manzenreiter, 2008). These kinds of activities also help to change the perception of Japanese to the foreign public, especially those involved with the programs. Finally, another characteristic of traditional sport diplomacy is the practice of boycotting. As Murray (2018, p.68) puts it, traditional sport diplomacy means 'we are not playing' or 'you are not allowed to play'. In this case, states act alone, or other states are banned from international competition or in most cases states boycott tournaments. In the 1920 Summer Olympic Games, Germany, Hungary, Austria, and Bulgaria were all banned from games held in Antwerp, Belgium for starting the First World War. Similar examples are the ban given to Germany and Japan from competing in the 1948 London Games. More recently, the sporting boycott of apartheid South Africa is a strong example of traditional sport diplomacy and a united message from nations all over the world against the apartheid regime. South Africa was banned from competing at the Olympics from 1964-1988 and was excluded from participating in other sports such as football, cricket, rugby, and many other sports.

The ability for states to withdraw or boycott an international sporting event may reflect the nation's ideological, policy and political stance on a matter. The Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan in December 1979, for instance, prompted the United States to boycott the 1980 Summer Olympics in Moscow. In this instance, the US president stated that the boycott was a

message to the Soviet Union that it could not oppress a sovereign state and continue conducting business with the rest of the world (Murray, 2018). More recently, due to the political upheaval in Zimbabwe, the England and Wales Cricket Board was encouraged by the British Government in 2009 to postpone their tour (Holden, 2009). Similar to this, due to Ukraine's selective justice system in the case of the opposition leader Yulia Tymoshenko, who is currently imprisoned, Britain, Germany, Sweden, and the European Union boycotted football matches played in Ukraine during the Euro 2012 tournament (Makarychev & Yatsyk, 2016). This was an action sending out a message that even during a sport completion, a blind eye cannot be turned on the issues of human rights. However, just like the evolution of diplomacy, the practice of sport diplomacy shears common practices with the practice of diplomacy, for example, the use of boycotts and bans as the equivalent of sanctions. Although sport diplomacy as a new diplomacy practice is a casual practice by countries.

2.2.2 Critics of Sport Diplomacy

By reflecting on the practice of traditional sport diplomacy, the use of sports for diplomatic purposes comes with some criticism from sports purists. The infringement of politicians into the business of sport or exploitation generated arguments about the mixture of sport and politics. Murray (2011) depicts that by looking at the good and bad sides of traditional sport diplomacy, it is a game of two halves. However, for sports purists, sports should be kept far away from politicians. People come to watch sports events and not the politicians or their activities (Addley, 2012). Redeker (2008, 495) explains that politicians think that they are leveraging sport as a strategic tool for political goals, but people pick up the opposite of what the state thinks they are sending. To Redeker (2008), national and international politics are nothing but just empty sounds when after passing through the gates of sport.

Furthermore, another criticism is that both institutions, sport and politics are not compatible. This is because, in diplomacy, the notion is to create a positive atmosphere and a possible win-win, but on the other hand, for elite and international sports, winning is everything with no evidence of a future relation except to win again (Murray & Pigman, 2014). Another criticism is that in traditional diplomacy, sport diplomacy does not work and rarely changes anything. For example, in the case of the Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan in 1980, the boycott proved to be ineffective. This is because the Soviet Union did not withdraw from Afghanistan until February 1989 when the communist experiment began to hit rock bottom. Similarly, before the 2018 Football World Cup in Russia, Russia had tens of thousands of troops in Eastern Ukraine and troops in Georgia, Russia's self-proclaim Republic. The Ukrainian president urged nations to boycott the 2018 FIFA World Cup to be held in Russia if it does not pull its troops out of Ukraine's territory (Reuters, 2015). However, in this case, international politics and diplomacy outweigh the soft power ability of sport (football in this case). The 2018 FIFA World Cup was held in Russia and during the build-up to international tournaments in Russia, revelations from newspapers depicted the corruption in the Russian Government and the protest the attitude towards the rights of minority groups in Russia (Sauer, 2022). Furthermore, even if nations boycotted the tournament, it was unlikely that Russia would have changed its mind looking at the case of the invasion of Afghanistan. Therefore, it appears that World powers like Russia do not regard the Olympic Truce as all IOC members contributing to peace and diplomatic solutions to the world's conflict. The former president of the IOC (1972-1975) said the games must go on and this was said shortly after the terrorist attack at the 1972 Munich Olympic Games, coming from an organisation known to be against the politicisation of sport (Guttman, 1984).

2.2.3 limitations and importance of sport diplomacy

There are limitations to how effective sport diplomacy can become, Key (2013), discussed that the real sources of power in international relations, sports are irrelevant but just playing games cannot change the shape of hard power and robust national interests such as security and economics. Murray (2018) depicts that traditional sport diplomacy is just a cute novelty in the political space. This context makes the literature dialogue on the evolution of diplomacy clearer. It explains where the discussion depicts that the state will always be in control of political and sovereign entities regardless of its diplomatic pluralisation and the emergence of new actors (non-state actors) in international relations.

To Hocking et al. (2012, p. 5), nations must embrace both continuity and change to have an integrative diplomacy that reflects the multiplicity of actors in twenty-first-century diplomacy. Continuity and change require attempting new things. This means that through cultural, digital, and public diplomacy, the government must come up with creative ways to engage the public. This creates a diverse and plural network for a democratised system that involves a win-win environment for states and non-state actors through partnership. Furthermore, sport diplomacy, still growing in theory and practice is a part of new diplomacy or simply public diplomacy with the characteristics of an inclusive network model that consists of state, and non-state actors, public partnership, and recognition. In other words, the government's Ministry of Foreign Affairs oversees and assesses the government's sport diplomacy plans and initiatives, which have the potential to improve a country's standing, influence, and power (Murray, 2018). In the twenty-first century, there is a growing importance of (new) diplomacy and soft power. However, in a globalised age, soft power is a huge and growing practice utilised by all state and non-state actors, which involves the use of music, art and sport and is recognised not as a backwater but as a tool that is increasingly important to a state's foreign policy and Image.

Sport diplomacy (sport) as a social institution is representative of the plurality and stands as a problem-solving tool in the twenty-first century (Friedman, 2007). This explains clearly, why Melissen (2011) discussed the democratisation of diplomacy that involves the attempt by Ministries of Foreign Affairs to work with unconventional non-state diplomatic actors, and public and individual actors to enhance soft power initiatives. This means working with civil society players that will progressively increase their legitimacy, credibility, and soft power in the international arena. In this case, a state can connect on a variety of sports levels in achieving these goals. This could be from amateur to elite sport and from domestic or national to international sport, the media, Mega events etc. For example, the Australian sport diplomacy strategy (2015 p.1) Sport diplomacy is the deliberate, planned, and consistent employment of sports, athletes, competitions, and non-state sporting actors by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and its diplomatic personnel. To establish a mutually beneficial long-term partnership that optimises government potential in commerce, investment, culture, people-to-people interactions, education, and tourism (dfat.gov.au, 2015-2018). With this definition, sport diplomacy is the utilisation of a fraction of diplomacy or international relations to bring together the collaboration of the public, private, state, and non-state actors to achieve a foreign policy objective. Furthermore, given the discussion on the evolution of diplomacy and sport (sport diplomacy) as an institution of global soft power, there are reasons why sport diplomacy is important.

To Murray and Pigman (2014, p 1102), sport diplomacy conveys vitality to modern diplomacy and positive proof that the Ministry of Foreign Affairs can adapt, reform, and remain relevant. The use of sport as a diplomatic tool in this case means that it is an original pioneering form of international engagement. To Hocking (2013, p.123) sport diplomacy is important because it illustrates that the Foreign Affairs Ministries are modern and progressive network institutions that are democratic and open. Another importance is that sport diplomacy aligns positively

with public diplomacy as discussed in the previous section. Sport diplomacy shares common characteristics and purposes with public diplomacy in the sense that it is utility for the government to break down barriers between the public and estrange states (Hocking, 2006). For example, a characteristic of Australian public diplomacy is to create a positive image in the Pacific region, especially the small island states. This is done through the Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. The practicality of sport diplomacy is another reason why it has become important to the government. As Keech and Houlihan (1999, 112) noted, international relations advances built around sports are low risk, low cost, and regularly high profile. For example, it is easy for a government to associate itself with mega sports events and in turn test how the public at home or abroad reacts to a change in foreign policy. Finally, sport diplomacy is generally seen as a positive, soft power tool, a means to bring people together, and settle a conflict between people and nations as explained earlier. Sport diplomacy as a soft power tool is far more appealing than hard power, which is the power of attraction in other words (Nye 1990, 166-167).

2.2.4 Historical overview of Japan's sport diplomacy from 1930-2020

Japan had an international reputation as a war nation in the 1930s, and this included its history of imperialism across Asia. At the time, the Olympic Games were only held in Western countries, and it was an opportunity for Japan to challenge the Games by making the Games universal (Collins, 2014). In 1940, Japan was close to rebranding its identity with the opportunity to host the Games, but the Games were cancelled because of the 1938-second Sino-Japanese War (Belson, 2020). The 1940 Olympic Games would have become the first Games to be held in Asia. The bid was successful in two ways: first, a domestic campaign was launched to persuade government officials of the nationalistic benefits of hosting the Games, and second, an international campaign was launched to market Tokyo as a destination that will make the

Olympic Games universal (Collins, 2014, p. 1129). According to Collins (2014), the campaign was sparked by Japan's chaotic political structure in the 1930s, which forced the nation to expand militarily throughout the national government and hindered the creation of a national leader to support the Tokyo campaign.

Japan took a bold move that validated the relationship between sport and politics (Mega event). This is because Japan sought the counsel of ambassadors and diplomats who were not IOC members; this action sparked a dispute inside the IOC as the campaign deviated from the IOC convention (Collins, 2014). The plan emphasised Japan's exceptional capacity to meld the distinctive legacy and culture of the "East," which was defined as the industrialization and modernization that came from the West (Collins, 2014, p. 1130). The 1940 Games were directly linked to nationalistic ideas, the 2,600th anniversary of Kigen, the bushido (way of the warrior), and the spirit of Japan (Seishin). The idea at the time demonstrated Japan's ability to successfully modernise while preserving its distinct national identity, which combines the best aspects of the East and the West. People-to-people interactions, or people-diplomacy as some may refer to it, were another important component. The Tokyo organising committee presented the Olympics to the government as a platform for advancing the bid to win over the Japanese people and show the world what Japan is really like.

In addition, Glynn (2008) outlined how "the majority of Olympic Games cities attempt to capitalise on their experience as global players by creating a legacy of social, cultural, economic, educational, and reputational benefits for the community, such as sustainable economic development, urban revitalisation, tourism, residential quality of life, or urban image." (Shimizu, 2014; Glynn, 2008). These factors are what Japan hoped to achieve at the 1940 Olympic Games. Shimizu (2014) opines that there is strong political power among the candidates who bid to host the Olympic Games. In the context of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, the campaign was primarily led by the Japanese government at the time presenting the

rebuilding of the capital city of Tokyo and using the remarkable past war experience, to portray the economic growth of the country.

The bid for the 1964 Olympic Games was focused on the contribution to rebuilding Tokyo and demonstrating to the world that Japan as a nation had achieved a lot including economic growth. Since hosting the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, Tokyo has shown an interest in hosting the Games a second time. During the Cold War period and at the time when the Japanese foreign policy was guarded by the legacies of war and the pressures of the Cold War, hosting the 1964 Olympic Games became an alternative tool to engage with the international community. In 1964 and before 1964, hosting the Olympic Games revolved around the elevation of Japan's international position.

The IOC also assessed the responses to the questionnaire submitted by towns vying to be considered as potential hosts of the 2006 games in January 2008. The IOC Evaluation Commission said in September 2009 that Tokyo had the lowest support rate of all the host cities, with 55% of its inhabitants expressing support. Following Japan's withdrawal as a bidder for the 2006 Olympics, the Tokyo government responded by claiming that Japan was unable to obtain intelligence abroad. In addition, they added that Japan at the time was incapable of social interaction. The Tokyo governor at the time stated that the mentality of the Japanese people was assuming wrongly that the world thinks the same way as they do which was naïve. However, he explained that bidding for the games was a good experience and there would be an all-out war in the future when bidding for the games (Shimizu, 2014, p. 607).

Furthermore, Tamaki (2019), suggests that a global city like Tokyo has become a beneficiary of globalisation. The growth of mega-cities such as Beijing, Shanghai and Seoul through globalisation has made these cities become rivals to Japan. However, according to Tamaki (2019), the concept of place is still significant even though Tokyo, as a global metropolis,

aspires for globalisation. Tokyo benefits from the network effect, which is the phenomenon wherein individuals and organisations are drawn to the city due to the concentration of several activities there. (Tamaki, 2019). The emergence of megacities in Asia such as Beijing, Shanghai and Seoul has made policy elites in Japan search for a new medium to distinguish Tokyo from the rest of its Asian rivals. However, hosting the 2021 Olympic Games can be a breakthrough event for achieving this agenda. The ability to organise a modern Olympic Games may be a point of transformation of Japan's identity narratives. According to Manzenreiter (2006, p. 151), "sport can simultaneously give a magnificent grand theatre and secular ritual, popular entertainment and communal celebrations" in the context of globalisation. But to bid for an Olympics today, one must deal with the IOC's mounting emphasis on matters like sustainability and location importance. According to Manzenreiter (2006, p. 157), athletic events continue to serve as a vehicle for a light-hearted portrayal of national identity. According to Kelly (2011, p. 2267), Tokyo was under pressure to appeal to East Asia's growing economic and ideological prominence as a region, which was consistent with the IOC's vision for the future of the Olympics (Kelly, 2011, p. 2267). Neehuas & Tagsold (2011, p. 406) explain that within the context of globalisation, there is a need to portray a 'Japaneseness' (uniqueness) (Neehuas & Tagsold, 2011). To Kelly (2009, p.1), the symbol of Tokyo in the 2016 bid signified the mission to unite the old and the new Japan. He explained further that Japan felt that the IOC had fewer expectations and had not fully acknowledged the region and the bid for the 2016 Olympic Games was about shorting Japan's image and international status (Kelly, 2009, p. 2).

In addition, modern Olympic Games are characterised and entail a lengthy bidding process and rigorous construction of infrastructure. The Games constitute a lengthy requirement for the projection of legacy and the movement is a means of localism, nationalism, regionalism, and globalism (Kelly, 2009, p. 3). Horn & Manzenreiter (2004, p. 195) argues that despite the

improvement in the economic and social environment, sport mega-events still provide a means for a safe form of expressing nationalism and creating a rare opportunity to daze the quietness many people have felt about the obvious displays of nationalism and the expressions of national identity since 1945. In the context of the Olympics, Tamaki (2019, p.6) depicts that the status of Tokyo as a global city elicits alternative stories of ‘otherness’ to emerge. Horn & Manzenreiter (2012, p. 109) explain that there is a need for cities to invest in iconic spaces for them to show their presence to the world. They argued that this is because sport mega events have increasingly made states embrace construction lobbies, which often embrace cronyism (Horn & Manzenreiter, 2004, pp. 190-191). Therefore, the organisers of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games must differentiate Tokyo from the world and its Asian cities. The modern Olympic Game depicts a universal language and global inclusion. However, the frequent bidding on the Olympic Games by Japan depicts that Japan knows the benefits of hosting the Olympic Games, which will serve as a national branding strategy through sport diplomacy and as a vehicle for its soft power.

2.2.5 Limitations of Japan’s Sport Diplomacy

The failed 2016 bid symbolised peace and maturity as well as a subtle reference to the post-war identity of pacifism and the decision to include the cities of Hiroshima and Nagasaki in the national awareness-raising campaign, which was an attempt to reinforce Japan's uniqueness. The Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games stood for peace and reconstruction (Tamaki, 2019). Although the Tokyo 2021 Olympics are confirmed, Tamaki (2019) contended that there are sceptics in Asia who wonder if Tokyo is qualified to host the Games. In the Straits Times piece, he went into more detail about this. An English language newspaper based in Singapore, in February 2017, the organizers decided to seek the ‘support’ of anime characters as a ‘strategy to lure more tourists to its shores using manga and anime’ while there is still lasting anxiety over the

fallout from the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear disaster (Tamaki, 2019, p. 12). An observation made by the (Agency France-Press and Reuters), depicts that there is a concern over ‘latent xenophobia’ in Japan- which points to another blunt reminder of the Japanese condescension towards Asia (Tamaki, 2019, p. 12). However, another observation made by the South China Post on the use of racial profiling by the Japanese police and the concerns over the purportedly ‘normalised standard procedure with Japanese police’ using ‘racialised caricature’ (Tamaki, 2019, p. 12). Furthermore, Tamaki (2019) went on to explain that there have been reports on an online petition, mainly from South Korean residents who have called on the IOC not to select Tokyo, due to Japan’s failure to recognise ‘the massive and inhumane atrocities’ committed in Asia during the war (Tamaki, 2019, p. 12).

However, these issues are a reminder to the organisers of the 2021 Olympic Games that the story of Japan's focus on the future did not go well with the rest of Asia. The New Straits Times reports that the resistance to migration is one of the challenges of population decline and it is an aspect of Japan's racialised worldwide view (Times, 2018). Domestic discontent is seen as another issue facing the Tokyo Olympics. This is because, the ability of Tokyo to attract all the attention and infrastructural investment depicts that the other regions are being sidelined, in trying to compete for capital and labour with Tokyo. Saiki, (2015, p. 34) Alarms that the total focus on Tokyo will undercut the oratory of including an ‘all-Japan’ if the irrationalities of infrastructure become specious.

Moreover, Nakamura (2018, pp. 5–6) contends that Japan would have recovered from the 3/11 tragedy if the periphery was included in the task. To the degree that rural areas were used to justify infrastructure improvements around Tokyo to win the bid to host the games. The regions should put more emphasis on rebuilding than on taking part in the national Olympic celebration. There has been a confrontation from a civic group named Neo Olympic 2020, they argued that cleaning up after the nuclear contamination should be the primary purpose rather

than spending so much on the Olympics (Tamaki, 2019). They went further to argue that there is a nationalistic facet towards the Olympics, stating that the 2020 Olympics is nothing but an interstate rivalry in disguise (Tamaki, 2019). Highlighting the domestic desertification of the Olympic Games. Criticism has been made regarding the hosting of the 2021 Olympics games, one of the criticisms among others is that the Tokyo 2020 Olympics is effectively a ‘fait accompli by the state’, which enables the government to ignore its issues of governance, particularly over the spiralling cost (Tamaki, 2019, p. 13).

2.2.6 The relationship between the Olympic Games, Japan’s politics, diplomacy, and sport

To Abel (2012, p. 203), even though the attempt for Japan to gain a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council failed, and the attempt to gain international recognition was lagging, there was still a lasting attempt to translate the image of ‘Cool Japan’ connected to the popular-culture export into a source of soft power. During the time of the Cold War, the Japanese foreign ministry used cultural means to improve Japan’s international position as early as the 1920s (Abel, 2012). History has shown that the image of Japan in the international community was struggling to gain acceptance, however, (Abel, 2012, p. 204) explains that the withdrawal of Japan from the League of Nations in 1933 did not stop the International Committee on Intellectual Cooperation to spearhead the formation of a national organisation for international cultural exchange. The efforts to improve cultural activities were seen as a non-controversial area for Japan’s reintegration into the international community and such efforts continued into the post-war period. This explains why (Abel, 2012, p. 203) depicts that ‘the persistent notion that sports are separate from politics helped to smooth Japan's return into the international community’.

In addition, while there was a concern about the image of Japan, Japan presented itself to the foreign audience through both the physical infrastructure and the attitudes of the people during

the Olympic Games in 1964. After the Second World War, the quest for Japan and the lingering devastation of the war, it was important for post-war Japanese leaders to improve international trade and improve the relationship with many countries and the correction of the negative image of Japan. At the time, there was also a need to maintain a security alliance with the United States, which also conflicted with the desire to improve their relationship with the rest of Asia. Abel (2012, p. 204) explains that the use of hard power by Japan was limited and this made foreign affairs experts follow a pattern that evolved during the Cold War to turn to soft power alternatives like cultural exchanges and popular international events.

In Addition, it was in this circumstance that Tokyo made its initial desire to host the Olympics. To Abel (2012, p. 204), highlighting a quote from Akira Iriye's publications *Cultural Internationalism and World Order* that 'culture, by being officially sponsored and promoted, was becoming politicised'. However, Japan at the end of the war did not loosen the governmental grip on cultural diplomacy and history has shown that the Olympics has always provided an understanding of the complex nature and relationship between culture and politics. By answering the question, of why the myth of separation of sport from politics persists, Abel argues that 'this myth has such stubborn staying power precisely because the sheen of the apolitical is an essential ingredient for political use of the games and indeed of any cultural endeavour turned to political uses. According to Abel (2012) 'cultural internationalism was powerful because the idea of transcending politics had meant' and people believed it and in the case of the Olympics, repeated it almost as a mantra' (Abel, 2012, p. 205). This has allowed possible controversial political content to be inserted with little dispute.

However, in the case of Japan, while there was resistance to Japan's participation in some multilateral organisations after the war, the apolitical nature of the Olympics provided an uncontroversial platform for Japan to reengage with the international community. The Olympic Games are noteworthy to the history of internationalism, and this is because of the apolitical

representation that has been used towards an obvious political expiration. In the aspect of Soft Power and for the relevance of this research, the Olympics has shed a sprouting role in soft power change in Japan's diplomacy over time. The concept of soft power as explained by Joseph Nye is the ability of a nation to be able to attract other nations through its culture, political ideas, and policies and if done the right way, it will make other nations cooperate without conflicts (Joseph S. Nye, 2004). According to (Joseph S. Nye, 2004), 'when policies are seen as legitimate in the eyes of others, soft power is enhanced' (Abel, 2012, p. 205). Nye (2004) also recognised the potential of the cultural influence conferred by Japanese popular culture. In addition, Nye explains that soft power is built primarily by civil societies and that governments are not fully in control of it. But soft power can turn political if a government tries to regulate it. In that case, the idea of soft power could lose some of its usefulness. Thus, "the notion that sport diplomacy is carried out by private individuals—as in the Olympic "people's diplomacy"—lends it greater credibility" (Abel, 2012, p. 205).

Previous sections of this review chapter have shown that sport diplomacy was not new in 1964 nor specific to Japan, the Olympics in its way has been political from the beginning. The efforts for a host country to use the Games to promote a specific political or diplomatic narrative are not new. For example, the 1936 Olympic Games were held in Germany at the time Adolf Hitler was the German chancellor. Concerning Tokyo and the Olympics, the reconstruction of cultural avenues of international engagement that were developed during the war which has become an important part of Japan's foreign policy has gained a move to the forefront with the deployment of 'cool Japan' (Abel, 2012, p. 206). Therefore, in the context of the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games, this leads to the framework of Japan's sports diplomacy as a vehicle for its soft power in three major components. The first is linking diplomacy to an international athletic event. The second is the role of technology in presenting a new national image as a prominent aspect of the Japanese new image. The third is the effort to make Japan more internationalist by

welcoming foreign visitors to a ‘world-class’ capital city by developing the Japanese people into a strong, ‘international’ citizenry, and through the sports events themselves (Abel, 2012, p. 206). The flow chart has been developed in the data analysis chapter to help simplify Abel’s (2012) soft power role in the context of Japan and the 1964 Olympic Games.

2.2.7 What is diplomacy?

Diplomacy is defined as the representation and governing of a recognised society in a fraction of the global political arena. In other words, diplomacy is the representation of sovereign states by officials called diplomats through peaceful means of negotiation and bargaining in world politics to improve relationships among sovereign states (Bridgman, 2015). Traditionally, the study of diplomacy and practices entails an ideal function on what skills diplomats should have such as being knowledgeable in the art of negotiations and resolving negotiations and disputes, to define and represent the national interest of their states. This ideal type of diplomatic skill is centred on functionalism, that the functions of a diplomat should be to negotiate, represent, communicate, and gather information. It is important to note that diplomacy is the engine room in international relations and according to Wight and Butterfield (1966. P.10-12) while the master institution in international politics is diplomacy, achieving foreign policy goals is always the main objective and diplomacy is a means to achieving the required set goals or objectives.

Diplomacy has evolved in the 21st century, with several emerging patterns of diplomatic processes including the fast growth and involvement of non-governmental actors in the mix (Langhorne, 2005). Diplomatic practice is state-centric but with a mixture of several unorthodox forms of political practices by states. This is because of the fast-growing factors of globalisation. However, this does not exclude the practice of old diplomacy but recognises the presence of what is known as new forms of diplomacy practices that involve non-state actors

or non-governmental organisations. Because of globalisation and the increase in the interdependence of states in global political affairs. New forms of diplomacy entail direct interaction with counterpart ministries across borders. In a multinational setting, new forms of diplomacy include an increased involvement of non-governmental organisations in international politics through delegation and forms of indirect rule. In this case, new forms of diplomacy open a new state-society interface at a global level (Castells, 2008; Kelley, 2010).

In a broader context, Military professionals have begun to develop new practices in mediation that will help them interact with a variety of existing actors and this is important for peacekeeping missions (Atkinson, 2014). Actors such as lawyers are involved in the daily legal interactions between states providing an authoritative and legal interpretation of other actors' schemes. Also, religious organisations and economists are not exempt from this category, because of the capacity of religious actors; they are powerful in organising transnational communities and economists can get more involved in diplomatic practices because of the expertise that entails economic governance. Therefore, the emerging practices of new diplomacy indicate that the states engage with various non-state actors in certain foreign policy affairs (Kelley, 2010).

Diplomacy is a political system that the state uses to exercise its centralised control over its social and economic affairs. However, sharing the influence and space of diplomacy with non-state actors has given rise to new forms of diplomatic practice. Non-state actors have been able to demonstrate impressive skills by influencing and shaping foreign policy in various ways that foreign ministries have not been able to comprehend. Kelly (2010) points out that the diplomatic profession is doing nothing more than pluralising, this means that the process by which foreign ministries open themselves to the public increases the chances and materialisation of the evolution of diplomacy into new diplomacy. This is because of the radical ways non-state actors or agencies are built (Kelley, 2010). In addition, this also means that the

age of diplomacy as an institution has given room for the age of diplomacy as a behaviour (Fitzpatrick, 2007). Traditionally, the age of diplomacy and international affairs are managed exclusively by state and state-sanctioned representatives (Baumann & Stengel, 2014). However, this has not changed and is still managed in the same manner and the processes that the diplomatic institution is built. States still hold conventional and exclusive control over international agendas and decide on matters that are of priority to their sovereignty. Diplomatic institutions are fundamentally structured so that states can decide on all substantive international actions. Furthermore, with diplomatic agencies, the directive of diplomatic actions is unchanged which means that policy drives diplomatic actions and not the other way.

2.2.8 How has diplomacy changed?

The exclusive control of the diplomatic structure does not mean that diplomacy acts unchallenged in international affairs. This means that the exclusive focus on traditional forms of international political power such as military and economic strength, which includes sanctions to smaller states and geographical advantage or rule over, gives room for these decisions to undercut the power of information (Langhorne, 2005). This means that the contemporary political atmosphere gives room for an unprecedented influence amid the rise of various global actors on the state. Non-state actors in international politics can bridge the gap by providing influential changes and unprecedented contributions that can shape policies and political actions in ways that diplomats cannot (Gelman, 2000). It is important to point out that traditional forms of diplomacy remain important in international affairs but with few changes to adapt to the current nature of contemporary diplomacy.

Furthermore, state sovereignty means that a sovereign state provides the necessary mandate for diplomatic actions, and this means that states appointed diplomats are important in diplomatic institutions. However, diplomacy has been able to integrate new approaches into the traditional

diplomatic model without sacrificing the centrality of its agents and institutions. The changing practice of diplomacy gave room for new diplomacy, understanding new diplomacy means understanding old diplomacy. While diplomacy is a neutral signifier of general interactions between political entities, Leira (2018) and Buckle (2012) point out that new diplomacy is as old as the concept of diplomacy. However, from the French Revolution, diplomacy was seen as ambiguous and carrying a negative connotation of aristocracy, duplicity, secrecy, privilege and mania for war alliance (Leira, 2018; Buckle, 2012). Because of the increase in radicalisation and revolution for change during the French Revolution, from the period of 1789 to 1792, French foreign affairs were in principle and were still in total prerogative from 1790 to 1791. However, the increased distrust of old diplomacy led to the establishment of a comite diplomatique of the French constitution assembly in 1790 (Caiani, 2012; Howe, 2008). The purpose of the committee was to check the practical and existing treaty of the old (monarch) and the desire to check and abandon the royal prerogative over external affairs. Before the French Revolution, diplomacy (old diplomacy) was in alignment with the monarch, which explains its characteristics of aristocracy, secrecy and mania for war and alliance. However, the revolution for a check in the internal affairs and the abandonment of the royal prerogative explains the term old diplomacy to new diplomacy.

Leira (2018) depicts that old diplomacy is complicated and not always a successful machine for the preservation of peace. However, new diplomacy is the extending and seeking or displaying of a new market and new material for peace. Jahn (2007) discusses that new diplomacy is the combination of liberal narratives and expansion (Jahn, 2007), An example associated with the combination of liberal ideas can be drawn from the statement made by an American diplomat who explained that American diplomacy is the reverse of the European diplomat where they work by intrigue and dissimulation (Melissen, 2005). In other words, American diplomacy entails asking for what they want and insisting upon it. What this means

is that the new diplomacy is knowing what they want and insisting upon it openly. However, according to Melissen (2005), new diplomacy is knowing what they want, fearlessly saying it and insisting upon it with disregard for consequences (Melissen, 2005). Furthermore, the liberal idea mentioned above is part of the earliest form of new diplomacy, which was implanted into the scholarly debates about the Great War, which led to a recurrent rejection, and debate of diplomacy and towards a newer form of diplomacy.

In summary, old diplomacy was categorised under the failures to avoid war and new diplomacy is the promise and hope for peace and mutual aid. The notion behind new diplomacy is to organise and aid international cooperation, but international cooperation is flawed. However, new diplomacy addresses issues in a more contemporary manner rather than a remnant of aristocracy, the consequence of war and the contrast of democracy. New diplomacy is characterised by the growth and development of the international organisation and the increase in economic development, technology and change in communication and weapons of ideology and conflict resolution. However, according to Gurgu and Cociuban (2016), Buckle (2012), and Zhu (2013), Newness is primarily the rapid growth of diplomacy services and functions, particularly the many functions related to intelligence, culture, education, propaganda and public diplomacy (Gurgu & Cociuban, 2016; Buckle, 2012; Zhu, 2013). Others like Kjellen (2004), and Legrand & Stone (2018) saw new diplomacy in the many international activities of government, which take place outside the channels of traditional diplomacy such as global sustainability and science in transnational governance impact (Legrand & Stone, 2018; Kjellen, 2004).

Furthermore, new diplomacy is essential to the reformation, training, planning, and improvement of communication and for a stronger conversation. Unlike old diplomacy, which was used as an analytical term in the past, new diplomacy is a combination of both political and analytical dimensions. In addition, the discourse around new diplomacy is centred on the

growth of diplomacy regarding new actors, arenas, institutions and practices and this includes the growing number of fields and actors that are considered diplomatic. This means that diplomacy has grown from connecting with just a fixed embassy, ministry or regularised diplomatic interaction and is now a set of approaches that is applicable across boundaries. Secondly, the thread of new diplomacy is the increase in the association of public diplomacy. A Canadian ambassador previously observed that the new diplomacy differs from the old diplomacy in that it is mostly public diplomacy and calls for different abilities, strategies, and levels of expertise (Melissen, 2005). This means that the conduct of diplomacy as new diplomacy is a new practice directed towards engaging the public rather than only the state government. New diplomacy is, however, a reduced state-centric practice in both analytical and policy terms. Therefore, it is important to recognise that diplomacy is now in a hybrid form, in other words, both old and new diplomacy coexist to strengthen one another.

2.2.9 TYPES OF DIPLOMACY

2.2.9.1 Public Diplomacy

Public diplomacy can be defined as any government effort focused on communicating with the foreign public. Gregory and Cull (2009) discussed that, before and during the Cold War, image building, propaganda and information directed towards the foreign public is what is known as public diplomacy today (Gregory & Cull, 2009). To Melissen (2005), public diplomacy is said to be as old as diplomacy itself. This is because, in ancient times, monarchs and their representatives were not ignorant of the importance and the consequence of public opinion among foreign nationals. For example, E.H. Carr wrote that power over opinion was not less essential for political purposes than military and economic power and has been associated with them closely (Carr, 1939).

However, the increased debate is on how countries can wield the power of attraction, public diplomacy, and soft power effectively. In postmodern international relations, countries that are likely to gain more attraction are those that can solve issues and improve cultures and ideas that are closely related to international norms that may be seen as credible and attractive abroad. Therefore, public diplomacy is a key instrument of soft power and new diplomacy (Melissen, 2005). To Gilboa (2008), Gregory (2008), and Cull (2013), one can understand public diplomacy through several categories, the first is on democratic accountability, and the second is through the intensification of social networks that transcend national and international boundaries. It also includes various factors such as the social relations represented by the impact of civil societies, terrorist organisations, the global financial market and the way people view their world and their places in each of these spaces and the global environment.

The third is the impact and development of technology such as cyber diplomacy, innovation in communication and information technology on foreign policy and diplomacy. The fourth category is like the third, and it is the impact of the media, which is key to public diplomacy. This includes the electronic media, which is not only a tool for the government but has now become a tool for the public in voicing out their opinion and can determine national or foreign policy. Additionally, there is a relationship between public diplomacy and image building also called nation branding. Nation branding is the process and possibilities of states to rebrand themselves in the global environment through various means such as the display of culture, education, and hosting of mega sports events (Gilboa, 2008; Gregory & Cull, 2009). Public diplomacy is also the management of a national reputation by a state, and this is a source of state power. In public diplomacy, national reputation in its simplest form is the construct of a state culture, policy, and conduct. However, public diplomacy entails the government process of creating an understanding of its nation's ideas, institutions and culture as national goals and policies. Achieving these goals and policies involves TV and radio broadcasts, film, books,

magazines, social media platforms, cultural and educational exchange, and the hosting of mega sports events such as the Tokyo 2021 Olympic Games.

Furthermore, it would be erroneous not to depict that public diplomacy and public opinion (domestic or foreign opinion) have a cognisant view on issues related to cross-national borders and foreign policy. However, what is certain is that for effective public diplomacy, public opinion creates an environment of opinion that drives the actions of policymakers to make effective or swift decisions. An environment triggered by public opinion may create, broaden, or limit the choices of policymakers. However, this relates to the earlier discussion that the perception of the foreign public concerning a state may become critical about decisions made. However, this means that positive and effective public diplomacy is the management of information flow, especially in the contemporary world of globalisation and information technology.

2.2.9.2 The Overlap between public diplomacy and nation branding

The practice of nation branding aligns with the strategies of marketing but in the case of a state, the promoted product is a country's culture, values, principles, and ideologies. The practice of nation branding involves a much more complex organisation than public diplomacy. This is because the practice of public diplomacy involves practitioners whereas, nation branding is the mobilisation of all national forces that can contribute to promoting its image abroad (Melissen, 2005). Public diplomacy and nation branding have overlapping features, and this explains why foreign ministries in most countries for example Japan, have goals and initiatives set aside for branding like the Cool Japan initiatives. In nation branding, marketing is the master of all discipline that involves communication. However, marketing in the context of nation branding means communication with the foreign public. This means that the principles of marketing are applied to international relations and in context, public diplomacy (Szondi, 2008). On the

contrary, marketing and nation branding do not serve the two discourses if they are completely separated. They are different but with a similar goal which is to increase the salience of the state's identity. State Officials are beginning to look for and leverage opportunities that will differentiate them from similar ideas with their neighbours that may be recognised as the bottom of the group of nations. For example, countries like China and Japan have made good use of international events (such as the Olympic Games) to show how different they are from their counterparts and the rest of the world. The difference associated with nation branding and public diplomacy is that branding portrays a level of ambition that edges out the aims and modesty of public diplomacy (Szondi, 2008). This means that for public diplomats, the world is recognised as a marketplace and diplomatic communication is only a part of a multi-layered transnational communication process (Raboy & Padovani, 2010).

2.2.9.3 Cultural diplomacy

The olive tree, a powerful microstate and emblem of the goddess Athena on the Mediterranean Sea's edge, served as the ultimate defender of the ancient city of Athens. The sea god Poseidon, the adversary represented by the string wave that causes marine storms. This god represents the vast Mediterranean Sea, the region, which was highly integrated and cosmopolitan, and the time when people were solely aware of the world. The large Poseidon Sea's powerful waves and the olive tree engaged in a historic battle (Friedman, 2000, pp. 26-34). The olive tree is a symbol of modern states and nations that are valiantly battling the powerful waves of the globalising sea, according to Tevdovski (2009). They may be an ancient tree on a rock, but their distinct cultural values and traditions are the only thing ensuring that countries will not be destroyed by the new global cultural flood (Tevdovski, 2009). The reality of globalisation has remained constant and is creating a change in the knowledge of people through education, expressive culture, and values, which may become a threat to all forms and practices of local

and national cultures and identities, thus forming a new cultural complexity with a large vacuum for cultural clashes around the world. Countries are beginning to invest in preserving and developing their culture, to show their values and identity to the world and in turn, to approach the ideas, principles, and values of other countries.

Culture serves as a metaphor for a necessary component of modern international relations, and cultural diplomacy has developed into one of the most prestigious instruments in diplomatic tactics over time. Although cultural relations are distinct from diplomacy, it has historically been practised near it. However, current advancements in both domains indicate that there is an overlap between the two concepts. This was stated by Melissen (2005). (Melissen, 2005, p. 19). Culture and diplomacy are important in international relations and have a history of concurrence. They are both based on dialogue and represent the need and desire of people and countries to have a good understanding of each other, their interests and their languages.

History has shown that culture has been present in playing an important role in the interaction of states. The presentation of gifts among the ancient rulers, books and rare artefacts were used as gestures of respect or appreciation, which also highlights the exposure of the cultures of states and rules depicting their wealth and values (Tevdovski, 2009). Throughout history, academics, artists, and musicians have shaped their societies and supported their governments in promoting and advancing their cultures as well as influencing political agendas. For instance, Aristotle, one of the greatest philosophers, actively promoted Macedonian interests in Athens, while Ruben, one of the most renowned figures in art history, was a royal artist and a powerful Holy Sea ambassador (Constantinou & Sharp, 2016). The first professional diplomats were persons of art, culture, language, and manners in the seventh and eighteenth centuries (Treverton & Jones, 2005). However, Decentralisation and democratisation in states, societies and on a global level have brought a huge complexity and a multi-layered relationship in the field of culture and diplomacy. The wider representation of people, government, public

institutions, big multinational companies, societies, and politics has brought different ways for the representation of people from diverse forms of civic organization.

Furthermore, from the perspective of modern society, culture has become very complex. Not exempting arts and folklore but the rise in urbanisation, design, fashion and cuisine and the development or inclusion of all categories of human reality has become an aspect of culture expressively and artistically. However, diplomacy in the 21st century involves the collaboration of diverse diplomats from different sectors and backgrounds working closely with professionals in the field, including academia and media as equal partners. States are represented by their culture and aspirations, the media, global television, sport, and music have all come to play a factor in modern diplomacy and are now an important part of culture and dialogue. This component, therefore, shapes the view of people and policymakers. Moualla and McPherson (2019) explored the potential of community archaeology as a tool for building inclusive societies and fostering cultural heritage in the context of Mozan, Syria. They discussed that community archaeology can act as a form of soft power to transform isolated communities into more inclusive societies. This includes enhancing dialogue and mutual understanding through collaborative activities like sharing stories, excavation, and interpretation by individuals from different backgrounds. They also talked about the shifting of symbolic community thinking, by engaging with their past, communities develop a shared sense of identity and belonging, promoting social cohesion (Moualla & McPherson, 2019).

Furthermore, Bond, et al. (2007) explain that culture should not be seen as subordinate or a constructive element of diplomacy but as a basic concept. However, in the quest to satisfy, the complex needs and identity of people, cultural diplomacy entails the collaboration between the government, the city council, professional institutions of culture, and the media (Bond, et al., 2007). Tevdovski, (2009) discussed that to enable successful cultural diplomacy, the presentation of a particular message or narrative of different states is carried equally by political

leaders, diplomats and cultural attaché, cooperation, social and image strategies including ideological movements and religious leaders. The world is interconnected and full of diverse cultures and values of nations and people. The complex nature of states has urged states to present and purpose their values and identity and at the same time try to approach the ideas and values of other states, which entails dialogue, debates and sometimes being an inspiration to others.

Furthermore, diplomacy is like gardening, according to Schultz (2005); you develop awareness and confidence while pulling weeds when you are young. That way, you'll have a strong foundation to work from in case of emergency (Shulltz, 2005). The head of the British Council in Paris, Paul de Quincey, said that you should show them what you can do rather than just preaching. According to the US Department of State's Advisory Committee on Cultural Diplomacy, the purpose of cultural diplomacy is to sow ideas, artistic methods and gadgets, political and philosophical debates, spiritual perspectives, and worldviews that may take root and grow abroad (US Department of State, 2005). As an inevitable part of diplomacy, culture is a representation of contemporary diplomacy in international relations. Few states have been able to utilise the art of using, effective, and durable public policies in the practice of cultural diplomacy.

From the standpoints of education and public diplomacy, Ang, et al. (2015) describe cultural diplomacy as "the exchanges of individuals and ideas that directly touch a relatively restricted number of people and are concerned with the promotion of a long-term mutual understanding between peoples" (Ang, et al., 2015). According to Tevdoski (2009), the term "conventional diplomacy" was created by certain states' diplomatic procedures (Tevdovski, 2009, p. 22). This encompasses information or knowledge transfer, educational exchanges, cultural programming, government-sponsored broadcasting, and the Cold War (Ivey & Cleggett, 2002). However, Jakhar (2019) argued that this is no better than state-sponsored propaganda, for

example in 2019, China's Confucius Institute was criticised for using its cultural program for propaganda purposes. They are seen as platforms for an authoritarian government like China to propagate a state-approved narrative; the reason is that the Chinese government is a government that is hostile to liberal ideas like free speech and free enquiry (Jakhar, 2019).

Art critic Aline B. Saarinen coined the phrase "cultural diplomacy" in the New York Times magazine in 1954. Former special assistant to the secretary of state Robert H. Thayer first used it in a political context in 1959. (Stelowska, 2015, p. 62). In a broader sense, the definition of cultural diplomacy revolves around the use of heritage, cultural products, and transactions, which could include education exchanges by a state as a way of enlightening and improving its identity, and quality to support its political, economic, and foreign policy objectives (Scott-Smith, 2018). Arndt (2006) made a distinction between cultural relations and cultural diplomacy. Cultural relations are said to grow naturally and originally without the help of the government, and cultural diplomacy is said to take place when formal diplomats, serving the national government try to shape the channel from a natural flow of cultural relations to an advanced flow of national interest (Arndt, 2006). Cumming (2003) argues that though countries like France have used the term cultural diplomacy since the late nineteenth century, cultural diplomacy became common with other countries in the 1990s (Cumming, 2003). In addition, (Ang, et al., 2015, p. 2) portray cultural diplomacy as a term in which much of it determinate is interest-driven 'stricto sensu'.

2.2.9.4 The overlap of cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy

Cultural diplomacy can be classified as a component of the 'Pantheon of reputed creation of the brand of a place, the brand of a country and the brand of perception and public diplomacy' (Stelowska, 2015, p. 63). Cultural diplomacy is a tool for diplomacy and is often recognised as a component of public diplomacy. Mark (2009) explains in his publication 'Discussion Papers

in Diplomacy' that cultural diplomacy is a subset of public diplomacy (Mark, 2009). In other words, cultural diplomacy is used as a government tool to support its foreign policy goals or diplomatic endeavours. In addition, the government use cultural diplomacy to communicate with a foreign audience to influence or push a certain narrative, and this is also evidence of public diplomacy. Cultural diplomacy is said to be a practice, which is undertaken to gain a certain normative and idealistic goal, which is couched in a form of mutual understanding (Cummings, 2003).

Scholars like Mitchell see cultural diplomacy as a political unit that carries out cultural relations, Mitchell went on to explain that independent agencies undertake international cultural relations and government agencies undertake cultural diplomacy. An example is the British Council, which is the UK's international organisation for cultural relations and education opportunities (Britishcouncil.org, 2023). The British Council aims to create a piece of friendly knowledge and understanding between the UK and other countries through the creation of opportunities, connection development and trust engagement. The British Council has worked with more than a hundred countries across the world in areas of arts, culture, and the English language. In 2019, more than eighty million people were reached directly and 791 million people overall including online and through broadcasts and publications (Britishcouncil.org, 2023). However, the British Council claims to be a registered charity organisation that engages in people-to-people interaction and is sponsored by the Foreign and Commonwealth Office Department.

Furthermore, Mark (2009) explains that there is no agreement on what culture is and that the term 'culture' may mean different things to a different society, although he depicts that traditionally the cultural part of cultural diplomacy is a high culture which includes Visual arts, literature, theatre, dance, and music. The British Council report namely the art of peace; the value of culture in post-conflict recovery highlights academic reasons for the use of art and

culture as a form of therapy in post-conflict regions. However, they used Rwanda as an example where the use of shared cultural heritage has been a key factor in the government's effort to create a unifying identity and to heal ethnic division following the genocide in 1994. The report also examined how art is used as therapy reaching over 2,000 children since 2015. Protecting children from criminal exploitation and criminal gangs since the start of the Syrian seven-year civil war, the theatre that was staged in 2015 is used as a method to reflect on the Syrian crisis and to demonstrate the civilization of Syria and how it has survived the previous crisis. However, this is aimed to help the audience imagine a better future after the conflict (McPherson, et al., 2019). Cultural diplomacy has evolved over the years. It now involves 'popular culture', which are cultural activities, and entertainment that attract the mass population. The way cultural activities are used can make it easy to differentiate facets of cultural diplomacy practices. For example, educational diplomacy involves student exchange programs, and art diplomacy and sport diplomacy involve various forms of art and various forms of sport development or exchange programmes. Mark, (2009, p. 6) explains that irrespective of how cultural diplomacy is used, there is little explanation for where the boundary lines are.

Scholars like Leonard and Sablosky share similar views that cultural diplomacy is a part of public diplomacy, and its key objective is to build a long-term relationship (Sablosky, 2003). Other views suggest that the practice of cultural diplomacy is done overseas. For example, the Institute for Cultural Diplomacy defines cultural diplomacy as a course of action, which is based on and utilises the exchange of ideas, values, traditions and other aspects of culture or identity, whether to strengthen relationships or enhance socio-cultural cooperation. To promote national interests and beyond' they went on to explain that cultural diplomacy can be practised by the public and private sectors (culturaldiplomacy.org, 2019). Milton Cumming an American scholar defines it as the 'the exchange of ideas, information, art, and order aspects of culture

among nations and their peoples to foster mutual understanding among nations’, (Cumming, 2003, p. 1). Furthermore, this explains the reason why some scholars see Cultural diplomacy as a tool or practice of public diplomacy. If Cultural diplomacy is practised as a means aimed at the public of a foreign country, then it can be concluded that it is a practice for public diplomacy, though this goes further and includes health, education, trust in government etc.

Nicolas Cull in an opening speech, given at the Harmony or Discord: exploring the impact of Music Diplomacy. A conference organised by the APDS at the University of Southern California, explains four forms of Cultural Diplomacy. The first is in the form of a gift, cultural information, presenting something less popular to a foreign audience, cultural dialogue, which leads to deepening and teaching cultural skills which leads to understanding and cooperation and cultural capacity building which is teaching cultural skills to promote understanding (Cull, 2015). Cultural diplomacy as discussed can be practised by both the government and non-governmental organisations but tends to be favoured by nation-states. Evan H. Potter in his publication *Branding Canada: projecting Canada’s soft power through Public Diplomacy* argues that Cultural Diplomacy like other forms of diplomacy needs to have a defined government input financially and ideologically otherwise it may not be seen as Cultural Diplomacy. Therefore, it can be said that there are similarities or relationships between cultural diplomacy and public diplomacy. Both practices develop relationships with the foreign public over a given period.

2.2.10 Research Gap

The literature review has discussed diplomacy, the evolution of diplomacy and other forms of diplomacy including sport diplomacy as a new type of diplomacy used by the ministries of foreign affairs as a soft power tool. However, because this research has adopted soft power as a concept. By investigating the concept of soft power, this research has identified gaps in the

literature review around the use and application of sport diplomacy as a vehicle for soft power. The key arguments leading to the gap in the literature are; that scholars have not yet developed or tested empirically a theory on the conditions under which a government can use soft power to their advantage (Kroenig, et al., 2010). Grix & Brannagan, (2016) argue that the debates on soft power tend to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework with which to understand a state's soft power strategy. Vuving, (2009) points out that one of the reasons for the widespread misunderstanding of soft power by scholars is the context that soft power is under-theorised and lacks academic refinement and analytical fuzziness. Similarly, and agreeing with (Mingjiang, 2009; Ichihara, 2006; and Womack, 2009) respectively, they argued that the equation of power with power resources is another reason for the misunderstanding of soft power. Pointing out that, limited serious efforts have been made to theorise the causal mechanism between domestic politics and foreign policy, despite the need to bridge the gap between comparative politics and international relations. In Nye's article, *soft power: The means to success in world politics*, he pointed out that soft power was only one concept of power and rarely sufficient by itself (Nye, 2004) (Nye, 2017). He pointed out that soft power is not a normative concept, and it is not necessarily better to twist minds and that 'Bad' people like Osama bin Laden can exercise soft power (Nye, 2017 , p. 2). Nye, (2017) points out that soft power was only one component of power and that the ability to combine hard and soft power into strategies where they reinforce each other could be considered 'smart power' (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State).

Secondly, Rofe (2016) argued for a more nuanced understanding of the complex relationship between the two phenomena of sport and diplomacy by recognising the diverse actors involved and the multiple ways they interact. Emphasising the concept of global diplomacy which, transcends nation-states and involves a wider range of players like athletes, sports

organisations, sponsors, and fans. Furthermore, proposing his framework that is based on the three concepts of communication, representation, and negotiation. To help us understand how different stakeholders use sports to communicate messages, represent identities and negotiate interest. Pointing out the need for a deeper understanding of how sport and diplomacy intersect in a globalised world, by acknowledging the increase in prominence of non-state actors and the impact of globalisation and digital technologies (Rofe, 2016).

Consequently, from the above, this research takes into consideration the argument that debates on soft power tend to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework. Equally, Soft power is under-theorised with limited resources and soft power is a normative concept. Furthermore, Nye (2017) notes that soft power is only one facet of power and that smart power is the capacity to integrate hard and soft power into mutually reinforcing strategies (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State). Although, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) provided a framework for identifying an ideal soft power using the case of Germany's 2006 FIFA World Cup and Qatar's 2020 FIFA World Cup. This research argues that there is a need for theorising soft power. It is important to restate that the research questions have been logically derived in an evidence-based way and the research questions were developed after interrogating the literature on the research topic and case study. This research will fill in this gap by answering the following,

1. What is an Ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool?
2. How can soft power be theorised as a concept in international politics and sport diplomacy as a vehicle?

This research hopes that by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, these gaps can be filled using the appropriate methodology.

CHAPTER THREE

3.1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter lays out the methodological consideration to achieve the research aim of investigating Japan's soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a Vehicle for its soft power. This chapter examines the nature of the study by understanding its main features of classical realism and interpretivism research paradigms. This research does not only justify the research paradigm that leads to the methodological justification, but it also points out the ontological and epistemological positioning of the research aims and objectives. Secondly, this section discusses the different strategies used best to understand and obtain knowledge of how the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was used as a soft power strategy. This includes examining the rationale behind the utilisation of a case study approach and a qualitative approach and concentrating on the semi-structured interview, secondary data analysis and analysis of government documents. By taking the research paradigm, strategies, and methods into consideration, they built together the purpose of collecting relevant data to answer the research aims and objectives.

3.2 ONTOLOGY AND EPISTEMOLOGY

It is important to explore and consider the ontology, epistemology positioning and research paradigms; it helps to understand the perceptions, beliefs, assumptions, and the nature of reality and truth concerning the research design (Sanders & Thronhill, 2009). They help shape and influence the research structure, data collection methods, and findings. Also, it is important to ensure that the research bias is minimised, understood, and exposed. Researchers are often influenced by sets of concepts and are often unaware of these influences on their thinking.

Blaikie (2000) explains this as a series of choices that researchers must consider, recognising the alignment that connects back to the original research problem (Blaikie, 2000). The incompatibility of a method with the research work may be the case if there is a failure to connect methods back to the original research problem. In social sciences, this is important because of the human element that is introduced as characteristic of a free will that may add complexity beyond what is seen in natural sciences (Blaikie, 1993). To understand the research philosophical underpinning of this research, it is important to understand the two key concepts of ontology and epistemology. They are important to show clarity in understanding the research paradigms and methodological application.

3.3 ONTOLOGY

Ontology is the views of the nature of reality and being, in social science, ontology involves the claims about the existence of things, what they look like, what units make them up, and how these units interact with each other (Blaikie, 1993). Ontology is the description of one's view, claims and assumption on the reality of nature citing if the objective reality exists or just a subjective reality created in one's mind (Blaikie, 2000). For example, looking at how individuals or groups determine or understand the existence of their reality, (Hatch & Cunliffe, 2006) highlights the complex nature of considering concepts such as culture, power and control, questioning if the reality of the concepts exists through the experience of it (subjective) or if it exists independently of those who live it (objective). Hatch & Cunliffe, (2006) argue that through a systematic approach to research, presuppositions and biases can be examined and addressed. This means that there is a need for the researcher to exclude their opinion and assumptions to investigate the research sincerely. The researcher's ontological position is a solution to the question of what the nature of the social and political reality is to be investigated (Grix, 2002). However, political reality is a key word because this research has a focus on

sports diplomacy, and it entails the investigation of an international relations or political concept- soft power.

3.4 Classical Realism and Interpretivism

Classical realism and interpretivism approaches are ontological positions that point out social phenomena, their meaning and their existence on the independence of social actors. Firstly, realism points out that the states are the main actors in the system of international relations and that there is no supranational international authority. This means that the state acts in its own selfish interest and states want or acquire power for self-preservation (Meyers, 2013). However, Classical realism suggests that human nature and domestic politics are the key factors in explaining a state's behaviour and the causes of interstate conflicts (Rose, 2011). Classical realism also suggests that humans act out of fear of aggression and are self-interested, they are generally not fundamentally benevolent, and this reflects states in international politics because of international anarchy (Wyatt-Walter, 1996). However, this is debatable because, from a structural realist perspective, some states act out of aggression not the fear of aggression from another, because of how powerful or dominant they want to become in the international system (Mearsheimer, 2007). Second, interpretivism incorporates human interest into the research. Interpretive researchers work on the assumption that language, consciousness, shared meaning, and tools are how one can access reality, regardless of how it is socially produced. Interpretivism is a term used to categorise several perspectives, such as social constructivism, and it disapproves of objective theories that hold that meaning exists in the universe apart from consciousness (Parsons, 2010). Interpretivist researchers may not use a variety of techniques to reflect various facets of the problem, instead concentrating on meaning (Bahari, 2010). However, by using different methods under interpretivist positioning, constructivism theory lends itself to the understanding that social phenomena are consistently accomplished by social

actors. This means that social interactions are in a constant state of revision and not only interaction. Secondly, because the aim of this research is not to measure soft power but to investigate the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy, objectivism is not a consideration for this research. Adopting objectivism and social constructivism means that the research will have to measure and formulate a method to discuss the measurement of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy.

As this research is focused on Japan as a case study, East Asia became a focal point in the hosting of mega sports events, especially the Olympics. For example, prior to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the 2018 Winter Olympics in Pyeongchang, Republic of Korea and the 2008 Beijing Olympics in China called this the Era of East Asia. Geopolitically from the perspective of classical realism, Prior to the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games, the literature review discussed Japan's political state as pacifist its constitutional war clause that renounces war and military foreign military engagement. Japan is extremely interested in hosting mega sports events from a historical context, the 1940 Olympic Games, the 1964 Olympics Games, the failed bid of the 2016 Olympic Games and then the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Given Japan's history of war and cultural imperialism and the significance of the 1964 Olympic Games, these events reveal the importance of using the Games as a soft power strategy for Japan. Cultural engagement and active sports diplomacy have become part of Japan's foreign policy and soft power strategy if Japan must remain active in global affairs. Considering the international system from the realist assumption where states seek self-preservation, the geopolitical unrest in East Asia and the ability of Japan's neighbours to wield soft (Smart) power is a concerning factor for Japan. Adopting classical realism will help the researcher to investigate Japan's national and foreign policy strategy. The hosting of mega sports events is an opportunity for a country to open its society, and display its culture, identity and economic strength. Japan has been able to do this by setting up a foundation by hosting the 1964 Olympic Games, the 2019 Rugby World Cup

and recently the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. This research asserts that it is an opportunity to make Japan an active player in Global affairs. In addition, as Japan's former Prime Minister, Shinzo Abe also points out through his ambition of trying to revise Japan's pacifist constitution to make Japan a first-tier country. This means, Investigating Japan's sport diplomacy that is investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy and what it means for Japan in global and regional affairs. As mentioned earlier, there are several ontological assumptions made towards research. When considering the different views that exist in terms of what constitutes reality? The question of how can that reality be measured and what constitutes the knowledge of that reality should be asked. This then leads to the idea of Epistemology.

3.5 EPISTEMOLOGY

Epistemology is simply the theory of knowledge. It helps to connect the relationship between the researcher (ontology) and what can be known from the research topic or problem. In other words, epistemology considers what establishes reality and considers the most appropriate ways into the nature of what is acknowledged as a possible reality. Erikson & Kovalainen (2008) ask about what knowledge is and the sources and limitations (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). Chia (2002) defines knowledge as the possibility of how and what to know and the need to gain reliable and verifiable knowledge reflected through the standard of methods used (Chia, 2002). Epistemology is defined by Hatch and Cunliffe (2006) as understanding how knowledge is formed, asking questions about how to tell good information from bad knowledge, and determining how reality should be presented or explained (Hatch & Cunliffe, 2006). In other words, epistemology reflects on the views of what is known about the world and how one can get to know it. To Grix (2002), the fundamental focus of epistemology is the process of

knowledge acquisition that goes into creating new models or theories that are superior to those that already exist (Grix, 2002, p. 177).

Positivism and interpretivism are two epistemological positions in research. In understanding epistemology, positivism advocates that epistemological position should be approached from the methods of natural sciences to the study of social sciences. Positivism suggests that objective reality should be applied to social interpretation and as far as empirical evidence and experimentation are concerned; logic and mathematical proof should be considered. Researchers who follow the objectivism assumption will follow the lead of epistemology positivism (Levy, 2015). Positivism relies on the numerical and statistical positioning of analysis. On the other hand, Interpretivism is an epistemological standing that takes into consideration the differences between objects and people in natural sciences and requires the subjective views of the social scientist to find the meaning of the social actors involved. A positivist researcher can argue that without the provision of concrete numeric and statistical facts, the investigation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games would be quirky. This is of the view that the social world realities can be studied and applied to the natural world, the explanation for studying the social world is value-free, and the explanations of casual nature can be provided (Yilmaz, 2013). However, because this research seeks to investigate the Tokyo Olympic Games as a soft power strategy coupled with the subjective components of the concept of soft power, it is difficult to apply the positivist positioning to this research. Braun & Clarke (2022) discussed that narrative is a good and accepted way of gathering quality data for interpretivism. It is also critical to note that narrative/interpretation provides and emphasizes the relationship and dimension of events, practices, and behaviours (Braun & Clarke, 2022). Therefore, as discussed in the literature review and the conceptual framework, it is difficult to measure a country's soft power and there is no exact prescription for doing so. In addition, this

is considered as the limitation of this research; however, it is important to reiterate that this research has proposed to fill this limitation or Gap by seeking to answer.

1. What is an Ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool?
2. How can soft power be theorised as a concept in international politics using sport diplomacy as a soft power tool?

It is important to point out that in the planning and execution of this research, this research made use of the paradigm-driven approach. This approach was instrumental in the development of the research gap and question. Punch (2014) discussed that the paradigm-driven approach entails beginning with a paradigm, and articulation of the paradigm, which then leads to the development of questions and methods. This contrasts with a pragmatic approach where the research begins with a research question that needs to be answered and then chooses methods for answering them (Punch, 2014).

3.6 DEDUCTIVE AND INDUCTIVE APPROACH

Two main traditional philosophical views on developing theories in both natural and social sciences are the Inductive and deductive strategies. These two broad approaches are linked between theory and research. The inductive approach is focused on a specific to a more general objective while the deductive starts with a general focus and ends with a specific one. In the inductive approach, measures and arguments are best measured based on observation or experience (Williams, 2007). In the inductive process, it is considered that facts can speak for themselves and are separate from the interpretation of researchers. In contrast, deductive approaches or arguments are based on laws, rules, and a variety of widely accepted principles. Creswell and Clark (2011) depicted that deductive research operates from a top-down process,

from theory to hypotheses to data that is added or contradicts theory (Creswell & Clark, 2011). They define Inductive research as a bottom-up approach, using the views of participants to build broader themes and to generate a theory of interconnected themes (Creswell & Clark, 2011). There are weak points in both inductive and deductive strategies. In inductive strategy, the justification of an inductive approach may be an issue since it is based on observation without room for basic assumption. The weakness associated with the deductive approach is that the empirical evidence falsifies the theory. However, the observations of researchers are not neutral and have been informed by preconceptions and values that are already theory-laden. This study adopts a deductive approach which entails the application of a deductive base approach to the literature review. Based on a case study design and approach, the case study on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games will help to draw a boundary in the research and to gain a deeper understanding by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as Japan's soft power strategy. In deductive research, the relationship between theory and social research involves the development of a conceptual framework based on the knowledge of a specific variable or domain that can be applied in fieldwork. Furthermore, arranging these approaches in a systematic order, the deductive approach starts with theory-observation-findings. However, this study contains a significant process of deductive approach.

3.7 Qualitative and Quantitative method

Qualitative and quantitative methods have their differences relating to questions of an ontological and epistemological nature of research. A quantitative method is concerned with the counting and measuring of variables and specific areas in social life. A quantitative method emphasises the quantification of data collection and the use of a deductive approach to finding the relationship between theory and research. Quantitative research is focused on testing theories and incorporating the practice and norms of the natural science model through

positivism and representing the views of social life objectively (Jick, 1979). The qualitative method relies on interpretive or critical social science, logic is applied in practice, and a linear path is followed in the research. In other words, a qualitative method is concerned with the production of a discursive, descriptive exploration of social actors and their meaning and interpretation (Ngulube, 2015). The qualitative approach considers the theoretical and philosophical perspectives rather than concentrating only on a single topic. The qualitative method is fundamentally interpretative; words are emphasised in the collection of data and analysis. Additionally, an interpretative process entails the iterative process being combined with the simultaneous processes of data collection, analysis, and writing up, as well as the back and forth between these stages (Scotland, 2012). Qualitative approaches also encompass participant observation, in-depth interviews, case studies, and ethnographic research.

This study adopts a qualitative research approach; this is because of the interpretative study and nature of the research. In analysis, a qualitative method helps to look deeper into problems and discover new thoughts and individual views. In comparison with a quantitative study, qualitative research has advantages. First, qualitative research aids in describing social groups or circumstances within a cultural framework so that one may comprehend how and why the participants act in certain ways. Second, qualitative research facilitates the gathering of open-ended, evolving data, which is crucial for determining the main purpose of themes from data, as opposed to testing preset themes against data. Thirdly, a qualitative approach is suitable for usage when the study issue is novel, has not been applied to a prior or group of people, and the researcher is unclear about the key variables (Creswell, 2003). An important characteristic of qualitative research is the ability to view events, norms, values, and actions from the perspective of the people being studied (Austin & Sutton, 2014). This is important to achieve the research aim of this study taking and observing the image of the social reality created by the Tokyo 2021 Olympic Games and the socially constructed realities by the actors involved.

In qualitative research, the field of study is not artificial or situated in the lab but involves the study of interactions and practices between the actors. This way, the research can be explored in detail and bring to light the full extent of the subject's account. However, this relates to what meaning is in qualitative data in a case study as it lends itself to qualitative approaches and deeper investigation through the case study (Yin, 2009; Dooley, 2002).

Qualitative research is based on the generation of data that is flexible and sensitive to social context. Fossey, et al.,(2002) depict that qualitative research is grounded in the philosophical position which is mainly interpretative because it is concerned with how society is interpreted, understood, experienced and produced (Fossey, et al., 2002). A qualitative method is also based on analysis and explanation that involve the understanding of complex and detailed context. It enables the researcher to do justice to the complex nature of the object under investigation. The existing study of the research deals with variables such as the people's perceptions (foreign public and the Japanese society), the actors involved, and state and non-state actors (Japanese government, its Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the International Olympic Committee) which is considerably varied and complex. Sports diplomacy as a soft power tool is relatively a new and developing area in sports sociology. Although, there are many resources and research work on previous mega events, more closely the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games and its impact on Japan at the time, and the impact of the Korea-Japan 2002 FIFA World Cup as a mega sports event on the peacebuilding of both nations.

3.8 Case Study Research Strategy

The definition of a case study technique is an empirical investigation into a current occurrence in a real-world setting where the distinctions between the phenomenon and the context are blurred and numerous sources of evidence are utilised (Yin, 1984; Yin, 2003; Flyvbjerg, 2011). A case study method as a research strategy is used in many ways to explore and understand

complex issues. It is considered a robust research method especially when an in-depth investigation is required. In social science, case study research is a recognised tool and is prominent in cases regarding education, sociology, and community issues such as politics, poverty, unemployment, drugs, addiction etc. Case study methods have been applied extensively to many disciplines, particularly in government, management, and education (Gulseen & Kubat, 2006).

There are two approaches to consider when considering the use of a case study method. Researchers consider the singular or multiple case design depending on the research question. A single-case design is adopted in situations where there are no other cases available for replication. A case study method helps a researcher to examine the data closely within a specific context. It selects a small or specific geographical location or a limited number of individuals as a subject for study. The case study method, in essence, explores and investigates contemporary real-life situation phenomena through a detailed contextual analysis of a limited event, number or condition. Gustafsson (2017) points out that a case study has a double function, which is, that is, case studies are studies of their unit, as well as case studies of a larger group of units. This means that a case study conclusion can be either confirmable or illustrative. A researcher studying many case studies compares them to a single case study to identify the variations and commonalities among the examples (Gustafsson, 2017).

In multiple case studies, the researcher finds contrasting or similar results from the study (Yin, 2003). However, a disadvantage of multiple case studies is that they can be enormously expensive and time-consuming to implement. W. Gibb Dyer & Wilkins, (1991) argues that single case studies are better than multiple case studies because a single case study produces an extra and better theory (W. Gibb Dyer & Wilkins, 1991). In a multiple case study, the more case study a scientific article has the less observation time the writer has to study the case studies. In addition, the more likely the case studies are stronger on their own. Yin, (2003)

points out that if a researcher wants to study a single entity, for example, a single group of people or a person from a single group, then a single case study is the best choice (Yin, 2003). When a single case study is used, it helps the researcher to question old theoretical relationships and explore new ones and this helps for a more careful study. In addition, it helps the researcher to get a deeper understanding of the subject (Gustafsson, 2017). The case study method comes with its criticism concerning its lack of robustness as a research tool and the concern of its ability to provide a generalising conclusion, but in this case, the method of triangulation is used to determine the validity of the procedure.

Yin (1994) explains that in the case study method, the generalising of results from either a singular or multiple designs stems from theory rather than from population. This means the replication of the case through matching patterns a method that links several pieces of information for the case to a theoretical proposition. In doing so, it helps to increase the level of assurance in the robustness of the method. Stake (1995) distinguishes three types of case studies to define the case study method (Stake, 1995). Specifically, the collective, instrumental, and intrinsic techniques (Stake, 1995). In an intrinsic case study, the investigation of the case is done solely for academic purposes. Unlike an intrinsic case study, which attempts to solve a unique problem of an individual case, an instrumental case study selects a small number of individuals to explore a particular behavioural pattern, and a collective case study gets data from multiple sources. In this research, a single case study method will help the research not only examine the significance of sport diplomacy as a soft power strategy through the case study of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, but it will also help to investigate the drivers, catalysts and elements that will create this impact. This will be achieved through the collection of data from multiple sources of evidence like semi-structured interviews with elite actors and government documents for analysis.

Furthermore, the holistic positioning of a case study to rely on the sources to generate a general picture of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy that is under investigation means that the method will help improve the triangulation of validity within cases because the evidence will be obtained from different sources. Furthermore, qualitative and quantitative research are associated frequently with the case study method. This study embraces qualitative research methods because the methods are important and useful to make an intensive and detailed examination of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy as well as finding and interpreting the data collected. This means that the multiple source perspective, the case study method will help in the consideration of not just the voices from the field and government documents but also the relationship between them. The case study will seek to examine the main objectives as follows:

- To identify an ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool.
- To critically evaluate Japan's sports diplomacy strategy as a positioning statement.
- To investigate the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool in their sports diplomacy
- To investigate the use of the Tokyo Olympic Games as a tool in Japan's soft (smart) power strategy

3.9 Document analysis

Document analysis as a form of qualitative research method, is a systematic procedure for reviewing and evaluating documents both printed and electronic-based material that includes computer-based and Internet-transmitted materials (Bowen, 2009). Document analysis is often used in combination with other qualitative research methods as a means of triangulation to

study the same phenomenon (Bowen, 2009). The triangulation of data means that the research can develop a variety of evidence that breeds credibility. Triangulation helps to reduce the impact of a potential bias that may exist in a single study by corroborating findings across data sets. Non-technical data for case studies, such as reports and internal correspondence, can also be used as potential sources of empirical data in document analysis. An example of this would be data about the participant's operating environment (Mills, et al., 2006). According to Bowen (2009), records of all kinds can aid a researcher in deciphering meaning, gaining comprehension, and gaining insights that are pertinent to their work. One important characteristic of document analysis is that it corroborates and augments evidence from various data sources and it plays an explicit role in undertaking case study research (K.Yin, 2009). Therefore, one of the tasks in this research is to access and analyse the official government documents that are relevant to addressing the research objectives.

Bowen (2009) discusses five specific uses of documents for analysis; the first is that the document provides data within which a participant operates. It provides background information and serves as a witness to past events providing insights that can help the researcher understand the history of a particular issue and the condition and impact of the phenomenon under investigation. Secondly, by using documents for analysis, suggestions and questions that need to be asked and situations that need to be observed are contained in documents. Thirdly, documents help to provide supplementary research data meaning that information from documents can help add to a knowledge base. In this case, researchers need to go through library catalogues and archives for possible related documents that can be analysed as part of the research process. The fourth is that documents serve as a means of tracking the changes and development of the case examined. In this case, the accessibility of various documents can help the researcher track and identify these changes. Little changes in research work can portray a substantive development in a research project (Yin, 1994). In this

case, reports in periodicals may be examined if possible. Finally, analysing documents is a way to verify findings and validate evidence from other sources.

To evaluate the quality of the evidence derived from documents, Scott (1990) proposes four criteria: representation, authenticity, believability, and meaning (Scott, 1990). Platt (1981), however, offers eight criteria for determining the authenticity of the document under analysis. One of these is to determine whether the text has any glaring flaws or inconsistent representations. To check if there are different versions of the same document. The thought is if the document has passed through several copyists. If the document has been shared with individuals who are interested in a specific interpretation of its contents, if the version is from a possible secondary source, if the document lacks consistency when compared to other similar documents, and finally, if the document is overly organised to represent a particular set of documents. May (1997), however, suggested that to determine the social and political context in which the paper was made, a researcher must use additional sources on the author's biography and political views. Additionally, another criterion is to see if the research's goal establishes the document's typical nature, which refers to a document's readability and comprehensiveness to the analyst.

Furthermore, official documents are analysed in their social context. Therefore, for this purpose, content analyses will be used. Content analysis is one of several research methods used to analyse text data. The use of content analysis in research is to focus on the characteristics of language as communication with the intention of the content or contextual meaning of the text (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). Content analysis is an umbrella term for various research approaches and techniques. Content analysis can also be defined as a research method used for the study and retrieving useful and meaningful information from documents. This process can be done by determining the occurrence of certain words or concepts within a text or a group of texts. In addition, the context of text here is defined broadly as books, newspaper

headlines, articles, advertising, historical documents, conversations speeches etc. Below is the list of documents for analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005).

3.10 Number and type of documents

Table 1

No	Names of Documents
1	Japan's Foreign Policy to Promote National and Worldwide Interest (2013, 2019, 2020, 2021)
2	Tokyo 2020 Guidebook
3	Olympic Host City Contract and Operational Requirement
4	Tokyo 2020 Games Foundation Plan February 2015
5	Tokyo 2020 Games Discover Tomorrow
6	Portland Soft Power 30 (2015-2019)
7	Global Soft Power Index 2020
8	Japan Soft Power Initiatives: Cool Japan Strategy
9	Cool Japan Initiative (established in 2014- 2021)
10	Cool Japan Strategy (2012-2021)
11	Cool Japan Proposal

12	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan Diplomatic Bluebook (2020). Specifically the Public Diplomacy chapter and other relevant chapters.
13	Report of the 2020 IOC Evaluation Commission
14	Tokyo 2020 candidate acceptance procedure
15	Tokyo 2020 candidate and questionnaire
16	Tokyo sustainability pre-games report and themes (Climate Change, Resource management, human rights, labour and fair business practices, involvement, cooperation and communication engagement, Natural environment and biodiversity).
17	Tokyo 2020 Fundamental Principles of the Sustainable Sourcing Code
18	Tokyo 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games Sustainable Sourcing Code
19	Newspapers: The Japan Times, Asahi Shimbun, Aljazeera, BBC, New York Times, The Globalist. Period of 2013-2020
20	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan Diplomatic Bluebook (2013, 2019, 2020, 2021). Specifically, the Public Diplomacy and Chapter Three.

Aside from documentary research, I conducted in-depth interviews to examine the perceptions of different actors and to enable triangulation of the data gathered. Also, it is important to note that the documents, especially Japan's foreign policy documents and Olympic Documents are the most important for data collection because they illustrate or reveal the intentions and goals of the policymakers in Japan. However, this is not to say that the interviews are less important,

they are also important because the expert opinion serves as a check and balance for the data collected from the above document.

3.11 In-depth interviews

An in-depth interview is useful in situations where the researcher wants to ask an open-ended question that elicits depth of information from a relatively small group of people in contrast to the survey that involves more of a quantitative method usually with a larger number of people (Guion, et al., 2001). An in-depth interview allows the interviewer to explore deeply the respondent's feelings and perspective on the subject matter of investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy. This will help the researcher gain results from rich background information that will help shape questions that are relevant to the research topic. For an in-depth interview, the interviewer must observe the necessary conditions for the successful completion of the interview.

The first is accessibility, this refers to whether the person to be interviewed has access to the information that the interviewer seeks. The second is understanding the person interviewed on what is required of him or her in the role of the interviewee. The third is motivation, this means that the person to be interviewed must feel that their participation and answers are valued for the case of their cooperation, which is fundamental to the research. (Kvale, 1996) The proposed seven stages of conducting an interview are thematising, and this is the stage where it is important to clarify the purpose of the interview. The second stage is designing; this stage is where the interviewer designs a way to elicit the information through the interview process after determining what he or she wants to know. The third process is the interviewing stage, and the fourth process is transcribing face; this involves creating a verbatim text of the interviewer by writing out each question and response using the audio recording. The fifth process is analysing which involves re-reading the interviewer's transcript and identifying

themes that emerge from the respondent's answer. The sixth stage is the verifying stage, which involves checking the credibility of the information gathered through the method called triangulation. The last stage is the reporting stage, which involves sharing the information obtained from the interview process and its results (Kvale, 1996). By conducting interviews, this research investigated the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power. The investigation process for this study includes asking questions, collecting data and analysing the data by identifying Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power. The data collected for this study took into consideration several variables such as Japan's culture, political values and foreign policy, and national and international image. The open-ended and fairly broad interview questions were drawn together from themes that emerged from the literature review, interview discussions and from the analysis derived from the document data source of the study. These formed meta-themes and sub-themes for the analysis. This study interviewed 11 participants with one of the participants recommending their books to me without participating in the interview process. This research took into consideration the criteria of over 20 years of experience working, travelling, and researching in areas of Japanese studies, culture, sports studies or sport sociology, statecraft, and policy.

3.12 Sampling strategy

To answer the research question, there is a need to select a sample to focus on while there is doubt that the researcher will be able to collect data from all cases. Thus, there is a need for sampling in research. In research, a researcher can't collect data from an entire population; hence, this research will draw a set of cases from a sampled population. The ability to extrapolate a sample's characteristics to the population it comes from is the foundation of sampling theory (Taherdoost, 2016). The nature of the study determines how the researcher will choose potential candidates for interview from a larger population. In this case, identifying

key participants or representatives of different groups is important. There are two methods of sampling techniques; they are probability and non-probability techniques. In probability, sampling every item in a population has an equal chance of being included in the sampling. Though it is the most time and energy-efficient sample, probability or random sampling offers the highest degree of bias flexibility (Brown, 1947). On the other hand, a non-probability sample is associated often with a case study research design and qualitative research. A case study with limited sample sizes, as was previously said, aims to investigate a real-world occurrence rather than provide statistical comparisons with a broader population (Yin, 2003). Participants in non-probability sampling do not have to be random or representative, but there must be a good justification for choosing to include significant people and participants over others.

In this research, purposive or judgemental sampling is adopted concerning the representatives of the actors functioning actively within the research focus in investigating the impact of the Tokyo 2021 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy. In purposive sampling, persons or events are selected deliberately to provide important information that cannot be obtained from other choices (Maxwell, 1996). In this case, the researcher includes cases or participants in the sample because they believe that they should be included. For this study, purposeful sampling is adopted to reflect the population accurately in a way that it is a microcosm of the population. This sampling method will focus on academic practitioners with over 10 years of research and field contribution to the Olympic Games, Japan's national and foreign policy engagement, Japan's society, sport diplomacy and soft power. This is important to make significant decisions with influence in the research area rather than concentrate on one group because it is easier to study. Therefore, the sampling of interviewees will be influenced by the roles and involvement of the actors around the research study area. However, both governmental and non-governmental representatives will be considered for this research. A total of 11 participants

were contacted and interviewed for this study and this included participants who lived in Japan, travelled to Japan for work and participants who live in the United Kingdom. It is also important to point out that, the interviews were conducted during the global and national lockdown of the covid-19 pandemic and made use of a snowballing or network sampling method.

3.13 Method of data analysis

This section explains how the research will use a thematic analysis to analyse the information gathered. A qualitative technique for data analysis called thematic analysis is used to find, examine, and interpret the patterns and meanings—or themes—that exist in qualitative data (Clarke & Braun, 2017). Thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis technique that involves examining a data collection for recurring patterns and then analysing and reporting on them (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Clarke & Braun, (2017) point out that rather than providing a theoretically informed or constrained framework for research, theme analysis gives a method and tool of technique that is unrestricted by theoretical commitments, making it the canon of a qualitative and analytical approach to qualitative research. Thematic analysis offers scholars a methodical and easily comprehensible process for deriving codes and topics from qualitative data (Clarke & Braun, 2017). Thematic analysis is not specific to a particular paradigm and can be used within post-positivist, constructivist, and critical realist research approaches (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). In the case of the interpretivist, (constructivist), thematic analysis is used to emphasise the social, cultural, and structural contexts that influence an individual experience. This helps to develop knowledge that is constructed through the interactions between the researcher and the research participants. Within a critical realist framework, thematic analysis allows the researcher to study the power relations that inform

reality to engage in an emancipatory investigation that values the voices of oppressed populations (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

According to Aronson (1994), theme analysis is a technique that can help close the gap between the post-positivist goal of understanding and many social scientists' need for a trustworthy, impartial, fact-based, and interpretive approach (Aronson, 1994). In thematic analysis, the development of key themes is important, and the term theme is the analysis method. Meta themes and sub-themes are patterns of meaning from data collected that inform the research question (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It provides a description and the organisation of the evident content of a set of data. Themes can be classified as either semantic often called manifest which addresses data on a surface meaning or secondly latent themes which address and reflect deeper an underlying meaning, assumptions, or ideology (Kiger & Varpio, 2020; Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data analysis will adopt a latent approach to reflect deeper an underlying meaning of the intentions of the Japanese government to use the Games as a soft power strategy. However, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy, a deductive approach will help to provide a broader analysis of the Tokyo 2020 Olympics to investigate if the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is a soft power strategy. Clarke & Braun, (2017) outlined the most adopted method of thematic analysis within the qualitative literature (Clarke & Braun, 2017). Clarke & Braun, (2017) designed their thematic analysis to be recursive rather than linear. This means that there are processes that may require the researcher to go back to earlier steps in light of new data or newly emerging themes that require further investigation. Nonetheless, the procedures are as follows: • Acquainting oneself with the data; • Producing preliminary codes; • Looking for themes; and • Examining themes. Identifying and labelling the themes; writing the reports and manuscripts.

It is important to note that this research will be adopting the following step in the analysis of data to find broader, expansive and in-depth meaning from investigating the Tokyo Olympic

Games as a soft power strategy. Furthermore, the data analysis and coding to generate themes will be done by using NVivo a qualitative data analysis soft power. The use of NVivo will help the researcher to organise the data effectively and generate codes that will then be developed into themes.

3.13.1 RESEARCH ETHICS

In social research, ethical issues are often difficult to define. Ethical decision-making is relevant when researching a particular area or population. Ethics is important when sampling, gaining access to data or researching respondents, whilst collecting and analysing data. The focus of Ethics in social research involves procedural issues, especially on the principle of informed content. To Homan (1991) ethics is the science of morality: those who engage in it determine values for the regulation of human behaviour. The decisions made at different stages in research may have ethical implications; therefore, in the topic of a study, choosing a population to investigate may have ethical implications. The right and freedom of individuals to choose whether to take part in research should always come first.

In conducting research, invasion of privacy is an example of ethical issues that may occur and be viewed as harmful and deprivation of privacy. However, the harm that may result from the unwitting disclosure of personal information is both foreseeable and unforeseeable harm that the researcher must protect people from (Kelman, 1982). For this study, ethical approval has been a success from the ethics committee to conduct interviews. Before undertaking primary research, the researcher needed to comply with the University of the West of Scotland's Research ethics policy. The procedure requires that my ethical application has already been examined and approved by the University research and ethics board. The data collected for this study took into consideration several variables such as Japan's culture, political values and foreign policy, and national and international image. The Open-ended and fairly broad

interview questions were drawn together from themes that emerged from the literature review, interview discussions and from the analysis derived from the secondary data source (document analysis) of the study. This study is aware of the different ethical issues and processes that may arise in the research. Therefore, measures are in place to ensure that all ethical principles are applied and fully adhered to, for example, the data was stored in a secured hard drive. Participant's information and consent forms were sent before the research and interviews were conducted. The information provided to the participants includes the aim, goals and objective of the research and gives them a choice to participate. It is important to state that the research interview was conducted on an individual basis and not through a focused group. The interviews collected were auto-taped and conducted in private online via Zoom call. Furthermore, to ensure privacy and confidentiality, each participant was given a code name and anonymised when requested.

The process of interview selection requires the use of purposive sampling, persons or events are selected deliberately to provide important information that cannot be obtained from other choices (Maxwell, 1996). In this case, the researcher includes cases or participants in the sample because they believe that they should be included. For this study, purposeful sampling is adopted to reflect the population accurately in a way that it is a microcosm of the population. This sampling method is focused on academic practitioners with over 10 years of research and field contribution to the Olympic Games, Japan's national and foreign policy engagement, Japan's society, sport diplomacy and soft power. A total of 11 participants were contacted and interviewed for this study and this included participants who lived in Japan, travelled to Japan for work and participants who live in the United Kingdom. It is also important to point out that, the interviews were conducted during the global and national lockdown of the covid-19 pandemic. This meant that the interviews were conducted online via Zoom. The COVID-19 pandemic was a difficult time to conduct research, especially online. However, it helped to

reduce the ethical risk that the researcher would have faced conducting research in the field, for example, by travelling to Japan and interviewing sports fans and Japanese citizens. It is imperative to add that as stated on page 111, Japan’s foreign policy documents and Olympic Documents are the most important for data collection because they illustrate or reveal the intentions and goals of the policymakers in Japan. However, this is not to say that the interviews are less important, they are also important because the expert opinion serves as a check and balance for the data collected from the above document.

CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING THE QUALITY OF MY QUALITATIVE DATA

Table 2

Moment:	Strategies & Principles for Assessing 'Quality'
Traditional	Quality assessed according to principles of the scientific method (e.g. <i>objectivity, transparency, reliability, replicability</i> etc)
Modernist (aka: The Golden Age)	Quality assessed according to emerging methodological principles (e.g. 'Bracketing')
Blurred Genres	Questioning of modernist criteria for assessing quality; emergence of new principles & concepts (e.g. the <i>4-D Framework – Lincoln & Guba, 1986</i>)
Crisis of Representation	Growing tensions and uncertainty as to how researchers can systematically assess issues of quality in their work. Assessment of quality viewed as <u>political</u> (as opposed to purely <u>technical</u>)
Post-Modern	Rejection of modernist frameworks for evaluating knowledge production. Emphasis on 'situated knowledges' and multiple truths give rise to new principles and approaches (e.g. ' Reflexivity ')
Post-Experimental	Rise of non-traditional approaches which are based on situated (c.g. ' <i>universalising</i> ') criteria .
'Methodologically Contested' Period	Increasing interest in performative (affect-based) approaches to understanding 'what can a research project DO ?' Development of performative methodological concepts (e.g. <i>diffraction vs reflexivity</i>)
The Future	Assertions that post-qualitative inquiry needs to <i>go beyond</i> methodology altogether. Emphasis on ontological and epistemological principles (e.g. <i>assemblages; rhizomes; deconstruction</i>) as guiding principles for doing post-qualitative inquiry.

The above table explains the criteria for accessing the quality of my qualitative data from the document analysis and interview. It is important to note that this research considered the above criteria in the process of investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan’s soft power.

3.14 Limitations of methodology

This research encountered several limitations especially the process of data gathering and interviews. This research began in April 2019, which was timely research to gather data to investigate the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The researcher planned to travel to Japan as part of the data-gathering process funded by the EventRights project, part of the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Maria Sklodowska-Curie grant agreement. This research initially considered the interviews of sports fans, policymakers, and academics and the interviews while in Japan. However, because of the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. I was forced to change my methodological approach by conducting a content analysis and interviewing participants online. This was a major setback and I had to revise my whole research approach, but I did well in this area because it enabled me to examine and analyse deeper into the foreign policy documents of the Japanese government as well as speak to experts with long-term experience in Japanese studies. I needed to draw on contacts from my supervisory team, and then use snowballing methods- so when I interviewed one person, they recommended others, but this too has its limitations.

It is also important to discuss that conducting interviews online, especially during a pandemic was a new and challenging experience. It was new because it was the first time the researcher experienced conducting an interview online. The lack of personal connection that is present in face-to-face interviews makes it difficult for interviews to build rapport with the interviewee, assess their interpersonal skills, and fit for the role. Another limitation of this research is the lack of interviews with policymakers or members of the JOC. However, this research has made it clear that the investigation of Japan's national and foreign policy documents covers the loophole of not interviewing government officials or policymakers. In addition, because of the pandemic, it was very difficult to reach out to government officials or diplomats who reside in and outside the United Kingdom. This was all very frustrating, but I had to go with what was

possible and use those interviews alongside the document analysis as best I could. The upside was that I spent far more time analysing the documents, creating themes, and exploring these themes in the interviews with the key participants. The next chapter leads to a presentation of research findings and analysis. The researcher decided to present these together as this allowed me to connect the dots to create a logical progression for the reader. This can help the reader see how the data supports the interpretations and conclusion. Also, this helps me to reduce redundancy, combining the findings and analysis eliminates the need to separate sections dedicated to each, making the thesis more concise and focused.

Chapter 4

4.1 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter discusses the findings related to meta themes such as geopolitics in Asia, highlighting Japan's foreign policy and national strategy and unpacking the developments that indicate a shift in Japan's use of soft power resources, including the re-interpretation of Japan's constitution to accommodate the full exercise of its sovereign power as an independent country (Smart power). This chapter discusses the findings surrounding the Sport for Tomorrow programme as Japan's Olympic and sport diplomacy strategy or project as indicated in its diplomatic document, identifying, and discussing the various ways the Japanese government has been able to make use of this strategy to engage with the government of other countries.

In terms of Japan's foreign and national policy, the dual otherness of the Japanese Prime Minister Abe is discussed, unpacking essential strategies that indicate his use of smart power. Smart power is the combination of hard power and soft power resources like his attempt to remilitarise Japan's constitution from pacifism to a more proactive military defence strategy, coupled with the active role he played in the bid to win the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The findings in this chapter are discussed under the narrative of techno nationalism, environmentalism, and superficial environmentalism, and important issues of how Japan has been able to leverage technology and climate change to enhance its image through the Olympic Games are discussed. Discussions around the use of hard and soft power narratives, the utilisation of Japan's nuclear disaster and the controversy surrounding Japan's imperial past as a sympathetic tool to host the Olympics; therefore, politicising the Olympic Games and improving its image.

4.2 key findings to research gap and research contribution; identifying an ideal (Japan's) soft power (smart) model

By investigating Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. This research has identified Japan's soft power/ smart power model in terms of accessing and answering the research questions, aims, and objectives. This research takes into consideration the argument that the debate on power tends to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept and secondly, that soft power as a concept is under theories with limited resources and that soft power is a normative concept. Concerning the 1964 Tokyo Olympics, this research highlighted three main elements of Japan's sport diplomacy. The first is associating diplomacy with an international sporting event. The second is that technology has played a significant role in projecting a new national image for Japan. The third initiative aims to increase Japan's internationalism by luring foreign tourists to its "world-class" capital city, fostering the growth of a robust, "international" population within the country, and promoting international sporting events (Abel, 2012, p. 206). In the context of Japan and the 1964 Olympic Games, Abel's (2012) soft power role was made simpler with the help of the flow chart below.

Figure 5

Summary of Abel's (2012) soft power role in the context of Japan and the 1964 Olympic Games.

Therefore, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, from the research findings, I have identified an Ideal soft (smart) power model for Japan in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, namely, *the neo-realist smart power model*. The chart below explains this model in the simplest form possible. Below is the thesis result and developed model from the data analysis. The model is shown below to provide clarity and highlight the main points of interest while examining Japan's use of sport diplomacy as a soft power tactic.

Thesis result and developed model from data analysis

Chart explaining Japan's soft (smart) power model, Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

The neo-realist smart power model

Fig 6

The diagram explains that the limitation of Japan's soft power strategy has a connection with Article 9 of its constitution, leading to a self-defence military that is only suitable for humanitarian engagement. The notion to change the limitations of Article 9 stems from Japan's Prime Minister Abe's administration whose strategy is to make Japan a first-tier country

regionally and internationally. The strategy includes changing Japan's geopolitical policies, including Japan's foreign and national strategy.

Firstly, this research has found that an examination of an ideal Japan's soft power strategy stems from an examination through the lens and the strategy of Prime Minister Abe's administrative policies, identified by the research as the neo-realist soft power model. This includes the remilitarisation of Japan's military and Abe's role in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid. Furthermore, an examination of both strategies gives more clarity that the re-interpretation of Japan's constitution and then hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympics is a strategy to make Japan's soft power and global visibility more effective to become a major global player. This narrative fits well with Nye, (2017) as he points out that soft power is only one component of power and that the ability to combine hard and soft power into strategies where they reinforce each other could be considered 'smart power' (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State). In his article, *soft power: The means to success in world politics*, soft power was only one concept of power and rarely sufficient by itself (Nye, 2004; Nye, 2017). The chart explains how Abe's strategy is a smart power strategy, this means that for an effective soft power strategy, there must be an effective Hard power strategy, and this strategy, Japan has lacked since 1946. Therefore, the key point from the findings is about effective global visibility. For effective global visibility, soft power resources are not enough, and it must be a combination of both hard and soft power resources.

Secondly, this research has revealed that, the reason for the under-theorisation of soft power is that most academics who seek to engage the term soft power in the context of international politics, statecraft, diplomacy, and sport diplomacy, do not consider international relations theories that are vital in the field. The three main international relations theories are realism, liberalism, and constructivism. It is important to understand that while the use of concepts is to sometimes propose a theory, the case of soft power is not different. It is important to consider

the relevance of any of the above-mentioned IR theories in any context in which soft power is applied. However, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The result from the above Japan's smart power model above indicates that the concept of soft (smart) power is like the notion of neorealist or structural realism in international relations that sees competition and conflicts as persistent features with limited potential for cooperation. The state of anarchy in the international system means that states are unsure of other state's intentions and their security. Hence in the case of Japan, the proposed intervention to remilitarise its constitution by former Prime Minister Abe.

Thirdly, considering that Japan has successfully hosted major sporting events in the past, such as the 1964 Tokyo Olympics, the 2002 FIFA World Cup, the 2019 Rugby World Cup, and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the country has excelled in sport diplomacy. However, the COVID-19 pandemic prevented the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games from living up to their full potential as a soft power instrument, which may have resulted in echoes of soft disempowerment. The discussion chapter provides thorough explanations for these significant discoveries, which represent major advances in knowledge.

4.3 Part 1: Document analysis

4.4 Introduction

For this study, I examined and analysed documents that included Japan's foreign policy with relationships or indications of Japan's sports diplomacy and soft power initiatives and activities. I then examined how these activities and initiatives contributed to the image of Japan and its soft power strategy. This helped me as the researcher to analyse and discuss Japan's soft power strategies through the lens of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The findings in this chapter are important because they set out the foundation by unpacking the Japanese foreign and national policies and strategies related to Japan's exercise of soft power and international

image. This research finds that Japan's foreign policy strategy to promote trust and understanding includes promoting its culture, sports, and tourism.

Furthermore, I carried out a qualitative analysis that included a thematic document analysis of Japan's diplomatic bluebook, foreign policy documents, Olympic Documents and selected electronic media articles. This investigation was carried out by extracting relevant discussions surrounding the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games from 2013 to 2021. The themes for the scope of this study are determined from two categories. The first are the meta themes that emerged from the literature review and conceptual framework. The second are sub-themes that emerged through the investigation and coding of documents using NVivo, a research tool for qualitative data analysis used to develop a codebook that shows the number of documents leading to codes analysed from the data collected. Therefore, the literature review and the use of NVivo formed the basis of the thematic groupings for this research in terms of meta themes (key theoretical and policy areas) and sub-themes (sport, politics, diplomacy areas). As a result, the findings and themes from the data are grouped into two categories: the first group in the foreign policy and soft power category and the second group in the category of sports diplomacy.

Summary of analysis

Theme A to E (SOFT POWER ANALYSIS)

After a thorough examination of Japan's foreign policy and the analysis of the relationships and indicators of Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power initiatives and strategy. As a meta-theme, theme A sets out the foundation of the analysis by analysing the overlap between Asian geopolitics and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The narrative of pacifism in Article 9 of Japan's constitution and the proposed remilitarisation of Japan's constitution to include having a proactive military demonstrates the need for an effective soft power strategy. However, theme A identified the use of Japan's Office for Development Assistance (ODA) as an alternative soft power and non-violent means to develop a close relationship with the eastern region of Asia and part of Africa.

Furthermore, Theme B buttresses Theme A findings, also as a meta-theme, on the use of ODA as an alternative soft power tool where ODA is used to strengthen Japan's relationship with Africa and Asia by using its strong economy, and diplomatic and geographical relationships, particularly in governance and infrastructure development. The key point from theme B is the use of foreign aid and development as an important soft power strategy for Japan to connect with the international community. Theme C further examines Japan's foreign policy and the foundation of its soft power the prime minister Abe's policies. Theme C as a meta-theme recognised Abe as Japan's post-war Prime minister and Abe's ambition to make Japan a first-tier country in the context of Abe's economic policy (Abenomics) and his role in the bid for Tokyo to host the 2020 Tokyo Olympics Games.

Theme C finds that Abe was objectively interested in remilitarising Japan's constitution, specifically changing the pacifist status of the articles of Japan's constitution. At the same time, promoting Japan's culture and delivering a speech on the importance of making Japan a host

for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. It is important to note that theme C began to reveal the key findings that led to the development of the smart power model as key findings for this thesis.

Having analysed Japan's foreign policy and soft power through the lens of Prime Minister Abe, Theme D analysed Japan's foreign policy strategy and national interest, including the importance of sports tourism on Japan's soft power. Theme D as a meta-theme reveals the key pillars of Japan's sport diplomacy and Japan's involvement in sports development. Page 175 of Japan's Diplomatic Blue Book highlights that parts of Japan's foreign policy are to promote national and worldwide interests and understanding through Japan's culture, sport and tourism. This included the Sport for Tomorrow program where Japan set out the objective to reach 10 million people across more than 10 nations and this is in partnership with Japan's sports agency and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Theme D reveals that the Sport for Tomorrow programme has reached its target of 12 million people in 204 countries, and this signifies an effective soft power and sport diplomacy strategy. Theme E as a sub-theme, set the foundation for developing the key findings and answering the research questions aims and objectives. Theme E analysed Abe's foreign policy strategy as a combination of Japan's hard and soft power resources. The key points on Theme E are the overlap between the 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle and soft power and the remilitarisation of Article 9 in Japan's constitution. Theme E reveals that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is an added advantage to Japan's economy and a bonus for Abenomics.

Sport diplomacy analysis (Theme F-J)

Theme F as a meta theme examines broadly the Sport for Tomorrow programme, Japan's Olympic project and sport diplomacy strategy. The analysis discussed the need for a bottom-up approach to Japan's soft power strategy. For example, this includes the STP registering 10.2

million participants in September 2019 from different countries and regions. Theme F analyses how sport diplomacy is an integral part of strengthening and building the relationship between the government exercising its sport diplomacy strategy and the targeted country. Theme G also as a sub-theme, examines the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games through the lens of technonationalism and superficial environmentalism (discover tomorrow). Theme G analyses the 1964 Olympic Games as a clear and effective display of Japan's soft power because of the positive narrative of war and peace that Japan used and this included the showcase of innovative technology after the Second World War. Pointing out that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is linked with the same idea of technology and environmentalism, in the of Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the world values environmentalism in the 20th century.

By examining the use of the soft power and hard power narrative, Theme H as a sub-theme, finds that Japan's foreign and national policies changed to focus more on employing soft power to interact with other countries because of the political changes that occurred between 1964 and 2020. Theme H also supports that Abe's strategy has a mixture of soft power and hard power resources, from remilitarisation to playing a significant role in Tokyo becoming the 2020 Olympic Host. And the effectiveness of both concepts is determined by how they are used in foreign policy which may include several instruments and degree of coercion and persuasion. Furthermore, in trying to understand the issues facing the hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and Japan's sport diplomacy. Theme I as a sub-theme examined the nuclear energy disaster as a sport diplomacy narrative for the Olympic Games. The Fukushima nuclear power plant disaster discredited the notion that Japan's adoption of nuclear energy was not sustainable. Similarly, the 2020 Fukushima nuclear accident served as a symbol for the bid to host the Tokyo Olympics, and the torch relay was scheduled to start in Fukushima. Furthermore, and related to challenges on Japan's soft power and sport diplomacy, Theme J as a meta-theme examined nationalism in Japan, the 'rising sun flag (Hinomaru): and Japan's

legacy of imperialism as a point of controversy at the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The Rising Sun flag made an official national flag in 1999 has strong ties to Japan's imperial past. In the case of Japan, waving its flag in international sports events like the Olympic Games has become offensive to its Asian neighbour, predominantly South Korea. Critics depict those fans using the flag to rewrite the history of human rights abuses by Japanese forces. Politicians from South Korea often compare the rising sun flag to the Nazi swastika. However, in the case of Tokyo 2020, South Korea wants the flag banned, with Japanese officials saying that the flag is widely used in Japan and not a political statement. Theme J gives an analytical view of how Japan's imperial past may affect its soft power as a host nation for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. This provides an issue for discussion on how this narrative affects Japan's soft power, especially on a regional level.

Voices from the field (Theme A- N)

This section of analysis provides insight from the interviews conducted with experts. To understand Japan's sport diplomacy as a soft power tool, Theme A as a meta-theme, discusses the 1964 Olympic Games, the impact of the Second World War on Japan's soft power and the reconstruction of its identity through sport diplomacy. It provides and analyses the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games and its positive impact on Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power while drawing further analysis on what could be expected in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, post-war Japan. Theme B as a sub-theme, analyses the role of the media on Japan's culture and cultural exports through the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. It discusses the role of the media presentation in Japan's image during the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The B also examined how the media presence in the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games helped to improve the positive relationship and public feeling towards Japan. In the case of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the pandemic is a limitation to the effective use of the 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power

tool. But the presence of the media during the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games as close games cannot be ignored. The uncontrolled presence of the media may have become a tool to use the Games as a soft power strategy effectively. However, because of the pandemic and the nature of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

Theme C as a sub-theme analyses the impact of COVID-19 on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy. For example, there is a possibility that the Olympic Games as a soft power tool did not entirely achieve its purpose. Secondly, suppose the Western media viewed the Games as successful after hosting through a difficult time like the pandemic. In that case, the idea of using the Olympic Games as a soft power tool may be relevant. Theme D as a sub-theme reveals key issues for analysis, the impact of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool on a national regional and international level. Theme E as a meta-theme expands further on the geopolitical nature of East Asia, Political and cultural power and its impact on Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy. Theme E reveals that the mono-cultural characteristics of Japan's society are a weakness in its soft power. To counter this weakness, measures must be put in place to attract the foreign public. Japan is a peaceful and democratic country, and Tokyo is a popular cultural hub.

Furthermore, Theme F expands on Theme E as a sub-theme by analysing the significance of having an open and global society through the Tokyo 2020 Olympics. Analysing whether the Olympic Games can serve as a soft power tool to rebuild, open and attract foreign visitors and tourists. Theme G as a sub-theme briefly analysed the hosting of the Rugby 2020 World Cup as a foundation for hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. However, revealing that it was the first major sports event Japan hosted before the 2020 Tokyo Olympics and before the pandemic, serving as a tool for exposing and opening Japanese society to the world. Secondly, it is important to compare factors such as tourism and the percentage of international audiences

viewing the Games from abroad compared to a closed Olympic Games affected by the pandemic.

Furthermore, theme H as a sub-theme analyses the salvaging of the Tokyo Olympic Games as a soft power tool from the impact of COVID-19. Revealing that the normal operation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was disrupted by the extraordinary development of Covid-19. This implies that Japan's soft power approach might have been impacted by multiplying effects. First, given the high expense of holding the Games, the pandemic's advent posed a threat to the organisation of the Games. Second, the Olympic Games were staged behind closed doors due to concerns over tourism. Theme I as a sub-theme, expand on the cost of not hosting the Olympic Games and the postponement of the Games amid the emergence of COVID-19. Theme I reveal that the cost of not hosting would cost Japan financially and culturally, especially in a case where throughout most of the post-war era, Japanese culture was not promoted in Asia due to fear of being associated with cultural imperialism once more. In the context of culture, Theme J as a sub-theme expands on Theme I by analysing soft power as a fluke concept that the government of Japan had a deliberate soft power strategy with the term (soft power) used throughout the tiers of government, including Japan's Olympic Committee. Soft power as an analytical concept can be examined from the significance of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games on Japan's image, and the second can be analysed from Abe's government's economic and constitutional policies. Part one of the findings discussed the latter as Abe's smart power strategy.

Furthermore, Theme K as a meta-theme examined Prime Minister Abe's motivation for Japan's soft power strategy. Revealing the need to make Japan a first-tier country. However, Theme K resulted in questioning whether the hosting of hosting sports mega event like the Olympic Games may create a positive atmosphere for the organisers or create an atmosphere of global and national criticism on several societal or political-ideological issues and in this case

amplified with the uncontrolled presence of the media. This, however, points to the importance of national soft power. That is what degree of satisfaction the citizens of the host country have towards its government. Finally, in terms of soft power, Theme L as a sub-theme is consistent with the previous analysis of the value of the Olympic Games as a tool for soft power. Theme L reveals that the main topic of conversation should be how the Olympic Games are organised and if they should be fundamentally rethought.

Analysis of sport diplomacy, voices from the field (Theme M-N)

Theme M as a meta-theme reveals the essential narrative of the good and bad Asia, revealing that sport diplomacy as a background national strategy is an important point for discussion especially in the case of Japan. sport diplomacy as a background strategy is a soft power tool (smart power) to supplement this geopolitical unrest and in the process seek to gain some form of global legitimacy from their actions by hosting mega sports events. This is an important narrative for discussion especially in the case of Japan. Finally, Theme N as a sub-theme Identified Japan’s sport diplomacy that the Sport for Tomorrow program is a soft power strategy for Japan.

The table below presents the key themes that emerged from the analysis.

Table 3

	DOCUMENT ANALYSIS (SOFT POWER)
Theme A	The Overlap between Asian geopolitics and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games: a foreign policy and soft power strategy?
Theme B-	Understanding Japan’s soft power through its Office for Development Assistance ODA in Africa and Asia
Theme C-	Understanding Japan’s foreign policy and the foundation of its soft power through Prime Minister Abe’s policy

Theme D-	Understanding Japan's foreign policy strategy and national interest; the importance of sports tourism on Japan's soft power
Theme E-	Abe's foreign policy strategy combines Japan's hard and soft power resources.
	DOCUMENT ANALYSIS (SPORT DIPLOMACY)
Theme F-	Sport for tomorrow: Japan's Olympic project and sport diplomacy strategy
Theme G-	Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games through the lens of techno nationalism and superficial environmentalism (Discover tomorrow)
Theme H-	Making use of the soft power vs hard power narrative towards an Olympic quest
Theme I-	Utilising the nuclear energy disaster as a sport diplomacy narrative for hosting the Olympic Games

DATA ANALYSIS ON FOREIGN POLICY AND SOFT POWER

4.5. Theme A: the overlap between Asian geopolitics and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic games: a foreign policy and soft power strategy?

According to Samuels (2006), a lot of Japanese observers don't think Japan has a workable plan in place for using its soft power. For instance, as Samuels (2006) noted, one of Japan's most eminent diplomats, Sadako Ogata, discloses that Japan's foreign policy approach has long been characterised by the "conspicuous absence of strategic thinking." Former ambassador Hisahiko Okazaki notes that Japan's strategy has been "naïve" and "sterile" since 1964, except for an extraordinary ten years between 1895 and 1905. Furthermore, political analyst Shin'ichi Kitaoka contends that the fact that idealism has supplanted realism in Japan is one of the country's biggest tragedies (Samuels, 2006, pp. 111-113). Japan is often described as 'groping' (Mosaku) for strategy while calling its post-war strategy incoherent. This strategy includes Japan chasing too many hares at once by pursuing a policy that is centred on the United Nations initiatives, Asian-oriented, autonomous, and consistent with the goal of its bilateral alliances

with the United States, which then leads to an ineffective foreign policy. This includes the demilitarisation policy that makes Japan a pacifist country. Japan has been barred constitutionally from maintaining an offensive military since the end of the Second World War.

This is because the US occupation authorities' primary objective after Japan was defeated in World War II was to completely demilitarise the country. The US occupation authorities wrote the Japanese constitution, which was ratified by the assembly in 1947 and forbade the use of force under Article 9. (Chanlett-Avery, 2011; Smith, 2019). Stating that;

1. Aspiring sincerely to an international peace based on justice and order, the Japanese people forever renounce war as a sovereign right of the nation and the threat to use of force as means of settling international disputes.
2. To accomplish the aim of the preceding paragraph, land, sea, and air forces, as well as other war potential, will never be maintained. The right of belligerency of the state will be recognised.

The above findings explain Japan's excessive engagement in soft power initiatives to seek international recognition. However, it is important to note that in practice, Article 9 has remained consistent since 1947. It is important to note that a constitution can only indicate so much and may be different in practice as not every political group once in power will always interpret provisions the same way. However, this is not the case for Japan, as the provisions in Article 9 have remained consistent and universally applied since its inception. This explains why Prime Minister Abe sought to reinterpret the constitution. Article 9 of the Japanese constitution clarifies why experts describe Japan's foreign policy as inconsistent, naïve, sterile, or in a state where idealism has dominated realism. It also explains the critics from the literature review about the ineffectiveness of Cool Japan as a soft power strategy for Japan. Therefore, this section discusses the state of Japan's soft power strategy, and to what extent the pacifist

nature of Japan's constitution has hindered Japan's ability for an effective soft power and nation branding, regionally and internationally.

The research findings from Japan's diplomatic bluebook state that;

‘as a responsible member of the international community, Japan will strive to achieve disarmament and non-proliferation, both to ensure and maintain its own safety and to achieve a safe and peaceful world based on the principle of pacifism advocated by the Constitution of Japan’¹.

Firstly, non-proliferation and disarmament are a soft power strategy that has positioned Japan as a major player in international relations as a peaceful and stable country. However, the Japanese government through Article 9 adopted the policy of disarmament and non-proliferation after the defeat in the Second World War. That said, non-proliferation and disarmament is a soft power strategy that has worked for Japan in the past, especially towards the end of the Second World and to the build-up of the 1964 Olympic Games. Furthermore, as discussed in the literature review, the 1964 Olympic Games reintroduced Japan as a peaceful nation to the world. Therefore, it is important to note that in traditional international relations and politics, the sole source of a country's power and dominance is hard power. This has become an issue for Japan ever since. Hard power is a strong-arm approach to international relations that includes military power and, in most cases, the ability to use economic sanctions and incentives or other sanctions.

Furthermore, Article 9 of Japan's constitution limits Japan's exercise of its soft power. The issue identified from the findings is the limitations in the combination of the exercise of Japan's hard power and soft power resources. Article 9 in Japan's constitution has limited the ability to use its political capabilities effectively and completely as a sovereign country. This is an

¹ Chapter three of Japan's diplomatic bluebook; Japan's foreign policy to promote National and worldwide interest: Disarmament and non-proliferation, page 175.

issue, given that the exercise of soft power alone cannot be measured effectively. This means that the Japanese government's inability to operate a more offensive military dictates the level and extent to which its soft power resources are used. Zachary (2008) points out that Japan has lagged in at least one offensive military capability since World War II. Arguing that Japan's rearmament, which is inevitable, would violate its pacifist post-war constitution, prompted concerns among its neighbours and around the globe, especially when Japan became a nationalistic and revisionist country under Prime Minister Abe (Kaufman, 2008, p. 266). Since 1965/1964, Japan has only possessed a self-defence military limited to carrying out peacekeeping missions. Therefore, it appears that the pacifist nature of Japan's constitution when it comes to making Japan a first-tier or significant player in international affairs is limited without exercising a proactive military.

Research has established that for effective soft power, there must be an effective exercise of hard power resources. Barr, et al., (2015) Point out that authoritarian states have embraced the idea of soft power increasingly. For example, countries such as China, Russia and South and North Korea have exercised their military power and, at the same time, effectively exercised their soft power resource. Nye (2013) argues the effort to harness the power of attraction is unlikely to bring any meaningful results. Nye (2013) argued that China and Russia do not understand what soft power is about. However, in practice, especially in the case of China, the effective exercise of its soft and hard power has made China a major player in matters of international relations and a show of strength. However, in Japan's case, to make the exercise of power by a sovereign nation like Japan stronger and more effective for global visibility. There is a need to have the ability to exercise its hard power resources effectively. Furthermore, the defeat in the Second World War helped shape Japan's approach to its foreign and economic policy regarding its regional, and international relations, and development. As a result, Japan

has used its Office for Development Assistance (ODA) to influence Asia economically and politically, especially in East Asia. Considering this,

The findings indicate that Japan has contributed regionally and internationally through its Office for Development Assistance (ODA). Sunga (2004) discussed that Japan believes that the project can play a meaningful role in the development of East Asia (Sunga, 2004). Japan has developed a close relationship with the eastern region of Asia in all aspects, including politics, economy, and culture, which has great significance for Japan's safety and prosperity. According to Japan's diplomatic bluebook from 2013 to 2019;

‘Japan's ODA performance in terms of its total disbursement was about \$22.53 billion, 20.7% from the previous years of 2013 and 2019²’.

The findings from Japan's diplomatic blue book show that Japan was ranked second among the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) member states of the Development Assistance Committee (DAC). From an international comparison point of view,

‘The amount resulting in Japan's position is 11.58 billion U.S. dollars, up 9.2% from the previous year, ranking fourth after the U.S., U.K., and Germany. However, this figure is attributed to the year 2013 for Japan. In 2019, Japan's ODA was \$15.5 billion U.S. dollars making Japan the fourth-largest donor country and the largest in Asia. The ODA represent 0.29% of Japan's gross national income (GNI)’.

Furthermore, from April 2020 to March 2021, Japan's ODA is estimated to increase by;

‘3% compared to 2019. However, this also includes a marginal increase of 1.2% in the foreign ministry's ODA budget. Historically, Japan is known for its focus

² Japan diplomatic blue book 2013 and 2019; Chapter 3: Japan's policy to promote national and worldwide interest.

and support through its bilateral ODA (77% of total ODA), including its contributions to multilateral ODA, a share of its total ODA. From the findings, this means that the government of Japan donates directly to the recipient country without a third-party organisation³.

According to the government of Japan,

‘Through ODA assistance, Japan prioritises infrastructural projects because of its immediate benefits and because it provides work for Japanese manufacturing company’.

Furthermore, Japan has a set of strategic priorities that includes developing and promoting economic growth, including public and private partnerships primarily with Japanese companies in its development cooperation. For example, the below findings from Japan’s diplomatic documents from 2013 to 2019 state;

“It is vital that Japan actively participate in international discussion in this manner to establish international frameworks that reflect Japan’s views. Japan works with various countries, international organisations, civil society, and other stakeholders to promote human security and to work proactively towards finding solutions to global issues”.

Therefore, from the findings, this research identifies ODA as a soft power resource for Japan to create an international environment favourable to Japan to realise a stable development of countries with shared values such as; freedom, democracy, and law and to strengthen relationships with these countries. In addition, Japan’s diplomatic document states that

³ Through its assistance, Japan prioritise infrastructural projects because of its immediate benefits and because it provides work for Japanese manufacturing company.

‘Japan will actively contribute to peace and the stability of the international community through ODA in areas such as peacebuilding, counterterrorism, enhancing maritime law enforcement capabilities and ensuring the safety in sea lanes’.

However, because of Article 9 of Japan’s constitution, Japan’s contribution as a major player in international politics with the use of ODA as a soft power tool for interacting with other countries, However, creating bilateral or unilateral relationships. Also, in terms of boosting its soft power through its culture and identity, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games appears to be an important vehicle with great promises to replicate the positive contribution of the 1964 Olympic Games that was a vehicle for its soft power after the Second World War.

4.6 Theme B- Understanding Japan’s Soft Power through its Office for Development Assistance ODA in Africa and Asia

The findings made it clear that Japan has prioritised its ODA to strengthen its relations with Africa and Asia by using its strong economy, and diplomatic and geographical relationships, particularly in governance and infrastructure development. For example, the Tokyo International Conference on African Development (TICAD), for instance, seeks to advance Africa based on the fundamental tenets of global cooperation and African ownership. About 10,000 people attend TICAD, including 42 African presidents and representatives from partner nations, NGOs, and international organisations to discuss the development of Africa. Through the three pillars of the economy, society, peace, and stability—people, technology, and innovation—TICAD seeks to improve Africa's development. This also includes business promotion by Japanese private companies and the African side with private companies from Japan and Africa cooperating. (Ampiah, 2005, p. 99) According to Japanese policymakers, TICAD is Japan’s way of highlighting Africa’s development problems, reminding the international community that the continent’s problems did not melt away with the end of the

Cold War. It is said that the development problem in Africa is a genuinely global issue that should be addressed collectively by the international community.

However, it is important to note that Japan's first TICAD was proposed at a U.N. General Assembly meeting in 1991 and was effectively organised by Takaya Suto, the former Director-General of the Middle Eastern and African Affairs Bureau of the Japanese Ministry of Foreign (MOFA). The findings reveal that Japan's sudden interest in Africa begs the question of why a sudden change in Japan's attitude towards Africa and why TICAD launched in the 1990s and not when Japan's economy was in a much healthier state than it was in the 20th century. This research study reveals that from the 1960s, when Japan's constitution prohibited Japan from exercising its hard power resources, focusing on Africa and its development became a necessary diplomatic move for Japan. Perhaps contributing towards international development and peace is a subtle diplomatic and soft power strategy to gain international recognition. However, this research finds the idea of foreign aid and development as a soft power tool problematic. Providing developing nations, especially those in sub-Saharan Africa, with aid in the form of social, economic, and humanitarian development has been a popular practice since the 1960s. Foreign aid is essential in lessening suffering, but it is not a long-term solution for sustainable or stable development. Foreign aid may have been a success in the late 1940s, but recently, foreign aid has been found to hinder development where it is indispensable (Lyons, 2014). Lyons (2014) points out that more money is involved than it took to rebuild Europe after World War II. At the same time, rich countries and famous politicians are judged by foreign aid and do not stop campaigning for foreign aid. Foreign aid does not seem to be showing any significant progress in alleviating poverty in Africa. Foreign aid is synonymous with the promotion of corruption and dependence. For example, in sub-Saharan Africa, the level of progress appears to be low compared to the enormous sum received. Foreign aid budgets to Chad, Angola, Nigeria, or the continent receive about \$50 billion in international

assistance annually. Instead of witnessing a dramatic change in development and improvements in the lives of about 600 million people living in poverty. The aid makes the rich richer and the poor poorer hinders economic growth in the region, and catalyses corruption. However, in Japan's case, its ODA is simply a foreign policy strategy and a soft power tool used by the Japanese government to create relationships with countries needing development assistance and in turn, to make Japan a significant player in international relations. Secondly, because of Article 9 in the Japanese constitution, the Japanese government has no option but to engage heavily in ODA. It appears that in order to investigate Japan's soft power strategy, Japan's ODA initiative had to be examined. For example, Japan's assistance for Myanmar includes the support of reform efforts toward democratisation, national reconciliation, and sustainable development. This effort also provides welfare improvement, poverty reduction that supports minority groups, and institutional and infrastructural development for sustainable growth. The engagement of ODA in Asia is a form of geopolitical rivalry. However, this geographical rivalry is like China's as China has a growing presence in Africa with a central position in the development of many African nations (Yu, 1977).

In 2012, Japan's view on China's presence in Myanmar and China's position with foreign investments of about USD14billion, including several undocumented investments, became a reason for Japan's renewed relationship with Myanmar since 1988⁴ (Steinberg, 2013)

According to the findings;

David I. Steinberg (2013) -Japan Chair Platform; Centre for Strategic & International Studies- From 1948 to 1988, Japan took the role of marginal assistance and influence until the military coup on the 18th of September, 1988.

⁴ David I. Steinberg (2013) -Japan Chair Platform; centre for strategic & international studies- From the period of 1948 to 1988, Japan took the role marginal assistance and influence until the military coup in September 18, 1988. Japan had provided Myanmar with US\$2.2 billion in foreign aid and reparations.

Japan had provided Myanmar with US\$2.2 billion in foreign aid and reparations.

According to section three-chapter two of Japan's diplomatic bluebook, MOFA states,

Japan has a long-standing, friendly relationship and historically close ties with circa 1.8 million Japanese descendants living in these countries. Many countries in this region face challenges like income disparities and poverty in rural areas, which are vulnerable to natural disasters. However, Japan has provided these countries with environmental, climate change, and disaster risk management. Japan proactively takes part in the discussion based on human security, demonstrating the country's desire and strong points such as health and disaster risk reduction, and building a framework for emerging countries and interested NGOs. Japan has made an effort to take initiatives and discussions with the international community to achieve millennium development goals (MDG's), which have since become Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)⁵.

The key point from the findings is that foreign aid and development is an important soft power strategy for Japan to connect with the international community. The findings indicate that foreign aid is a crucial instrument of international engagement or interactions between countries. For Japan, foreign aid or its ODA is a vital instrument of its foreign policy, being a top four aid donor. From the findings, it is evident that Japan engages in several foreign development assistance programmes with a focus on Asia and Africa because of its inability to exercise the entirety of its strength primarily through hard power resources like every sovereign nation. Hence their focus is on development, people-to-people relations, and education.

Furthermore, Article 9 of Japan's constitution means that Japan had to find subtle ways to display its influence and image internationally. The findings point out that, in the 1980s, Japan was criticised domestically and globally over the commercial nature of its aid. As an aid superpower at the time, the money went into the private accounts of corrupt political leaders in

⁵ <https://www.mofa.go.jp/files/000177715.pdf>

Asia and into projects that created severe environmental damage. Japan responded by revising its ODA charter in 2003⁶.

‘Japan’s ODA White Paper (2003), the revision of the ODA charter and Japan’s new approach: Japan has contributed to the development of developing countries as one of the largest donor countries in the world. But because of the severe economic and fiscal situation in Japan, the critical view of ODA held by the Japanese people, etc. in recent years, the ODA budget is in decline. Japan’s ODA in 2002 came to \$9.283 billion, a 5.7% decrease from the previous year. In this context, the government is vigorously promoting ODA reform with the keywords of transparency, efficiency, and public participation’.

The findings show that Japan’s revised aid charter still maintains vital aspects such as human security, poverty alleviation, health and women’s welfare and leaving the military and defence-related activities outside of the aid zone⁷, and these are classified as soft power strategies. The findings show that because of the pacifist characteristics of Japan’s soft power, Japan has resulted in ODA as a medium for interacting with the foreign public. These results show the importance of soft power for Japan by engaging in aid development in order to improve its image among other countries.

4.7 Theme C- Understanding Japan’s foreign policy and the foundation of its soft power through Prime Minister Abe’s policy

This research has identified ODA as Japan’s soft power tool and a means to interact with countries through aid, development, education, and people-to-people relations. Thus, it is important to discuss what this means for Japan in expanding its soft power goals with the

⁶ Japan’s ODA White Paper (2003), the revision of the ODA chapter and Japan’s new approach: Japan has contributed to the development of developing countries as one of the largest donor countries in the world, but because of the severe economic and fiscal situation in Japan, the critical view of ODA held by the Japanese people, etc. in recent years, the ODA budget is in decline. Japan’s ODA in 2002 came to \$9.283 billion, a 5.7% decrease from the previous year. In this context, the government is vigorously promoting ODA reform with the keywords of transparency, efficiency, and public participation.

⁷ Purenendra Jain (2016) East Asian forum, economic, politics and public affairs in East Asia and the Pacific; Japans foreign aid: what’s in it for Japan?

extensive use of its ODA as a soft power tool. From the findings, what is next for Japan is connected to former Prime Minister Shinzo Abe's leadership, Japan's post-World War prime minister. It is important to acknowledge that Abe left office in 2020 and however, tragically died in 2022. But these latest events however have had no impact on what the data had revealed about his administration and political policies. In terms of Japan's soft power, this section discussed the importance of hosting the 2020 Olympic Games on Japan's geopolitical image. Discussing if the Olympic Games translate into an effective strategy to display Japan as a political and economic powerhouse.

This research finds that Abe had a clear policy plan and a clear vision for Japan and its status on the international stage. Abe had a clear plan to make Japan a significant player globally compared to his predecessors. Until 2012 when Abe became prime minister, Japan had difficulties defining its identity in a post-war order⁸. According to Hugo Dobson (2017);

is Japan really back? 'The Abe Doctrine' and Global Governance; Japan's Prime Minister Abe has emerged as a comeback kid of Japanese politics and in his second term in office is now widely regarded as a rare example of strong leadership as he seeks to arrest and reverse his country's perceived decline.

The results show that Abe looked strong and proactive when he was re-elected in 2012, demonstrating leadership in several areas, including revitalising Japan's economy with the help of the "three arrows" of "Abenomics" (monetary easing, fiscal stimulus, and the promotion of growth strategies through structural reforms). This also includes promoting historical revisionism and criticising the dominant post-war interpretations of Japan's experience of the Pacific War. Additionally, there is uncertainty about efforts to transform Japan into a more

⁸ Hugo Dobson (2017) is Japan really back? 'The Abe Doctrine' and Global Governance; Japan's prime minister Abe has emerged as a comeback kid of Japanese politics and in his second term in office is now widely regarded as a rare example of strong leadership as he seeks to arrest and reverse his country's perceived decline.

"normal" nation using "proactive contribution to peace," constitutional amendment, and reinterpreting Japan's self-imposed restriction on collective self-defence (Dobson, 2017, p. 200). Japan was second behind China in 2010, partly because of Japan's ageing population and growing debt. However, in 2012, the research found that Abe's vision for Japan was the prospect of a stronger and more assertive Japan, which included changing Japan's pacifist constitution when China continued to grow its military capabilities and the ongoing threat of North Korea⁹. In addition, China's ambitions and increased military aggression keen to establish an alternative roadmap for international development that challenges U.S. dominance.

According to the globalist;

Shihoko Goto (2020): Japan's longest-serving prime minister achieved not only a stable Japan but one with a clear view of its own identity and role in the world.

Abe sought to enhance its defence capabilities by guaranteeing that the rule of law prevails over Asia. However, the findings show that Japan's strategy under Prime Minister Abe is identified as a mixed strategy of hard power and soft power resources to make Japan a major player in international relations. Abe's strategy for Japan is to reaffirm Japan as a global power, and this entails the re-interpretation of the Japanese constitution to remilitarise, including Japan's involvement in development assistance and, finally, the significant role Abe played in Japan hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

The findings reveal that Foreign Minister Fumio Kishida and Prime Minister Abe together with the members of his cabinet attended a session of the International Olympic Committee (IOC) IN Buenos Aires, Argentina. According to the Olympic Games bid.

⁹ The Globalist- Shihoko Goto (2020): Japans longest-serving prime minister achieved not only a stable Japan but one with a clear view of its own identity and role in the world.

‘Foreign Minister Fumio Kishida, Prime Minister Shinzo Abe, and other members of the cabinet will be attending a session of the International Olympic Committee (IOC) in Buenos Aires, Argentina on September 7 to support Tokyo’s bid for the 2020 Summer Olympic Games, when the host city of the 2020 Games will be elected’. (Gamesbids, 2013)

Also that;

‘Abe is expected to cut short his attendance at a summit of the Group of 20 major economies in St. Petersburg, Russia September 5-6 to attend the session and support Tokyo’s bid’. (Gamesbids, 2013)

Abe’s action to cut short his attendance at the summit of the group of 20 major economies to attend the Olympic bid summit signifies how important hosting the Olympic Games was to his administration and policies.

Furthermore, there appears to be an element of geopolitical motivation in Abe’s proposed policy. In recent years, the relationship between China and Japan has deteriorated, but the long-lasting bilateral relationship between both countries has seen minimal conflicts since the late 1990s. Smith (2009) discusses that Sino-Japanese relations will likely be tested or constrained by five key issues. The first is the territorial and resource dispute. The second is on nationalism and issues of mutual antipathy, the third is on Taiwan’s political status, the fourth is on the rapid rise of China’s military power, and the fifth is on the U.S.-Japan security alliance. Pointing out how these issues are managed or resolved will play a major role in the Sino-Japanese relationship and the overall geopolitical environment in East Asia. Abe’s policy and attempt to remilitarise Japan’s constitution point to the geopolitical importance of Japan’s image and soft power in becoming an active international and geopolitical power.

Furthermore, the different global views of China's leaders are more consistent in adopting the realist views of international politics and in contrast, Japanese leaders are viewed to favour liberal institutionalist values. These different lenses are issues in the relationships of both

countries with the potential to create misunderstanding. Also, Brands (2021) points out that Japan, the sleeping giant of global affairs, is waking up. Brands (2021) illustrates how Tokyo is driving the fourth foreign-policy revolution in the modern period due to Beijing's threat and Washington's ambivalence. Point out that the Japanese quiescence era is ending, primarily because of the bellicosity of China. It is important to highlight the geopolitical issues in East Asia, especially between Japan and China, because of the enormous political and economic power they both possess. However, it makes sense to see why Abe's policy to remilitarise and at the same time push to host the 2020 Tokyo Olympics is a key smart power strategy. Japan does not operate a normal political system; as a sovereign state, Japan is stuck in a position where it cannot exercise its collective self-defence. In addition, Japan relies on the US-Japan Security Treaty on collective self-defence for its national security. With the aspiration to become a major player in the regional and international role and the pressure of a rising and aggressive China, it became logical that the Abe government address and reinterpret its self-imposed restrictions.

Furthermore, in terms of looking at the Olympic Games as a soft power strategy for Abe, it appears that the adoption of liberal policies by the Japanese government gives them a soft power edge over China. The findings show that Beijing faced an increased international backlash over its policies, including its treatment of ethnic Uighurs in Xinjiang and its controversial new security law in Hong Kong (Gallagher, 2021). The letter includes a statement saying;

‘Al Jazeera: Rights groups ask IOC to take 2022 Winter Games away from China

‘The IOC must recognise that the Olympic spirit and the reputation of the Olympic Games will suffer further damage if the worsening human rights crisis, across all areas under China's control, is ignored’.

The letter makes the case that the prestige of the 2008 Olympics prompted the government to implement further measures, such as ethnic policies and programmes aimed at the Xinjiang Uighurs. China contends that societal stability and national security depend on its policies in Tibet, Hong Kong, and Xinjiang. In response, the IOC said that it had obtained assurances from Chinese officials that they would uphold the Olympic Charter's tenets and decided to stay impartial on political matters. Similarly, in 2008, human rights groups protested ahead of the Games, but the IOC defended its choice, saying that the Games were a force for good. The IOC highlights the International Olympic Charter claiming the political neutrality of the Games. However, in the case of the IOC, the problematic question that remains to be answered is how long the IOC will deny or not recognise that the Games have become a symbol of peace, diplomacy, internationalism, and display of political agenda. However, it is essential to discuss to what extent this narrative contributes to Japan's soft power strategy as a deliberate action. Sports mega-events like the Olympic Games translate into the display of financial and political strength. Given the political tensions mentioned.

4.8 Theme D- Understanding Japan's foreign policy strategy and national interest; the importance of sports tourism on Japan's soft power

In analysing Japan's diplomatic documents, the discussion around national interest in sports tourism was an indication of Japan's soft power strategy that points out the need to discuss Japan's ability to achieve the promotion of its culture, sport, and tourism by hosting the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games. It is important to discuss these key pillars of Japan's sport diplomacy, especially in the context of the 2020 Olympic Games. How Japan's engagement in sports development and international cooperation amounts to soft power.

For example,

Chapter three of Japan's diplomatic bluebook states that; Japan's foreign policy is to promote National and worldwide interests: Culture, Sport, and Tourism, page 175.

The findings specifically on Japan's diplomatic bluebook reveal that;

‘Japan's foreign policy strategy promotes trust and understanding, including promoting its culture, sports, and tourism diplomacy.’

The overlap between sports and tourism has significantly increased over the years from the period of 2013 to 2018 Japan recorded a tourism boom of 31 million; sports have become a tool for generating social and economic benefits for societies. In the history of sports mega-events, host countries expect to record rapid growth in all their industries, especially tourism. As a result of their significant significance as economic engines and their good social and cultural effects, Lee (2003) notes that many countries are attempting to grow their sports tourism sectors. It appears that Japan's government recognise the importance of tourism growth through sports events. In addition, tourism diplomacy can be replaced with cultural diplomacy as it signifies the cultural interaction between tourists from different cultural backgrounds.

Similarly, Volume 1 chapter 1 of Japan's Olympic candidature file on motivation and vision for its Olympic bid states that;

‘We will unite the power of the Games with the unique Culture and qualities of the Japanese people, and the excitement of a city that sets global trends. (Tokyo 2020 Candidature file 2020)

However, Japan's foreign policy, as well as national and international objectives, are intended to be achieved and promoted through the 2020 Olympic Games as part of a soft power strategy, utilising its culture, sports, and tourism. Furthermore, the Japanese government points out that;

‘There is a need to pursue strategic diplomacy while rationally accounting for and adapting to, changes in the international situation. While this strategic

diplomacy has a set goal, it is not easy for countries to execute and account for effectively the effectiveness of this strategy'. To achieve this strategic diplomacy, and protect and promote Japan's national interests, Japan pursues diplomacy to strengthen the Japan/U.S. alliance. This includes tackling outstanding issues of concern regarding North Korea, strengthening diplomacy with neighbouring countries, such as China, the Republic of Korea (ROK), and Russia, and addressing the increasingly tense situation in the Middle East.

Strategic diplomacy is an important word used by the Japanese government, and previous findings highlight the geopolitical tensions in East Asia, Abe's administrative policies and strategy. The use of the term strategic diplomacy agrees with the geopolitical rivalry in Asia. In addition, this includes economic, political, and cultural rivalry. Strategic diplomacy from the lens of Abe's Government means remilitarisation and Hosting the Olympic Games, and this is a smart power strategy for strategic diplomacy. However, the question for discussion is whether Japan's strategic diplomacy has been effective so far. Especially considering the national and foreign policy of Abe's government.

Additionally, this research reveals that Japan's diplomatic approach entails addressing global concerns and engaging in economic diplomacy, wherein Japan will spearhead attempts to build new common rules. Through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA), Japan aims to foster mutual understanding and trust using strategic communications. The MOFA bases its strategic communications on three pillars, namely;

'(1) Making further efforts to disseminate Japan's policies and initiatives, including the accurate Image of Japan, (2) sharing Japan's rich and varied attractiveness. (3) Expanding the circle of people with a great affinity toward or knowledge of Japan while enhancing the capabilities of its overseas missions, which are on the frontlines of public diplomacy.

Concerning the first pillar, the main objectives of MOFA are to increase public awareness of matters concerning historical recognition and the maintenance of territorial integrity, as well as to promote a broad comprehension of Japan's contributions to global peace, stability, and prosperity. MOFA actively promotes Japan's position and viewpoints via various channels, including daily press conferences, interviews, article contributions, and speeches made by the Prime Minister, Foreign Minister, and other government officials at international conferences and official visits to other countries. Japan maintains active diplomatic relations with the governments and people of the countries it has designated as its host nation. Japan's strategy to promote trust and understanding includes promoting its culture, sports, and tourism diplomacy.

Most importantly, chapter three of Japan's diplomatic bluebook states that; Japan's foreign policy promotes national and worldwide interest: Culture, sport, and Tourism, page 175. States that;

‘The promotion of sport, culture and tourism diplomacy is a policy from the Japanese government to a large number of nations that have developed an interest in Japan. MOFA and the Japan Foundation (J.F.) carry out several projects ranging from introducing Japanese culture and sports to promoting inbound tourism, which aims to create positive images of Japan abroad, boost the overall Japanese brand, and encourage a deeper understanding of Japan. Including increasing the number of foreign visitors to Japan’¹⁰.

Furthermore, the study finds that Japan's diplomatic mission overseas organises;

¹⁰ Chapter three of Japan's diplomatic bluebook; Japan's foreign policy to promote National and worldwide interest: Culture, sport, and Tourism, page 175.

‘cultural project that introduces a wide range of Japanese culture, from traditional arts such as tea ceremony and flower arrangement to aspects of modern culture such as anime and manga and fashion’.

Nonetheless, the results show that planning and participating in sporting events is an important aspect of Japan's foreign policy approach. This describes Japan's participation in the competition to host major sporting events such as the Olympic Games in Tokyo in 2020. Maybe having the Games will enhance its tourism diplomacy and aid in the creation and promotion of its culture. Using the 2020 Olympics as a vehicle for soft power, like the Tokyo 1964 Games, is an extra benefit that will help Japan achieve its diplomatic and foreign policy objectives. The results show that sport plays a significant role in Japan's soft power and foreign policy.

Additionally, this study discovers that Prime Minister Abe started the Sport for tomorrow initiative to use sports to benefit the world community in Japan's diplomatic paper. In this instance, the Sport for tomorrow initiative is identified by this study as Japan's soft power and sport diplomacy tactic. As the nation selected to host the Olympic and Paralympic Games in 2020, Japan made a commitment in September 2013 in Buenos Aires to spread the love of sports to over 10 million people across more than 100 nations. In partnership with Japan's Sports Agency and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Japanese government has spearheaded the SFT initiative. As stated in the programme handbook;

‘Starting in 2014, “All-Japan Initiatives” have taken place with 448 consortium members across the public-private sectors of Japan and implemented 6,804 programmes. (As of the 31st of March 2020)’.

The Sport for tomorrow programme has reached its target of 12 million people in 204 countries. This signifies an effective soft power and sport diplomacy strategy.

Furthermore, the sport for tomorrow programme is based on the following three pillars:

Moreover, the following three pillars form the foundation of the sport for tomorrow programme:

1. Global Collaboration and Communication via Athletics

Support in the form of both material and intangibles has been given, with an emphasis on developing nations and areas. Examples of this support include introducing Japanese sports culture and content, boosting competition, and using sports to improve the world through peace and development.

2. Academy for Tomorrow's Leaders in Sport

To lay the groundwork for educating the next generation of leaders in international sports, Japan's Academy for Tomorrow's Leaders in Sports Universities came together. There is now a master's programme for young people in Japan and overseas, along with short-term seminars.

3. "PLAY TRUE 2020: Global Development of Anti-Doping Movement"

Sports values-based education has been created and put into practice in collaboration with international sports federations, anti-doping organisations, and educational institutions. Athletes and sports enthusiasts have sent "TRUTH in Sport" messages to the world based on the following pillars:

1. International Cooperation and Exchange through Sport

Global Collaboration and Communication via Athletics Support, both material and intangible, has been given with an emphasis on developing nations and areas. Examples of this include boosting competitiveness and promoting sports, with the goal of utilising sport to transform the world (peace and development). introducing international sports exchange programmes, Japanese sports culture, and the foundations of international collaboration through sports,, an academy for tomorrow's leaders in sports and key pillars are key signifiers in Japan's soft power and sport diplomacy intention. Although, the sport for tomorrow program was established in reaching out to other countries and young people through its sports and development program. Ubaidulloev (2018) Points out that sports for international Cooperation is an effective tool for creating peace through sports cooperation. Sport is valuable as a vehicle for social development

and progressive social change. Sport development is about providing individuals with opportunities to engage in development by participating in various types of physical activities. However, the findings have shown that Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy entails international sport cooperation and development through sport, and this is a benefit for its soft power.

4.8.1 Theme E- Abe's foreign policy strategy combines Japan's hard and soft power resources.

The key point in this section is the overlap between the 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle of soft power and the re-interpretation of Article 9 in Japan's constitution. In 2013, just after winning the bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Prime Minister Abe reinterpreted the clause in Article 9 of the Japanese constitution to widen the meaning of self-defence after failures to make the Japanese military proactive. As a result, the cabinet approved the interpretation of the constitution that permits the use of the 'right of collective self-defence under certain limitations'¹¹.

The New York Times- Motoko Rich (2017), Shinzo Abe Announces Plan to Revise Japan's Pacifist Constitution.

TOKYO — Prime Minister Shinzo Abe of Japan announced on Wednesday a plan to revise a pacifist Constitution that has been in place since American occupiers enacted it in 1947. In a video message delivered at a celebration of the 70th anniversary of the Constitution, Mr. Abe said he wanted to make “explicit the status” of the country's self-defence forces, as Japan's military is known, by amending the constitution by 2020. As Japan faces continuing security threats from North Korea, Mr. Abe said that there should be no room for arguing that, the military, with just over 227,000 active-duty troops, “may be unconstitutional.”

¹¹ The New York Times- Motoko Rich (2017), Shinzo Abe Announces Plan to Revise Japan's Pacifist Constitution. <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/05/03/world/asia/japan-constitution-shinzo-abe-military.html>

On the other hand, a new national security strategy emerged from the reinterpretation of Article 9. This was a well-thought-out political move to increase Japan's influence. In this situation, the Japanese government can offer initiatives to further global cooperation and peace, such as the strategic use of foreign aid to address worldwide problems that are thought to pose a threat to the peace and security of Japan and the surrounding areas. As a result, Japan's military can participate in peacebuilding phases that include humanitarian aid during hostilities, conflict prevention that could jeopardise national sovereignty, and assistance in bringing an end to hostilities, including support for development and reconstruction. However, critics argue that separating non-military purposes from military purposes is challenging. Japan's government emphasises that its promise to refrain from offering military support and its strategic use of foreign aid do not contradict. This means that Japan will support foreign military forces in the growth of cooperation for non-military goals like public welfare or disaster assistance (Furuoka, 2016). What is remarkable about Japan's post-war foreign policy strategy is its use of its aid budget for largely military activities, even though they are not for combat purposes. The use of aid to protect its national interest is crucial for Japan's foreign policy engagement and relations. However, this is important for reintroducing Japan into the international community. Not as a pacifist country but as a country that can exercise its power through its military like other sovereign nations.

Furthermore, to Daisuke (2018) it is less clear the direction these reforms are taking the country (Daisuke, 2018) through the interpretation of Article 9 and the inclusion of Japan's military into its foreign aid initiative. As noted earlier from the findings, Abe is trying to move Japan away from its post-war pacifism. This means revolving Japan into an extensive and proactive international player, simply responding to growing regional challenges, especially with China's ability to combine soft power and hard power resources. Abe's policy trajectory has raised questions about the ambiguities of whether his reforms represent a radical departure of Japan

from its pacifist nature (Hughes, 2014) or whether his reforms are evolutionary or revolutionary as (Liff, 2015) suggests. In 2012, after winning his return as prime minister, Abe declared that Japan was back and expressed his desire to make Japan a ‘first-tier power (Hughes, 2014, pp. 1-2) Abe’s notion of Japan is back, a national and international strategy used by Abe to reimagine Japan as a major player in global politics.

Furthermore, the strategy to assume the right of collective self-defence is a significant shift in Japan’s military posture that may help counter China’s aggression. This means that Japan’s handicapped hard power will lose its restrictions and harmoniously play a major role in its foreign policy strategy. However, it is unclear how this shift in Japan’s hard power will help its statecraft in the Asian region or internationally. In addition, Abe recognised the Olympic Games as an instrument of political, economic, and prestige gain to achieve Japan’s reality of becoming a first-tier power. For an effective foreign policy strategy, this research finds that the re-interpretation of Japan’s defence and security policy is not enough to achieve its goals hence Abe’s huge support for Tokyo to win the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In 2013, Tokyo’s bid to host the Olympics was almost a failure after concerns were raised because of the Fukushima disaster. However, Abe intervened at the 2013 IOC summit¹².

Kristo Tamm (2020), *The Diplomat: What will Tokyo’s Postponed Olympics Mean for Japanese Politics?* Shinzo Abe’s legacy is on the line. For Abe, hosting the Olympic Games is about national pride and an opportunity to demonstrate his leadership. To Abe, “it is extremely important for the national government to continue in our aspiration to promote Japan as a sports nation further” Kristo Tamm (2020).

Additionally, Abe points out that based on the lesson from Tokyo’s bid for the 2016 Olympic and Paralympic Games, Japan have retained the best of its bid plan while adding important new strengths. He continues, ‘

¹² Kristo Tamm (2020), *The Diplomat: What will Tokyo’s Postponed Olympics Mean for Japanese Politics?* Shinzo Abe’s legacy is on the line.

Now that our candidate File is complete, Tokyo is one step closer to implementing an innovative and aspiring Games plan. The Games in 2020 in Tokyo will offer athletes, spectators and Olympic and Paralympic Family members a true once-in-a-lifetime experience¹³.

Hosting the Games creates a platform to display Japan's resilience while enhancing its economic growth and achieving Abe's goal of preventing Japan from becoming a tier-two country, especially in Asia. The Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is a strategy to cement Japan's status as a global power and economic powerhouse and a significant player in the international community. Politically, it is an opportunity to cement Prime Minister Abe's policies, such as Japan's security and economic strategy that he has tried to implement since 2012. Furthermore, this means for Japan that hosting the Olympic Games is an added advantage to Japan's economy and a bonus for 'Abenomics'. Furthermore, findings from the Reuters-Elaine Lies (2013) depict that,

Japan Olympic win boosts Abe, but Fukushima shadows linger; Japan savoured its victory on Monday in the race to host the 2020 Olympic Games, anticipating an economic boost to spur its revival from two decades of stagnation and help it recover from the devastating 2011 earthquake and tsunami. Prime Minister Shinzo Abe's bold gamble to throw himself into the Tokyo bid paid off handsomely, his claims to have the problems of the crippled Fukushima nuclear reactor under control ran into fresh resistance'.

'James McBride and Beina (2018), Council on Foreign Relations: Abenomics and the Japanese Economy- Japan's prime minister Shinzo Abe has introduced an audacious set of economic policies designed to spur the country out of its decades-long deflationary slump'.

¹³ Prime Minister of Japan and His Cabinet; Speeches and Statements by the Prime Minister. Press Conference by Prime Minister Shinzo Abe Following His Attendance at the G20 Summit Meeting in Saint Petersburg and the 125th International Olympic Committee Session Saturday, September 7, 2013

Abe's economic plan, known as "Abenomics," aims to rescue Japan from the more than two decades of economic deflation it has experienced. Abenomics is the name given to a series of bold fiscal and monetary policies along with structural changes aimed at rescuing Japan from the economic slump¹⁴. However, winning the bid to host the Olympic Games was an added advantage. According to the Tokyo bid committee, the addition of 150,000 employment will stimulate the third-largest economy in the world's GDP by more than 3 trillion yen (\$30 billion) (Lies, 2013). Abe's economic strategy was strengthened by Tokyo's victory over rivals Madrid and Istanbul, even though he risked his reputation for the bid. Furthermore, a sharp increase in Tokyo share prices indicates a positive impact on national confidence, which is a crucial component of Abe's pro-growth policies and economic success¹⁵.

4.9 FINDINGS ON SPORTS DIPLOMACY

4.9.1 Theme F- Sport for Tomorrow: Japan's Olympic Project and Sport Diplomacy Strategy

The finding points toward a need to discuss the impact of the sport for tomorrow program (STP) program as a bottom-up approach to Japan's soft power strategy. From Japan's Olympic bid document, Volume 1 of the 2020 Olympic candidature file focuses on its vision and motivation to host the 2020 Olympic Games. The document points out that Tokyo 2020 will bring together sports and Olympic values in the heart of the world's most forward-thinking safe cities. Through;

¹⁴ James McBride and Beina (2018), Council on Foreign Relations: Abenomics and the Japanese Economy- Japans prime minister Shinzo Abe has introduced an audacious set of economic policies designed to spur the country out of its decades-long defaltory slump. The results have so far been mixed.

¹⁵ The Reuters-Elaine Lies (2013): Japan Olympic win boosts Abe, but Fukushima shadows linger; Japan savoured its victory on Monday in the race to host the 2020 Olympic Games, anticipating an economic boost to spur its revival from two decades of stagnation and help it recover from the devastating 2011 earthquake and tsunami. Prime Minister Shinzo Abe's bold gamble to throw himself into the Tokyo bid paid off handsomely, his claims to have the problems of the crippled Fukushima nuclear reactor under control ran into fresh resistance.

‘Delivery, with guaranteed quality and maximum benefits and Celebration, with the city hosting a dynamic and welcoming party that will inspire the youth of the world’.

In achieving this, Prime Minister Abe announced the launch of the sport for tomorrow (SFT) programme in Japan as a programme for contributing internationally through sports. Chapter three of the diplomatic bluebook (Japan’s Foreign Policy to Promote National and Global Interest in Culture, sport and Tourism Diplomacy) states that;

‘For a very large number of foreign nationals who develop an interest in Japan, Japanese culture is a motive for their interests. MOFA and the J.F. carry out various projects ranging from introducing Japanese culture and sports to promoting inbound tourism, aimed at creating positive images of Japan abroad. Boosting the overall Japanese brand, and encouraging a deeper understanding of Japan, as well as fostering the circle of people with a great affinity toward or knowledge of Japan and increasing the number of foreign visitors to Japan’.

Furthermore, The Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA) state that

‘Under the “Japan Brand Program,” MOFA has dispatched experts of various fields overseas to share Japan’s outstanding cultural assets, which represent a culmination of Japan’s experience and wisdom, as well as to establish a national brand and give Japan a stronger presence in the world. MOFA holds seminars, workshops, and demonstrations that reflect each expert’s characteristics and that share their values and experiences with the audience, paving the way for international exchange’.

Therefore, from the findings in the document, STP is a part of the Japan Brand Program. The findings from the document state that;

‘It is also important that Japan takes the opportunity of the TOKYO 2020 Games to further enhance Japan’s presence in the field of sports. As part of the “Sport for Tomorrow (SFT)” program, MOFA is engaged in various initiatives such as sports exchanges and sports promotion support projects overseas, dispatching

sports instructors through the JICA volunteer program or the J.F. MOFA also donates sporting equipment and improves sporting facilities through Cultural Grant Assistance. In addition, MOFA provides information about these initiatives in Japan and abroad through MOFA's "Mofa Japan x SPORTS" twitter account. Furthermore, MOFA supports the Host Town Initiative that promotes mutual exchange with the countries and regions participating in the TOKYO 2020 Games'.

Through public-private cooperation with Japan, the SFT programme has supported several projects. Over ten million people in over 100 countries—including developing ones—have been the program's aim for more than seven years, from 2014 to 2020. (sportanddev.org, 2020). This is positive news for Japan's sport diplomacy, but it's crucial to talk about the implications for Japan's soft power and the Olympic Games. In addition, to improve the world's future, to spread the ideals of the Olympic and Paralympic movements among people of all ages, especially the bright young people. The Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA) has also carried out a wide range of programmes, including the development of sports facilities, the dispatching and visiting of sports instructors and athletes, and the introduction of Japanese culture in the field of sports, as noted in Chapter 3 of Japan's diplomatic bluebook 2020. The programme registered 10.02 million participants in September 2019 from 202 different countries and regions. From the Diplomatic Bluebook 2019, the data shows that Japan engages in forms of sport diplomacy by providing necessary support to several countries in need of sport development. Okada (2018) talked about how the global community has been making progress with sport for development for a while now. But it wasn't until lately that the Japanese government started looking for methods to support the industry as Tokyo bids to host the 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games (Okada, 2018). Japan's Cultural Grassroots Project grant aid, for example, was used to build baseball fields in Tanzania (GCGP). Tanzanian citizens also

gain from the progress, not just baseball players. Tanzanian elementary and junior high schools now teach baseball, thanks to Japan's introduction of the sport to the country.

In addition, in Madagascar, Rugby is a popular sport, but teams practice in old Rugby balls. The Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) helped donate rugby balls to the Madagascar Team. This generated a response from the chairman of the Madagascar Rugby Union that the contribution would be instrumental in helping the team get into the Olympics. In South Sudan, the Ministry of Higher Education acknowledged that they received various forms of assistance from Japan through sports. Including Japan's cooperation in Karate, the Karate athletes contribute to enhancing the relationship and people-to-people exchanges between Japan and South Sudan. Additionally, Okada (2018) discloses that the sports industry in Japan is facing several challenges as a result of the country's slow economic growth and that the importance of using sports to support emerging nations has not been adequately communicated. From the findings, it appears that promoting national interest through sports entails engaging in sports development with other national sports federations. The findings show that the use of sport for tomorrow to engage with other countries is a strategic move for Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power.

Furthermore, sport diplomacy is an integral part of strengthening and building the relationship between the government exercising its sport diplomacy strategy and the targeted country. Sport diplomacy strategy is the use of the collective desire for sport to exceed language and sociocultural differences. Sport diplomacy is defined as "exchanges in the promotion of discourse and cultural understanding between people worldwide" by the US Bureau of Educational and Cultural Affairs. The possibility to forge connections with America and gain knowledge of different cultures is presented by the utilisation of sports as a platform for international interchange and engagement in American culture. For example, tens of thousands

of individuals from over 180 nations have participated in America's sport diplomacy programme.

However, in the case of Japan, The Japan-US relationship after the Second World War, the U.S. occupation of Japan and the formulation of Japan's pacifist constitution by the U.S. depicts that Japan's diplomatic strategy, especially in sport diplomacy, is like that of the United States. Therefore, like the American sports diplomacy strategy, Japan has used the sport for tomorrow programme to create and foster its relationship with other countries through sport. However, hosting the 2020 Olympic Games is a sport diplomacy strategy because of the narrative of hosting a sustainable game and creating a future for the future generation. Therefore, sport for tomorrow program serves as a bottom-up approach and a direct link in developing relationships with the sports federations of other countries and governments through sports development and the introduction of Japanese sports in these countries.

4.9.2 Theme G- Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games through the lens of techno nationalism and superficial environmentalism (Discover tomorrow)

Volume 1 of the Olympic candidature file reveals that the team for the Olympic Games was discovered tomorrow. The Japanese Olympic Committee in their letter to the International Olympic Committee states that the slogan for the 2020 Olympic Games bid was to

‘Discover Tomorrow’

In addition, stating that;

‘The people of Japan has long maintained a healthy balance of respect for our cultural traditions with a forward-looking perspective that understands the necessity of progress. We believe that staging the Olympic Games in Tokyo 2020, would have a wonderful opportunity to

showcase the best of Japan's unique tradition and modern cultures to the world'.

From the document, I find that one of the ways of achieving and showcasing Japan's unique tradition is through Techno-nationalism. Techno-nationalism is the awareness that technological innovation and capabilities are linked directly to a country's economy, social stability, and prosperity. Techno-nationalism is used as a term to understand how technology may affect a country's culture or society. This includes the use of nationalistic agendas to promote a connected narrative to national identity. Through techno-nationalism, it is believed that a country's technological innovation determines the nation's success, especially across its people, believing that technological advancement drives the overall growth and sustainability of the country (Edgerton, 2007).

On the slogan of Discover Tomorrow, and to inspire the world, the 2020 Olympic bid documents state that;

'Tokyo is a city where the world comes to discover the future. The power of continual innovation and a dynamic youth population'. Also, showcase its unique combination of hypermodern living and respected historical value has made it a place of intrigue and inspiration for many of the most influential artists, entrepreneurs and inventors of recent years'.

Japan saw a rise in electrical appliance usage following World War II because of a form of techno-nationalism in science and technology. For Japan's self-identity, the atomic bomb tragedies in Hiroshima and Nagasaki marked the beginning of a new era. For Japan, the war's loss ushered in a new era of nationalism. From a terrible, negatively impacted state-led nationalism to a "softer" sort of nationalism. That was associated with the notion of a shared

commitment to economic progress driven by technology and research (Low, 2010, p. 197). According to Low (2010), a lot of daily life in Japan is viewed through the lens of economics, and the softer kind of nationalism known as techno-nationalism obscures Japan's conception of the state and its political and economic apparatus. illustrating how electrical goods and power produced by nuclear energy became more closely associated with Japanese identity in postwar Japan.

Sangjung and Shunya (2000) point out that electrical household appliance was the foundation of Japan's post-war nationalism. Consumer products were linked to Japan's image and its technological strength that emerged just before the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games (Sangjung & Shunya, 2000). This research finds that Japan has been able to use the Olympic Games as a political tool if looked at through the lens of techno-nationalism in the case of the 1964 Olympic Games and similarly use a combination of technology and superficial Environmentalism in the case of the 2020 Olympic Games. The 2020 bid documents state that one of the motivations for hosting the 2020 Olympic Games is through;

Innovation- stating that; Using Japan's renowned creativity and technology to benefit sport and the Games, through Tokyo 2020. The global sporting family will discover tomorrow Our Games will combine innovation and inspiration to showcase the Olympic values, and the comprehensive benefits and legacies of sport and the Olympic Movement; We will unite the power of the Games with the unique culture and qualities of the Japanese people, and the excitement of a city that sets global trends.

Similarly, I find from the Olympic organisation that;

Olympic.org (the 19th of November 2020)-Technological innovation at the Olympics Games Tokyo 1964: The number of technological advancements

introduced at the Games Tokyo 1964 was such that a British journalist at the time described it as the ‘science fiction’ Games.

The number of technological advancements introduced to the 1964 Olympic Games was described as the ‘science fiction’ Games. Satellite technology was used at the time to relay live pictures to the global audience, and this was characterised as the most innovative technological advancement in the coverage of the Games¹⁶. The cooperation between NASA and the Japanese government, which enabled the launch of a communications satellite, allowed for the successful transmission of the Games. enabling the live transmission of the Olympics to a global audience that spans one-third of the planet and enabling the live broadcast of a full marathon race for the first time (Olympic.org, 2020) The 1964 Olympics featured a few other firsts, such as close-pick up microphones and slow-motion replays for TV coverage. The opening ceremony was among the activities that were shown in colour for the first time. Scholars who have examined how technology was used in Tokyo 1964 have acknowledged that the Games showcased Japanese broadcast technology to the world and aided the country's television sector in breaking into international markets.

Stephanie Wilson (2019)- From Techno nationalism to Superficial Environmentalism: Japan’s Olympics as a political tool

However, the discussion in the literature review presents the Olympic Games as a symbol of diplomacy, internationalism, a symbol of peace, and the expression of political views or powers. This is because of the problematic or contradictory narrative that the Olympics is politically neutral, not recognising its history of Berlin 1936 and London 1948, where the

¹⁶ Olympic.org (19 November 2020)-Technological innovation at the Olympics Games Tokyo 1964: The number of technological advancement introduced at the Games Tokyo 1964 was such that a British journalist at the time described it as the ‘science fiction’ Games.

Games were tied to propaganda and political showmanship¹⁷. However, in the case of Japan, the 1964 Olympic Games was a political tool through sport diplomacy to enhance its international image after demilitarisation by displaying its technological and economic breakthrough that was tied to the way of every Japanese, leading to a new kind of post-war nationalism that is reliant on technology and economics.

Therefore, the 1964 Olympic Games can be characterised as a clear display of soft power that surrounded Japan at the time because of the narrative of war and peace that Japan used and then the showcase of technology. However, the Tokyo 2020 Olympics is linked with the same idea of technology and now, environmentalism; in this case, the world values environmentalism more than in the 20th century.

Section 5 volume 1 of Japan's candidature file shows that by hosting the Olympic Games, they hoped to promote a platform for the highest environmental standards. And also, to become a model of urban sustainability, zero waste and new green areas. The environmental philosophy states;

‘Beyond the sports competition itself, the Games hold significant power to communicate, and exert enormous influence in terms of environmental education and awareness. To this end, holding the Games in the heart of Tokyo, one of the world's largest and most modern cities, will be a showcase of comprehensive sustainability strategy and a prime example of how cities, humanity and environmental protection can be closely aligned’.

¹⁷ Stephanie Wilson (2019)- From Techno nationalism to Superficial Environmentalism: Japan's Olympics as a political tool

They moved forward by providing the three pillars of the Tokyo 2020 sustainable strategy which are;

Minimal impact of Games- this aims to achieve a carbon-neutral game by introducing renewable energy through public transportation and low-energy vehicles, including zero waste policy.

Green urban plan- The Tokyo 2020 Games will also be a catalyst for the greening of more urban areas, to enable the community to further enjoy a comfortable urban lifestyle in harmony with the natural environment. As well as being designed and built sustainably concerning energy, materials, and water conservation, Tokyo 2020 precincts and venues, particularly in the Tokyo Bay Zone, will incorporate significant green areas and green corridors connecting venues and the centre of Tokyo will be established with special consideration towards biodiversity.

Sustainability through The Tokyo 2020 Games will raise environmental awareness and encourage action, with sport as a driving force. A favourable environment is an essential element in achieving outstanding performance. At the same time, the joy and pleasure from sport, and the influence of role models and “proof by good example”, has the power to drive people to undertake concrete action. Therefore, progressing sustainability through sport will also be a pillar and a powerful and important principle for the Tokyo 2020 Games. Various approaches including education, participation and collaboration will be promoted.

The global consciousness of climate change and the recognition of sustainability has increased. In the case of the Tokyo Olympic Games, this research finds that Japan has adopted the idea

of environmentalism. Japan's consciousness towards climate change and environmental awareness are essential to gain a bonus to its image as a host country. However, Japan's consciousness of climate change may be superficial, for example, Japan's population accounts for just 1.64% of the world's population but emits carbon of about 4% of the global total, the fifth largest in 2016 according to the International Energy Agency. Therefore, Japan's commitment to environmentalism within the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games may not be perceived as genuine. However, the notion of environmentalism and its importance to Japan's image using the Tokyo Games remains to be seen. For a country to be seen as attractive, the country involved must adopt an attractive idea that is accepted generally by the global audience, and Japan is no different. However, just like techno nationalism and the 1964 Olympic Games, environmentalism has been used by the Japanese government with the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool to gain soft power and to become a role model on the global stage. Therefore, it is important to see how the idea of Technology, environmentalism, and sustainability impact Japan's use of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool.

4.9.3 Theme H- Making use of the soft power vs hard power narrative towards an Olympic quest

This study finds that Japan's foreign and national policies changed to focus more on employing soft power to interact with other countries because of the political changes that occurred there between 1964 and 2020. Through the Olympic Games, Japan has been able to establish itself both domestically and internationally, particularly in soft power domains. The Olympics present a desirable chance for the post-war nation to demonstrate its soft power and win back the trust of other nations as a peaceful nation. The findings also show that the transformation of Japan's security policy is a significant achievement for Abe's administration, including several bills passed in 2015 that included the re-interpretation of the Japanese constitution. This strategy has been criticised by many in the region with hostile desires to rewrite the country's

post-war constitutions. For example, the findings show that Abe has been criticised for visiting the controversial Yasukuni Shrine, igniting criticism and condemnation among neighbouring countries. China and the Koreas regard the Yasukuni Shrine as a symbol of Japan's imperial military past¹⁸.

CNN-by Ed Payne and Yoko Wakatsuki (28, 2013) Japanese Prime Minister Abe visits controversial Yasukuni war shrine. A 30-minute visit by Prime Minister Shinzo Abe to a controversial shrine that includes the names of convicted war criminals ignited a predictable firestorm of criticism and condemnation Thursday from Japan's neighbours.

The Yasukuni Shrine is regarded by China, North Korea and South Korea as a symbol of Japan's imperial military past. All three countries suffered under Japan's military aggression in World War II. Millions of Chinese civilians and soldiers, and hundreds of thousands of Koreans, died.

So, each time a top Japanese official has visited, the countries have protested -- saying the visits honour war criminals and deny Japan's atrocities in Asia.

Also, the dispute between the sovereignty of islands in the East China Sea is called the Senkakus in Japan and China; the divorce has always threatened the relationship between both countries. This unhealthy diplomatic relation also extends to South Korea with the dispute in which trade and military intelligence deals were scrapped between both countries, and the legacy of World War 2 partly inspires this dispute. Abe's strategy for Japan comes with mixed reactions from both the national and international community.

¹⁸ CNN-by Ed Payne and Yoko Wakatsuki (28, 2013) Japanese Prime Minister Abe visits controversial Yasukuni war shrine.

Abe's ambition is to bring Japan out of deflation, strengthen its military, and move to counter China's growing influence. For example, Green, the senior vice president of Asia and Japan Chair at the Centre for Strategic and International Studies, met with Abe to show him the result of the latest CSIS survey of foreign policy leaders in Asia. The findings show the greatest threat to peace in Asia, with Japan at the bottom. North Korea was seen as the greatest threat, followed by China, India, Russia, the U.S. and then Japan. Green discussed that;

‘Abe looked at that, and then he turned to me and said in Japanese, Hmm, That's a little disappointing. Explaining further ‘and this was not that he wanted Japan to be scary, but he wanted Japan to be respected’ (Drew, 2020).

Abe's strategy for Japan came with a mixture of soft power and hard power resources, from remilitarisation to playing a significant role in Tokyo becoming the 2020 Olympic Host. The effectiveness of both concepts is determined by how they are used in foreign policy. The application of hard and soft power includes several instruments of different degrees of coercion and persuasion. For Japan and Abe's administration, the mixture of foreign policy aid, the remilitarisation and re-interpretation of Japan's constitution in Article 9 and the Hosting of the Olympic Games are all instruments of hard and soft power resources. However, the effectiveness of this strategy on Japan's image, making it a major player in international politics, remains to be seen. Heywood (2011, Figure 9.1) notes that the availability of power resources determines how well hard and soft power strategies work (Heywood, 2011). Rich nations, such as the United States and Russia, can maintain sizable armed forces and exert economic pressure on other states. Soft power is used because it is economically challenging for developing or tiny states to use hard electricity. The use of soft power resources is independent of a nation's size (Nye, 2004, pp. 111-112; Leonard, 2002, p. 53). In the case of Japan, the third-largest economy in the world with 6.02% of the share world GDP has the resources to exercise its soft power and hard power effectively. However, the limitation to

Japan's soft power resources was Article 9 in the constitution, which Abe has reinterpreted to remilitarise. compared to how crucial soft power assets are to China's and Japan's respective strategies. Heng (2010) notes that China's capacity for soft power is hampered by its state-led model of an authoritarian political system, while Japan's war past limits its ability to wield soft power. However, a nation's socioeconomic structure and historical heritage define how effective its soft power is. Heng (2010). In Japan's case, the 1964 Games served as a balance in Japan's history of war and imperialism while a technological giant and a peaceful nation.

However, this research finds that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games serves as a balance between Abe's vision and foreign policy strategy of militarisation and the desire to show Japan's power and Uniqueness as a first-tier country. In 2013, Abe hosted the IOC Evaluation Commission, and he pointed that;

‘Japan has its narrative that inspires many, that’s why we hope Tokyo will be chosen, the narrative is from devastation and revitalisation’. (Gamesbids, 2013)

Also on 16 November 2021, the IOC recognised Abe for leading Japan through the Tokyo 2020 bid and postponement, including his Rio 2016 Closing Ceremony Cameo as a Super Mario. The findings read that;

‘Ex-Japanese prime minister ABE Shinzo receives Olympic Order, Abe, 66, was bestowed the award by International Olympic Committee President Thomas Bach during a ceremony at the Japan Olympic Museum’.

According to the IOC president;

“Ever since that September day in Buenos Aires, you have demonstrated your unwavering commitment to the Olympic Games and the Olympic values," Bach said referring to the IOC Session on 7 September 2013 - when Tokyo was named host city of the 2020 Olympic Games. “This was evident in all your

personal engagement in overseeing and supporting the preparations for the Olympic Games Tokyo 2020. With your unfaltering belief in the power of sport, it is no exaggeration to say that you have forged a special friendship with the Olympic community." (Olympics.com, 2021)

This, however, emphasises how crucial Abe's policies in elevating Japan to the top rank are dependent on the success of Japan's Olympic Games. It is crucial to remember that the application of hard and soft power varies with time. The exercise of hard power requires less time because of the physicality of its resources. On the other hand, soft power resources take a long time before their effects can be recognised. In the exercise of hard power, military and economic coercion produces an immediate but short-duration effect, while the exercise of soft power, attraction and persuasion tends to cause a long-term effect in change. However, to gain the kind of international respect Abe thought it essential that Japan place a balance in the exercise of both resources.

4.9.4 Theme I- Utilising the nuclear energy disaster as a sport diplomacy narrative for hosting the Olympic Games

Koide Hiroaki (2020): The Fukushima Disaster and the Tokyo Olympics- Nine years after the Fukushima nuclear disaster, fundamental issues remain unresolved. In fact, the "Nuclear Emergency Situation" declared on the 11th of March 2011 has yet to be rescinded. Many domestic critics saw the Olympics as a ploy to distract from the nuclear disaster.

Before Tokyo won the bid to host the 2020 Olympic Games, Abe hosted the International Olympic Committee Evaluation Commission (EC). To Abe,

‘Japan has its narrative that inspires many, that’s why we hope Tokyo will be chosen; Prime Minister Abe said in his official address, the narrative is, ‘from devastation to revitalization.’ (Gamesbids, 2013)

This means that the disaster and Olympics will allow Japan to help the world instead of the world helping Japan will become a fresh take on how it ties in with Tokyo's bid. Secondly, Abe points that;

‘It is about the disasters we endured, the earthquake, tsunami and nuclear failure. But it is also about the revitalisation’ furthermore, it he points out that,
‘It could be a natural disaster. It could be a man-made disaster. But still, you can make a come-back. That’s the powerful message that Tokyo 2020 can send to the whole world’. (Gamesbids, 2013)

It appears that Abe draws the bridge signifying empathy, bravery, and composure. Fundamental problems remain unresolved following the Fukushima nuclear accident, despite the declaration of a "Nuclear Emergency Situation" in March 2011 that has not yet been reversed. Japan's nuclear power growth has been guided by national policy. In terms of the Fukushima nuclear disaster, for a show of strength in sports diplomacy, after the IOC reviewed the environment theme of the bid document, the director of Japan's Bureau of Environment presented to the EC that;

‘We anticipated such concerns, in the overall session we addressed this. It wasn't that the IOC was concerned’.

During the session, the IOC team was served tap water instead of bottled water to prove that it was safe to drink. The director pointed out that,

“I talked about the tap water, that’s why we offered the tap water to the IOC evaluation commission.”

His demonstration from Japan's Olympic Committee and Abe points to a display of strong sports diplomatic strategy. From research, this sport diplomacy effort landed Japan the opportunity to host the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games. Furthermore, the government has created regulations like the Electric Business Act and the Act on Compensation for Nuclear Damage

to encourage the production of nuclear power and to allow power firms to enter the industry. This act encouraged the flocks of large corporations eager to participate in profit with the inclusion of a vast sum of money. In addition, the expended publicity and media advertisements spread the story of safe nuclear power (Hiroaki, 2020).

Furthermore, in a state-centric education where the Japanese government plays a dominant role that includes the setting of school curricula and textbook selections. The government has ensured that the dream of nuclear power is instilled in the children and future generations (Hiroaki, 2020). Despite the widely held belief that Japan is home to a safe nuclear power plant, the country makes up only 0.3% of the planet's landmass. It is also located in an area where four major tectonic plates collide, which is also the epicentre of 20% of global earthquakes and 7% of global volcanoes. However, the construction of a nuclear power plant and the narrative of a safe nuclear power plant on an unstable landmass is ironic and dangerous. Although, these nuclear plants are not located in cities but in less populated areas. In March 2011, a vast earthquake resulting in a tsunami assaulted the Electric Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Station which triggered the Fukushima nuclear disaster¹⁹.

BBC (the 6th of August 2020) Hiroshima bomb: Japan marks 75 years since nuclear attack; on the 6th of August 1945, U.S. bomber dropped the uranium bomb above the city, killing around 140,000 people. Three days later a second nuclear weapon was dropped on Nagasaki. Two weeks later Japan surrendered, ending World War 2.

More than 200,000 people lost their lives at Hiroshima and Nagasaki because of the atomic bombs dropped on Japan during World War II. Regarding the Fukushima accident, the

¹⁹ Koide Hiroaki (2020): The Fukushima Disaster and the Tokyo Olympics- Nine years after the Fukushima nuclear disaster, fundamental issues remain unresolved. In fact, the "Nuclear Emergency Situation" declared on 11 March 2011 has yet to be rescinded. Many domestic critics saw the Olympics as a ploy to distract from the nuclear disaster.

Japanese government admitted that 168 times as many hazardous materials were released there as they were from the Hiroshima bomb. As a result, homes and lives were lost during the evacuation of nearly 100,000 people from a highly contaminated area that spanned 1,150 square kilometres. Based on the results, the question still stands: Should these games be held in Japan, a nation still dealing with the fallout from a nuclear accident? Japan has experienced a significant amount of nuclear devastation than any other nation from the period of 1945 to 2011²⁰.

The New York Times- Boy Born on Day A-Bomb Fell Chosen to Light Olympic Flame; A young athlete born within sight of the atomic blast that devastated Hiroshima was chosen this week to light the flame that will burn throughout the Tokyo Olympics.

NBC News the 13th of January 2020- Can Japan's recovery Olympics Heal Fukushima's nuclear scars? huge tsunami slammed through the walls of Fukushima's power plant. Three nuclear reactors melted down, spewing radioactive particles into the air.

Hiroshima and Nagasaki became icons of Japanese suffering in the 1950s and 1960s which fuelled a robust anti-nuclear movement. The bombing presence was felt during the 1964 Games as a student born on the day America's bomb fell on Hiroshima, Yoshinori Sakai, lit the Olympic flame²¹. Japan's remembrance of the bombing established the tone of these Games as one of resilience and national strength. This account emphasises the point, especially to America, the Image of Japan as an innocent victim in the war. Despite Japan's expansionist

²⁰ BBC (6 August 2020) Hiroshima bomb: Japan marks 75 years since nuclear attack; on 6 August 1945, US bomber dropped the uranium bomb above the city killing around 140,000 people. Three days later a second nuclear weapon was dropped on Nagasaki. Two weeks later Japan surrendered, ending World War 2.

²¹ The New York Times- Boy Born on Day A-Bomb Fell Chosen to Light Olympic Flame; A young athlete born within sight of the atomic blast that devastated Hiroshima was chosen this week to light the flame that will burn throughout the Tokyo Olympics.

image and foreign policy and its empire from 1868 to 1974, Japan used its experience of nuclear destruction to contribute to its national image and soft power at the Olympics in 1964. Japan has a complicated relationship with nuclear power development, including the influence of America and Japan's adoption of nuclear energy. On the 11th of March 2011, Japan became a victim of a nuclear disaster.

The Fukushima nuclear power plant disaster discredited the notion that Japan's adoption of nuclear energy was not sustainable. Similarly, the 2020 Fukushima nuclear accident served as a symbol for the bid to host the Tokyo Olympics, and the torch relay was scheduled to start in Fukushima. Simons et al. (2020) note that Fukushima will assist in launching the Tokyo 2020 Summer Olympics by establishing a ceremony touch relay next to its catastrophic power station, as the Games came to be associated with the nuclear accident²². According to the director-general of disarmament, non-proliferation, and science for Japan's Foreign Ministry, 'The Olympic torch will pass through Fukushima, and there will be Olympic events in Fukushima' (Simmons, et al., 2020) Hosting the Olympic Games is a symbol of rebirth and a planned revitalisation for the region. Prime Minister Abe in Buenos Aires, where Tokyo won the bid to host the Olympic Games, stated that he wants to be very clear that there have never been, are not currently, and will never be any health issues of any kind. And that the government has already chosen, and we have begun a programme to ensure that there are no issues at all (Lies, 2013).

Tokyo pledged nearly half a billion dollars to clean up the nuclear plants, with critics saying that it was aimed at winning the Olympic vote. Fukushima will host baseball and softball matches at the 2020 Tokyo Olympics, with organisers, hoping that the games will boost the

²² NBC News January 13, 2020- Can Japan's recovery Olympics Heal Fukushima's nuclear scars? huge tsunami slammed through the walls of Fukushima's power plant. Three nuclear reactors melted down, spewing radioactive particles into the air.

recovery effort from the region. The Azuma baseball stadium is about 70km northwest of the ruined Fukushima Daiichi power plant. In addition, will host the opening match of the baseball and softball fixtures. According to Yoshiro Mori, the Tokyo 2020 organising committee president, ‘By hosting the Olympic baseball and softball events, Fukushima will have a great platform to show the world the extent of its recovery in the ten years since the disaster’ (McCurry, 2017) The IOC has initially declined the proposal to host the Games at the Azuma baseball stadium in Fukushima. Still, the Japanese Baseball softball president welcomed the change of heart by the IOC. Stating that ‘it is a great step’ that would ‘inspire hope and highlight the regeneration in Fukushima’ (McCurry, 2017). However, the narrative of a recovery Games, especially for Fukushima, highlights similarities from the 1964 Olympic Games, showing Japan’s’ ability to use its difficulties as a resource for soft power through sport diplomacy. In other words, the Japanese government can channel its nuclear disaster and its war history as a valuable tool to establish itself as a peaceful and developed nation. However, it is important to discuss this narrative in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, evaluating if it was an effective soft power strategy in using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool.

4.10. Theme J- The inclusion of the ‘rising sun flag (hinomaru): Japan’s legacy of imperialism; and point of concentration and controversy at both the games.

The Rising Sun flag made an official national flag in 1999 has strong ties to Japan’s imperial past. The flag was redesigned in 1964 to reinvent it as a symbol of democracy and internationalism. The flag will be used in the 2020 Olympic Games, and despite Japan’s view of the flag as a symbol of peace, the imperial connotations have not diminished. In September 2019, South Korea requested the flag be banned at the Tokyo 2020 Olympics, but Japan refused. The request not to use the flag comes from Japan’s war crimes including the use of girls and women from South Korea as comfort women by the Japanese soldiers during World

War 2. The use of the flag has resulted in painful memories of the past and therefore has the potential to politicise the Games in terms of Asian geopolitics.

However, fans cheering and waving their flags in stadiums is common in international sports events. In the case of Japan, waving its flag in international sports events like the Olympic Games has become offensive to its Asian neighbour, predominantly South Korea. Critics depict those fans using the flag to rewrite the history of human rights abuses by Japanese forces. Politicians from South Korea often compare the rising sun flag to the Nazi swastika. However, in the case of Tokyo 2020, South Korea wants the flag banned, with Japanese officials saying that the flag is widely used in Japan and not a political statement.

When Japan invaded Korea and a portion of China in the 19th century as part of its colonial expansion, the rising sun flag was adopted for military use (Stephan, 2001; Orita, 2020). The Navy adopted the flag during World War II, and that is where most of the controversy sprang from. During the war, Japanese forces seized most of Asia and committed crimes against the native populace (Finn & Finn, 1992). The flag is still of the Japanese Navy, even though it is flown slightly differently for normal military use. During their reign of economic exploitation, the Japanese colony coerced hundreds of thousands of Koreans into labour as they expanded into other sections of China (Duus & Peattie, 2021). The Japanese soldiers coerced women and girls from the Philippines, China, and Korea into sexual slavery. Seeing the Japanese flag fly is a symbol of Japan's refusal to confront its past, as many South Koreans identify it with a lengthy history of tyranny and war crimes (Huff, 2020). The argument by most South Koreans is that the flag shows Japan's inability to accept responsibility for its colonial transgressions. The South Korean foreign minister describes the flag as a symbol of Japanese 'imperialism and militarism' (Illmer, 2020). The chairman of the parliamentary committee for sport, An Minsuk, said that the flag is 'akin to a symbol of the devil to Asians and Koreans, just like the swastika is a symbol of Nazis that reminds Europeans of invasion of horror (Illmer, 2020).

According to this analysis, the continuous trade conflict between the two nations is the root reason for the flag controversy. A major trade dispute developed out of a diplomatic debate about labour and pay during World War II. The rising sun flag is a cultural symbol in Japan. Throughout Japan, many items with designs are used, including flags of Japanese Maritime Self-Defence Force vessels, joyful flags for birthing, "good catch" banners used by fishermen, and seasonal festivities. However, under Prime Minister Abe, his ambition to improve Japan's status as a first-tier country appears to be allowing extreme nationalism to go on. Japan's inability to deal properly with its brutal imperial past also comes because of the significant role the U.S. has played in securing Japan as an ally during the Cold War. Hence, the Japanese government did not have to resort to reparations and redress that would appropriately deal with its past, says Harrison Kim, assistant professor in history at the University of Hawaii (Illmer, 2020). Japan has not effectively implemented a permanent way of memorialising and apologising for its imperial crimes in law, education, and culture. According to the BBC article,

BBC News the 10th of August 2010- Japan apologises to South Korea for its imperialist past-Japan has offered another apology to South Korea for its wartime colonisation of the Korean peninsula. It also promised to return cultural relics in the near future, including records taken by Japan of an ancient Korean royal dynasty.

BBC News the 19th of September 2020- Yasukuni Shrine: Japan's ex-PM Abe visits controversial memorial. Mr Abe posted a picture of himself at the Yasukuni Shrine, telling his followers he had gone there to inform the spirits of his resignation.

However, in 2010, the former prime minister of Japan, Kan, expressed his sincere regret and apologised for the harm and suffering brought about by Japan's colonial reign. "By the colonial rule that was against their desire," he stated, the people of Korea were deprived of their nation

and culture, and their ethnic pride was deeply hurt²³. He hoped to improve the relationship with Korea that has often been overshadowed by the country's shared history. The findings have shown that under Prime Minister Abe, his actions appear to have been the opposite. The findings show that in 2020, just days after stepping down as Prime Minister for health reasons, Abe visited the controversial war memorial called the Yasukuni Shrine. In the past, visits by Japanese leaders have been seen as a lack of remorse for its militaristic past. This is not a surprise from a leader seeking to revise Japan's pacifist post-war constitution to legitimise the military formally²⁴. However, an issue for discussion is how this narrative affects Japan's soft power, especially on a regional level. If Japan seeks to become a top-tier country in Asia above China, peace and reconciliation with its neighbours is an important part of gaining soft power. It is important to evaluate the importance of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool in addressing this issue.

²³ BBC News 10 August 2010- Japan apologises to South Korea for imperialist past-Japan has offered another apology to South Korea for its war-time colonialization of the Korean peninsula. It also promised to return cultural relics in the near future, including records taken by the Japan of an ancient Korean royal dynasty.

²⁴ BBC News 19 September 2020- Yasukuni Shrine: Japan's ex-PM Abe visits controversial memorial. Mr Abe posted a picture of himself at the Yasukuni Shrine, telling his followers he had gone there to inform the spirits of his resignation.

Chapter 5

PART 2

DATA ANALYSIS: VOICES FROM THE FIELD

5.1 Introduction

This study investigated the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power. The investigation process for this study includes the data collected and analyses through the lens of identifying Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power. The data collected for this study took into consideration several variables such as Japan's culture, political values and foreign policy, and national and international image. The open-ended and fairly broad interview questions were drawn together from themes that emerged from the literature review, interview discussions and from the analysis derived from the document data source of the study.

Table 4

PART 2	VOICES FROM THE FIELD (SOFT POWER)
Theme A-	The impact of the Second World War on Japan's soft power, the reconstruction of identity (image building) through sport diplomacy; Tokyo 1964 and 2020 Olympic games
Theme B-	The media influence on Japan's culture and cultural export through the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games
Theme C-	The Impact of Covid-19 on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy
Theme D-	Understanding Japan's Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy through the international, regional and national levels and the impact of the media on these levels.
Theme E-	The Geopolitical Nature of East Asia, political and cultural power and its impact on Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy.

Theme F-	The Significance of an Open and Global Society through the Tokyo 2020 Olympics
Theme G	The hosting of the Rugby 2020 as a foundation for hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games
Theme H	Salvaging the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games as a soft power tool from the impact of Covid-19
Theme I	The cost of not hosting and postponement of the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games
Theme J	The Olympic Games as a fluke concept and a weak excuse
Theme K	Prime Minister Abe's motivation soft power strategy
Theme L	The Olympic Games need a fundamental reimagining.
	VOICES FROM THE FIELD (SPORT DIPLOMACY)
Theme M	Understanding Japan's sport diplomacy; Following the money
Theme N	Identifying Japan's sport diplomacy; the strategy of sports for tomorrow programme.

5.2 The soft power of the Olympic Games

Countries use sports mega events such as the Olympic Games, to improve their global image, international standings in soft power indices and relationships with other countries (Guilluanti, 2004). Guilluanti, R. (2004) argues that mega sports events are used by countries to improve their global image. While arguing that these events provide a platform for countries to display their culture, values and achievements to the foreign public. This also includes the promotion of tourism, trade and investment. Therefore, the literature review discusses how the Olympic Games influence the destination image of a host country in comparison, countries such as

England, Russia, Greece, and Brazil have leveraged the Olympic Games as a soft power vehicle. For instance, (Hahm, et al., 2018) used a quasi-experimental design on an internet platform and triangulated the aforementioned countries' images of their countries, destinations, and Olympic Games. Russia received the lowest scores for both country and destination images, while Brazil and Greece had the strongest images of their destinations. England had the strongest country image overall. However, these results are impacted by factors such as culture, identity, political image, foreign policy and the already existing global views of the host country. Historically, from a political context, the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games and the Berlin 1930 Olympic Games are perfect examples of how nations leverage sports mega-events for political achievement and to rebuild an already dented reputation. The discussion of findings and analysis for this chapter comes from the discussions of interviews gathered from experts with many years of experience in matters of sports diplomacy, the Olympic Games, and the study of Japan's society.

5.3 Theme A- The impact of the Second World War on Japan's soft power, the reconstruction of identity (image building) through sport diplomacy; Tokyo 1964 and 2020 Olympic games

Historically, the literature review discussed the legacy of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games on Japan, especially from a post-war era. The 1964 Olympic Games helped reintroduce Japan as a peaceful country. Masumoto (2012) Discussed the Olympic education in Japan during the Olympic Games as an appropriate event for post-war Japan to revive and to declare a new Japan as a peaceful and loving country to the world. Examining the East Asian Olympic Games, the Tokyo 1964, Seoul 1988, and Beijing 2008 games serve as both a coming-out party and a symbol of the Olympic Games' legitimization. Moreover, it promotes the universalism of the Olympic movement worldwide. Collins (2011) notes that the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games, known as the East Asian Olympic Games, served as a template for subsequent Asian Olympic

aspirants. Japan has always been a model of modernisation for the Asian region as the first nation to resist Western colonisation and the hosting of the 1964 Olympic Games that became a coming-out party for post-war Japan to universalise the Olympics and to induce the theme of harmony to model Japan as a Peaceful rising country (Collins, 2011). The 1964 Olympic Games were an effective tool for Japan's soft power, as discussed in the literature review. However, this section discusses Japan's ability to harness the human value of culture and identity in the 2020 Olympic Games and how it translates into using the Games as a soft power tool.

In my interview about soft power with WY, whose research focuses on physical education and sports, pointed out that

‘Japan has a unique way of looking at the way it presents itself and I think their current approach to the world is informed by the tragic involvement in the Second World War and how they ended is very tragic and in a very humbling manner. After the end of the war. Japan, decided to follow a unique path to reconstruct their identity and to rebuild themselves as a global power but in a unique way’.

My discussion with WY reveals that Japan can harness its inner strength from a defeat in the Second World War and channelling that strength into sports to reconstruct its identity. A reconstruction of Japan's identity using the 1964 Olympic Games is in itself a soft power strategy that was successful at the time. The discussion with WY sets an already discussed historical foundation of what scholars have discussed in the literature review about the legacy of the 1964 Olympic Games. WY points out that the greatest resource for Japan is the ability to use effective human resources, with the greatest resource for Japan being the people, and this relates to the people's culture, the Japanese culture.

‘Because on like the US, they don’t have a huge geographical mass and they don’t have huge Natural resources. I think their greatest resource is the Human resource, their greatest resource is the people and when you talk about the people, the distinctive feature of a people is their culture. And that is why when you look at the accomplishment of Japan, it has to do with the people.

This reveals that the capacity of Japan to make effective use of its human resources, which includes the Japanese people and Japanese culture, is a soft power strength that Japan possesses. Culture includes the impact of family, education, religion, the social life and system of the people, and the choices they make. For example, technology diplomacy or the use of technology in the 1964 Olympic Games is a symbol of Japan’s effective use of its human resources and display of its culture and identity. (Abel, 2012) Discussed Japan’s sporting diplomacy and pointed out that in terms of both the physical infrastructure of Tokyo and the attitudes of the Japanese people, like new roads, trains, and satellites to facilitate the live broadcasting of the Games, all contributed to making Japan more internationally attractive.

From research, academic literature points to the fact that the Cool Japan initiative is a soft power policy for improving Japan’s global image and influence. (Daliot-bul, 2009) discussed that Cool Japan, as a government-owned brand, is designed to create new cultural imagery for Japan and is primarily a national strategy to promote Japan's industrial policies and cultural diplomacy. He points out that the cool Japan strategy is advised as a mechanism to mobilize the nation in unsettled times. The Cool Japan policy is an example of Japan's ability to harness its human resources effectively, including technology, anime, manga, Japanese fashion, cuisine etc. However, this narrative overlaps with the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid. From part one of the document analysis, the findings explore Prime Minister Abe’s soft (smart) power strategy during the Olympic bid; he dressed as a Super Mario, symbolising the narrative of cool Japan and Japan as a cultural country. Abe’s action is an example of how sports become a

platform for Japan's soft power. My interview with WY discussed how people and culture translate into the key role sport play in amplifying national identity and culture.

‘And when you talk about people and culture, then sport plays a key role because sport gives people a sense of identity. The accomplishment in sport have a way of binding communities together, they have ways of binding fans together, they have ways of binding a nation together. And success at the international level instils a sense of pride that is unique, a sense of pride that does not come from any other source’.

WY discussion fits well with (Aizawa, et al., 2018) views on the long-term impact of the Tokyo 1964 Olympic Games on sports participation. Their research highlights that while participation in sports has decreased with age, the sports participation rate in Japan has increased. Investigating whether the shared experience of hosting the 1964 Olympic Games played a part in the increase in sports participation. Furthermore, they suggest that individuals who experienced the 1964 Olympic Games in their youth participated in sports more frequently than other generations. This means that from my interview, WY's discussion on the role of sports in giving a sense of identity to people and creating a binding nation was a narrative that was effective in hosting the Olympic Games. The sense of nation-building and strong identity in the context of Japan can be classified as a national or internal soft power strategy from the Japanese government. Simply, after Japan's defeat in the Second World War, the 1964 Olympic Games played a huge role in uplifting the Japanese people. However, in the context of the 2021 Tokyo Olympics, national identity, resilience and the narrative of harnessing Japan's human resources are important factors in Japan's soft power strategy.

Japan has been successful in using sports as a soft power tool. My discussion with WY agrees with the fact that the 1964 Olympic Games, the 2002 FIFA World Cup and the 2019 Rugby World Cup have all been a success. WY points out that,

‘But where they have been more successful is in hosting, from the 1964 Olympic Games and in the recent past organising the Winter Olympics, the World Rugby World Cup and

hosting the 2020 Olympic Games and the co-hosting of the 2002 World Cup. In the 21st it has been a key pillar in enhancing their brand as a society that is heavily invested in the people, that is harnessing their culture in terms of identifying themselves and promoting themselves across the globe’.

In addition, (Abel, 2012) points out that Japan's 1964 Olympic Games was a successful sport diplomacy and diplomatic strategy. It is important to emphasise that the above-mentioned sports events have been a useful tool in harnessing the Japanese brand, its cultures, and identities and strengthening its sense of national pride. Therefore, it is significant to discuss the questions asked about the legacy of the 2020 Olympic Games in the context of soft power or nation branding. It is clear to see what the 1964 Olympic Games stood for rebuilding, reconstructing, portraying Japan as a peaceful country, perfect sports diplomacy, and diplomatic and soft power strategy. But due to stringent laws and a pandemic epidemic, the 2020 Olympic Games became the first to be postponed without the participation of spectators from both abroad and at home. This adds to the question if the 2020 Olympic Games is an effective tool for Japan’s soft power. Secondly, Japan used the 1964 Olympic Games to reposition its image in the global community for World War II. This was done by turning itself into a technological powerhouse and the satellite broadcasting of the first Olympic Games in 1964.

In addition, the unsuccessful 2013 Olympic bids emphasised the restoration and recuperation from the Fukushima nuclear accident and the 2011 tsunami. The 2020 Olympics somehow has managed to align with Japan’s ability to show strength to recover from difficult times, especially with the emergence of the Coronavirus and the pandemic. These issues from the pandemic have made this research more vital to discuss the impact of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games on Japan's soft power. However, as a regular host of huge sports events, Japan has demonstrated the ability to successfully host these events and harness the human resources, which is the culture and identity of the Japanese people. However, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic

Games came with a different challenge because the Games were organised behind closed doors with no fans and foreign visitors. In this case, harnessing human resources to their full potential through the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games comes from a different dimension from previous Games.

As a branding tool for Japan, it is crucial to emphasise the significance of successfully hosting the Olympic Games in 2020. Perhaps, this will help identify if a successful Game equals soft power. Although the literature points out that successful games may not equal soft power or positive image branding, for example, in the case of the 2016 Olympic Games in Brazil, political corruption and bad environmental hygiene became an issue. In the case of Russia, the global non-acceptance of its political ideologies on human rights and societal behaviour is non-conforming to the international standard of liberal democracy.

5.3.1 Theme B-The media influence on Japan's culture and cultural export through the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

This theme discusses the role of media representation in Japan's image during the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. It is also important to discuss to what extent the media has helped salvage Japan's 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The findings reveal that soft power is an identified effective strategy for Japan, especially in a place where entertainment and culture can do so much in giving the global community a realistic feel of the Japanese culture. In the context of the Olympic Games, the media plays a massive role in the image branding of the host country. Building and maintaining a country's image helps the nation gain more advantages in a global economy and political competition. The positive image of a country can use the foreign policy of other countries in favour of the country in question. However, this means increased foreign investment, tourism, trade and effective multilateral or bilateral relationships with other countries. Lee & Hong (2012) examine the influence of international public relations on a target country's news coverage and the public perception towards other

countries. They point out that in the case of the U.S., news coverage the public relations impact directly and significantly on the U.S. public perception of the countries covered. Secondly, the more favourable and frequently the U.S. news media covered foreign countries, the more significant and favourable the U.S. public perceived and felt towards those countries. In the context of Japan and the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, the presence of the media has helped to improve the positive relationship and public feeling toward Japan.

In the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, from my discussion with AB, the concentration of the media in the Olympic Games plays a vital role in making the Games an effective soft power strategy. An event as broad as the Olympic Games greatly influences public perception of Japan's image and culture. For example, Japanese movies and cultural exports give a glimpse of Japan's culture, but the Olympic Games allow experience Japanese culture effectively with the chance to travel as a tourist or sports fan with foreign visitors from different countries at the same time. AB points out that,

‘Soft power can be an effective strategy for Japan to some degree. Yes, for instance, in American culture, a lot of people are watching a Japanese movie called drive my car that is nominated for an Oscar. That is a little glimpse into Japanese culture, but something as broad as the Olympics still can do a hundredfold in terms of giving people a sense of what is going on in Japanese culture to some degree. So I think it can be effective there’.

(Berkowitz, et al., 2007) Points that the 2008 Olympic Games became an opportunity for China to improve its global image. By introducing the concept of national branding, they analysed that the Olympic Games was a marketing tool for China to increase its global equity. Similarly, (Bodet & Lacassagne, 2012) examined the British perception of the 2008 Beijing Olympics based on a social representation theory research strategy carried out among British citizens. (Berkowitz, et al., 2007) Points that there were transferable elements from the sporting events to the place, few positive elements were transferred, and several negative associations remain. In other words, the value of sporting events in place branding strategies is

definite, but the limitations to this are the transferable negative elements and lack of media control. While sporting events can positively brand a country's image, the already present negative image and the uncontrolled presence of the media helped amplify this negative perception. For example, outside the sporting world, China has been accused of human rights violations and restrictions on the freedom of speech. However, this image of China does not conform to the view of the liberal democratic model.

Similarly, in the case of Japan, the 1964 Olympic Games have been described by scholars as successful and Japan's lens of the global arena has been perceived as democratic and peaceful. This can be identified in Article 9 of Japan's constitution, where Japan adopts a pacifist constitution. This constitutional change perhaps distinguishes Japan from its Asian counterparts, for example, China. However, in the context of the Olympic Games, the media perception will be consistently favourable in branding Japan's image, as seen in the 1964 Olympic Games. However, the pandemic is a limitation to the effective use of the 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. But the presence of the media during the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games as close games cannot be ignored. The uncontrolled presence of the media may have become a tool to use the Games as a soft power strategy effectively. However, because of the pandemic and the nature of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

5.3.2 Theme C-The Impact of Covid-19 on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy

In using the Games as a soft power tool, the 2020 Tokyo Games comes with a different challenge not seen in history. The interview with AB points to the difficulty in using the Games as a soft power tool because of the pandemic. The pandemic came as an unexpected and unforeseen challenge to the organisation of the Games. AB discussed that in 2020, the position of Japan in hosting the Olympics was different from the 1964 Games.

‘I think the positioning of Japan in 2020 is so different from 1964, but I think it functions differently. 64 was about World War two recovery, I think in 2020, particularly with Covid-19, the aims are probably different from what the objectives ended up being’.

The Covid-19 pandemic has led to questions about the successful use of the 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, which remains an issue for discussion. Similarly, JG, a widely published author on sports politics and policy, points out that Covid-19 changed the perception and organisation of the Games, especially looking at what Japan was hoping to achieve if the Games were to be normal.

‘Obviously, things have changed because of Covid-19. I think the question will have to change a little bit because you will have to ask whether Japan can still achieve what it set out to do initially. Because one of the key things is that there are no foreign visitors apart from the athletes, there are no crowds, and that is going to be an issue for their soft power strategy. As we may know, the key things, the multiplies for tourists going to country of Japan and then going back and forth, has a long-term knockoff effect’.

From the discussion with JG, it was made clear that the relationship between sport and tourism has developed faster over the past 20 years than in any other decade. This relationship has grown into a global norm with increased tourism during sports events, which has massively contributed to the host country's economy. Parker (2019) discussed that because of the influence of globalisation in emerging markets, sponsorship spending in the Asia-Pacific region was the fastest growing of any region in 2016 at 5.7%. Like the sports industry, Asia and the Pacific recorded an 8% led growth in international tourist arrivals in 2016 (Parker, 2019). The growth may have been because of the 2008 Beijing Olympic Games leading up to the Pyeongchang Winter Olympic Games and the 2019 Rugby World Cup the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games in Japan.

The increase in tourism through sports events can vary in size, and in the context of the Olympics, the Olympic Games is a mega sports event which attracts a significantly large

number of tourists. In examining the increase in tourism through sports events, In the context of a major sporting event, Zouni et al. (2020) investigate the relationship between the destination image, event image, and satisfaction. Following an assessment of how the destination affects the degree of satisfaction and the intention to return, an assessment is made of how the event affects these factors and how the degree of satisfaction affects the intention to return. The outcome suggests that there is a strong correlation between the degree of satisfaction and the assessment of the event and destination. It is discovered that the intention to return to the location is significantly influenced by the three variables—event image, contentment, and destination image. In the case of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, it is clear to say that given the successes of the 1964 Olympic Games. Including factors such as the attractive Japanese culture, Japan is a good destination area for tourists to visit, more so because the Olympic Games is an attractive global sports event for athletes, tourists, and sports fans and Tokyo is an attractive cultural city. From JG's interview, it is clear to see the concerns of whether Japan can still achieve what it has set out to achieve, especially in the context of soft power because of the absence of fans because of Covid-19.

JG points out that it is important to examine if Japan can still set out to achieve what it wants through the Games. AB points out that there is still an element of soft power in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games because Japan can boast that amid the pandemic, they were able to host the Olympic Games.

‘In many ways, a lot of the goals of promoting Japanese culture and Tokyo went away, so, I think you certainly have some losses for that. The silver lining for that though, is that one of the messages that at least Western media seems to advance was that Tokyo was able to host successful a major Olympic Games in the midst of a pandemic and do so safely. That congruence after the nuclear meltdown is beneficial to the understanding of Japanese culture because you hear about tourist hesitancy and the hesitancy of Japan because of nuclear power, because of the tsunami. So the ability to

say yes, we were able to safely and effectively host this summer games helps booster that notion there.'

AB's point gives contrasting views on the Olympic Games as a soft power tool; the first is that the goal of promoting the Japanese culture and Tokyo went away. As discussed earlier, this was because of the pandemic and a lot of the goals to promote Japan's culture, and Tokyo were lost. Then, the purpose of using the Olympic Games as a soft power tool was defeated or unsuccessful. However, there is a possibility that the Olympic Games as a soft power tool did not entirely achieve its purpose. Secondly, suppose the Western media viewed the Games as successful after hosting through a difficult time like the pandemic. In that case, the idea of using the Olympic Games as a soft power tool may be relevant.

5.3.3 Theme D- Understanding Japan's Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy through the international, regional and national levels and the impact of the media on these levels

From my interviews, this theme reveals a key issue for analysis, the impact of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool on a national regional and international level. From my interview with JG on understanding Japan's soft power strategy using the Olympic Games, he points out that it is important to investigate the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as an instrument of soft power on the international, regional, and national levels. This is one way of investigating the Games as a soft power tool for Japan. According to JG,

'One way I am looking at it, and it is something I have been thinking about Solomon, is on three different levels. The international level, regional level and national level' (JG).

- a. 'One is on the international level- the international will be the soft power you might have what's impact globally.'
- b. 'The other will be regional- because your case study is a very specific one because it's very regional because regional politics play very strongly in Asia, so you got Japan, China and South Korea all hosting mega-events and competing for mega-

events. Because as Brazil in South America, you know is a regional level and then you got the ‘....

- c. ‘National level-, which originally, I think the idea with the Games, was in part for soft domestic power, so Japan is very, you will obviously say not very multicultural. I visited last year up until the year before, and there were not many different people there. Hardly will you ever find a black person there. No black people, they did not speak or hear many different languages apart from Japanese, so they are very monoculture, I think they were trying to use these Games to change that, and the way you do that is by getting people to come to the country. So, that’s one thing they are not going to be able to do. So if you assess how effective is soft power strategy. Because of Covid-19, I think it is going to be a lot less effective. It might be because people can’t go, but they might have a much bigger audience which is a good thing. They might have more people watching the games because they can’t go’.

Also, WY points out that technology played an important role in the successful hosting of the Games. To WY, the Games were successful because of the strong partnership Japan had with sponsors.

‘You know 2020/2021 and 2022 to some extent have been very tough years for people but especially for politicians, for the government and Japan is no exception. Leading to the Games right from the closing ceremony in Rio in Brazil, I think there was excitement going into Japan for 2020 and of course, everything was lining up from 2016 Rio. To the Rugby World Cup, it was like Japan was on the right, the trajectory was upward and then Covid-19 hit in late 2019 and in 2020 so the Games had to be moved. I think that caused a lot of doubt and frustration, and all the projections in terms of the monetary benefits had to be thrown out of the window. Especially when they made the decision to host the Games without fans, without an international audience that was a bold decision. But if there is anything that I have learnt in the last two years, I have learned that technology has taken over, Covid-19 enhanced the utilisation of technology and Japan to me was best placed to handle these games within the Covid-19 hit environment. They set a precedent for China in the 2022 Winter Olympics we just witnessed. Because the Japanese were more innovative and were able to ride it out’.

The interview with WY was almost like a reflection of what Japan could have achieved if the pandemic had not happened. Similarly, to AB, WY states that a lot had to be thrown away amid the emergence of the pandemic. However, a key point from my interview with WY is the vital role of technology during the Games. JG points out that the 2020 Olympic Games may have an enormous global audience who watched the Games from their TV because of the restrictions from the pandemic. In addition, in the earlier discussion, AB points to the advantages of the media representation of Japan's culture through the Olympic Games. However, it appears that technology has been a useful tool in Japan's soft power. In the case of the 2020 Olympics, the media is an aspect of technology that needs to be discussed. For example, it is important to discuss the number of global audiences tuned in to watch the Olympic Games. Understanding the statistics will help measure if the Olympic Games is an effective soft power strategy, especially in reaching out to the Global audience.

Similarly, AB points to the power of the media as a key means of communication to the foreign public in accessing the Games; according to AB,

‘I think the presence of the media helps in a variety of ways including most formidably that the media is disproportionately on an aspect of social media such as Twitter as compared to the general population. So they were able to use that as a megaphone to convey that and particularly at a time when everyone was isolating at home the media's impact was more massive than normal. Even more than that though, here is what you get from the Olympics; it's not just the number of media there is that they are all reporting on something at the same time and at the same manner. You got a good three weeks where the focus was on Japan and what was going on with the Olympics there. That matters because there are other things that might be pop-culture phenomenal. But we are viewing them or discussing them at the same time.

Concerning new media, (Santomier, 2008) suggests that new media is a significant dimension of branding and global sports sponsorships. This is because it provides the capability to communicate with consumers worldwide through multiple digital platforms. In the case of the Olympics, the consumers are the foreign public; however, it is important to discuss the role of

the media in amplifying the Olympic Games as a soft power tool. Furthermore, WY, depicts that Japan's strength in hosting sports mega-events is in its investment in infrastructure, and the commercial benefits through sponsorships and partnerships, including tourism. However, in his view, he narrowed the success of the 2020 Olympic Games to Japan hosting the Games through the pandemic. However, this ignores the other factors of Japan's strength in Hosting mega sports events like the Olympics. It is important to discuss Japan's inability to utilise its core strength in full in the hosting of the Olympic Games.

5.4 Theme E- The Geopolitical Nature of East Asia, political and cultural power and its Impact on Japan's Sport Diplomacy and Soft Power Strategy.

Key problems regarding Asian geopolitics and its intersection with hosting mega-events in sports surfaced from the discussion with JG. He emphasises the significance of hosting the Olympic Games for the area while examining Japan's declining economic standing in relation to other Asian nations, such as China. Japan has one of the largest and most developed economies in the world, as well as a workforce that is hardworking and well-educated. Japan is one of the world's greatest populous consumption marketplaces due to its affluent populace. Prior to China taking over, Japan's economy was the second biggest in the world, after the US economy, from 1968 and 2010. However, Japan's economy is the second largest in Asia, trailing only China's and the United States in terms of size. JG makes the point that it's critical to talk about how local politics will affect the 2020 Olympic hosting, particularly as it relates to the local economy.

‘But I think the regional aspect is important for them because the economy is stagnated as you know, it has gone backwards and it stagnated at the moment and in the region, they want to be a major player so hosting the Olympics they hope is going to give them that status’.

First off, holding major sporting events in an area has a greater significance than just hosting the Olympic Games in Tokyo in 2020. Increasing the city or nation's profile, long-term

investment, jobs and investment, excitement, and immediate economic gains are all included in this. Tan & Lee (2021) shows that the four years between 2018 and 2022 may be a sign of the Western world's diminishing interest in the Olympics in terms of the Olympic movement. Second, Asia's ascent in the world political economy can be reflected in the geographic concentration of the event. Thirdly, unstable geopolitics surround the three Olympic Games in 2018–2020 and 2022. For example, the reconciliation of North and South Korean relations was one of the main themes at the PyeongChang 2018. Similarly, the relationship between Japan and Korea relations was all-time low during the Tokyo 2020 Olympics. Also, the diplomatic tensions between the USA and China showed no sign of being resolved (Lee & Tan, 2021). The organisation of the three Olympic Games in Asia surrounded a series of regional and diplomatic incidents. However, the issue is how this affects Japan's soft power in raising its profile, especially as a host nation for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Aside from the internationalist ideal of the Olympics, that sport brings people together and countries. The Olympics cannot be separated from the issues of nationalism and identity, international and interregional rivalry, and domestic politics (Bridges, 2020). The environment of East Asia may have accentuated the tendency that sport is political and more so more political in Asia.

Japan has been living in the shadows of China economically and politically (super-power), despite Prime Minister Abe's claim that Japan is back. Japan has continued to struggle from the lost decade of the 1990s and 2000s in reconstructing its economy and society's way of life to cope with the 21st century. The Tokyo Olympic Games may be important to Japan's regional image. The international sporting rivalry may help Japan pit against its closest geopolitical and sporting rivals, like China and South Korea. Discussing the regional importance of the Games means that Japan must show its neighbours that sports can transcend long-standing animosity.

Similarly, WY adds to Japan's stagnated economy by relating it to the geopolitical economy rivalry in East Asia, pointing out that;

‘Because Japan is still healing from the economic downturn of the 1990s when the economy did so well. Because China has had such a dramatic economic growth record. Japan of course grew very fast but towards the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, the economy terribly slowed down. So, they are still in recovery mode. So putting on a mega event of this size is to project to the world that yes, we are back, that yes, we are functioning, so yes, I think it was timely and was a form of rebranding Japan that it is still a powerful economy. It is still a powerful nation, and it still has a voice. Even though they shy away from the military exhibition and other oppressive ways, we identify with other states. Their part is much more human and acceptable’.

Likewise, AB also points out that,

‘In many ways, you can say China is more powerful because of the size of the economy and more power because they have nearly 10 times the population than a country like Japan that the comparisons are really apples and oranges and in many ways, soft power strategies helps to contrast that with the strategies of China. It makes it much more akin to South Korean, where they are trying to promote democracy, an element of soft power and coolness in ways that permeate other aspects of pop culture.

From my interview with WY and AB, the regional importance of hosting the Olympic Games comes from two key areas, the first is on the economy, and the second is on the display of political strength. These two factors are important in discussing the efficacy of the Tokyo Olympic Games as a soft power tool. In terms of Economy, research has shown that host cities can be guaranteed an increase in tourism and recognition, which helps boost the foreign public perception of the host country. Secondly, on political strength, Japan needs to become active and relevant. Part one of this chapter revealed Japan's smart power effort through Prime Minister Abe to make Japan a first-tier country. However, key issues for discussion will be the importance of the Olympic Games on Japan’s economic and political regional profile and how this translates into a larger international image.

Equally, according to WK, WK depicts that aside from soft power, many more issues are going on in Japan than just the Olympic Games.

‘One problem for thinking of soft power and Japan is that there is a lot more going on for Japan about the Olympics than just soft power. Two other things going on are domestic politics and economics. It has nothing little to do with soft power or the international world, but it was the efforts of the Tokyo governor in 2016 to get the Olympics. Who was concerned about Tokyo’s place in the world as a global city? Not so much for Japan but for Tokyo and Tokyo as the premier city for Japan and a city with its global reveries like London and Paris and New York and Seoul and Singapore. What was going on was a kind of global city rivalry. The campaign for 2020 is a little different because this time is not the Tokyo governor but Prime Minister Abe, who really wanted the Olympics.

From the discussion with WK, there are contrasting views on the Olympic Games as a soft power tool. First, the opinion that there is a lot more going on than just soft power, mainly domestic politics and economics, needs to be clarified. This is because previous interviews point out that Japan needs a boost to help its struggling economy and quiet political involvement nationally and regionally. In the context of the Olympic Games. The Olympic Games, as identified, is a strategy to achieve this aim. However, the Issues of domestic politics and economic issues have a lot more to do with the Olympic Games, especially from the lens of Prime Minister Abe’s political actions. Secondly, the opinion that Prime Minister Abe wanted the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games for Japan and not just about global city rivalry speaks to the importance of the Games to Japan’s image. Part one of this chapter identified that Abe’s role in the bid to host the 2020 Olympic Games is a smart power strategy if combined with his policy to remilitarize Japan’s constitution. However, it is important to discuss the narrative to understand what the government of Japan hoped to achieve by hosting the Olympic Games.

5.4.1 Theme F- The significance of an open and global society through the Tokyo 2020 Olympics

Similarly, on Japanese culture and society, JG reflects on an ethnographic observation of Japan’s society, pointing toward Japan’s effort to open its society globally and culturally and highlighting the importance of the economy as the reason for wanting to open its society.

‘My sense was before the pandemic when I went a year before, my sense about the serious talks in Japan, the sense I got was that they want to open up their inward-looking culture. They are an inward mono-cultural society, they are also relatively patriarchal, and I am married to a German national who in Germany is very advanced, maybe not advanced in some of the neighbouring countries but are very advanced in gender equality. And so, my wife would have been shocked by Japan. If I were shocked, she would have been shocked. So I think they wanted to break this, they wanted to change this and become more outward-looking, and more internationally focused a lot of this, and a reason for this is the economics and of course as well as culture. That aspect for them, I think, is going to be more difficult with these Games, and I think the Games is going to be one that is viewed from outside wherever we are and not interacting. And as your supervisor will know this better than anyone, you need this interaction to adapt to change cultures, and that is not going to happen to a great extent or never be a great extent’.

From JG's ethnographic reflection, it is important to point out that a country's national pride is derived from its cultural values and diversity. But JG's reflection points out the impact of globalisation. The world has become one and a global village; ordinarily, countries attempt to be more diverse and outward-looking in a globalised world. This means opening up their society and culture to the world and seeking global legitimacy through tourism, cultural events, and sports. In the case of Japan, Japan

Similarly, WY points out that,

‘The thing that makes America appealing is the multicultural composition of the nation; it gives people an idea that everybody is welcome. Of course, we have issues but still globally, the projection is that it is still a very diverse society. When you look at Europe, a lot of countries have been pushing towards that diversity and that comes in through embracing players that come from different parts of the world to embrace them and to give the honour to represent you. So that the minorities in your country can also feel that yes I am represented. One other thing when you talk about Japan and when you talk about sports is that they are not also as diverse. So, we are not just talking about racial composition we are talking about the opportunities available for women to participate in international sports. Because Japan is much more like a patriarchal society and that’s one of the challenges Japan faces: women are still lacking behind the men in terms of opportunities.

Furthermore, WY also highlights the importance of diversity while pointing out some key strategies Japan has followed in creating diversity, especially through sport. According to him,

‘I think Japan just like the other Western countries pushes for immigration to diversify the populations because a lot of people realise that in diversity there is strength. Because when you have a diverse population you market yourself better to the globe. Because when you go to Africa, Africans see themselves in Japan, when you go to Europe they see themselves in Japan. But at present, that is its weakness. Like other countries that are opening up. When you go to Australia minority faces show up in sports, if you go to Europe the same thing. They have diversified. You will see, Arabs, and Africans. South Americans. That is why Japan in their soccer league, they rely on imports from South America even naturalise some of the South Americans to play for the soccer national team. I think that is a way of showing the world that we are welcome and open to diversification’.

The Olympics has acquired a global cultural, commercial, and political image however this is not new as the literature has linked it to the 1932 Olympic Games. For countries like China, hosting the 2008 Olympic Games has continuously sought to acquire international recognition in sports participation. One of the most distinctive elements of globalisation is the visible expansion of mega sports events like the Olympic Games. In a global context, a sporting event is viewed by countries as a partial measure of their status. Horne (2007) the growth of mass communication technology has made it possible for events like the Olympics to reach an unparalleled global audience, which has led to the spread of mega-events. Secondly, towns and regions can benefit greatly from these promotional chances as they can be used to market a variety of commercial products. This includes showcasing their attraction to the global audience to attract tourism and outside investment. From my interview, it appears that tourism is an ultimate advantage for a country's soft power through hosting the Olympic Games. However, in the case of Japan, tourism is an important factor in opening its society. However, from the interview, having a multicultural society is a weakness of Japan. The issues of gender equality and opportunities for women in sports are also a weakness of Japan's soft power

strategy. This means that lack of gender equality probably weakens their soft power strategy as this will always be cited by tourists or the foreign public. In addition, are there measures to counter this cultural stereotype? However, to investigate Japan's soft power, gender equality is one of the internal issues that this research must discuss.

Furthermore, from a different cultural perspective, HL, gave a contrasting view of Japan's society, especially from an educational perspective. According to HL;

‘Ok, particularly from a UK westernised capitalist position, the first time I went was in 2015, I was a PhD student. From an educational perspective, let's start there in terms of culture; it was not different from UK UK-based system. There is a level of reference where you get titles like sensei. But it is very much a hierarchical respectful culture. And I think what we need to recognise is that if you are looking at soft power, this is all intertwined; their whole cultural being is intertwined around this hierarchical, very respectful position. Even when I have been to teach at the university, it's the same process for the students even though they were a globalised group of students because it's an Olympic programme. They are very respectful of my position, my doctorate, which at the time I have only had for about 8 or 9 months and for me, it did not feel quite real. But it's all intertwined culturally’.

It appears that the mono-cultural characteristics of Japan's society are a weakness in its soft power. To counter this weakness, measures must be put in place to attract the foreign public. Japan is a peaceful and democratic country, and Tokyo is a popular cultural hub. However, from the interview and in the context of the Olympic Games, it is clear that a lot more issues are going on, such as economy, political dominance and image branding. Therefore, the question for discussion is whether the Olympic Games is an efficient tool for Opening up Japan's society and Tokyo as the host city. The London 2012 Olympic Games is an example of how the Olympic Games can serve as a soft power tool to rebuild, open and attract foreign visitors and tourists.

5.4.2 Theme G - The hosting of Rugby 2020 as a foundation for hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

This theme indicates that analysis of the soft power implications of the 2019 Rugby World Cup is crucial for understanding Japan's soft power strategy. Understanding the Olympic Games in Tokyo 2020 in advance of the pandemic will be made easier with this. Disregarding the topic of Japanese society's shortcomings from earlier, JG said in our conversation that comparing the Japanese rugby scene of 2019 to the 2020 Olympic Games offers a useful lens through which to analyse this storey in terms of soft power. Despite being smaller than the Olympics, the Rugby World Cup brought many visitors to Japan because it was the first Asian event. According to JG;

‘What I think you should do is compare the previous 2019 Rugby World Cup although the Rugby World Cup is not an Olympics, and it is nowhere bigger than the Olympics. But it is the first Rugby World Cup in Asia, and it is one of the first that attracted many a lot of people to Japan and started that process of open up so those things that we would have expected from the Olympics started developing’.

From JG's discussion, it is important to discuss Japan's 2019 Rugby World Cup for several reasons. It was the first major sports event Japan hosted before the 2020 Tokyo Olympics and before the pandemic, serving as a tool for exposing and opening Japanese society to the world. Secondly, it is important to compare factors such as tourism and the percentage of international audiences viewing the Games from abroad compared to a closed Olympic Games affected by the pandemic. Thirdly, Japan's Rugby team is a symbol of what Japan hopes to achieve in an open and globalised society. JG points out that Japan's Rugby team was made up of players who naturalised in Japan and originally were not Japanese by birth. This speaks volumes about the soft power strategy of Japan through sports diplomacy.

‘Another key point here is that their national Rugby team was made up of many people who naturalised, who weren't Japanese, so have people from Australia who married Japanese women, people from South Africa. So that was very interesting because you

have a whole country cheering a team that you have mostly no Japanese, but they are Japanese but not originally Japanese. There was the interaction with a lot of teams there, lots of fans and lots of fun and visitors and that's what we thought was going to happen with the Olympics, and that's not going to happen because of Covid-19'.

Previously my interview with WY points out that Japan has been successful in hosting mega sports competitions, including the Rugby World Cup.

5.4.3 Theme H - Salvaging the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games as a Soft power Tool from the Impact of Covid-19

The normal operation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was disrupted by the extraordinary development of Covid-19. This implies that Japan's soft power approach might have been impacted by multiplying effects. First, given the high expense of holding the Games, the pandemic's advent posed a threat to the organisation of the Games. Second, the Olympic Games were staged behind closed doors due to concerns over tourism. However, it is important to discuss the effect of hosting the Olympic Games without fans and an influx of tourists. Thirdly is the number of international viewers watching the Games from abroad. The findings reveal the importance of the media's presence in Tokyo effectively broadcasting the Games to foreign viewers, answering the question of how attractive the media has portrayed Japan to the world, especially in the absence of fans and tourism during the Games. On these issues, according to JG,

‘so I think the one aspect that we are not going to have is on what we said about the interactions of things, you know the tourism the multiplier effect, you know we won't have that, but we would have the media, and you will be able to see if everything goes well. If everything fronts well, they probably will be able to showcase themselves to some extent. One of the problems that I have got is that if there is no crowd and there is no atmosphere, especially in the athletics arena and cycling. If there is no atmosphere, that may impact the way it's carried out through the media. Because if it's boring to watch, you might get a drop, I mean there is something about it'.

‘Because, we have never had Games like this before. I wrote a paper on the effect of Covid-19 on sport, one of the sections I got was about this lack of crowds, and it really does take a lot on sports’.

This part is a reiteration of earlier interviews that highlight the influence COVID-19 has had on the Olympic Games organisation. It is necessary to talk about the media's role in preserving the Olympics as a soft power instrument for Japan. A crucial topic of conversation when it comes to public diplomacy and engaging with the international public is the media's contribution to preserving the Olympic Games. Similarly, on the impact of the media on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, AB gave a few points. The first is the huge concentration of the media in Japan.

‘I think it’s been 20 years we have a film short in Japan ‘Lost in Translation’ that had an impact, but it’s a bleeding impact over the course of time. It did not have remotely the spike, the focus that you get for something like the Olympics or like hosting a World Cup. Because by their nature, sports are epic because we know they will go away. We know that there is very little interest right now in watching the finals in the 100 metres from Tokyo. We know who won, we missed the moment, we are not discussing that anymore. We have to consume it for a finite amount of time, that’s one thing you get in sports and you don’t get any other place. So media is huge, it’s not just the amount of media; it’s the fact that it is all concentrated in a given point in time’.

Secondly, about catching the moment and exposing the Japanese culture because of the huge concentration of the media,

‘It's about catching the moment, it's about knowing, you know we are constantly looking for something we can discuss with friends and family. So for instance, right now, I think more cultures are knowing way more about Ukraine than they knew before. That is a by-product that there is a media scene to this. There is a reason why we are focusing on Ukraine right now. Obviously very different circumstances, but because we have drawn our attention to something, that means you are going to talk about it to others. As opposed to a book you read about Japanese American experience or Japanese British experience. So whatever it is, you don’t necessarily know that everyone else is interested in that book, therefore you don’t have the conversation, therefore, you don’t have the conversation and therefore you don’t have the influence for people who are talking about your culture in some way. So you need to somehow

permeate through with an immediacy so people will know this is something we can talk about right now. I know I can reference Ukraine and the chances is that you know what I am talking about there are benefit to that that you don't get in some ways that I think Japan was able to accomplish'.

Japan may have used the massive media concentration surrounding the 2020 Tokyo Olympics as a soft power strategy. Although there is some repetition in this part, it does highlight how crucial it is to talk about how the media shapes public perception of Japan. According to Zion et al. (2011), the media is crucial to sport's rise to prominence as a global social, cultural, and economic institution. Additionally, (Filo, et al., 2015) note that social media's advent has had a significant impact on how sports are delivered and consumed. by looking into new media technologies and analysing the corpus of research already available on social media in the sports industry. Three categories of social media were distinguished by them: strategic, operational, and user-focused. The research reviews the ways in which social media helps foster interactions between people and brands. Building these partnerships requires contact and engagement on both ends. The advent of digital network communication technology towards the end of the 20th century might be considered a defining feature of new media. Online streaming, blogs, social media, websites, etc. are a few examples. Lastly, it is argued (Hutchins & Sanderson, 2017) that watching sports mega-events on television is the main way that fans experience them. through examining the interactions between social networking sites like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat, and the digital live streaming of Olympic events via desktop computers and smartphone apps. Argues that social networking services, which have a large user base and economic influence of their own, expand the television logic of media coverage and sports coverage. This is done by anchoring the flow of content across screens through social networking. illustrating how this setup strengthens television's position as the main medium for consuming sports mega-events. Studies have demonstrated the impact of the media, both new and broadcast media, on major sporting events. But to respond to the

research question, we must talk about how the media, as a soft power instrument, helped to save the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

5.4.4 Theme I - The cost of not hosting and postponement of the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games

HL depicts that the loss of not hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games would have been financial and Japan would still have gained from it because they have the support of the sport for tomorrow program, which is a sport diplomacy strategy to help other countries build and develop sports. HL discussion reveals that there is a need to analyse Japan's cultural policy to understand the role of culture in the relationship between Japan and its Asian neighbours in a geopolitical context.

According to HL;

‘Even if they have got to that point where they are able to deliver it last year, their step up to that point can still derive what they have gained for it. The loss would have been financial if it did not go ahead. But they would still have gained from it because they have the sport for tomorrow programme. They have links to universities that are delivering master's programmes or postgraduate and those programmes have had active internship-based curricula. I guess they have got people who are graduates of those programmes in the Olympic community itself, and they may not be Japanese people. They could be from anywhere in the world. It is such a thorough system that they are actually training people who are in Olympic community-based activities, but even from a soft power perspective, you are still upscaling and leveraging human development which then you take to your nation. And there are a number of nations I hear through whispers of people I know vaguely saying that their nations in and around Asia are looking to hosting in the next 2030 years so it's a big drive forward’.

Likewise, JD points out that after Tokyo was announced as the host of the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games. There was a huge tourism boom from the period of 2013 and 2020, and this was a huge change that was not really anticipated.

‘The other thing that first happened when the games were first awarded, the biggest thing that happened between 2013 and 2020 was a massive tourism boom for Japan. And that was a huge change that was not really anticipated, and that was an area where the government had some initiative primarily Asian tourism boom Korean and Chinese really mostly south-east Asian for the government that was purposeful and that visa restriction was loosened a little bit. And some other things were put in place, and access was much better. So all of a sudden, before the pandemic, there was this huge volume of tourism and that would have been different for the Tokyo 2020 Games’.

From the preceding discussion on whether Japan was successful in achieving its aim by using the Olympic Games as a soft power tool, my chat with HL and JD took a different turn. The primary topics of debate from the interviews have been how Japan's capacity to use the Games as a soft power tool is impacted by the advent of Covid-19. Japan already has a successful soft power strategy, as noted by HL and JD, particularly in light of initiatives like Sport for Tomorrow and education. Japan had a notable surge in tourism after the news that Tokyo would host the Olympics. In a similar vein, WK provided a historical synopsis of Japan's economic stagnation and how it affected travel there. According to WK;

‘What is interesting is that 20 years ago In Japan, because of its economic stagnation and other things and the popularity of China at the time, when I was going to Japan in 2000-2001, 2002. Everyone was complaining because no one was paying attention to Japan, it wasn't important anymore, and there were no visitors from other parts of the world. But over the last ten years really the amount of tourism in Japan has gone up 10 to 15 times. They would set these goals by 2015. We wanted to have 10 million visitors; they had 10 million visitors and tourists by 2011. Without the Olympics, they were

already achieving this kind of international exposure and tourist enthusiasm, economic revenues without the cost of the Olympics’.

From my interview, it appears that two factors need to be discussed in depth. The first is on whether the announcement of Tokyo as the Olympic City impacted positively on the growth of tourism and what it means for Japan’s soft power and the second is on the impact of Covid-19 on the Olympic Games and how it impacts Japan's soft power. However, previous discussions from JG point out that closed Games because of the pandemic may affect Japan's soft power, for example, tourism. However, from JD, HL and WK discussions, Japan has begun to see a positive effect on international exposure and tourism even before the Games. However, from the literature review, research has shown that it is difficult to measure the impact of soft power, especially after hosting a sports mega event like the Olympic Games. Therefore, an in-depth discussion is needed on whether the announcement of Tokyo as the Olympic host city helped to boost Japan’s soft power before the impact of the pandemic.

In addition, amid the hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games behind closed doors, JD points out that if the Games were held in normal times, the games would have been very Asian and would have had a better chance of Going Viral. According to JD;

I think the games would have felt very Asian because even more than Beijing, I think for Tokyo, the vast majority of spectators would have been Asian, again primarily Chinese and Korean but also Southeast Asian. I think there would have been potential for a better word ‘go viral’. I think it might have been an opportunity for Japan to build soft power within Asia, to share their wartime image of militarism and colonialism and to also present itself as much more integrated into Asia. Because their constant fighting with China and Korea has meant that Japan has not seemed very Asian, and this would have been an opportunity.

The significance of the Olympic Games as a vehicle for soft power is also given a distinct perspective by JD's talk, particularly when viewed from an Asian standpoint. JD's talks are in line with evaluations of the literature regarding the background behind Japan's cultural imperialism in Asia. (Otmazgin, 2012) Points that throughout the past 100 years, Japan's diplomacy and cultural policies in Asia have undergone significant transformation. First, this stems from the aggressive imposition of Japanese culture during the period of empire-building. Secondly, throughout most of the post-war era, Japanese culture was not promoted in Asia due to fear of being associated with cultural imperialism once more. According to JD, the Olympics might have evolved into an instrument for peace-making.

5.4.5 Theme J- The Olympic Games as a fluke concept and a weak excuse

WK gave a different dimension to Japan's soft power in connection to the Olympics. He described soft power in two categories firstly, soft power as an analytical concept and soft power as a fluke concept, according to WK;

‘But I think it is an important issue, particularly for Japan, and it is connected to the Olympics, but I will distinguish between soft power as an analytical concept and soft power as a fluke Concept. The term was used by everybody from Prime Minister Abe down to Olympic officials because they do that, and if we are analysing the Olympics, we need to take that seriously, but I can't really take it at face value because I don't think they really know what they are talking about. Moreover, soft power is a very soft concept, a very mushy concept, I think’.

WK's discussion points that the government of Japan had a deliberate soft power strategy with the term (soft power) used throughout the tiers of government, including Japan's Olympic Committee. Soft power as an analytical concept can be examined from the significance of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games on Japan's image, and the second can be analysed from Abe's government's economic and constitutional policies. Part one of the findings discussed the latter

as Abe's smart power strategy. However, historically, and more recently, there has been clear evidence of soft power strategies employed by Japan's governments, such as the Cool Japan initiatives, which have been discussed from an analytical perspective in the literature review and part of the data findings. Secondly, soft power as a fluke concept can be examined from Japan's government's cultural approach to exporting its cultural products abroad hence the cool Japan policy. In addition, hosting the Olympic Games to match the economic and political strength of its neighbours like China may also signify that soft power is a fluke concept in Japan. This is because research has criticised the Games as too expensive and not sustainably efficient. However, hosting the Olympic Games because of the notion of nation branding, economic growth, investment, or tourism may be a fluke concept for Japan. So, for example, if countries like China, Brazil and Russia have been able to host a mega sports event like the Olympics, why not Japan? If Japan's government look at hosting the Olympic Games from this narrative, then the soft power and the Olympic Games as a soft power tool is a weak excuse.

According to WK;

‘What is so interesting about the Olympics, not just from a global diplomacy point of view but just as a mega event is how the multiple levels on which you have these struggles going on domestically and regionally and globally. So soft power is such a broad concept analytically that it is hard to identify and issue these different levels. Like I said it is an important concept because Abe thought that it was all about soft power.

Soft power as a fluke concept may also mean jumping on the bandwagon because many countries have begun to set up several soft power initiatives to improve their image around the world by setting up language institutes and hosting SMEs, for example, China and its language institutes. Soft power as a fluke concept may also signal that even though the Games are becoming very expensive with little impact on host cities as previous Games have shown. Japan

is willing to host the Games with the hopes that it will benefit economically and culturally. For example, staging the Olympic Games is costly and financially risky for cities and nations. According to Flyvbjerg et al. (2016), each Olympic Games has cost an average of USD 8.9 billion over the last ten years, indicating that hosting the Olympics is one of the most expensive and financially hazardous types of megaprojects that towns and nations may choose. According to Shervani et al. (2020), Japan had to spend \$6 billion on support and lost revenue to arrange and execute the Games, despite working extremely hard for seven years. The Covid-19 pandemic's emergence highlights the financial risk associated with hosting the Olympics.

According to JD, Japan's soft power strategy is described as '*jumping on the bandwagon*' because of the many problematic societal or cultural problems. However, amplifying its soft power initiatives may help address these issues. According to JD;

'They tried to jump a little bit on that bandwagon, maybe the Japan foundation and its offices around the world have been most active in that regard, and they have been because they are focused on cultural production, the ministry of foreign affairs try to leverage on the success of anime and manga. But in the end, like we have seen in the last weeks and the statement about women, Japan is always hand strong by all this by the conservatism of government offices and their views of Japan is suddenly stuck at the early 20th century'.

Following the 21st-century notion that hosting major sporting events like the Olympic Games may assist positively promote a country's image is equivalent to jumping on the bandwagon for Japan. Japan, for instance, was effective in using the 1964 Olympic Games as a marketing tool. But in 2008, after several decades, China made progress by organising the costliest Olympic Games ever. According to a study, Japan's economy has struggled, and it is behind China in terms of economic expansion and exports of Asian culture. Additionally, the Winter Olympic Games, which stood for peace, were hosted by Japan's neighbours to the north and

south prior to the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games. But in 1964, considering Japan's battle to regain its position as a premier country as it had in the years preceding and following World War II. It would be prudent for Japan to bid on and host major sporting events to broaden its society and improve its reputation both locally and globally. While bringing up the cultural and gender concerns in Japanese society, JD also makes the same remarks as in earlier talks. the political conservatism of Japan, where reform is elusive. Joining the bandwagon may have been motivated by these societal difficulties, particularly in light of Japan's aspirations for a multicultural society.

‘In addition, I think that is somewhat emblematic of the struggles of the ministry and, to some extent, the government. That certainly holds for Prime Minister Abe. I mean, he was obviously in Millan last year, but he is an example of that tension where he goes. I think he generally wants to embrace all opportunities cool Japan and the like, but personality-wise, he has totally countered everything that he believes in. He probably thinks of anime and manga as a side embarrassment culturally and would rather have the world admire flower arrangements. However, that remains the tension, and I think another thing that is Mori as the head of the local Olympic organising committee and the statement he made last week about women are just the most outrageous. But all along, he is very old, and he is very old in the head, and he is not going to spearhead anything that would get younger generations in Asia or around the world excited, and I don't think they might realise that’.

From the literature review and from JG's discussion, more recently, before the opening ceremony of the Olympics, Japan's Olympic Committee (JOC) faced a series of controversies on Gender issues, drawing a reference from Yorito Mori, the former JOC chief who apologised for his sexist comments made on Women that led to his resignation. This discussion on gender issues also supports JG's narrative of the monoculture and inward-looking Japanese society. It also points to the conservative nature of Japanese society, which may have resulted from the

high percentage of the elderly population. Like WK's discussion on counterculture and cultural policy, Japan's government has adopted conventional cool Japan initiatives and JD's point on Abe's thinking of anime and manga as a side embarrassment speaks volumes about the cultural practices and issues in Japan's society and the government's position of these counter-cultural policies.

5.5 Theme k- Prime Minister Abe's motivation soft power strategy

JD discussed in the interview that Japan's government is conservative also my discussion with WK, supports JD's narrative on Japan's government as conservative, according to WK;

'Abe as a conservative right-wing politician at the same time as the last ten years, has been talking about soft power and the Olympics, and his been trying to change the constitution to allow offensive military operations. You know they have in Japan military armament industry and its huge most of which is manufactured and sold to other countries. But, the so-called self-defence forces, army and navy, are quite extensive and every day brings new close calls with Chinese and the south China sea. There are two levels going on simultaneously through the same Prime Minister Abe, who is pushing Japan in a hard power way to confront China to expand its military to get into offensive operations to have closer collaboration with the United States in supporting Iraq a while ago and other operations now and then. He is also talking about Japan and the Olympics as a cultural soft power with biennial influences'.

The conservative feature and the extensiveness of Japan's military, including Abe's aim for a constitutional change, fit well with part one of the findings. Abe's hard power is discussed in part one as a smart power strategy where Abe sought to remilitarise Japan's constitution to allow for a proactive defence military and then Abe's role in the Tokyo 2020 bid campaign. The key issue from WK's discussion is on a regional level, where he discussed Abe's hard

power strategy as an attempt to confront China by expanding its military. In addition, WK's narrative on the regional level supports JG's earlier discussion on examining soft power from the regional level. From the narrative of the conservative nature of Japan, it appears that the geopolitical tension in Asia is a reason for Prime Minister Abe to propose a shift towards a proactive military policy. The proposed policy to move away from pacifism signifies Abe's goal to make Japan a major player in political matters, especially on political tensions involving its neighbours. Furthermore, WK points to the geopolitical tension in Asia and the competition for countries like China, Japan, and South and North Korea, pointing out how it plays a role in their efforts to bid for and host the Olympic Games.

'China and Japan particularly are in fierce competition to outdo one another in putting on the Olympics so is this geopolitical rivalry among the East Asian country that is really important, that really changed the centre of Gravity in the Olympics. But for real, a lot of the economic centre in the Olympic Movement depends, I believe, on Asia, particularly East Asia, the audiences and the branding and everything else'.

Similarly, JG discussion on the motivations behind Japan's soft power also points to the regional level. According to JG, this is because of the ascendancy of China. Repeatedly, he laid emphasis on the regional level as one way of uncovering the motives of these countries, especially in the case of Japan.

'I will suggest that it is not international, that is more regional first and for most because of the ascendancy of China. Do you have the books on emerging states and soft power that, is the one you were reading? If you look at the last chapter where I have just started talking about this, you know international, regional and national. I think that is a good way of conceiving their motives and what they can achieve. Because it might be that they might achieve other things like domestic, but they certainly can or cannot achieve

the sort of regional, you know 'Abenomics' that guy he certainly did want them to become better armed and stronger, and he was trying to overturn things in parliament'.

From my interview, it is important to discuss the geopolitics of sports in East Asia, discussing the policies and motives of these countries, specifically China and South Korea. This appears to be one way of identifying and investigating Japan's soft power.

Similarly, JD discusses further the importance of the regional aspect of soft power for Japan in terms of hosting the Olympic Games. Reflecting on the proposed boycott of the 2022 Olympics in China and the narrative of good Asia and bad Asia.

'And this is where of course what is currently happening with the beginning of a boycott Beijing 2022 movement also offers a twist if we still have the Games this summer, of course, not a normal Games. If Tokyo had happened as planned, it would be the good Asia, and whereas increasing now, it is going to be the bad China for 2022. That is a narrative that Japan benefits from massively across Asia right now, the good part of Asia has gone bad, meaning authoritarian if we think about Thailand, to some extent Philippines, India with democracy pandering. Again, who knows how powerful that narrative is but the contrast between 2020 Tokyo and 2022 Beijing would have been clear. And that might have also led to a different soft power impact, and that's all gone because if anything happens this summer, it is not going to be very Asian because there is not going to be spectators. It is just going to be just flat, people watching on TV'.

When gauging a nation's soft power, important variables include political philosophy, economics, culture, event success, democracy's quality, and international public opinion. The standard of democracy and human rights is the second most crucial factor when it comes to Asia, more especially China and Japan. Considering the narrative surrounding Asia's good and bad, it seems likely that Japan will surpass Asia in terms of human rights in the context of the

Olympic Games. Due to China's human rights record, some nations have announced diplomatic boycotts of the 2021 Olympic Games in Beijing, China, implying that their diplomats would not participate (BBC, 2022). WY adds that

‘Globally, people have a lot of respect for Japan for the audacity of the Japanese people. They came away with the positive impression of the resilience of the Japanese people and a sense of humility. Ultimately, when you are talking about soft power, those are the attributes you want to be identified with. You can contrast that with Moscow but for Japan, these Games were given the circumstances, the games were successful, and Japan continues to brand itself in a unique way’.

Similarly, WK points to the image problems of China even after the 2008 Beijing Olympics and in comparison, to Japan’s image. According to Wk;

‘China, on the other hand, has very serious image problems and it deliberately was using 2008 as a way of presenting itself as a dynamic and creative, friendly and open society. In the end, people came and was impressed with the architectural and the opening ceremonies and was not so impressed with the political freedoms and the control with the government, but I am not very sure if they were successful in using the Games diplomatically in that way. Obviously, that is not the issue for Japan. For Japan, is demonstrating that they can have economically efficient and environmentally sustainable games, that they are actually leading the world making sure in this sort of thing. Again, Covid-19 and other things have really made this unlikely to happen. They keep talking about soft power, and they really think in those terms, but I think it is much more likely now after a year of coronavirus and the political controversy, and three days ago, there was a serious earthquake in Japan. One will hope that there nothing like that will happen before the Olympics’.

Also, AB points out that,

‘I think Japan is now positioned in a different place globally were people are much more ready to pause different parts of the foreign eastern culture in general. China comes across as a different type of power. I don’t Japan is trying to or should have tried to be seen on equal feet with China because of all the problematic human rights and lack of free speech or things that we don’t ascribe to Japan’.

Similarly, WY depicts that,

‘There is that pursuit for unique national identities, and Japan has distinguished itself better. They don’t have a lot of negatives that come with hosting the Games. They may have their own internal issues. For example, I am not ignoring the fact that there were a lot of protests with regard to how the government handled covid-19. But when you compare with Russia and China where we have human rights abuses, where we have issues of control of human freedom, you can see that there is a clear distinction here. I think culturally Japan is much more diverse but it may not be as diverse as some of the Western countries but that is neither here nor there because of their own unique history and location in the world for example there has to be something enormous to move from Africa to Japan because culturally, we have no connections.

Conversely, in terms of using the Olympic Games as a soft power tool, it is important to examine if the Olympic Games is a better strategy for soft power. The question for discussion is whether hosting mega sports events like the Olympics is the right strategy for opening up a conservative and monoculture society like Japan. From previous cases of the Olympic Games, the literature review has shown that hosting sports mega event like the Olympic Games may create a positive atmosphere for the organisers or create an atmosphere of global and national criticism on several societal or political-ideological issues and in this case amplified with the uncontrolled presence of the media. This, however, points to the importance of national soft power. That is what degree of satisfaction the citizen of the host country has towards its government.

5.5.1 Theme L- the Olympic Games need a fundamental reimagining

Research has shown that the organisation of the Olympic Games is somewhat problematic. For example, more recently, the Olympic Games have been hosted in countries tagged as authoritarian or not conforming to global human rights values. For example, countries like China and Russia, and with the narrative shifting to the idea that the IOC turns its attention to countries willing to spend on the Games no matter the cause. Secondly, amid the controversies, it appears that these countries mentioned may know the value of hosting the Olympics as it may signify economic and political strength and a show of power, especially when governments shy away from the games because of the unsustainable expenses. Considering this, WK points out the limit of soft power and the ways countries have sort to use it. According to Wk,

‘And there is also the limit of soft power to me as a concept because China is talking the same way while it’s locking up its minorities and suppressing them, and Russia was the same way with the Olympics. It seems to me that countries are trying to have it both ways. Is not that there is a hard power country or a soft power country, but these are both dimensions of national power that many countries seeking a prominent role are going to play at the same time’.

But WK makes clear that this is a tenuous justification and that it is important to examine the idea that nations are vying to host the Olympics to gain soft power. This is a result of the way nations pretend to utilise soft power but, when faced with challenges, resort to using hard power tactics. In Japan's example, the organisation of the Olympic Games was carried out despite the challenges posed by the epidemic, social problems, and discontent among the populace. But it's crucial to consider the Tokyo Games of 2021 from the perspective of the Games as a flimsy justification for a soft power tactic. WK discussed that;

‘Hopefully, the Olympics can figure out what the model would be, but it seems to me that this notion of countries trying to host the Olympics and then what the hosting requires and another way soft power then becomes some kind of weak excuse for putting this one because of the realm people like to talk about it. It’s a crucial topic because if you look at it critically, you can then challenge some of the claims that they are making about doing this for soft power, and it’s preventing the Olympic movement from a more fundamental reimagining of what it needs to become to survive’.

From the above conversation, there are three ways to look at using the Games as a soft power tool. The first is whether the Games have devolved into a cheap cover storey; the second is whether soft power prevents a serious rethinking of the requirements for the Games' survival; and the third is the difficulties facing the Games' organisation. The main obstacle facing Japan and the Tokyo Games has been organising the event given the epidemic and the low level of support from the country's populace for the Games to proceed despite the outbreak. JG also contributes to the conversation about the difficulties the Games' organising faces. The discussion by JG speaks to the narrative of soft power on a national level. The Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games were postponed because of the emergence of a pandemic. Last year, the Games, which was held, received very low support from the Japanese population on whether the Games should be held. The shallow support is a key issue to be discussed, looking at how low public support for a sports mega can affect a country's soft power. According to JG;

‘So we didn’t mention the fact that over 60% of the population don’t want the Games, that’s really bad. Most successful Games in terms of internal soft power, and external, regional all this dimension must have the public behind them. Most of the successful Games have achieved all this, so we have never had over 60% of the population say that they don’t want the Games, so that is a start. So you need to get that in somewhere, you need to consider that’.

Equally, AB points out that the low public support for hosting the Olympic Games amid the pandemic is depleting Japan's soft power. According to AB;

‘So what does the government want to get? What is the foreign policy people want to get out of hosting the Olympics? And I am not even sure what that is, and what I do think is that maybe it's backfiring. I feel like if they want the 2020 Games to be a soft power resource, I think it is more depleting their soft power in the end. I think the pandemic has created a reversal in the soft power impact of the Olympics. Because what I see in the news is how the Japanese government is putting money before people and putting money before public health. And not really getting a good response, and people are looking at their own government and saying this is a problem. You are prioritising the Olympics, and we still don't have vaccines, so it's really creating this point where Japanese people are critical of their own government and is actually creating a very bad impression of the Japanese government to the rest of the world so isn't that bringing Japan soft power down a notch' (AB).

The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic shows a lot of fundamental issues with the organisation of the Olympic Games. In the case of Japan, AB discussed that hosting the Olympic Games amid the emergence of the pandemic is depleting Japan's soft power. And this is also in contrast to the previous interview that described hosting the Games through the pandemic as a soft power tool for Japan. Furthermore, JG points out that Japan's political and economic dimensions will not be affected if the Games were cancelled or not as big as expected at the earlier stage of the pandemic. According to JG;

‘The longer-term dimensions around things like trade I don't think they will be affected if the Games is not as big and bombarded. I still think that things like that will be ok. Because if you look at the 2008 Olympics in China, there are lots of negative things about human rights abuses lots and lots of negative things. But, three or four-five years down the line. China was a major player, they were invited to the UK, met Prime

Minister David Cameron they were high up in the international prestige on the political stage. I think in that aspect, this sort of politics, international politics, will be fine, but it is more of those nuanced things that we have talked about. More of the cultural internal, or the national identity these things I think will be difficult to impact through diminished games, or what will be a diminished Games' (JG).

Furthermore, from a critical look at the Olympic Games and Japan as the host country, WK discussed the concerns around the hosting of the future Games and how it may be affected politically because of the different challenges facing the organisation of the Games.

'What will be interesting is the combination of 2020, 2022, 2024 in Paris. Because 2020 may or may not happen, even if it happens, it will be very complicated, and then 2022 is going to be much more politically controversial than 2008 was for Beijing. And with the Hong Kong controversy, there is much more in the walls of tension now than there was in 2008. and so the 2022 Olympics seems to me that it will be far more difficult to pull off. And the question is when we go to Paris, the question is how to try to normalise, try to bring it back to a normal Olympics, I don't think because there is a lot and the question about all the money that is involved and who knows how'.

Based on my interviews, this section is consistent with the previous discussion about the value of the Olympics as a tool for soft power, the Olympics' significance for Japan, the goals Japan hopes to accomplish by hosting the Games, and how the pandemic could potentially hinder Japan's ability to host the Games. But the main topic of conversation should be how the Olympic Games are organised and if they should be fundamentally rethought. What does Japan's soft power stand to gain from hosting the Olympic Games during a pandemic in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympics and the outbreak of the disease?

5.6 Analysis of Sport Diplomacy

5.6.1 Theme-M Understanding Japan's sport diplomacy; following the money

This theme has exposed an essential story about good and bad Asia, which JD highlighted in a previous interview. This also covers Japan's soft power implications from its sport diplomacy approach of supporting other national sports federations in developing support. As the literature study discusses, international organisations and the government can use sport diplomacy as a strategy to forge closer ties. Sports are increasingly seen as such a high-level diplomatic matter, as illustrated by Redeker (2008). By attempting to redefine sports, they proposed a new way of thinking about the relationship between sport and politics. For example, what do countries have or hope to achieve through sports? This can be understood by looking at organised or grassroots sports to tackle issues of poverty and insecurity, promote culture, and sport for peace and social development. Around the discussion of Japan's sports diplomacy, JD depicts that;

‘When you say sports diplomacy, for example, I worked for the Mongolian national Olympic committee, so when you say sport diplomacy, one of the things I think of immediately is money and how national Olympic committees are supported by other national Olympic committees, particularly within Asia’

The key and most important point from JD's discussion is following the money. Following the money in terms of sport diplomacy could be looked at from two angles. The angle of diplomacy, which is, for example, the government using sports as a neutral foundation to start a seemingly political discussion or agreement. Secondly, following the money for example can be how rich countries like Japan have used sport as a diplomatic tool to create friendly relationships through its national Olympic Committee or other Japanese sports committees or federations by providing financial and developmental assistance. What this means is that by providing such assistance through sports, Japan can create a favourable relationship with the countries they have engaged with, and this is the type of sports diplomacy strategy that has

probably earned Japan the right to host the 2020 Olympic Games. Jackson, (2013) depicts that sport continues to occupy an ambiguous position within the context of politics, foreign policy, and diplomatic relations. Research identifies cases where sports have helped develop better cultural understanding and cases where sports have fuelled conflicts.

The literature review and the findings from Japan's foreign policy documents in part one of this chapter talks about sport for development and peace where Japan provides development assistance through sport to countries in need of standard sports equipment and facilities. This also goes as far as introducing Japan's combat sports to such countries. However, to understand Japan's sport diplomacy as a soft power tool, it is important to analyse the narrative of following the money. In addition, JD gave an example of the narrative of following the money from a first-hand perspective;

I know that for the Mongolian National Olympic committee, a lot of meetings in Vancouver and London were built around some sort of competing with other Asian-rich national Olympic committees. Who would pay for training facilities in Mongolia, you know, partly looking for the support of the IOC? Including where games are going to be held but also, ultimately, the ministries of foreign affairs who are also involved in this. So I do think that this is somewhat removed but related to a national strategy that sport diplomacy is sort of in the background and quiet but builds a lot of ties between the officials and sports organisations, especially within Asia'.

Furthermore, sport diplomacy as a background national strategy is an important point for discussion especially in the case of Japan. In part one of this chapter, I discussed how hard power is still a primary strategy for countries to consider especially in matters that affect sovereignty or nationalism. As discussed, in part one of the findings, the combination of hard and soft power becomes a smart power especially when looked at by Abe's administration. Furthermore, from previous interviews, participants made mention of the geopolitical rivalries

and unrest in East Asia. However, sport diplomacy as a background strategy is a soft power tool (smart power) to supplement this geopolitical unrest and in the process seek to gain some form of global legitimacy from their actions by hosting mega sports events. This is an important narrative for discussion especially in the case of Japan.

5.6.2 Theme N- Identifying Japan's Sport Diplomacy; the Strategy of Sports for Tomorrow program

Similarly, HL discussion on Japan's sport diplomacy points out that Japan's sport for tomorrow programme is an important sport diplomacy strategy for Japan. According to HL;

'Also the sport for tomorrow programme which is direct from the back of the Olympic Games which is what I am semi-linked to. One of their stated original aims way back five to six years ago was to get a million multiple coaches out in the world. What does that bring to Japan? It is a direct link by people from that human development perspective of being linked to places like Vietnam, Cambodia, Rwanda, and all nations that you are starting to see linked through different programmes with Japan.

HL's discussion on the sport for tomorrow programme fits well with JD's discussion on how the National Olympic Committee helps to contribute to other national Olympic committees in terms of financial or infrastructural assistance. In addition, HL's discussion fits well with WY's discussion on Japan's soft power, on how Japan's greatest strength is its ability to harness its human resources. HL points out that Japan's original aim of the programme goes back about 5-6 years before the Olympic Games. Aiming at creating a close tie to a direct link with the people of the countries involved such as Rwanda, Vietnam, and Cambodia. However, as discussed earlier, the question of what this means for Japan remains to be discussed. This research has, however, identified the sport for tomorrow programme as a background diplomatic tool to enhance Japan's soft power strategy. However, it is important to discuss and understand the motives behind the sports for tomorrow program. Part one of the findings on

document analysis identified the sports for tomorrow program as a foreign policy tool for helping and creating relationships with other nations and their national sports federations through sports.

Furthermore, from a soft power perspective, and leveraging the human economy by pointing out how Japan has sought to use education through sport to create a soft power system, for example, sport for development and peace. The key point is to measure the immediate impact of sports diplomacy as a soft power tool for Japan. According to HL;

From a soft power perspective, they are harnessing the use of education, and they have a great system to educate. They have got a lot of knowledge to provide in sport, how you set up sport, sport for development and peace. Also, this programme is the perfect way of doing that and that's how they grow their programme. So again, if it works, we won't know until 7 years down the line. I imagine whether that human driver of soft power is because they are leveraging the knowledge economy and that is one way of doing it, and I don't think we will ever see such an effort or drive to do that'.

From my Discussion with HL, it appears that education through sport programmes is an important part of Japan's soft power. (Wojciuk, et al., 2015) Points that education is an important contribution to a country's soft power in international relations. Arguing that education has not been adequately covered in the existing international relations literature. In addition, (Amirbek & Ydyrys, 2014) point out that; education is an effective tool of soft power for national interest and a country's image. From research, it appears that Japan's government know the value of education and in the case of sport diplomacy as discussed by HL, Japan is harnessing its human resources to teach about sport programs, development, and culture. However, to investigate the efficacy of Japan's soft strategy, it is important to discuss the extent to which its sport diplomacy strategy through education has been successful. In conclusion, the use of thematic analysis in the form of meta-themes and sub-themes was most used for the

purposes of qualitative research and this helped with coding and framing the narrative data. This led to me being able to produce a new smart model of soft power for Japan.

CHAPTER 6

Discussion

6.1 Introduction

Having analysed the data and findings, this chapter will discuss extensively the key thematic areas revealed as recurring issues from the analysis to answer the aims, objectives and research gaps that were revealed. It is interesting to note the areas that kept being brought to the fore by interviewees and emphasised in policy documents. That said, the researcher, is conscious that one always has to question why you are being told certain things and what is not being said is often important even if at first you can't see it. This is why it was important to triangulate between the range of interviewees, policy and political documents and the literature. What follows is a summation and discussion of those areas that were seen as the key thematic issues following the whole process of answering the research aim, objective, and question. This chapter is divided into two parts addressing the research questions, and with sub-themes addressing the research objectives.

PART ONE

HOW DO WE THEORISE SOFT POWER AS A CONCEPT IN INTERNATIONAL POLITICS USING SPORT DIPLOMACY AS A VEHICLE?

6.2 Addressing and Theorizing Soft Power

This section answers the research question by discussing the analysis of the overlap between Asian geopolitics and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a key theme of the analysis. The research has identified from the literature review and from the findings that there is a need to address and theorise soft power specifically in the context of sport diplomacy and by theorising soft power, it should be applied to similar contexts in international relations, diplomacy, and sports diplomacy. The research has identified that soft power is the ability of a country to influence the behaviour or interest of others through persuasion instead of the use of force or coercion. Soft power is often associated with cultural and ideological attraction. It also includes the ability to shape international norms and agendas. The common critique of the concept of soft power is that soft power is difficult to measure and quantify, it is often based on perceptions and opinions, rather than objective data (Pamment, 2014). This however makes it challenging to assess the effectiveness of a country's soft power efforts. Also, another critique is that soft power may become a useful tool for cultural imperialism where a country may use its cultural influence to impose its own rules, norms, and values on others, instead of respecting and learning from the cultural diversity of other countries. From the literature review, Otmazgin (2012) talked about how Japan has historically imposed and introduced its culture during the period of building its empire, but for most of the post-war era, it has been cautious about promoting its culture in Asia out of fear of being perceived as engaging in cultural imperialism once more (Otmazgin, 2012). Furthermore, soft power can be used to mask the use of hard power, where countries use economic, political, or military means to achieve their goals (Ding, 2010). Countries may use soft power to legitimise or justify their actions, making it more

difficult for other countries to respond or resist. In addition, it is argued that soft power is not as effective as hard power, especially in cases where the countries involved do not prioritise the same values or interests. Finally, soft power as a concept in some cases is criticised as a form of Western-centric thinking, which is not to the rest of the world, particularly in non-western countries.

Key debates from the literature review repeatedly point out that soft power tends to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework. Discussing that soft power is under-theorised with limited resources and that soft power is not a normative concept. Examples of the debates are; Grix & Brannagan, (2016) argue that the debates on soft power tend to focus on semantics or failures to engage with the concept, rather than providing a conceptual framework with which to understand a state's soft power strategy. Vuving, (2009) points out that one of the reasons for the widespread misunderstanding of soft power by scholars is the context that soft power is under-theorised and lacks academic refinement and analytical fuzziness. Similarly, and agreeing (Mingjiang, 2009; Ichihara, 2006; Womack, 2009) respectively, they argued that the equation of power with power resources is another reason for the misunderstanding of soft power. Pointing out that, limited serious efforts have been made to theorise the causal mechanism between domestic politics and foreign policy, despite the need to bridge the gap between comparative politics and international relations. Lastly, Nye noted that soft power was only one type of power and was rarely sufficient on its own in his piece *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (Nye, 2004; Nye, 2017). Nye (2017) notes that soft power is merely one facet of power and that "smart power" is the capacity to integrate hard and soft power into mutually reinforcing strategies (a term used by Hillary Clinton as Secretary of State).

Therefore, by investigating sport diplomacy as a soft power tool using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The research findings have revealed that the reason for the under-theorisation of soft power stems from the lack of engagement with the concept of key international relations theories that are vital in the field to create a clear foundation for the concept to be applied effectively. It is important to consider the three main theories of realism, liberalism, and constructivism in any context to which soft power is applied. Simply, Realism deals with security and material power, liberalism deals with economic power interdependencies and factors at the domestic level, and constructivism is concerned with the role of ideas in shaping the international system. To put into context these theories, it is important to discuss the case of Russia and China and the hosting of mega sports events.

The Case of Russia

Firstly, in the case of Russia and the FIFA 2018 World Cup, there are complex views about Russia from the period of cooperation and rivalry between Western states and views on Russia that are largely influenced by the geopolitical tensions that involve the conflict in Ukraine and Syria (Szostek, 2016; Bogolyubova & Nikolaeva, 2023). Using the strategic narrative conceptual framework, Szostek (2016) explored how country branding, which includes state-funded "mega-projects" like the Olympics in Sochi, helps the Russian state market and preserve its identity as a friendly and alluring travel destination.

In contrast, to the concerns of Human rights, western countries have criticised Russia for restricting press freedom and political opposition, as well as human rights abuses in conflict zones. Vladimir Putin, the president of Russia, was a key personality at the centre of the 2018 FIFA World Cup (Cole, 2021; Crilley, et al., 2021). He played a major role and was involved in its organisation and promotion. For example, in terms of a political symbol, Putin used the World Cup as a tool to display Russia's political and economic stability, and cultural heritage

to the world (Arnold, 2018). Also, in terms of diplomacy, Putin used the World Cup as an opportunity to engage in diplomacy with leaders of other countries and to build relationships with international organisations; he encouraged national pride in the tournament and Russian citizens rallied behind the event (Castro, 2018). Overall, Putin was a central figure in the 2018 World Cup using the event to promote Russia's interest and to assert its place on the world stage.

The Case of China

Secondly, In the case of China, generally, the Chinese Communist Party has dominated China, which has been in power since 1949 (Brown, 2012). The party exercises strict control over the government and the media and has been criticised for its lack of political freedom, human rights abuses, and censorship. At the same time, the Chinese government had been heavily involved in the organisation and promotion of international sport in China, through infrastructure investment, and national image, by viewing mega sports events as a showcase of China's political, and economic stabilities as well as the promotion of its cultural heritage to the world (Broudehoux, 2007). The Chinese government has been faced with many controversies such as human rights concerns that include the restriction on freedom of speech, assembly, and press. Despite the controversies, China remains an attractive destination for mega sports events, due to its rapidly growing economy, its large population, and its well-developed infrastructure.

The Case of Russia and China in the Context of international relations theories; soft power and sport diplomacy

The case of China, and Russia are similar in the context of using sport diplomacy as a soft power tool effectively from a neo-realism or structural realism ideologies. Where states are unsure of other states and decide to maximise power dominance economically, militarily, and culturally. Although post-war Japan is politically different and liberal. However, these

countries have been successful in their respective sport diplomacy strategy by using mega sports events like the Olympic Games and FIFA World Cup as vehicles for soft power. If examine from a political context both China and Russia have effectively exercised their hard power resources and have used sports as a soft power resource to mask their hard power strategies which have made them a fast-growing or controversial power globally. Because of the anarchy in the international system and the rapid evolution of diplomacy and state relations, the presence of other forms of diplomacy to gain recognition and legitimacy, such as nation branding, public diplomacy, cultural diplomacy, and sport diplomacy. These countries have resulted in the realist, constructive and liberal idea that the hosting of mega sports events is a useful tool for gaining legitimacy while at the same time engaging in hard power activities. However, the case of Russia and China needs to be well studied for further research to understand what an ideal soft power strategy is for these countries. Because their relationship with the international community and the use of sport as soft power might fall under any of the theories or a combination of both theories.

The Case of Japan in the Context of international relations theories; soft power and sport diplomacy

This research's case study, which examines Japan's utilisation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy, demonstrates this. The endeavour by Japan to remilitarize and change Article 9 of the constitution, as well as its hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, are examples of a neo-realist strategy to gain importance in both regional and international affairs. When these factors are considered, it becomes clear how soft power can be theorised using any of the basic theories of international relations. Theorising soft power in the context of neo-realism means that soft power is a secondary tool in the pursuit of the state's national interest and hard power (military and economics) is the most imperative factor of state influence in the international system. For clarity, Mochizuki (2007) discussed that

because of the Rise of China's presence, Japan has engaged in a vital domestic debate about China policy around four options; the first is cooperative engagement with soft hedge, the second is competitive engagement with hard hedge, thirdly, balancing and containment, the last is strategic accommodation. Mochizuki (2007) discussed further that Japan's mixture strategy is consistent with different theoretical traditions such as offensive realism, defensive realism, and liberalism. This will result in the future development of Japan-China interaction a shift in the military power balance and changes in US strategy.

Furthermore, governments aim to maximise relative power to survive, and the best method for this to occur is for a state to establish itself as a global hegemon. This is in line with realist theory (Mearsheimer, 2001). The question is how might states respond against a rising power with expanding relative capabilities with the potential to become a regional hegemon? Mearsheimer identifies four tactics: appeasement, bandwagon, buck-passing, and balance. Bandwagon and appeasement are considered poor strategies by proponents of offensive realism because they assume that states are vastly outmatched by their adversaries and that it is illogical for them to resist their requests. Since the enemy will use force to get what it desires (Mochizuki 2007). It follows that a state that is not helpless or alone will decide to take the initiative and fight. Appeasement in this context refers to giving in to an aggressive condition to pressure the aggressor to change course and potentially establish the status quo. It is assumed that the state's violent behaviour stems from a keen awareness of its strategic vulnerability and that appeasement will lessen the state's sense of insecurity and aggression's primary motivation. According to Mearsheimer, an aggressor state's desire for conquest is likely to be piqued rather than diminished by appeasement. On the other hand, aggressive realism's premise is to counterbalance a rising power or to transfer the blame to a different state or state that will counterbalance it. Mochizuki (2007) discusses Mearsheimer's points those great powers balance against capabilities, not intentions, this is because intentions are unknowable and can change

easily. A state-balancing behaviour takes the basic form of enhancing its military capabilities to counter external threats. Also, external balancing is where a state forms alliances with other states to balance against the threatening state (Mearsheimer, 2001; Mochizuki, 2007).

However, by relating these strategies to Japan's political behaviour. The data has revealed that there is a need to remilitarise Japan's constitution, reinterpretation of article 9 because of the nature of pacifism, also the need to make Japan a first-tier country. Appeasement and bandwagon explain Japan's current political behaviour where it seeks to maintain a pacifist state. However, the data reveals a smart power strategy where Japan's political behaviour entails a power strategy of power balancing and offensive realism. This is because Japan's government under the leadership of Abe resorted to following the construct of hosting mega sports events like the 2019 Rugby World Cup, and the 2020 Olympic Games to display economic and cultural strength like its rival China. Also, includes the attempt to move away from pacifism and have a proactive military like its rivals China, South Korea, and North Korea.

The point from this theoretical discussion is that soft power in the context of sports diplomacy should be and can be theorised by understanding the state's behaviours using the core international relations theory. It is also important that scholars in sport diplomacy begin to recognise that sport diplomacy is an aspect of international relations or global politics that can be used to determine a state's behaviour and when soft power is involved as a concept. It is important to theorise soft power with an appropriate theory to fit into the context for discussion. This among other future research knowledge is a research strategy to mend the gap and debates about the under-theorisation of soft power and the identification of an ideal soft power. By investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy, this research identifies that soft (smart) power is a neorealist or structural realist ideal of state behaviour in international relations. The neo-realist notion suits well with Nye, (2017) on smart power as

the combination of both hard and soft power where they reinforce each other for effectiveness. However, for future research, the researcher will seek to combine theories and soft power to address issues around sport diplomacy in addressing state's behaviour. By doing this, an ideal soft power strategy can be identified effectively. This is a recommended contribution to future research in sport diplomacy and state projection through the hosting of mega sports events.

PART TWO

WHAT IS AN IDEAL SOFT POWER STRATEGY USING THE TOKYO 2020 OLYMPIC GAMES AS A SOFT POWER TOOL?

6.3 The hosting of international sports events; Japan's sport diplomacy and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool

This section links with the thematic areas in chapters 4 and 5 about understanding Japan's foreign policy, national interest, and the importance of sports tourism on Japan's soft power. Secondly, the soft power of the Olympic Games. Firstly, it is important to discuss if Japan's sport diplomacy was successful in hosting the 2020 Olympic Games. The first point is that hosting the 2020 Olympic Games is an indication that Japan's sport diplomacy was successful, secondly, in a general context, a well-known example of Japan's sport diplomacy is the hosting of the 1964 Olympic Games, which was a major milestone for Japan as it demonstrated its post-war recovery. Apart from the success of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, Japan's success in sport diplomacy was in 2002 when it co-hosted the FIFA 2002 World Cup with South Korea, and in 2019 when it hosted the Rugby World Cup. These sports events provided Japan with the opportunity to display its culture, hospitality, and organisation and to strengthen its ties with other nations. Japan's sport diplomacy extends beyond the realm of traditional sports, for example, before the 2020 Olympic Games, the government of Japan launched the sport for tomorrow program in 2013 the research data revealed for the document analysis that through the program, Japan reached more than 10 million people in over 100 countries throughout the world. Therefore, the success of the programme indicates success in Japan's sport diplomacy. Furthermore, in recent years, Japan has used Esports, and competitive video games, to engage with other nations and promote its technology and innovation (ManuelPalma-Ruiz, et al., 2022). In 2018, Japan hosted the first-ever Asian Games Esports Championship that featured

athletes from across the region competing in various Esports events. Overall, Japan's sport diplomacy has been successful in improving its international image and promoting itself on the global stage and has been able to display its culture, values, and technological prowess. Furthermore, Japan's sport diplomacy success includes its cultural boom before the start of the 2020 Olympic Games. The promotion of culture leading to increased tourism is one of the major factors and impacts of hosting any mega sports event. Before the 2020 Olympic Games, the data reveal that Japan experienced a tourism boom because more people visited Japan to experience its culture, technology and way of life. Japan's tourism in recent years has steadily increased, however, the anticipation around the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games helped to boost the visitor number. There are several factors to the increase in tourism leading to the build-up of the 2020 Olympic Games.

The first is Japan's reputation as a safe and welcoming destination. Japan is known for its low crime rate, efficient public transportation system, and warm and hospitable people. Secondly, Japan has a range of diverse attractions, including modern cities, beautiful countryside, ancient temples and shrines, and iconic landmarks like Mount Fuji and the cherry blossoms. The Portland Soft Power 30 placed Japan in 8th position citing Japan's soft power strength in its culture and hosting high-profile international events like the G20 Summit and the 2019 Rugby World Cup leading to the build-up to the 2020 Summer Olympic Games (softpower30, 2019). This is also an indication of successful sport diplomacy even prior to hosting the Games on a soft power front.

In addition, studies have revealed that Japan's government tried to market the country as a travel destination before the Olympic Games. As was already indicated in the previous paragraphs, this also entails showcasing the nation's distinctive culture and attractions through the hosting of international events and the introduction of marketing campaigns like the Cool Japan initiative. Therefore, the Tourism boom in Japan leading to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic

Games was a result of the country's reputation as a safe place; a welcoming destination and its diverse range of attractions, and most importantly, the government's effort to promote tourism. By investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, the findings point out that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games is a sport diplomacy success and soft (smart) power strategy.

6.4 The nexus between the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and article 9 of its constitution; a smart power strategy

These areas link back to the thematic areas of making use of the soft power and hard power narrative towards an Olympic Quest the impact of the Second World War on Japan's soft power and the reconstruction of its identity through sport diplomacy from Chapters 4 and 5 respectively. What is interesting is the cross-over between the need for international political awareness, e.g., Japan's foreign policy versus the need to satisfy home-based sport diplomacy goals. This part will draw out further some of that discussion. By investigating Abe's administrative policies and his role in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid, this research has identified Abe's actions to revise Article 9 and his role in the 2020 Olympic bid including his closing ceremony impersonation at the Rio 2016 Olympic Games as a smart power strategy. Abe developed strong relationships with world leaders such as former Australian Prime Minister Malcolm Turnbull and Donald Trump (Manning, 2017).

In contrast, Abe had a strained relationship with his Asian-Pacific neighbours because of his unwillingness to acknowledge Japan's heinous behaviour during the Second World War (Filippello, 2018; Pizzolato, 2014). Abe has been criticised by his Asian neighbours for his extreme warlike outlook on position on the legacy of the Japanese empire and the atrocities committed throughout Asia and the Pacific (Saarinen, 2020). Abe's action as former prime minister explains his vision for a more assertive Japan. Abe was a prime minister with a revisionist idea about the Second World War and his complicated feelings about America

(Mito, 2008). Another considerable issue during Abe's administration was whether Japan should have accepted American terms regarding its constitution influenced by America after the defeat in the Second World War. In contrast, from the lens of Abe's policies, the constitution has been characterised as self-defeating and weakening. However, rewriting the constitution and positioning Japan's place in Asia and the world became important goals for Abe (Pyle, 2018). It is important to note that the constitution did not prohibit the right of self and Japan has a strong military with U.S. backing but does not have the right to wage war abroad or fire any weapon, except in self-defence but engage in humanitarian missions together with the United States and with the UN peacekeeping force. Because of the geopolitical unrest in Asia and the dissatisfaction with Japan's relationship with the U.S., rewriting the constitution became a logical strategy for Abe who advocated for an increase and strengthening of Japan's defence spending (Mochizuki, 2007). Mochizuki (2007) discussed that Japan has shifted away from friendship diplomacy to a mixed strategy that involves both positive engagement and realistic balancing to hedge against the potential threats that China may pose in the future. Furthermore, the 2020 Olympic Games complete Abe's administrative policies as a smart power strategy. By drawing the relationship between the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and Article 9 of Japan's constitution. The findings reveal that the common denominator for what Japan's government under Abe was trying to achieve by attempting to rewrite Article 9 and leading at the front in the bid for Tokyo to become the 2020 Olympic host is global visibility. Global visibility in this case means nation branding, increased tourism, more bilateral and multilateral international and regional relationships, and recognition as a powerful and dominant force in global affairs. Global visibility also means the recognition of Japan as a leader in the affairs of Asian geopolitics. Ilevbare & McPherson (2022) point out that international sports competitions like the Olympic Games are an important vehicle for soft power. Ilevbare & McPherson (2022) discussed that because the Olympic Games is a vehicle

of soft power, it provides the opportunity for digital exposure, culture, tourism and international engagement. However, these factors fall under global visibility and in the case of Japan; it helps to open Japanese society. Therefore, by pointing this out, Japan's smart power strategy is a combination of Abe's administrative policies and the hosting of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

6.5 Japan's sport diplomacy and soft (smart) power strategy a positioning statement in global and regional affairs

This research has discussed the discourse around power in international relations and the relationship between hard and soft power highlighting the thematic areas of understanding the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power strategy through the international, regional, and national level. Second, the geopolitical nature of East Asia, political and cultural power and its impact on Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy from Chapter 5. Concisely, hard power is the exercise of political and sovereign strength through the display of military capabilities and economic stability in the emergence of conflict and dispute. To have power in international politics and relations is the ability to influence the actions of other countries in ways they normally will not act. Hard power is the capacity for a country to coerce another country through military intervention, coercive diplomacy, and economic sanctions to force or impose a national interest (Wilson, 2006). In the case of soft power, Joseph Nye defined the concept of soft power on a domestic level concerning America and that a nation's behaviour at home can enhance its image abroad. Legitimacy, in turn, helps to advance its foreign policy objectives (Nye, 2017). Soft power can be categorised into levels, first on a domestic level that includes culture and political institutions. For example, in terms of political legitimacy, political institutions must uphold the principles of democracy and liberalism. These principles play a huge part in a country's exercise of hard power. In addition, in terms of culture, social

cohesion, quality of life, tolerance, cultural prominence, and abundant opportunities for individuals all create culture (Gallarrotti, 2015).

These factors attract respect and admiration from other countries and in turn, can help boost a country's soft power. Attraction is important for soft power because it draws other countries to accept the demands of the country involved. Therefore, the factor of attraction is the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool that indicates success in Japan's sport diplomacy. In most cases, mega sports events are a tool for expressing a political idea that may push for legitimacy and global acceptance. Literature has discussed the case of China, for example, China's military aggression and accusation of human rights violation, at the same time, China's ability to host mega sports events like the Olympic Games, which possesses huge soft power potential. Literature on soft power and sports mega-events (Guilianotti, 2015; Chen, et al., 2012; Hunter, 2009) have all discussed the 2008 Beijing Olympics Games as a soft power tool for rebranding China's image. However, China is a good example of how a government combines and uses sports as a positioning statement in global affairs to engage with the foreign public in the pursuit of global governance. Therefore, in discussing Japan's sport diplomacy as a positioning statement in global affairs, the data reveals that through the lens of Abe's administration. Japan's sport diplomacy is a positioning statement in global affairs and this, however, entails the Understanding of Japan's political revolution.

6.5.1 Japan's political revolution: Japan's third revolution as a quest for a robust soft (smart) power strategy

In the context of giving a piece of contextual evidence for Japan's soft power strategy. It is important to discuss Japan's political revolution and its relationship to become a major player in global affairs. Japan's modern era has indicated a shift in Japan's foreign and national politics from a remarkable change of three political leadership transitions. The Longest serving prime minister in Japan's history has been Shinzo Abe before Yoshihide Suga took over and

then Fumio Kishida. All three prime ministers could be categorised as post-war prime ministers. Understanding Japan's soft power strategy means understanding how both Domestic, regional, and international aggression helped push Japan into a revolution of foreign policies. Brands (2021) Points out that, all three of Japan's revolutions were a result of an epic geopolitical disruption. The first revolution was after the forced opening of Japan by the West in the 1850s and this resulted in the Meiji restoration and the construction of the modern military and economy that resulted in making Japan a great power that defeated China and Russia in major wars (Fulcher, 1998; Allinson & Anievas, 2010; Norman, 2000). The second revolution happened in the 1930s with the collapse of the world economy forcing a challenge to its objectives in China, which led to Japan indulging in militarism, imperialism, or violent expansion for an economic quest of autarky in Asia that ignited World War Two. However, Japan in the second revolution can be characterised as a wartime country. The third revolution was the devastating defeat in the Second World War and the occupation of the U.S. army in Japan. The third revolution led to Japan's post-war leaders renouncing Japan's independent foreign policy by outsourcing its security to the U.S., allowing for a reconstruction of Japan and a regional development that propelled East Asia into an era of relative stability and peace (Brands, 2021). In this case, Japan's third revolution is the key focus, because it helps to clarify Japan's sport diplomacy and smart power strategy in terms of Japan's military strength and economy. In addition, it clarifies Prime Minister Abe's foreign and national policy intentions of making Japan a first-tier country and identifying where the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

The third revolution is a foundational point for understanding the importance of an effective soft power strategy for Japan. The third revolution signified major changes in Japan's constitution as a sovereign country. One of the major changes is the pacifist nature of Japan's constitution to exercise only a self-defence military because Article 9 of the constitution

renounces war. This means that Japan does not have a proactive military and cannot engage in active military activities except to defend only its territory. Before this section, this research discussed economic and military strength as the primary sources of a sovereign country and of cause the people who elect political leaders to cement the credibility of the state involved as democratic. In the case of Japan, Japan has been focused on harnessing the strength of its human resources through soft power initiatives like the Cool Japan policy since the end of the Second World War (Margolis, 2021). It also includes the export and display of its cultural pride like Anime and Manga and the hosting of mega sports events like the 1964 Olympic Games, the Rugby World Cup in 2019, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the sport for tomorrow program and other international cultural events. This research reveals and argues that while Japan has been successful in engaging its soft power resources, Japan is lacking tremendously in exercising its smart power resources. Therefore, this indicates and leads towards why Japan's sports diplomacy and soft power is a positioning statement in global affairs. Military and economic strength helps to strengthen a country's sovereignty and hard power, akin to the traditional international relations theory on realism and state behaviour.

In the case of Japan, it is important to discuss the elements of its security and economic strength and their relationship to Japan's smart power. This means discussing the importance of Article 9 in Japan's constitution. As discussed in the later sections, a strong military helps a sovereign country protect its citizens from direct threats and maintain peace and security nationally, regionally and internationally. The armed forces serve as the first line of defence against any form of external threat and the last for national civil unrest. Secondly, economic power is an important element for a country to exist because a sovereign country can invest in other forms of power such as military power and some forms of soft power like culture, tourism, and global prestige events. By examining Article 9 of Japan's constitution, this research finds that Japan

is a strong economic power in global affairs; Japan is the third largest economy in the world behind America and China.

Therefore, by investigating Article 9, this research has identified three key findings and how these findings reveal that Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy is a positioning statement in global and regional affairs. The first is that renouncing war indicates an element of soft power if looked at from the lens of the principle of disarmament. The principle of disarmament is a principle that helps to reduce, limit, and abolish weapons; it is used to describe types of weaponry for countries (Panico, 2022). Disarmament, however, means the total abolition of weapons of mass destruction. Nevertheless, the data has pointed out that this has limited Japan's strength to act actively in regional conflicts involving its neighbours. The second is that Article 9 signifies the start of the third revolution in Japan's politics and foreign affairs objectives. Thirdly, article 9 gave birth to Japan's sports diplomacy as a soft power tool and this includes the 1964 Olympic Games that served as a reintroduction of Japan into the international community as a peaceful nation and helped to rebrand Japan as a technological powerhouse at the time. Furthermore, the data and analysis chapter reveal that Article 9 in Japan's constitution has become an expensive section of its foreign policy objectives, especially with the emergence of regional unrest and the rising tensions in East and Southeast Asia. These regional tensions are an indication that Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power a positioning statements in global and regional affairs. Examples of these regional tensions include, East and Southeast Asia experiencing territorial maritime disputes identifying the tensions between China and its neighbours in the East and South China Seas (Andy, 2011) (BA, 2011). Additionally, these wars rank among the world's greatest threats to both economic growth and global security, according to analysts. China sees Taiwan as an indestructible part of its territory and is looking into these conflicts (Lee, 2020). Conversely, North Korea is a nuclear weapons state that is isolated and unpredictable (DeTrani, 2021).

Experts have determined that the most likely potential trigger or the start of large military hostilities are the conflicts in North Korea and Europe in 1914. (Parliament, 2022). Comparably, there is another unsettling confrontation in the South China Sea, where five nations—China, Brunei, Malaysia, the Philippines, and Vietnam—are at odds over marine borders. China is constructing artificial islands in the region, which some believe might be used for military purposes, because of the wars, fisheries, oil, and gas that are at stake (Parliament, 2022). Furthermore, China, Japan, and Taiwan have been engaged in a protracted competing sovereignty dispute over eight uninhabited islands and rocks in the East China Sea. These islands are called the Diaoyu Islands in China, the Tiaoyitai Islands in Taiwan, and the Senkaku Islands in Japan. Japan and China have been unable to agree on a maritime boundary in the East China Sea (Sato, 2020). Furthermore, there are other conflicts such as China and Taiwan relations. That poses a risk of escalating tension between both countries and North Korea where the Korean peninsula has the greatest concentration of armed forces anywhere in the world (Min-Seok, 2020).

These are all serious geographical and regional conflicts of territorial and maritime disputes that pose a risk of serious military escalation. These disputes, however, justify that Article 9 in Japan's constitution must be revisited. Revisiting Article 9 means investigating Abe's policy to re-establish Japan as a forceful presence in international affairs and his policies to stimulate the economy that came to be known as Abenomics. Abe was a prime minister whose goal had always been to redefine Japan's position in East Asia. By attempting to create a more assertive Japan through proactive diplomacy. Japan increased its defence budget by 10% under Abe's leadership, following years of decrease. In 2015, Abe's administration interpreted the constitution to allow Japan's troops to fight overseas for the first time since World War Two (Wright, 2022; Kingston, 2022). However, as a conservative leader, Abe failed to revise pacifist article 9 completely, which caught the attention of Japanese citizens who were worried

about putting troops in harm's way far from home (Sieg, 2019). Japan's conservative government has viewed the Japan-US constitution as a humiliating symbol of defeat but as a break from entanglement in foreign conflicts (Sieg, 2019). A revision of the article would have become a huge symbolic approach for Abe's administration and the conservative party. It would have shaped the way Japan's self-defence force operates and cooperates especially with the US military and other militaries in Asia where the relationship is increasingly tense. Because Japan is progressively challenged by the geostrategic changes in the Asia-Pacific region, a revision of Article 9 seems overdue in the eyes of Abe's administration. Abe has demonstrated that for a country to be proactive and dominant in global affairs, soft power cannot survive on its own and there is a need for an effective combination of both hard and soft power resources (smart power).

In terms of soft power resources, Japan has been active in effectively exercising its soft power resources over the years. For example, the cool Japan policy has been a first-hand soft power resource in Japan's foreign policy and engagement. The Cool Japan campaign highlights the aspect of Japanese culture that appeals to international audiences. Japan's brand strategy, known as the "Cool Japan" approach, attempts to promote Japan's allure and appeal to the global audience. However, the Cool Japan initiative includes Japanese contemporary culture and products such as anime, manga, games, and traditional Japanese cuisine, including Japanese technology. The Cool Japan initiative is aimed at making Japan's cultural industries a driving force for its economic growth that will increase Japan's soft power. It is similar to the industrial policy that helped kick-start Japan's post-war economic evolution. However, from earlier discussions, this research maintains that an over-reliance on soft power resources for foreign policy engagement like in the case of Japan is not efficient for a sovereign country to be active in global affairs. This argument has been justified using several geographical tensions and conflicts in Asia that may clarify the need for a revision of Article 9 by Abe's

administration. Therefore, considering these factors, the data strongly reveal that by examining Abe's administrative policies, its sport diplomacy and soft power is a strategic positioning statement in global and regional affairs.

6.7 How effective was the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool?

The effectiveness of soft power or measurement of soft power is an ongoing debate among scholars as demonstrated in the literature review. This research has investigated and found that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games had the potential to become a major opportunity for Japan to promote its soft power. The Games would have become a platform to display its culture and values to the world. The Olympic Games would have become a great way to give international visitors an experience of Japan through its hospitality, cuisine, culture, welcoming spirit and in general everything Cool Japan. However, the data showed otherwise with the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic that resulted in the postponement and reorganisation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a closed Games with no visitors and fans allowed to travel or attend the Games. For this reason, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games has not entirely been a soft power tool for Japan. Covid-19 hampered the potential of using the Games as a soft power tool and this is because of the absence of tourists, sports tourists, and international visitors and sports fans during the Games.

However, because the findings reveal that before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Japan witnessed a huge tourism boom, it became essential to investigate these findings further. The research carried out by the International Monetary Fund on Japan's tourism boom before the pandemic speaks volumes of the importance of Japan's sport diplomacy in successfully hosting mega sports events and how this event may have contributed to its soft power through tourism.

Fig 7

Source: International Monetary Fund (2020) by Anh Thi Ngoc Nguyen

The information shows that before early 2020 COVID-19, there had been a ten-year surge in foreign visitor numbers in Japan's tourism sector (International Monetary Fund 2020a, 2020b). The number of arrivals almost tripled from 2013 to 2018 to a record 31 million. The key point taken from the data is that there is a high possibility that the huge tourism boom is a result of the combination of the cool Japan initiatives, the bidding to host mega sports events from the period of Korea/Japan 2002 World Cup, the 2019 Rugby World Cup and the continuous bid to host the Olympic Games until the successful bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. By examining these major sports events, the data shows clearly that before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Japan's sport diplomacy was a success that led to success in its soft power because of the boom in tourism as revealed.

Furthermore, it is also important to point out that although the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games may have not been a soft power tool, Japan's sport diplomacy leading up to the win to host the

Games may have been a contributing factor in Japan’s tourism boom from the period of 2013 as seen in the above chart. Because the findings reveal that in normal times, free from Covid-19 the Games would have become more Asian. The above chart reveals that most international visitors come from Japan’s neighbouring countries with China being the highest followed by South Korea. It is also significant to point out that Europe and others, come below others who contribute more to Japan’s inbound tourism.

Fig. 8

Source: International Monetary Fund (2020)

Furthermore, a piece of evidence that casts doubt that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games may not be considered a soft power is seen in the IMF data suggesting that there was a significant drop in tourism global tourism, and this was no different from Japan. This leads to the question of how soft power can be measured. This research argues that it is difficult to measure or know to what extent soft power can become a success, but if examined in the context of sport diplomacy and hosting international sports events like the Olympic Games as a soft power tool,

the success or effectiveness of soft power can be measured in fragmented sectors, for example, the increase in tourism or sports tourism. As a result of investigating, the growth in tourism before, during and after the Olympic Games can help determine to what extent soft power has been effective. Although, it will require quantitative or mixed-method research to get a near-adequate result for such research. However, it is important to note that even though the 2020 Olympic Games may not be a soft power tool. Before the Olympic Games, the adopted chart from the IMF shows that by looking at Japan's inbound tourism, Japan's sports diplomacy has been successful, and this has led to the growth in tourism before the emergence of Covid-19 that affected the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

6.8 Soft disempowerment (national and regional level)

Soft disempowerment is a subtle or direct form of disempowerment that occurs when individuals feel insignificant or inferior in each setting. This can happen in various forms such as exclusion from opportunities or decision-making process. Individuals may also experience discrimination in workplaces based on gender or race. However, an organisation or a community needs to create an inclusive environment, the hosting of mega sports events has come with criticism that includes the displacement of people, trafficking, and underpayment of workers (Preuss, 2004; Maharaj, 2015). Evidence from Nakamura (2018, pp. 5-6) argued that the regions affected by the 3/11 nuclear disaster need to prioritise rebuilding instead of participating in the national Olympic celebration and to the extent that the rural areas were exploited in the bid to justify infrastructural investments around Tokyo to win the bid to host the Games. The findings from my interview with WK, chapter 5 voices from the field described soft power as a fluke concept that there are so many issues facing Japan internally than hosting the Olympic Games. Although, the International Olympic Committees were convinced about public acceptance and Japan's government's confidence that they had resolved the issues

concerning the nuclear disaster and the huge public acceptance before Covid-19 was a good qualification that the Olympic Games was well received by the Japanese. However, given the ambiguity around the results, it is unclear whether or not soft power can be employed through the Olympic Games. The Olympic Games in Tokyo 2020 should be discussed as a vehicle for soft disempowerment considering the advent of Covid-19. It is imperative to consider certain of the concerns covered in the research, such as gender inequality and the low level of public support resulting from the epidemic. This is because the issues surrounding the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games have some echoes of soft disempowerment.

6.8.1 Gender Inequality and Japan's Olympic Committee

Historically, Japan has been a patriarchal society, but there has been progress towards greater gender equality there are gender-based challenges and imbalances in Japan. The glass ceiling women face barriers to advancing to higher-level positions in the workplace (Shirahase, 2014). There is the issue of unequal pay and Japanese women generally earn less than men for doing the same job (Hakim, 2016). Furthermore, it is revealed that women in Japan struggle with their work-life balance with home responsibilities and the traditional gender roles are still expected from most of the household (Broadbent, 2012). In addition, underemployment is also an issue as women are often relegated to non-regular, low-paying jobs with limited opportunities for career growth. While there have been efforts to address these issues with the inclusion of policy change and the promotion of gender equality and women empowerment. There is still much work to be done because the interview data revealed that Japan needs effective global visibility with a need to open its society.

By addressing the social issues in sports, Woods, and Butler (2020) defined sports as a reflection of society. They discussed that sports reflect the values, norms, and cultural beliefs of a society (Woods & Butler, 2020). Sports mirror broader social inequalities, such as gender

and racial disparities. One of the ways that sports reflect a society is through the distribution of resources and opportunities. The allocation of funding and facilities while athletes mirror broader social inequalities for example, women's sports are mostly underfunded and underrepresented in comparison to men's sports, and this reflects a broad social issue of gender inequality. In addition, athletes from ethnic minorities may face unequal opportunities and discrimination in their sport and this reflects a larger racial inequality in the society. All these issues are classified as soft disempowerment. In the context of Japan's Olympic Committee (JOC), it is evident that gender equality has been a long-standing issue within the JOC. Some of the identified challenges are; the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions to make key decisions within committees such as the board of directors. In addition, to the unequal distribution of resources, there have been concerns that male athletes receive more resources and support compared to female athletes. The resistance to change as some of the JOC members have been slow to embrace changes aimed at the promotion of gender equality.

Before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the former Tokyo Olympic boss's sexist remarks fuelled the debate about Japan's gender equality. The former JOC president, Yoshiro Mori 83 years of age said that the increase in women's participation or female representation makes meetings take twice as long and if one raises her hand to speak then all the others feel they need to do the same (Harding, 2021). The findings from the interview revealed prior to Mori's event that Mori is old in the head and that there is no new idea to make plans for the future generation. This is partly because of the conservative nature of Japanese society and the political system. For example, Mori was the former prime minister, and it was said that his contemporary Taro Aso has a long history of making similar comments, but such remarks have not harmed their political careers (Harding, 2021). However, the public criticism reached a point where Mori had to step down as head of the Tokyo 2020. The question is whether this marks a change in Japan's gender equality and if the Olympic Games were pressured by

cooperating sponsors and international opinion for his resignation. In addition, Japan is placed 121st globally by the World Economic Forum in terms of gender equality (GGFR, 2020). There seems to be a problem with the image of gender equality, and these problems are important in Japanese sports.

In terms of soft disempowerment, if the Games were held in normal times with the influx of sports tourists and tourism into Japan. Perhaps the issues of gender equality would have become so significant that the foreign media or social media outlets would have raised alarm on the issues. Because of covid-19, this was not the case, and it would be difficult to understand to what extent this would have affected Japan's image during the Games. After the incident, nevertheless, it seems that the IOC and JOC talked about ways to end abuse and harassment in Japanese sports. The JOC passed laws about the abuse and set up a hotline for consultation to end abusive behaviour in sports. The JOC has trained over 300 elite coaches and staff members in various aspects of integrity and compliance (JOC, 2020).

6.8.2 Low public acceptance before and after the organisation of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

The 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games faced a lot of criticism among this criticism is the cost of hosting the Games which was a major concern to many people because the budget for the event continued to increase over time. The environmental impact of the Olympic Games was an issue, and this included the construction of new facilities and the ecosystem and carbon footprint of the event. In addition, a lack of transparency and criticism in the planning and decision-making process and a lack of accountability for how public funds were being used. The Covid-19 pandemic was a major factor in the low public acceptance because the pandemic led to concerns about the safety of athletes and spectators, as well as the impact of the pandemic on the local economy and community.

The 2020 Summer Olympic Games were originally scheduled to be held in 2020 and were faced with numerous challenges, including low public support because of the covid-19 pandemic. The outbreak of the virus had a significant impact on the world with the worldwide travel restrictions and lockdown. As a result, it was difficult to attend large gatherings including the Olympic Games. The key issue from the pandemic was that the JOC faced the difficult task of ensuring the safety of athletes, spectators, and the local community. In addition, there were concerns that the hosting of the Games would increase the spread of covid-19 cases some felt that it was not appropriate to hold the Games while so many people were still suffering from the pandemic. Kyodo a Japanese news media reported that 35.3 per cent wanted the Games to be cancelled and 44.8 per cent wanted the Games to be postponed (White, 2021).

Because this research investigates the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as soft power. Because the research has identified an ideal soft (smart) power strategy for Japan. The cool Japan initiative and the boom in tourism indicate that Japan is a soft power nation. However, covid-19 pandemic is becoming less logical for the Games to go ahead. Among its citizens, hosting the Olympic Games in the middle of a pandemic became less attractive. Nonetheless, based on information on the country's tourism development, Japan stood to gain leverage from the Olympics by obtaining the right to host the Tokyo 2020 Games. It is now simpler to refer to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as an instrument for soft disempowerment thanks to the rise of Covid-19. Among other soft power goals, the staging of the Games during a pandemic undermines the goal of increasing tourism and effectively redefining Japan's political and national image in the media. It is crucial to note, though, that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, as an instrument for soft power, reflects soft disempowerment more than soft power.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and recommendations

This research investigated Japan's sport diplomacy by examining the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle of soft power. This research has discussed the findings from the data analysis to answer the research question of what an ideal soft power strategy is using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. Secondly, answering the question of, how do we theorise soft power as a concept in international relations using sport diplomacy as a vehicle. This includes key objectives such as identifying an ideal soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. Critically evaluating Japan's sport diplomacy strategy as a positioning statement in global and regional affairs, investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool in Japan's sport diplomacy and investigating the use of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a tool in Japan's soft power strategy.

This research has revealed that an examination of an ideal Japan's soft power strategy stems from an examination through the lens and the strategy of Prime Minister Abe's administrative policies, identified by the research as the neo-realist smart power model. This includes the remilitarisation of Japan's military and Abe's role in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid. Furthermore, an examination of both strategies gives more clarity that the re-interpretation of Japan's constitution and then hosting the Tokyo 2020 Olympics is a strategy to make Japan's soft power and global visibility more effective to become a major global player. Secondly, this research has suggests that, the reason for the under-theorisation of soft power is that most academics who seek to engage the term soft power in the context of international politics, statecraft, diplomacy, and sport diplomacy, do not consider international relations theories that are vital in the field. The three main international relations theories are realism, liberalism, and constructivism. It is important to understand that while the use of concepts is to sometimes

propose a theory, the case of soft power is not different. It is important to consider the relevance of any of the above-mentioned IR theories in any context in which soft power is applied. However, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool. The result from the above Japan's smart power model indicates that the concept of soft (smart) power is similar to the notion of neorealist or structural realism in international relations that sees competition and conflicts as persistent features with limited potential for cooperation.

Furthermore, this research discussed the evolution of diplomacy by differentiating between old or traditional diplomacy and new diplomacy. While old diplomacy focused on hard power resources, new diplomacy focused on soft power resources and this is because of the impact of globalisation, leading to the pluralisation of diplomacy outside traditional diplomacy practices. For example, soft power is a valuable tool for diplomacy because it helps to build relationships and interests between countries without the use of offensive military and economic sanctions. Soft power helps to build relationships and promote cultural exchange through, for example, the use of digital diplomacy and public diplomacy, helping to promote a country's image abroad. Hard power traditionally involves military associations, economic power, and sanctions and, the negotiation of arms control treaties. In most cases, hard power is attributed to war, conflict, and the displacement or destruction of infrastructures.

This research investigated the two phases of sport diplomacy firstly, the hosting of sports events and secondly, the interpretation and impact of sports events by the host country. It was not possible to investigate what impact the Games have made on global rankings yet as that needs a longer timeframe than this research would allow. The first phase of this research depicts that the hosting country could use sport as a diplomatic tool to achieve its national and foreign policy goals. In the second phase, there is the evaluation and assessment of the impact of the sports event, the impact of the media coverage and the assessment of public opinion, infrastructure, and sustainability. However, the success of sport diplomacy or the hosting of

mega sports events depends on both phases and how countries can carefully host and interpret such events for national and international gain. Also, sport diplomacy is the use of sport as a vehicle to achieve foreign policy objectives by promoting cultural exchange, nation branding, and the building of relationships, regionally and internationally.

In Japan's case, the government has promoted sports activity as a vehicle for diplomacy since hosting the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, which was a turning point in Japan's post-war recovery. Japan has actively used mega sports events like the FIFA 2020 World Cup, the 2019 Rugby World Cup and recently, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for its soft power. However, Japan's sport diplomacy includes engaging in international sport development programs like the Sport for Tomorrow programme that was launched in 2014 by Japan's government to promote sports and physical education in developing countries. The key aim of the program includes promoting the values of the Olympic Games through cultural exchanges. Also, to boost Japan's image, and display Japan's commitment to sports and physical education.

Likewise, Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power entail the ability to attract and influence the foreign public through its culture, values, and ideas, rather than military or economic coercion. This research attributes Japan's soft power strategy to Japan's constitutional pacifism found in Article 9 of its constitution that, Japan's military is only for self-defence purposes and not to wage or engage in external war. Another existing soft power strategy is the Cool Japan initiative to promote Japan's culture like anime, manga, video games, fashion, and cuisine. While the Cool Japan initiative has recorded some success, the initiative has received some backlash. The Cool Japan initiative has been criticised for its lack of cultural diversity for focusing heavily on a myopic range of Japanese pop culture's such as anime, manga and J-pop, overlooking other important parts of the Japanese culture. However, this has led to debates that the Cool Japan initiative is shallow and excessively commercial. In addition, the initiative has been

criticised for its lack of impact on Japan's economy. Despite the significant investment from the Japanese government.

Therefore, by investigating the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a soft power tool, this research identified key debates around the concept of soft power. Firstly, this research reveals that while Grix & Brannagan (2016) identified the framework for an ideal soft power, using the case of Germany's 2006 FIFA World Cup and Qatar's 2020 FIFA World Cup, there are growing debates about the under-theorisation of soft power and how different countries sought to wield or leverage mega sports events as a vehicle for soft power. Consequently, this research argued and demonstrated that there is a need for theorising soft power in the context of sport. In doing so, this research adopted a qualitative method of collecting and analysing data by examining Japan's foreign policy document, specifically, Japan's diplomatic blue book, the Japan Olympic bid document from the period 2013 to 2020 and the interview from experts and voices in the field of sport diplomacy and soft power. By adopting this methodological approach, this research has identified key points from the data analysis and discussion.

Contribution to original knowledge

The first contribution is to investigate Japan's sport diplomacy and soft power strategy using the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a case study. This research has identified a neo-realism soft (smart) model drawn from the analysis of Japan's foreign policy and Olympic documents including the data from the analysis of the interview. I identified three major components of Japan's sport diplomacy, which are, linking diplomacy to an international athletic event, the role of technology in presenting a new national image as a nation branding strategy, especially in the Tokyo Olympic Games and Japan's effort to make Japan more internationalist by welcoming visitors to a world-class capital city.

Secondly, the research established and demonstrates that there is a relationship between Japan's pacifist constitution Article 9 to the hosting of mega sports events specifically the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The examination of an ideal soft power strategy stems from an examination of Prime Minister Abe's government policies. This includes the remilitarisation of Japan's constitution and Abe's significant role in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic bid. However, a combination of both strategies becomes a smart power strategy. This portends that for effective soft power, there is a need for an effective application of hard power resources. In terms of proactive hard power resources, Japan has lacked this since 1946 after the Second World War. Therefore, for effective global visibility, soft power resources are not enough and there has to be a combination of both hard and soft power resources.

The third contribution is on the theorisation of soft power as a concept, this research established that the reason for an under-theorisation of soft power is the absence of academic engagement of soft power to key international relations theories such as realism, liberalism, and constructivism. It is important that academics and experts begin to consider the importance of international relations theory in the context of soft power and sport diplomacy. Therefore, Japan's neo-realism smart power model indicates that the concept of soft power is similar to the idea of neorealism or structural realism in international relations, which sees competition and conflict as persistent with limited potential for cooperation. However, the presence of anarchy in the international system means that states are unsure of other states' intentions and their security. Hence, the proposed remilitarisation of Japan's constitution by Prime Minister Abe. In addition, there are case study examples from Russia and China that point out how these countries have effectively leveraged the combination of soft power and hard power resources for national and international pride and relevance. This has led to a developed framework called the neo-realist smart power strategy.

Thesis result

Chart representation

Chart explaining Japan's soft (smart) power model, Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

The Neo-Realist smart power model

Fourthly, this research established that Japan's sport diplomacy has been successful taking into consideration Japan's ability to bid and win as host of the mega sports events like the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, Korea Japan 2020 FIFA World Cup, 2019 Rugby World Cup and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. However, not so much for its soft power because of the

emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic and the national and worldwide lockdown restricting tourists and sports fans from attending the Games. Therefore, arguing that Japan did not meet its full potential of using the Games as a soft power tool. In contrast, I also established that before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Japan had seen an increase in its tourism with further investigation from the International Monetary Funds that Japan's tourism had witnessed a boom in the number of international tourists over the past decade from the period of 2013 to 2018. A key point from the data is that there is a high possibility that the huge tourism boom is a result of the combination of the Cool Japan initiative and the consistent bidding to host mega events until the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The data however indicates a possibility of the success of not only sport diplomacy but also Japan's soft power.

Finally, soft disempowerment and low public acceptance are issues revealed from the research because of the Covid-19 pandemic. For example, there are arguments that the 3/11 nuclear disaster needed to be prioritised instead of participating in the national Olympic celebration. Another example is, before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the former Tokyo Olympic boss's sexist remarks fuelled the debate about Japan's gender equality. The former JOC president, Yoshiro Mori 83 years of age said that the increase in women's participation or female representation makes meetings take twice as long and if one raises her hand to speak then all the others feel they need to do the same (Harding, 2021). The hosting of the Olympic Games in the middle of the pandemic defeats the purpose of tourism and effective media representation of Japan's national and political image and other soft power objectives. Therefore, this research established that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for Japan's soft power has more of an echo of soft disempowerment than soft power at least on a national level at this time. Perhaps the long-lasting impact may change.

Recommendations and implication for future research

What is interesting about this research is the cross-over between the quest for international political awareness, for example, Japan's foreign policy aligning with the need to satisfy home sport diplomacy goals. From the literature review, data collection and analysis, it is clear that there is a need for recommendations and a rethink about how sport diplomacy as a vehicle for soft power is discussed, how we identify an ideal soft power and the application of soft power as a concept in the mix. Firstly, I will lay out my key contribution in two categories. The first is the investigation of an ideal soft power by a host nation and the second is the theorisation of soft power.

Because of the debates around soft power as under-theorised or vague. I recommend that it is important for academics and practitioners to understand the concept of soft power from the lens of state behaviour and not just in terms of national branding, public diplomacy, or cultural diplomacy, which are all soft power or new forms of diplomacy practices. By doing so, scholars can begin to understand the state's projection and behaviour in using mega sports events as a vehicle for soft power. For example, reflecting Nye's discussion of soft power; In Nye's article, *soft power: The Means to Success in world politics*, he discussed that soft power is not a normative concept, meaning that soft power is a non-normative political concept in that it is used to describe the way the political system works, the behaviour of political actors and the outcomes of political processes. This contrasts with normative concepts that are used to evaluate how the political system should work or how political actors should behave. Therefore, asserting that soft power was only one concept of power and rarely sufficient by itself (Nye, 2004) (Nye, 2017). This is why I recommend the theoretical discussion of the relationship between soft power and international relations theories in the context of sports

diplomacy as a vehicle for soft power. Mainly as the growing trend revolves around awarding the hosting of mega sports events to so-called illiberal nations like Russia, China, and Qatar.

Secondly, Grix & Brannagan, (2016) layered the foundation by providing a framework for identifying an ideal soft power using the case of Germany's 2006 FIFA World Cup and Qatar's 2020 FIFA World Cup. This research has drawn from that framework and taken it to a different dimension by developing a neo-realist smart power model in the context of Japan's sport diplomacy as a vehicle for its soft power and looking at the crossover of international politics and domestic sport diplomacy. This neo-realist smart power model has a positive impact on future research as it can shape the way sport diplomacy as a soft power tool can be researched and this is cross-sectional with the identification of an ideal soft power strategy by a country. This smart power model will provide and direct future research in sport diplomacy as a soft power on how to investigate host countries' behaviour and their reason for projecting themselves through mega sports events.

General recommendation

This research has revealed that Japan has a positive history of using sport as a tool for diplomacy from the Meiji Restoration to the 1964 Tokyo Olympics, and the 2019 Rugby World Cup. Sports have also played an important role in Japan's foreign relations. There are several things to recommend from what the data has revealed from Japan's sport diplomacy. Firstly, by analysing section three of Japan's diplomatic blue book that talks about the promotion of sport and culture. It is clear that Japan need to increase funding for grassroots sport programs, and this will help, give everyone in Japan the opportunity to participate in sport, regardless of social status or background. Also, Japan needs to invest in sending more athletes to international competitions as this will help boost the soft power profile on the world stage. Secondly, there is a need for Japan to use sports to promote gender equality, the Japanese

government can use sports for gender equality by organising events and initiatives that encourage girls and women to participate in sports as this is an issue that is not heavily addressed in its documents.

Finally, the emergence of Covid-19 which led to the postponement of the Games and a decline in the national public support of the Games indicates the need for new public value management in the context of hosting mega sports events. public value management is an approach to public management that focuses on creating value for the public. It is based on the notion that the institutions, public or private should be managed in a way that meets the needs of citizens and society. Secondly, Public value management is a novel approach to public management, and this is because of the recognition that traditional approaches to public management have not been successful. However, the impact of covid-19 on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games indicates that there is a need for a rethink around the importance of hosting mega sports events like the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and the values of the Games in the middle of crisis. The issue of covid-19 and its impact on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games indicates that the International Olympic Committee and the National Olympic Committee need to take into consideration the four key elements of public value management.

The first is to identify the public value that the Games are trying to create, and this involves the needs of citizens and society. The second is to assess the performance after the public value has been identified. The IOC need to assess its performance in terms of creating effective value through sports. This involves measuring the outputs, outcomes and impacts of the sports activity in terms of crisis. Thirdly, there is a need to manage the value of the Olympic Games because public value management and mega sports event are not just about measuring performance, it is also about managing the value of the sports event which was almost lacking in the middle of the covid-19 pandemic. Finally, there is a need to effectively communicate the value and importance that the sports events will create for its citizens and stakeholders as this

is something that was an issue between the International Olympic Committee, Japan Olympic Committee, and the public. Therefore, there is a need for a rethink and articulation from sports administrators and sports bodies particularly the International and National Olympic Committees of the importance of hosting mega sports events at a time when there are debates around the expense of hosting, issues of climate change and environment sustainability and the long-term impact of the post Games. It appears that national country-level sports organisations need a rethink the value they provide aside from sports performance and the monetary value of the Games if they are to continue to justify the spend attributed to them based on sports diplomacy. These issues need to be considered moving forward in the context of sports diplomacy as a soft power tool. Therefore, in the context of sport diplomacy and a soft power tool, I will end with a quote from Nye's (2017);

'I have come to realise that concepts such as soft power are like children. As an academic or a public intellectual, you can love and discipline them when they are young, but as they grow, they wander off and make new company, both good and bad. There is not much you can do about it, even if you were present at the creation. As the Princeton political scientist, Baldwin (2016) has recently written, "Nye's discussion of soft power stimulated and clarified the thoughts of policymakers and scholars alike—even those who misunderstood or disagree with his views". Perhaps that is all one can hope for'. (Nye, 2017, p. 3) ...

Further research

After conducting this extensive research, publishing two articles from it, and presenting at conferences where I had the opportunity to display my multidisciplinary research ideas in sport diplomacy, international relations, international law, and security studies, I plan to look for further publications in the areas of sport diplomacy. But specifically, around the role of sport diplomacy on African developments in the context of investigating state's behaviours in the context of hosting and participating in mega sports events. Over the past four years, I have read and examined the literature on sport diplomacy and soft power, and I have carefully observed

the lack of research materials around case studies on sport diplomacy and soft power in Africa, with the most common case study being South Africa. This signifies that sport diplomacy and soft power are an area that is still new and under-researched in the context of Africa. The impact of sport diplomacy on African foreign policy with other continents. Although, the term Africa is broad, my future research will be looking at specific case studies of African countries looking or in need of using sports as a soft power tool. This will go some way to continuing to contribute to the theory around international sport diplomacy. Thereby, contributing specifically and immensely to the field of sport diplomacy.

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Appendix

Code book 1

PhD dissertation

This codebook contains the code/themes from documents, interview and online media contents framed with the help of NVivo. It contains a brief and selected description associated with the code, including the number of files and references.

Nodes

Name	Description	Files	References
Asian geopolitics, Tokyo 2020, leverage for soft power	<p>This code includes Japan's foreign engagement with other countries and international aid and support initiatives. For example, 'In East Asian region, Japan has a close relationship with the region in all aspects including politics, economy, and culture that is stated to have great significance in the safety and prosperity of Japan. Japan's assistance in the East Asian region is approximately 50% of the bilateral office for Development Assistance (ODA) of Japan'. Japan proactively takes part in the discussion based on the principle of human security and demonstrate the country's strong points such as health and disaster risk reduction to build a framework with emerging countries, NGOs and the private sector.</p> <p>Secondly in terms of the narrative surrounding the importance of the Olympic Games in Tokyo and its position in Asia. The growing concerns over China's geopolitical ambitions, human right record and the threat to boycott the Beijing 2022 Games is set to be an opportunity for Japan to take advantage of its soft power growth using the Olympics. For example 'From Techno nationalism to Superficial Environmentalism: Japan's Olympics as a Political Tool A political Olympic Games may appear contradictory, due to an official statement from the International Olympic Committee, claiming the political neutrality of the Games. Previous Olympics such as Berlin 1936 and London 1948 were tied to propaganda, war, and political showmanship. However, throughout the 20th century, the Olympics have come to symbolise peace, diplomacy,</p>	12	39

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>internationalism, and represent political power. Tokyo 1964 and Tokyo 2020 serve as powerful examples of the political potentiality of the Olympics, and powerful comparisons on the continued benefit of the Olympics in Japan. Throughout the 1964 Games, and in the current run-up to the 2020 Games, Japan has exerted and gained political power through several similar processes. Rather than looking at the rather obvious winning of events to show national strength’.</p>		
Sport for tomorrow	<p>From Japans diplomatic blue book this code includes for example</p> <p>‘At the International Olympic Committee (IOC) Session held in September 2013 (Buenos Aires, Argentina) when the decision was made to hold the 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games in Tokyo, Prime Minister Abe announced the launch of the Sport for Tomorrow (SFT) program in Japan as a program for contributing internationally through sports’. Japans ministry of foreign affairs (MOFA) has consistently undertaken various initiatives through international exchanges in the field of sports, such as Japanese martial arts (“budo”), to raise awareness and enhance understanding of Japan as well as to create a sense of affinity with Japan among many people in the world. Sports play an important role in promoting mutual understanding and facilitating international exchange that transcends borders, languages, and race. Together with the public, efforts are made to bring international exchange through sports to deliver the value of sports to the world from Japan even after the Olympic and Paralympic Games Tokyo 2020.</p> <p>For example ‘Voices from SFT participants From Tanzania Support for the development of baseball grounds, provided through Japan’s Grant Assistance For Cultural Grassroots Project (GCGP), not only benefits baseball players in Tanzania but also all the citizens of Tanzania. Japan has introduced baseball to Tanzania as a new sporting activity. We are considering the introduction of baseball into the education curriculum of all elementary and junior high schools in Tanzania’.</p>	1	6

Name	Description	Files	References
<p>The effective nature of Japan's foreign policy soft power strategy, sport diplomacy and the promotion of national and global interest.</p>	<p>Japan's foreign policy and relationship with the international community includes matters of peace and security, economic diplomacy, culture sports and Tourism. For example, taken from Japan's diplomatic blue book and a quote from the prime minister. 'I will continue to take further steps with a particular focus on six policy areas: (1) further strengthening of the Japan-U.S. Alliance, the cornerstone of Japan's foreign policy. (2) tackling outstanding issues of concern regarding North Korea, (3) advancing diplomacy with neighbouring countries, such as China, the Republic of Korea, and Russia, (4) addressing the increasingly tense situation in the Middle East. (5) Engaging in economic diplomacy in which Japan will lead efforts to establish new common rules, and (6) addressing global issues. Japan aspires to ensure its national interests in the political, security, and economic domains, as well as to maintain and develop a desirable international order that is based on universal values such as freedom, democracy, human rights, and the rule of law. To this end, Japan needs to pursue strategic diplomacy, while rationally accounting for and adapting to changes in the international situation.</p> <p>For example,</p> <p>'Efforts to Promote Understanding and Trust in Japan</p> <p>1 Strategic Communications</p> <p>(1) Initiatives in Strategic Communications The Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA) is implementing strategic communications based on the three-pillar approach of (1) making further efforts to disseminate Japan's policies and initiatives, including the accurate image of Japan. (2) sharing Japan's rich and varied attractiveness, and (3) expanding the circle of people with a great affinity toward or knowledge of Japan, while enhancing the capabilities of its overseas missions, which are on the frontlines of public diplomacy. Regarding pillar (1), MOFA focuses mainly on promoting public understanding of Japan's</p>	8	42

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>contributions to peace, stability, and prosperity in the international community, and the maintenance and strengthening of the international order based on the rule of law, as well as on enhancing public awareness of issues concerning the recognition of history and the maintenance of territorial integrity. Specifically, MOFA is actively communicating Japan’s position and viewpoints through opportunities such as daily press conferences, interviews, contributions of articles, and speeches at official visits to foreign countries and international conferences by the Prime Minister, the Foreign Minister, and other government officials. Japan’s diplomatic missions overseas are also actively communicating with the Governments of assigned countries and their citizen’.</p> <p>(2) Cultural, Sports, and Tourism Diplomacy</p> <p>‘Overview For a very large number of foreign nationals who develop an interest in Japan, Japanese culture is a motive for their interests. MOFA and the JF carry out various projects ranging from introducing Japanese culture and sports to promoting inbound tourism. Aimed at creating positive images of Japan abroad, boosting the overall Japanese brand, and encouraging a deeper understanding of Japan, as well as fostering the circle of people with a great affinity toward or knowledge of Japan and increasing the number of foreign visitors to Japan. For example, diplomatic missions overseas organize “Cultural Projects of Diplomatic Missions Overseas” that introduces a wide range of Japanese culture, from traditional arts such as the tea ceremony and flower arrangement to aspects of modern culture such as anime, manga, and fashion’.</p>		
Tokyo Olympics Cool Japan and soft power	This code falls under the narratives asking questions if Tokyo’s soft power push can ensure a positive Olympic legacy different from the Tokyo 1964 Olympics. For example, “We will have to see how the games roll out, but I believe the key phrase is human legacy,” said Makoto Hamaoka, a senior researcher at Mitsubishi Research Institute.	6	10

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>While Japan has hosted past games, including the 1964 Olympics and 1998 Nagano Winter Olympics, left tangible legacies in terms of infrastructure, a mature city like Tokyo should be aiming to address social and environmental issues and embrace diversity to boost the nation’s welcoming image, he said, an aspect that was played up in the 2012 London Olympics.</p> <p>“Human resources are increasingly important in a greying and shrinking population, and this should be an occasion where the nation shows how it can host an inclusive, accessible and sustainable event,” he said.</p> <p>Also, other examples with relations to this code include</p> <p>“Japan’s other weird, more esoteric manga characters may have also been considered, such as Burnt Bread (Kogepan), Afro Ken (the dog with the rainbow afro), and some other Sanrio characters such as Badtz-Maru (a penguin), Two Little Stars or My Melody (a rabbit). I think we’re all feeling luckier by the minute that Doraemon was chosen.</p> <p>However, I suspect it was a close feline race and that we narrowly missed having to endure a Hello Kitty Olympics. With Kitty-chan’s worldwide appeal, with over 50,000 of her products sold in more than 60 countries, it would have been tough for this entrepreneurial feline to lose out to Doraemon. Hello, Kitty is worldlier, and more instantly recognizable. However, she appeals largely to women and girls because she represents innocence and childhood. She cashes in on nostalgia by older women and mothers who want a safe, trusting and loving childhood for their own children. Furthermore, Hello Kitty has both English and Japanese parentage and actually lives in London. And she is not very sporty either. Her hobbies are reading, music, travelling and eating homemade cookies. Not exactly an Olympic image. Besides, she has no smile”.</p> <p>Also, discussions were linking the cancellation of the Olympic Games to boosting Japans soft power. For example “Swift Olympic cancellation will boost Japan's soft power</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>On March 3, in response to the yearlong #KuToo protest against employers forcing working women to follow impractical dress codes, like mandatory high heels, Prime Minister Shinzo Abe said that this should not be allowed.</p> <p>But he added that it was difficult for the government to make a final decision since private companies had their own rules on the high heels policy. It would require further discussion with all the parties involved.</p> <p>Sound familiar? Abe hedging his bets here mirrors a problem as uncomfortable as a tightfitting stiletto: a final decision on whether to hold the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.</p> <p>Given the spread of the coronavirus and reactive global lockdowns, it is not now a matter of if the Olympics will be cancelled but when. Abe needs to get ahead of the situation by announcing the cancellation or risk dawdling further and diminishing Japan's immense soft power''.</p> <p>''How Abe handles the final decision and announcement and its cascading consequences will reflect on Japan's leadership in future global matters and its preeminent soft power.</p> <p>In fact, Monocle magazine named Japan it's number one soft-power country in 2020 for everything from tackling rural depopulation and the management of an ageing society to service industry excellence and emergency preparedness.</p> <p>What can Japan do now to preserve its goodwill? It could fully embrace the Olympic spirit of competition and celebration but in a new worldwide exchange program of ideas and solutions for relief and recovery, marshalling Japan's global reputation. The Japanese government has shown a strong commitment to the U.N.'s 2030 Sustainable Development Goals; these goals did not evaporate with the arrival of COVID-19''. - Dr Nancy Snow is Pax Mundi (World Peace) Professor of Public Diplomacy at Kyoto University of Foreign Studies.</p>		
Cultural and Economic Impact	For this code, there are several discussions indications of the cultural and economic impact of the Tokyo Olympics. For example, ''In June, 2013, the bid committee announced the results of their preliminary calculations: an economic ripple effect	32	78

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>of 3 trillion yen, and employment creation for 150,000 people. Now that the results of the bidding have been decided, estimates of private research institutions show far higher figures. The economic effects of holding the Olympic and Paralympic Games span quite a wide range of industries, including, but not limited to, the development of facilities such as stadiums and athlete villages, as well as urban infrastructure, amplification of consumer spending accompanying the hosting of the Olympics and Paralympics, and an increase in travellers from overseas”.</p> <p>“For the 1964 Olympics, Tokyo completely changed the framework of the city. Considering the capital that was invested into improving the grounds and transportation infrastructure, investments including hosting expenses and related industries, as well as consumer spending induced by hosting the Olympics, the previous Tokyo Olympic Games also brought about an immense economic effect. After that, Japan achieved a level of economic growth so high, it surprised the world. Though we cannot say that that was a direct result of the Olympics. There is no mistaking that social capital such as the Tokaido Shinkansen, which was established with the goal of opening for business on October 1st, 1964, just before the opening ceremonies, as well as the Shuto Expressway, which had been rapidly completed around that time, supported Japan’s economic development thereafter”.</p> <p>Other quotes relating to the cultural and economic impact of the Games include.</p> <p>“Tokyo, Having Strengthened Cultural Activities for its Olympic Bid. In fact, Tokyo had reinforced its cultural projects leading up to its bid for the Olympics. In August 2005, former Governor Ishihara announced the bid for the 2016 Olympics and decided to establish Tokyo Council for the Arts in the following year. The Olympic cultural program was even discussed at the first council held in March 2007 (with KMK Chairman Yoshiharu Fukuhara as chairman)”.</p> <p>“The government has set a target of attracting 40 million foreign tourists and having them spend ¥8 trillion. During the Olympics alone, as many as 10 million visitors are expected to arrive, meaning sports fans could be facing a room shortage in the capital. To accommodate the linguistic needs of</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>international visitors, the travel sector has been working to provide signs and directions in English, Chinese and other languages while improving the accuracy of existing foreign language signage found in towns and cities”.</p> <p>“Cancelling Olympics would reduce Japan's GDP by 1.4%, study says If the spread of the new coronavirus forces the cancellation of the Olympics, it will reduce Japan annual gross domestic product by 1.4 per cent, a securities firm estimates. In a report Friday, SMBC Nikko Securities Inc. projects the sporting extravaganza will create ¥670 billion (\$6.4 billion) in consumer demand and that cancelling it will sap about ¥7.8 trillion from GDP”.</p> <p>“If you’re still wondering why Tokyo should even want the 2020 Summer Olympics, and why the international business community and companies like Toyota, and a debt-ridden government would be in favour of such a financial endeavour, consider this. We all know that Japan is suffering from a shrinking population. If you can’t increase your population on your own, the next best thing is to invite a few hundred thousand people to come and spend their money. It is called “population borrowing.”</p> <p>“Japanese economy would take ¥2.4 trillion hits with no spectators for Olympics Holding the Tokyo Olympics and Paralympics without spectators would result in an economic loss of up to ¥2.4 trillion in Japan, said Katsuhiro Miyamoto, an honorary professor at Kansai University. According to his estimates released Friday, holding the Tokyo Games behind closed doors would cause a loss of ¥381.3 billion in spending related directly to the games, or 90% of the original projection for the events. Because of people’s waning enthusiasm for the quadrennial sporting events, stimulus effects on household consumption expenditures will halve to ¥280.8 billion and corporate marketing activities will be dampened. Economic gains from promotional sporting and cultural events after the games will also be reduced by half to ¥851.4 billion. Any move to limit or ban spectators would also lead to weaker tourism demand and fewer business opportunities”.</p> <p>“Economic hit</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>Most of the domestic spending on the Olympics has been done, so a cancellation would have minimal effect in that regard, economists said.</p> <p>A Bank of Japan study in 2016 estimated games-related spending would peak at 0.6 per cent of gross domestic product (GDP) in 2018 and be less than 0.2 per cent of GDP in 2020, research consultancy Capital Economics noted.</p> <p>Tourism, a major contributor to recent Japanese growth, could take a hit, although economists said the greater threat was from the coronavirus spread itself’.</p> <p>Last year, Japan hosted 31.9 million foreign visitors, who spent nearly 4.81 trillion yen (\$43.1bn).</p> <p>Nomura Securities had a forecast consumption of 240 billion yen (\$2.22bn) from event-related tourism in 2020, which it said would evaporate if the Olympics were cancelled.</p>		
Emerging difficulties for Japan and the Tokyo Games	<p>Geographically, The security environment surrounding Japan is becoming increasingly severe. In addition to the threats posed by weapons of mass destruction and ballistic missiles, new threats such as cyber-attacks are emerging. While the change in the global power balance provides opportunities for security cooperation in the Asia-Pacific region, it has also given rise to many regional issues and tensions. In order to respond to such security issues,</p> <p>defend its territorial integrity, protect the lives and property of Japanese people, as well as to ensure peace, stability, and prosperity of the international community, Japan will contribute even more proactively to the peace and stability of the region and international community from the policy of “Proactive Contribution to Peace” based on the principle of international cooperation.</p> <p>While Japan has measures in place including political and public support. for example “Japan, a Parliamentary Democracy, has a population of approximately 128 million, with 13 million in the City of Tokyo and 36 million in the Greater Tokyo Area. Japan has the third-largest economy in the world, which grew by approximately 2% in 2012. For the period 2013-2016, the Economist Intelligence Unit projects an average annual growth rate in the range</p>	31	72

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>of 1% to 2% (as of April 2013). The International Monetary Fund shows a nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of USD 5,964 billion (2012) and a nominal GDP per capita of USD 47,000 (2012). The Commission is confident that the Japanese economy would be able to support the necessary infrastructure development needed for the delivery of the Games”. In terms of hosting, the Games there are emerging threats facing Japan as the Olympic host. For example, the 2020 Olympics: Canada and Australia will not send athletes to Tokyo. Both countries' Olympic committees also are calling for the Games to be postponed until 2021. "While we recognize the inherent complexities around a postponement, nothing is more important than the health and safety of our athletes and the world community," the Canadian Olympic Committee and Canadian Paralympic Committee said in a joint statement Sunday. "This is not solely about athlete health -- it is about public health." The Australian Olympic Committee's executive board met by teleconference Monday and unanimously agreed that an Australian Olympic team could not be assembled given the changing circumstances across the world, the committee said in a statement. The committee also said, "our athletes now need to prioritise their own health and of those around them, and to be able to return to the families." "It's clear the Games can't be held in July," said Ian Chesterman, Australian Team Chef de Mission for Tokyo. "Our athletes have been magnificent in their positive attitude to training and preparing, but the stress and uncertainty have been extremely challenging for them." Australian Olympic Committee CEO Matt Carroll said athletes should prepare for the Tokyo Olympics in 2021’.</p> <p>Other related narrative includes,</p> <p>“Decision on holding Tokyo Olympics ‘could go either way,’ says Kono</p> <p>The delayed Tokyo Olympics may not go ahead this summer as planned as the COVID-19 pandemic rages, a Japanese cabinet minister said on Thursday, saying the host needs to be ready for anything.</p> <p>"We need to do the best we can to prepare for the games at this moment, but it could go either way," Taro Kono, administrative and regulatory reform</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>minister, said in an interview at the Reuters Next conference.</p> <p>A global COVID-19 resurgence, including record infection levels in Japan, has raised fresh doubts about the games, which were postponed by one year in 2020’.</p> <p>‘For weeks, Japanese and Olympic officials have insisted that the games will go forward and that a further delay is not possible. Organizers have been trying to come up with plans to hold the games in a manner acceptable to the Japanese public, announcing an array of safety measures.</p> <p>But polls show an increasing wariness. In a survey this month, NHK found that nearly 80% of respondents believed the games should be postponed or cancelled. In October, less than half of the respondents said that. The figure rose to 71% in December’.</p> <p>Norway's Olympic body asks IOC to postpone Tokyo Games until pandemic ends ‘GENEVA – Norway’s Olympic committee said Friday it has asked the International Olympic Committee not to hold this summer’s Tokyo Games until the coronavirus pandemic is under control.</p> <p>The Norwegian Olympic and Paralympic Committee made the request in a letter to IOC President Thomas Bach after discussions with individual sports governing bodies in the country, it said. Calls from athletes and sports officials for the postponement of the games have mounted in recent days, adding pressure on the IOC, Tokyo organizers and the Japanese government, who have insisted that they plan to hold the games as scheduled’.</p>		
Pandemic and Tokyo Games	<p>This Code highlights the discussions surrounding the impact of the coronavirus on the Tokyo 2020 Olympics. For example,</p> <p>‘‘2020 Olympics: Postponing games is a 'realistic option,' organizers say</p> <p>< Committee President Yoshiro Mori conceded that although the preference is to host the spectacle as normal in July, organizers would work alongside the International Olympic Committee (IOC) to explore alternatives amid the novel coronavirus outbreak.</p>	29	64

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>"Postponement isn't our first course of action but we cannot consider it as a realistic option either," Mori said in a news conference Monday, ruling out the idea of cancelling the event entirely.</p> <p>It comes after the IOC executive board said Sunday it is considering postponing this summer's Games and has given itself a four-week deadline to make a decision.</p> <p>Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe also said a decision to postpone may be needed if the Games cannot be held in a complete form”.</p> <p>KUALA LUMPUR – “In 1906, preparations for the 1908 Olympics were underway in Rome when Mount Vesuvius erupted and devastated Naples. The Italians, already strapped for funds to build Olympic venues, used the disaster as an excuse to back out of their commitment. The International Olympic Committee (IOC) did not miss a beat: In November 1906 — a mere 15 months before the opening ceremonies — London was selected as a replacement and held the games on time. Among other feats, the city built the first dedicated Olympic Stadium.</p> <p>In 2020, the new coronavirus is a much graver threat to the Olympics than any volcano. Cases are spreading across Japan, qualifying events are being cancelled, and countries around the world are cutting off travel to the country. With three weeks until the start of the torch relay, and five months until the opening ceremonies, the future of the 2020 Summer Games is less certain than any Olympics in decades. The IOC and Tokyo organizers recently told the news media that there is no “Plan B.” But even if Tokyo 2020 proceeds as originally planned, future games probably won’t. The coronavirus could change the Olympics in ways that may make them safer but certainly less appealing to athletes, spectators and commercial sponsors”.</p> <p>“In one sense, disease outbreaks are just another manageable, albeit dangerous, risk. The 2002 Winter Olympics in Salt Lake City experienced a flu outbreak; measles was imported during the 2010 Vancouver Winter Games; norovirus swept through Pyeongchang. Tokyo 2020’s organizers, too, have prepared for a range of risks, including an</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>earthquake (judged the greatest threat), terrorism, and a range of endemic and imported known diseases, including measles, rubella, dengue and sexually transmitted infections. None are welcome, but if handled properly — and protocols exist — they would not derail the games.</p> <p>An emergent pandemic, however, presents a different set of issues. Unlike an outbreak of flu or measles, a pandemic by its very definition is not just local. If Japan is successful in containing the coronavirus (and it is a long way from that), other countries might not be — at least, not in time for July’s opening ceremonies. Regional outbreaks are already interfering with training and Olympic qualification events; they’ll also have the knock-on effect of deterring travel by spectators and some commercial partners. Even if a replacement site existed for the 2020 games, it would face the same challenges as Tokyo. There is no repeating 1908 in 2020; the games are just too complex, expensive and global.</p> <p>This probably won’t be the last time that the Olympics face this scenario. For years, scientists have observed that pandemics are growing with frequency. It was only a matter of time before one threatened to cancel the games (in fact, zika virus nearly derailed the 2016 Rio Games, and SARS hung over Athens 2004).</p> <p>Now that it has happened, the lack of a Plan B doesn’t just pose problems for Tokyo 2020. It calls into question the economic, political and athletic viability of the games in their current form. Already, the IOC struggles to find cities willing to compete for the right to spend billions hosting the games. Tokyo’s troubles will make that quest even harder. Likewise, marketing and broadcast partners will face questions about the value of their years-long, multimillion- and billion-dollar investments in a vulnerable short-term event’.</p> <p>Tokyo Olympic CEO says games to be a symbol of solidarity</p> <p>“The CEO of the Tokyo Olympic organizing committee believes this year's Summer Games can be a symbol of solidarity that will help reduce the emotional distance between people who have been</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>struggling with loneliness and anxiety in a "dark and sombre time" caused by the novel coronavirus.</p> <p>In a recent interview with Kyodo News, Toshiro Muto said the value of staging the Tokyo Games has changed significantly since the virus swept the world and forced people to isolate or change their lifestyles to minimize the risk of infections without knowing when the pandemic will come to an end.</p> <p>Toshiro Muto, CEO of the Tokyo Olympic and Paralympic organizing committee, gives an interview in Tokyo on March 5, 2021. (Kyodo)</p> <p>"Before the outbreak of the virus, I think people would have understood if I explained the merits of the Olympics, but we are now in a serious crisis that may only happen once in several centuries," he said.</p> <p>"If we were to talk about the Olympics during these times, I've acknowledged that discussions would have to be held on a completely different level."</p> <p>The Olympics have promoted peace and the wellbeing of individuals for many years. He suggested that a successful Tokyo Games can be an inspiration during this challenging period and contribute to bringing people together mentally, if not physically. "If we want to create solidarity instead of division, it can be done through the Olympics. Everyone knows that sports have the power to change the world," the 77-year-old said. "It depends on the efforts put forth by Japanese people to make the most of the chance."</p>		
Games bid, Catalyst for development and reconstruction	<p>This code falls under every discussion that relates to the games bid and hosting while recognising the games as a tool for reconstruction and development. For example,</p> <p>“Tokyo made its pitch well. It has held three Olympics (one summer and two winter), so there's no question of whether Japan can handle it. Its bid motto was: a safe pair of hands. But there were questions about whether Japan could hold its Games with verve and passion.</p> <p>"Previous Tokyo bids had been praised for their competence but criticised for lacking passion. That was not an accusation that could be levelled at them this time, with the urbane Princess Takamodo breaking with royal protocol to travel to Buenos Aires and lobby on behalf of the bid, and Mami Sato</p>	44	107

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>– a Paralympic athlete who saw her hometown devastated by the [2011] tsunami – delivering poise and passion," writes The Guardian, a British newspaper.</p> <p>Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe also emphasized a point that made the London 2012 Games such a notable success. Just as London organizers promised to make their Games a gift to the world rather than primarily a statement of British patriotism, Mr. Abe noted that the 2020 Games would be Japan's way of thanking the world for the help it gave Japan after the 2011 tsunami'’.</p> <p>2020 Olympics: Why did Tokyo win the Summer Games?</p> <p>For the International Olympic Committee, it came down to a matter of Tokyo's "safe hands."</p> <p>The choice for the 2020 Summer Olympics came down to Istanbul, Madrid, and Tokyo, and among that trio, the situation at Japan's Fukushima nuclear power plant turned out to be the least of the IOC's concerns.</p> <p>Istanbul is the city beset by recent civil disorder, with critics accusing the Turkish prime minister of autocratic tendencies. It also sits just north of the brutal civil war in Syria.</p> <p>Madrid is the capital of a nation that could become the next Greece – a country that spent itself into financial crisis, partly by overspending on its own Olympics. This, as protesters in Brazil, takes to the streets to protest government spending for the 2014 World Cup and the 2016 Summer Olympics.</p> <p>The IOC is an organization that does not like bad press. It sometimes goes to almost absurd lengths to try to ensure that the Olympic movement is suffused only in a rosy glow. So when the IOC chose Tokyo over Istanbul, 60-36, in the final round of voting in its meeting in Buenos Aires Saturday, it was a signal that the committee wanted to make sure the drama in 2020 was all of the right sorts.</p> <p>“There you have one candidature addressing more the sense of tradition and stability and another candidature addresses the longing for new shores," Thomas Bach, an IOC member from Germany, told Around the Rings, a website that covers the Olympic</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>movement. "This we have seen in the past also with different bids and this time the IOC members – in a fragile world – have decided in favor of tradition and stability."</p> <p>2020 Tokyo Olympic Games can't rescue Japan</p> <p>HONOLULU, HAWAII – “In the run-up to the 1964 Tokyo Olympics, Gov. Ryotaro Azuma called the games an opportunity to build a new Tokyo and a new Japan. Azuma’s vision materialized with resounding success. For postwar Japan, the games were a watershed moment, transforming Tokyo’s infrastructure and reconstructing the nation’s identity. We should not expect a repeat performance in 2020. When the Olympic flame returns to Tokyo next summer, expectations will be high for the event to once again transform the city and the country. Organizers want the games to “change the future of Japan.” Prime Minister Shinzo Abe sees the Olympics as “vitalizing ... the whole of Japan.”</p> <p>The goals are bold. With plans for robots, automated fuel-cell cars and man-made meteor showers, the games will likely live up to organizers’ promise of being the</p> <p>“Most innovative in history.” But the event will do little to affect the kind of dramatic change leaders advertise. If 1964 marked a rebirth of Japan, 2020 offers redundant upgrades to an already advanced, wealthy megacity. True transformation requires a confrontation with the sticky problems holding back Japan’s society, like gender inequality, lack of diversity and rigid notions of ethnic identity. No sports event can grapple with such a task”.</p> <p>“It has been decided that the Olympic and Paralympic Games will be held in Tokyo in 2020. Will they bring new vitality to Japan, which has been stalled with no way out for a long time? Expectations to that effect have been increasing on all sides.</p> <p>In June 2013, the bid committee announced the results of their preliminary calculations: an economic ripple effect of 3 trillion yen, and employment creation for 150,000 people. Now that the results of the bidding have been decided, estimates of private research institutions show far higher figures. The economic effects of holding the</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>Olympic and Paralympic Games span quite a wide range of industries, including, but not limited to, the development of facilities such as stadiums and athlete villages, as well as urban infrastructure, amplification of consumer spending accompanying the hosting of the Olympics and Paralympics, and an increase in travellers from overseas.</p> <p>For the 1964 Olympics, Tokyo completely changed the framework of the city. Considering the capital that was invested into improving the grounds and transportation infrastructure, investments including hosting expenses and related industries, as well as consumer spending induced by hosting the Olympics, the previous Tokyo Olympic Games also brought about an immense economic effect’’</p> <p>Winning the Games also appeared to affirm Abe’s efforts to restore Japan’s confidence at a time when it has appeared increasingly eclipsed by neighbouring China.</p> <p>“Japan has seemed to be overshadowed by the rise of China and other developing nations,” said Harumi Arima, an independent political analyst. “These Olympics will give the Japanese a chance to feel reborn, to feel for themselves that Japan can still be vibrant.”</p> <p>For the International Olympic Committee, environmental concerns in Japan appeared less urgent than the Syrian war on Turkey’s border, a harsh crackdown against anti-government protesters recently in Istanbul and Spain’s economic recession and high unemployment.</p> <p>The Olympic movement has also been buffeted by protests in Brazil over heavy government spending for the 2014 World Cup and the 2016 Olympics, to be held in Rio de Janeiro. And there has been criticism of what the West considers antigay legislation passed in Russia ahead of the 2014 Winter Olympics in the Black Sea resort city Sochi, a Games that will come with a \$50 billion price tag.</p> <p>Amid such economic, political and human rights maelstroms, Tokyo was seen as a calm harbour. It won handily over Istanbul in the second round of voting, 60-36, in a secret ballot of Olympic delegates. Tokyo presented its bid as a “safe pair of</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	hands,” an appeal that clearly resonated with Olympic officials.		
International Cooperation and Exchange	<p>This code falls under the Japans international cooperation has and exchanges that include sport, cultural exchanges and also peace and security. For example,</p> <p>Japan engages in peacebuilding activities as one of its key diplomatic agenda. ‘For instance, Japan proactively cooperates with United Nations (UN) peacekeeping operations (PKOs) and the UN Peacebuilding Commission and engaged in activities on the ground with Official Development Assistance (ODA), as well as human resource development.</p> <p>Japan has pursued proactive initiatives to achieve the goal of “a world free of nuclear weapons.” As the only country to have ever suffered atomic bombings in war, these policies allow Japan to fulfil its mission of conveying to the world the devastation caused by nuclear weapons and improve the security environment surrounding Japan. In January 2014, Minister for Foreign Affairs Fumio Kishida delivered a speech in Nagasaki on nuclear disarmament and non-proliferation, in which he unveiled policies including the “Three Reductions” and the “Three Preventions” policies. Under the framework of the Non-Proliferation and Disarmament Initiative (NPDI), launched by Japan and Australia in 2010.</p> <p>Also in terms of sport and cultural exchanges, The revitalization of the Japanese economy contributes to the growth of the world economy. A strong economy is essential to robust diplomacy. Japan will strategically carry out economic diplomacy for creating an international economic environment that contributes to revitalizing the Japanese economy and for achieving dynamic growth. for examples,</p> <p>Cultural Diplomacy (1) Overview</p> <p>“Respect for mutual understanding is essential for people-to-people and cultural exchanges. Therefore, endeavouring to deepen foreign countries’ understanding towards Japan is important through introducing Japanese traditional culture, cuisine and pop culture such as animation, manga and fashion, while at the same time Japan is</p>	8	55

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>making efforts to understand overseas views and cultures’’. MOFA performs a wide range of activities to foster pro-Japanese groups in the next generation and promote understanding towards Japan. Examples of these activities include providing information on studies in Japan and building alumni networks through Japan’s diplomatic missions overseas. collaborating with the JET Programme which invites young people from abroad to local areas, undertaking exchange programmes for young people from Asia and the US as well as for adults, sending visiting professors to universities and research institutions overseas, and offering subsidies for research activities.</p> <p>Also, other narratives under this code include, “C. Sports exchange Sport enables communications beyond language and can be an effective tool for promoting friendly relations and the understanding of Japan. As a host country of the 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games in Tokyo, Japan is attracting much interest from foreign countries The Government of Japan commenced the “Sport for Tomorrow” programme as an international cooperation initiative through sport in January 2014. This programme implements various sports exchanges/sport promotion projects in different countries, with the aim of spreading the value of sport by 2020, targeting over 10 million people in more than 100 countries. Particularly, since the year 2014 marks the 50th anniversary of the 1964 Tokyo Olympic Games, there were a number of commemorating events by sports organizations in various countries, and MOFA was actively involved in these events through diplomatic missions overseas’’. ‘Initiatives toward the Tokyo 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games (Sport for Tomorrow) “Abe Cup” Judo Tournament in Côte d’Ivoire On 11 January 2014, a judo tournament was held in the West African country of Côte d’Ivoire, far from Japan. This was the largest judo tournament in Côte d’Ivoire. As the tournament coincided with Prime Minister Abe’s visit to the country, it was designated by the Government of Japan as the first project under the “Sport for Tomorrow” programme, which aims to</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>contribute to the global community through sports. Organized as a cultural project by the Japanese embassy, this memorable occasion received the unprecedented involvement of the governments of both countries, the judo community, local citizens, as well as the press’.</p> <p>‘International contributions in the sports area for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games Other than Côte d’Ivoire, the Government of Japan is implementing international contribution projects in the sports sector in more than 100 countries, targeted at more than 10 million people by 2020. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs is also engaged in initiatives to promote the Olympic movement and spread the value of sports to all generations, including the youth who are responsible for the future. These initiatives include developing sports facilities and equipment and providing support through the dispatch and invitation of instructors and coaches. The Government of Japan is keeping up efforts to ensure that the Tokyo 2020 Games, which will take place in five years, will be a wonderful event that enriches the lives of athletes, spectators and all other people who are involved.</p> <p>‘Sports Exchange Sports enable communication beyond language and can be an effective tool for promoting friendly relations and a better understanding of Japan. As Japan gains more attention for the TOKYO 2020 Games, since January 2014 the Government of Japan has been implementing the “Sport for Tomorrow (SFT)” program as an international cooperation initiative through sports. This program offers various types of sports exchanges, and human development projects with the goal of spreading the value of sports to over 10 million people in more than 100 countries by 2020’.</p>		
INTERVIEW CODES	The codes in this section include discussions from the interview done to date and placed under several appropriate themes.		

Name	Description	Files	References
Benefits of the Tokyo Olympic Games to Japans domestic, cultural and economic growth	<p>“One problem for, thinking of soft power and Japan is that there is a lot more going on for Japan about the Olympic than just soft power. Two other things going on are domestic politics and economics, it has nothing little to do with soft power or the international world but it the efforts of the Tokyo governor in 2016 to get the Olympics. Who was concerned about Tokyo’s place in the world as a global city. Not so much for Japan but for Tokyo and Tokyo as the premier city for Japan and a city with its global reveries like London and Paris and New York and Seoul and Singapore. What was going on was a kind of global city rivalry”.</p> <p>“Putting on an Olympic is fascinating to me but it is such a huge mega-event that it depends on so many circumstances, political, social and economic that I can’t imagine why any country will want to do it”.</p>	1	3
Emerging difficulties for Tokyo 2020 games plans	<p>“So I hope that the attempt to use the games as a showcase and sort of peace and soft power diplomacy strategy I think was suddenly doomed to fail from the beginning because of the pieces that they emphasised have fallen flat. For example, the sort of Eco part to the Games, the hydrogen business has not fully worked out. Obviously, who knows what would have happened for Japan without the pandemic. I am sure it was going to be a great game last summer it’s just hard to imagine that the sort of global cultural splash would have been big. The whole-cell phone thing for language translation did not really work out they were going to have some sort of automatic cell phone translation business”.</p>	1	1
Hosting the Olympics a smart power play	<p>“Abe as a conservative right-wing politician at the same time as the last 10 years has been talking about soft power and the Olympics and his also been trying to change the constitution to allow offensive military operations. And you know they have in Japan military armament industry in Japan that is huge most of which is manufactured and sold to other countries. But the so-called self-defence forces, army and navy are quite extensive and every day brings new close calls with Chinese and the south china sea. so two levels are going on simultaneously through the same prime minister Abe who is pushing Japan in a hard power way to confront China, to expand its military, to get into offensive operations, to have closer collaboration with the United States in supporting Iraq. A while</p>	1	1

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>ago and other operations now and then he is also talking about Japan and the Olympic as a cultural soft power with biennial influences.</p> <p>And there is also the limit of soft power to me as a concept because china is talking the same way while locking up its minorities and suppressing and Russia was the same way with the Olympics. It seems to me that countries are trying to have it both ways. Is not that there is a hard power country or a soft power country but these are both dimensions of national power that many countries seeking a prominent role are going to play at the same time.</p>		
<p>IOC needs a fundamental rethinking about how to stage the Games in the 2020s</p>	<p>“The Olympic movement if it wants to survive in the 2020s, I think it's going to have to do some fundamental rethinking about how to stage these games may be in a slightly different format than letting individual countries thinking this is the great soft power of the art and just put it on. The Olympic will benefit Tokyo at the cost of other cities in Japan in other regions. Japan already has a strange imbalance it's like in England where London has absorbed so many of the resources and attention at the expense of other cities. There is less tourist travel with Glasgow and Edinburgh it's not quite as unequal but in the case of Japan, the discrepancies between Tokyo and the rest of the country are very strongly felt. Most of the people I know outside of Tokyo are not enthusiastic about the Olympics. When Brazil had the world cup and no money for infrastructural upkeep.</p> <p>It will make more sense to distribute the Games across countries or a couple of countries because it will build support and spread facilities but it often gets caught up in local politics because what you end up with is a facility that you don't use when the Games are over. Thinking about the Games as distributed and the other which people have talked about is having a single cite in the world Greece or where ever why the facilities are used over and over and it becomes a permanent Olympic Cite and its always been an interesting idea to me. I have very complicated feelings about the Olympics, they become too big, economically costlty for the host country and environmental suspect there is so much invested like the Russian cheating scandal and so on. On the one hand, it is the only place that gives</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>2</p>

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>prominence to a range of sport that would not survive if they did not it after 4 years.</p> <p>Swimming and tracks and sailing and field hockey it's a unique conception sport that gives equal attention to man's sports and women sport the only time in the world that ever happens that gives equal attention to countries that are sending 250 athletes and a country that is spending 5 athletes, equal attention to high and low profile sports. The Olympic as a concept is something that the world needs. But it also has a group of effect the notion of being able to swim for the Olympic means that most countries their national sports policy will invest more money in youth and athletic training in a lot of different sports to get soft power prestige to participate and winning medals. So it has an important ripple effect. It seems to me that across the world in different countries, sports policies and keeping athletics from just turning into basketball and soccer and baseball.</p>		
<p>Japans soft power and its counter-culture</p>	<p>“That certainly holds for prime minister Abe I mean he was obviously in Millan last year but he is an example of that tension in Japan. I think he generally wants to embrace all opportunities cool Japan and the likes and but personality-wise he has totally counter everything that he believes in. He probably thinks of anime and manga as a side embarrassment culturally and would rather have the world admire flower arrangement but that remains the tension”.</p> <p>“It is true that even before the Olympics Japan in the 90s liking a strong military, they saw their cultural exports, manga and anime, cuisine video games as one way of generating influence and image of the brand to international relations. The government did not really control those exports and a lot of those exports some of the anime and video games the government was not that happy with because they were sort of use as a counter-culture movement”.</p> <p>“Part of what is going on it that within Japan, the government to try to take over to co-opt this cultural export to make them if not convention or at least something, they could generate some official pride in. in some ways putting out something like the Olympics is a way for creating a more conventional soft power to balance some of the counter-cultural</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>3</p>

Name	Description	Files	References
	export that perhaps they don't think, the government officials and politician representative".		
Japans government, conservative society issues of social and gender equality	<p>“But in the end, as we have seen in the last week and the statement about women, Japan is always headstrong by all this and by the conservatism of government offices and their views of Japan is suddenly stuck in the early 20th century. And I think that is somewhat emblematic of the struggles of the ministry and to some extent the government”.</p> <p>“And I think another thing is that Mori as the head of the local organising committee and the statement he made last week and about women are just the most outrageous. But all along he is very old and he is very old in the head and he is not going to spearhead anything that would get younger generations in Asia or around the world excited and I don't think they might realise that”.</p>	1	2
Olympic Narrative as a soft power tool a weak excuse?	“But it seems to me that this notion of countries trying to host the Olympics and then what the hosting requires and another way soft power then becomes some kind of weak excuse because of the realm people like to talk about it. It's a crucial topic because if you look at it critically you can then challenge some of the claims that they are making about using the Games as a soft power and it preventing the Olympic movement from a more fundamental reimagining what it needs to survive”.	1	1
Soft power as an analytical and fluke concept?	“For me, two-aspect about soft power is definitional about the definition and formulation of the concept and the second is about evaluation. And “Form me I remember, I am old enough to remember when Joseph Nye first came up with this notion of soft power and I was sceptical at the time and I must confess I am still sceptical. But I think it is an important issue particularly for Japan and it is connected to the Olympics but I will distinguish between soft power as an analytical concept and soft power as a fluke Concept”.	1	1
Soft power rivalry and the use of sport in Asia	“And this is were of cause what is currently happening with the beginning of a boycott Beijing 2022 movement also offers a twist if we still have the Games this summer, of cause, not a normal	1	5

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>Games. If Tokyo had happened as planned it would be good Asia and whereas increasing now it is going to be the bad china for 2022. That is a narrative that Japan benefits from massively across Asia right now. The good part of Asia has gone bad meaning authoritarian if we think about Thailand, to some extent the Philippines, India with democracy issues. Again who knows how powerful that narrative it but the contrast between 2020 Tokyo and 2022 Beijing would have been clear. And that might have also led to a different soft power impact and that's all gone because if anything happens this summer it is not going to be very Asian because there is not going to be spectators".</p> <p>“The campaign for 2020 is a little different because this time it, not the Tokyo governor but Prime Minister Abe who really wanted the Olympics. But part of what he wanted the Olympics for, was not a kind of soft power but the real rivalry. In 1964, the effort was to draw Japan to the western powers and that has been its enemy. In 2020, the Enemy is more of East Asia; it is not Australia, England and France, but its china and South Korea and North Korea. Because the Olympic movement not just diplomatically but economically has shifted from the 20th century when it was very Euro American centric to the 21st century where the largest audiences with biggest media contracts the most attention and most interesting hosting are really coming from East Asia”.</p> <p>“China on the other hand has very serious image problems and it deliberately was using 2008 as a way of presenting itself as a dynamic and creative, friendly and open society. in the end, people came and was impressed with the architectural and the opening ceremonies and was not so impressed with the political freedoms and the control with the government but I am not very sure if they were successful in using the Games diplomatically in that way. Obviously, that is not the issue for Japan. For Japan, is demonstrating that they can have an economically efficient and environmentally sustainable, that they are actually leading the world making sure in this sort of things. But again, Covid-19 and other things have really made this unlikely to happen. They keep talking about soft power and</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	they really think in those terms but I think it is much more likely now after a year of coronavirus and the political controversy and three days ago, there was a serious earthquake in Japan. One will hope that nothing like that will happen before the Olympics”.		
Sport diplomacy as a background national strategy, quiet but building ties	“So I do think that this is somewhat removed but related to a national strategy that sport diplomacy is sort of in the background and quiet but builds a lot of ties between the officials and sports organisations especially within Asia”.	1	1
What is the strategy of sport diplomacy in Asia		1	1
Sport diplomacy equals follow the money, lobbying, competing for and with similar interest	“When you say sport diplomacy, for example, I worked for the Mongolian National Olympic committee so when you say sport diplomacy, one of the things I think of immediately is money and how national Olympic committees are supported by other national Olympic committees particularly within Asia. I know that for the Mongolian national Olympic committee a lot of meetings in Vancouver and London were built around some sort of competing with other Asian rich national Olympic committees. Who would pay for training facilities in Mongolia and then do this and that, you know partly looking for the support of the IOC including where games are going to be held but also, ultimately the ministries of foreign affairs who are also involved in this”.	1	1
The Importance of soft power to the Japanese government	<p>“The term was used by everybody from Prime Minister Abe down to Olympic official because they do that and if we are analysing the Olympic we need to take that seriously but I cannot really take it as face value because I don’t think they really know what they are talking about. And soft power is a very soft concept a very mushy concept I think.</p> <p>“What is so interesting from the Olympics not just from a global diplomacy point of view but just as a mega event is how the multiple levels on which you have this struggles going on domestically and regionally and globally so soft power is such a broad concept analytically that it is hard to identify and issue this different levels. Like I say it is an important</p>	1	3

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>concept because Abe thought that is was all about soft power.</p> <p>This leads to my second point, which is the evaluation because even if the Olympics is about soft power how do we know if it works. Two things here, Abe says 2020 is all about soft power that is going to enhance Japans position, we are not going to know that for 4 or 5 years afterwards. Thinking about Rio the Olympic was supposed to enhance Brazil image but it was a disaster it had the opposite effect. What is interesting about the Olympics if you think of it most of them have actually not helped the image of the country. Some of them have been pulled off with success but by a large Atlanta, London, Sochi, and Beijing”.</p> <p>“Everyone tries to justify the Olympics because of soft power but not all of them over time generate the kind of soft power branding that was used to justify the Olympics in the first place. Thinking about the 2020 Olympics, it may not even happen obviously because of Abe. Abe is gone, his dying and all of his effort to rebrand the Olympics is dying and the controversies about the sexiest remark is not very good soft power. What is interesting is that these countries like Japan draw so much attention to the Olympic, the values of the Olympics as a soft power initiative but they actually end up doing a poor job of making it a soft power. If they do the games, they will probably have the organisational expertise to probably pull it off without creating a super spreader covid disaster. Now there is a lot of anxiety surrounding the Games that in terms of soft power personally, I do not think it will have the kind of positive benefit that they wanted to”.</p>		
Tokyo 1964 Legacy in contrast to Tokyo 2020		1	1
Tokyo 2020 bid win and its cultural impact	<p>“The other thing that fist happen when the games were first awarded. The biggest thing that happened between 2013 and 2020 was a massive tourism boom for Japan and that was a huge change that was not really anticipated and that was an area where the government had some initiative primarily Asian tourism boom Korean and Chinese really mostly south-east Asian. For the government that was purposeful and that visa restriction was relaxed a</p>	1	3

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>little bit, some other things were in place, and access was much better”.</p> <p>“So all of a sudden before the pandemic, this huge volume of tourism and that would have been different for the Tokyo 2020 Games. I think the games would have felt very Asian because even more than Beijing, I think for Tokyo the vast majority of spectators would have been Asian, again primarily Chinese and Korean but south-east Asian. I think there would have been a potential for a better word to go viral. I think it might have been an opportunity for Japan to build soft power within Asian, to sheared there wartime image of militarism and colonialism and to also present itself as much more integrated into Asia. Because of the constant fighting with china and Korea has meant that Japan has not seemed very Asian and this would have been an opportunity”.</p> <p>“What is interesting is that 20 years ago In Japan because of its economic stagnation and other things and the popularity of China at the time, when I was going to Japan in 2000-2001, 2002. Everyone was complaining because no one was paying attention to Japan, it wasn’t important anymore, there were no visitors from other parts of the world. But over the last 10 years really the amount of tourism in Japan has gone up 10 to 15 times. They would set these goals by 2015 we wanted to have 10 million visitors, they had 10 million visitors and tourist by 2011, without the Olympics they were already achieving this kind of international exposure and tourist enthusiasm, economic revenues without the cost of the Olympics.</p>		
The relationship between the Japans government and the leverage of its sport and cultural exports		1	1
Social issues and gender equality	‘Japan’s ruling party wants women – not their views – at meetings Politics News Liberal Democratic Party proposes allowing female legislators to join key party meetings as observers, amid growing complaints over sexism. After a sexism row sparked by Tokyo Olympics chief’s saying women talked too	12	28

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>much at meetings, Japan’s ruling party has said it wants women to attend key meetings – but only if they do not talk. Under the new proposals, the ruling Liberal Democratic Party (LDP) will allow five female legislators to join the party’s main meetings as observers. Toshihiro Nikai, the party’s secretary-general, said on Tuesday that he had heard criticism that the party’s board was male-dominated.</p> <p>Anti-sexism petitioners make their case to Tokyo Games organizers — with 150,000 signatures A petition and a total of 157,425 signatures seeking measures against sexist behaviour were handed to the Tokyo Olympics and Paralympics organizing committee Tuesday, after Yoshiro Mori, president of the committee, drew anger for his derogatory remarks about women earlier this month.</p> <p>The signature campaign started on Feb. 4, the day after Mori said at a Japanese Olympic Committee gathering that women talk too much in meetings. Mori has offered to step down from the post to take responsibility for the remarks.</p> <p>At a news conference later on Tuesday, the submitters of the petition called on the Tokyo Olympics organizing committee to make the process of picking Mori's successor transparent.</p> <p>The petition urges the committee to take measures to prevent such sexist remarks from being made again, increase the proportion of female members on its Executive Board to at least 40% and ensure transparency in the management of the organization.</p> <p>An official of the committee who received the petition offered the view that Mori's comments in question were discriminatory against women, according to Momoko Nojo, a fourth-year student at Keio University and one of the initiators of the campaign. At the news conference, Nojo, 22, said: "It's not an issue only for Mori. Japanese society, which has tolerated such remarks, is also problematic."</p> <p>‘The sexism scandal engulfing the Tokyo 2020 Olympics With just five months and six days to go until the Olympic opening ceremony, large parts of Japan are still under a state of emergency and a vaccine has only just been approved for use here. As if those weren’t big enough challenges to overcome,</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>the Tokyo Olympic Organizing Committee was plunged into scandal earlier this month after its president, Yoshiro Mori, suggested that women talk too much in board meetings, leading to his eventual resignation. New York Times bureau chief Motoko Rich breaks down Mori’s sexist comments and what his resignation says about the status of women in Japanese society.</p> <p>Olympics minister Seiko Hashimoto appointed Tokyo Games chief</p> <p>‘Seiko Hashimoto was appointed the new president of the Tokyo Organising Committee after stepping down as Olympic minister Thursday, replacing Yoshiro Mori after his sexist remarks led to his resignation just five months before the games are set to begin.</p> <p>Tamayo Marukawa, a ruling Liberal Democratic Party lawmaker in the Upper House and former Olympics minister, will retake the role just vacated by Hashimoto, Prime Minister Yoshihide Suga said later in the day. Marukawa served as Olympics minister from 2016 to 2017. Hashimoto stepped down from her ministerial post due to restrictions that prevent a minister from simultaneously serving as president of a public entity.</p>		
Sustainability and Tokyo Olympics	<p>Environment</p> <p>‘Tokyo 2020 aims to host a carbon neutral Games, covering all the carbon emissions associated with the entire Games project, which the Commission feels could be ambitious. Significant resources have been allocated both within the OCOG and non-OCOG budgets to meet this target but, should Tokyo be elected as the host city, it would be important to have a clear understanding of the exact scope of this programme and how the carbon footprint and compensation/offset initiatives would be measured.</p> <p>Tokyo 2020 aims to achieve zero waste to landfill through comprehensive waste avoidance and minimisation plan, supported by a hierarchy of reuse, recycle and recover. This covers both the construction phase and Games operations.</p> <p>There is already a considerable amount of park and green space in central Tokyo, and there are significant plans to promote biodiversity</p>	14	45

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>conservation and create additional green space in the Tokyo Bay area’.</p> <p>“Games planning is fully aligned with Olympic long-term urban development strategies: a ten-year plan launched by the Tokyo Metropolitan Government in 2006 entitled “Tokyo’s Big Change – the 10 Year Plan” has been extended under the new label of “Tokyo 2020 Vision” which aims at further improving the city environment and developing and improving infrastructure in a sustainable manner”.</p> <p>“But despite calls for sustainability, most of the new venues are expected to run annual deficits after the games wrap up. According to estimates made by the Tokyo Metropolitan Government. Except for the Ariake Arena — the venue for volleyball and wheelchair basketball, which will be able to host competitions and concerts after the games — five out of the six new venues owned by Tokyo are likely to be bleeding red ink”.</p> <p>“The venues have already been slimmed down to cut costs, and we plan on increasing profitability by introducing measures such as selling their naming rights,” said Kenji Suzuki, senior director for venue opening preparations at the city’s Bureau of Olympic and Paralympic Games. Day-to-day management of the venues will be handled by designated administrators, Suzuki said, and the metropolitan government will work with them on devising ways to attract visitors and host events.</p> <p>Some experts, however, have voiced scepticism over the post-games promotion of Olympic sites.</p> <p>“Plans for the legacy of London 2012 were closely examined from the onset of the bidding process,” said architect Kazuya Yamazaki, who joined British firm Allies and Morrison after moving to the U.K. in 2001. He worked on several London Olympic projects including the Greenwich Park Equestrian & Pentathlon venue before founding his own firm in Tokyo.</p> <p>Rejuvenating the East End of London and particularly Stratford, the site of the Olympic Park, was a major piece toward securing the games’ legacy, Yamazaki said. The project transformed what</p>		

Name	Description	Files	References
	<p>was once a run-down area into a thriving centre of business, retail and tourism.</p> <p>“But I don’t get the sense that organizers for Tokyo 2020 are very focused on the legacy of the Olympics,” Yamazaki said. “They talk about attracting crowds to the venues, but how? There aren’t that many events that can gather tens of thousands of people.”</p> <p>“sustainability remains a major challenge and key theme for Tokyo Olympic Games in 2020 Preparations for the 2020 Tokyo Olympics have kicked into full gear, with the world’s biggest quadrennial sports event just three years away. One of the biggest challenges facing any host city for the Olympics is how to make the event sustainable. For Tokyo, organizers are trying to come up with new ways to make the games sustainable, through such projects as recycling metals from discarded cell phones into the medals awarded to Olympic athletes.</p> <p>The Tokyo 2020 Organizing Committee in April started a project to collect old mobile phones and small electronics from across the country. Scrapped electronics products are “urban mines” treasured for their rare metals, but Tokyo is the first Olympic host city ever to try to make use of these recycled materials. The project is off to a good start, with 500,000 cell phones already collected through NTT Docomo, which has supported it.</p>		
Legacy		4	11
Vision Concept and Legacy		3	14

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Interview Questions

PART TWO

VOICES AND VIEWS FROM THE FIELD

INTERVIEW STRUCTURE LIMITATIONS AND QUESTIONS

Interview Questions

This study is on sports diplomacy as a soft power tool focusing on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. This study aims to examine the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a vehicle for soft power with data collection and analysis of the research findings and variables through the lens of soft power (culture, political values, and foreign policy, national and international image) now identified as the conceptual framework for this study. The open-ended and fairly broad

interview questions for the data collection process are below to achieve the research aim and objective.

The general research question of the study

How effective is Japan's soft power strategy, using the Tokyo 2020/21 Olympic Games as a tool for improving its image in international relations?

Other interview questions are.

- a. What is the importance or benefit of hosting the games on Japan's cultural initiatives and strategy, such as the Cool Japan policy? Given that, the Cool Japan policy has been criticised for being ineffective in recent years.
- b. Japan's foreign policy has made clear its effort to promote its national and global interests through its efforts for peace and stability, international cooperation and response to global issues, economic diplomacy and the steps to promote understanding and trust in Japan. Is Hosting the Olympic Games the right strategy for boosting these efforts, especially in promoting understanding and international cooperation?
- c. Sport mega event is known for their contribution to the economic and cultural development of the host nation. Is hosting the Olympic games a huge opportunity for Japan to gain back its economic and cultural position, especially with China's rise as a global player?
- d. Considering how deeply the Olympics affects society, politics, the economy and public discourse. What difference will the Olympic Games bring to Japan? The Olympic Games are constructed as a legacy that is supposed only to yield positive outcomes, not recognising the difference in opinion from diverse groups, given that sport mega-event helps in understanding how Japan works, far beyond the mega-event itself.
- e. The 1964 Tokyo Olympics symbolised Japan's recovery from World War II, Tokyo 2020 is labelled as an opportunity to symbolise Japan's recovery from the so-called two lost decades of the 1990s-2000s and the massive devastation of the March 11, 2011 earthquake, tsunami and nuclear meltdown in northeast Japan. How beneficial is the Olympic Games to this narrative, or is this just another catchphrase attached to hosting the Olympic Games?

Specific questions for participants' article in 2015

- f. You wrote in 2019 about the concept of soft power and SME and highlighted five interlinked dimensions of a state's soft power. This mirrors some of the big reviews, such as

the Portland soft power 30 rankings. How do you think Japan can use these key areas as vehicles for soft power linked to the Tokyo Olympics, given they have already seen some backlash about the games going ahead?

Publication

In line with regulation 4.97 of the University of the West of Scotland regulatory framework, this research produced an academic paper- Understanding COVID-19: A Hybrid Threat and Its Impact on Sport Mega-Events. A Focus on Japan and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

Reference- Ilevbare, S.I. and McPherson, G., 2022. Understanding COVID-19: A hybrid threat and its impact on sport mega-events. A focus on Japan and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. *Frontiers in sports and active living*, 4, p.720591.